

UWS UNIVERSITY OF THE
WEST *of* SCOTLAND

**NATIONAL ECONOMIC POLICY AND CORPORATE
SECTOR DEVELOPMENT IN A DEVELOPING
ECONOMY:**

**A STUDY OF AGRICULTURAL COMPANIES DEVELOPMENT IN
SOUTH-WEST NIGERIA**

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Abstract

There is no doubt that Nigeria is an agricultural country with food sufficiency up till the late 1970s but this seems to be a thing of the past as a result of neglect of the agricultural sector by the Nigerian government due to the discovery of crude oil and subsequent oil boom in the late 70s. This study, however, seeks to identify factors inhibiting the development of agricultural companies in South-West Nigeria and how to overcome such barriers through conducting an empirical study.

This empirical study aims to investigate how the national economic policies can be used to aid the development of agricultural companies in South-West Nigeria using a conjugative mixed-method approach which will comprise both qualitative and quantitative methods. The study will focus on the development of a conceptual framework and development of a model for the effective implementation of agricultural policies using the logistic regression model.

The methodological approach adopted for this study is the conjugative mixed method. Survey and semi-structured interviews were used to collect data from the six (6) states within the region. Chi-square, heatmap and multiple regression analysis were used to analyse the data collected and determine the relationship between developmental variables and the development of agricultural companies in South-West Nigeria.

The findings from the study show that the bane of the agricultural sector in Nigeria was due to the lack of an agricultural regulatory framework and policy transmission mechanism and over-dependent on oil revenue among other things. The model developed showed linkages between the economic variables and the development of agricultural companies in South-West Nigeria.

Therefore, this study suggests adopting a reliable agricultural framework and agricultural models that will aid the development of agricultural companies, which will lead to food sufficiency and a reduction in the level of poverty in the South-West region of Nigeria.

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DEDICATION

This study is dedicated to my God, my precious wife (Temitayo Eunice Adetuyi) and my children, Samuel Adetuyi, Victor Adetuyi and Michael Adetuyi for their great support and sacrifice during the PhD journey. Love you all.

CHAPTER ONE

1.1 Introduction

At the dawn of this millennium, several predictions were made that small agricultural farms will disappear (Hazell, Poulton, Wiggins, & Dorward, 2010) and transcend into agricultural companies through the implementation of appropriate agricultural policies. Despite these predictions, most of these small farms persist in African countries including Nigeria which is the most populous nation in Africa. The lack of revolution in the agricultural sector of most of these developing nations in Africa has led to food insufficiency, hunger, poverty, and stagnation of economic growth. Other challenges such as poor corporate governance, lack of clear policy goals and continuity have all contributed to the steep decline in the economic growth and development of most of the countries in the continent (Anam et al., 2024)

Therefore, it is generally believed that most African countries are riddled with abject poverty; food insecurity; environmental degradation; malnutrition, and poor economic growth due to a lack of agrarian revolution. In consonance with the general belief, the Nobel Laureate Arthur Lewis in 1954 said there is a positive correlation between the industrial revolution and the the agricultural revolution and an economy with stagnated agriculture will not show industrial development (Barrett, Reardon, Swinnen, & Zilberman, 2019).

Against these backdrops, the African Development Bank (ADB) in May 2016 approved a developmental strategy for Agricultural transformation in Africa between 2016 and 2025 tagged "Feed Africa". The goal of the strategy is to eliminate abject poverty in Africa by the year 2025; end hunger and malnutrition in all African nations by 2025; make African countries major agricultural produce exporters where it has comparative advantages. The development and approval of this strategy have further confirmed the need for economic growth and development through the agrarian revolution in most African countries including Nigeria which is traditionally an agricultural country (Iwuchukwu and Igbokwe, 2012).

Therefore, the goal of this study is to determine how agricultural policies can be used to influence the development of agricultural companies in South-West Nigeria through the development of a framework and model and identification of the right policy transmission mechanisms. The output of the study will by extension useful to other regions of the country and other developing nations around the world.

This chapter also entail the background to Nigeria's economic problem; the statement of purpose; the aims and justification for the study; research questions and objectives; the geography of Nigeria and the structure of the study.

1.2 Background of the study

In the early 1960s, shortly after independence Nigeria was at the same level as countries such as Indonesia, Malaysia, and Singapore in terms of economic growth and development. While most of these countries have diversified their economy through structural transformation (Barrett et al., 2017) and have become emerging economies, Nigeria has failed to diversify and improve its economy, thereby resulting in an increased level of poverty, unemployment and decrease in economic activities across the economic sector(Adams, 2016 and Anam et al., 2024).

The Nigerian economy can be regarded as a developing economy rather than an emerging economy like India, China, and Malaysia because its industrial base is underdeveloped. The World Bank (2018) classified the developing nations as those countries with less than \$4,035USD per capita income. Therefore, in line with the World Bank definition, Nigeria can be regarded as a developing nation because her per capita income of \$1960USD is less than \$4,035. Also, based on the World Bank report of 2018, Nigeria's human development index (HDI) is at 0.534 in form of living standards and education. Furthermore, the average life expectancy of 56 years is low when compared with other emerging economies such as Malaysia with an HDI of 0.804 and a life expectancy of 77 years.

The Nigerian economic progress has been impaired due to the neglect of the agricultural sector which underpinned the economic growth and development of the nation in the early sixties (Afolabi, 2015) by the Nigerian government as a result of the discovery of oil in commercial quantity (Adams, 2016) and followed by the oil boom in 70s which led to the manifestation of Dutch Disease (Ibietan, 2011). Consequently, the country has been unable to match its economic growth with the rapid population growth thereby resulting in a country that used to be an exporter of agricultural products now importing food and other agricultural produce from other countries around the world. However, in many developing nations such as Malaysia, Thailand, and Indonesia, agriculture has played a vital role by addressing challenges like poverty, food insecurity and as a significant source of foreign exchange earnings (Adeola, 2015) through transformational policy in their agricultural sector (Divanbeigi and Saliola, 2016).

Nigeria as a country needs to establish economic policies that will promote the development of agricultural companies in form of an increase in agricultural produce and the application of modern technologies in the agricultural sector which will, in turn, lead to an increase in national productivity (Mau, 2014). The economic retreat by the Federal government of Nigeria on economic policy proposal, further confirm the need for a transformational agricultural policy as the President of Nigeria Muhammed Buhari (2016) stated that "it is obvious to Nigerians that food production and self-sufficiency of the country requires urgent action as for so long the government policies on agriculture have been half-hearted and suffered inconsistencies". It is therefore imperative that the growth and development of Nigeria's economy depend largely on the development of Nigeria's agricultural sector and not on crude oil whose price fluctuates from time to time globally. Base on the current state of the agricultural sector the Muhammed Buhari administration has decided to embark on aggressive agricultural revolution through the use of agricultural marketing system (Chima, 2017). Nonetheless, emphasis should be on the type of economic policies and mechanisms used by government agencies in the quest for growth and development of the agricultural sector rather than the broad-brush approach used in the past (Storey 1994; Talbot and Reeves

1997). However, Memon and Tahir (2012) believe that the performance of a business in terms of increase in output, increase in sale revenue, higher return on capital employed, growth of assets and increase in earnings per share of companies are the traits of growth and development in any sector of the economy. Mokhtar (2004) also agrees that an upward movement in these factors (return on capital employed, assets, and earnings) will indicate a positive impact of economic policy on the company's growth and development, while the opposite indicates a negative impact (Mokhtar, 2004).

Therefore, Nigeria being an agricultural country (Afolabi, 2015) need to develop its agricultural sector through agricultural transformation mechanisms (Divanbeigi and Saliola, 2016; Barrett et al., 2017) such as the transition from a semi-subsistence agricultural system to a mechanised agricultural system and development of an appropriate entrepreneurial regulatory framework that will lead to the development (Adams, 2015; Afolabi, 2015; Harrison, Paul and Burnard, 2016; Hazell et al., 2010) of the agricultural companies in the country. Moreover, most developing countries such as Congo DR and Nigeria that have failed to transform their agricultural sector have remained trapped in hunger, poverty, and economic stagnation (Hazell et al., 2010). Against the background, this study will assess the impact of economic policies on the development of agricultural companies in Nigeria with a focus on the Western Region of the country.

1.3 The purpose of the study

The purpose of this study is to determine the impact of national economic policies on agricultural companies' development in the South-West of Nigeria. The development of agricultural companies shall be measured in terms of agricultural output; turnover/sale; return on capital employed; return on equity; earning per share; availability of infrastructures and application of modern technologies in agricultural processes (Divanbeigi and Saliola, 2016; Adeyemi et al., 2023). The research was orchestrated by the quest for the reasons for the lack of development in the agricultural sector considering "several government interventions and programmes aimed at promoting agricultural

sector without significant impact on Nigeria economic development” (Afolabi, 2015, p.63). The study is to provide a template on how national agricultural policies can be used to influence the development of agricultural companies in South-West Nigeria and by extension in other regions within the country. Figure 1 below shows how the contribution of the agricultural sector to the national GDP nosedived between 2005 and 2018 fiscal years with the highest contribution of 36.40% in 2009 and down to 25.36% in 2021 as a result of neglect of the agricultural sector. This shows about 31% decrease over the period.

Source: Statista (2024).

1.4 The aims of the study

The study aims to investigate how the national economic policies can aid the development of agricultural companies in South-West Nigeria using a conjugative mixed-method approach that will comprise both qualitative and quantitative methods. The study will focus on the development of a conceptual framework and development of a model for the effective implementation of agricultural policies using the heatmap, chi-square and multiple regression model.

1.5 The originality of the study

Review of various academic journals on agricultural policy revealed there is a lot of literature on agricultural policy in Nigeria, but most focused on the national economy and national development. However, the paucity of literature and data on the impact of agricultural policy on agricultural companies development in South-West Nigeria has created a gap and basis for further study. Consequently, this study is unique as it focuses on the gap which exists between agricultural policy and agricultural companies development in South-West Nigeria.

To justify the originality of this study which Guetzkow et al. (2004) regarded as the production of new findings and brand-new theories. Originality, therefore, entails using a new method, a distinctive data collection approach, researching a topical issue, and in an under-studied area. However, the adoption of an appropriate data collection instrument such as a survey and interview will promote clarity, responsiveness and aid the originality of data and methods. While an innovative approach will aid the originality of the findings and result of the study (Guetzkow et al., 2004; Easterby-Smith et al., 2012). The development of the empirical framework and agricultural models will distinguish this study from earlier research conducted on agricultural policy development in Nigeria. The model will be capable of establishing a link between agricultural policy and agricultural companies development. The paucity of study on the agricultural companies development in South-West Nigeria will further justify the originality of this area of study.

1.6 The research questions:

The pertinent research questions that will underpin the aim of this study are as follows:

- i. Has the national economic policy been used to **aid the development** of agricultural companies in South-West Nigeria?
- ii. Are there **models** on how agricultural policies can be used to influence the development of agricultural companies in South-West Nigeria?

- iii. What are the impacts of the **regulatory framework** on agricultural policy implementation in Nigeria?
- iv. Has **policy transmission mechanisms** been used to influence agricultural policy implementation in South-West Nigeria?
- v. Has agricultural diversification influenced the **return on capital employed (ROCE)** of agricultural companies in South-West Nigeria?

1.7 The research objectives:

The main objectives to be achieved from this study are explored through the use of interviews and questionnaires with further analysed using econometrics such as regression and correlation. The objectives are capable of establishing the link between the variables listed in the objectives and the agricultural companies' development in South-Western Nigeria. These objectives are as follows:

- I. To critically explore economic policy scenarios that can lead to agricultural company development through agricultural policy analysis.
- II. To develop a model using artificial intelligence, capable of establishing linkage between the agricultural policies and the agricultural companies development in South-West Nigeria.
- III. To critically evaluate and suggest a practicable agricultural regulatory framework that will serve as a policy guide toward the implementation and achievement of agricultural companies development in South-West Nigeria
- IV. To identify and evaluate how policy transmission mechanisms can be used to educate stakeholders for the development of agricultural companies in South-West Nigeria.
- V. To critically examine various diversification barriers faced by agricultural companies in South-West Nigeria towards achieving the desired ROCE.

1.8 Geography of Nigeria

Nigeria is a federation, politically divided into six regions and comprises 36 states with Federal Capital Territory (FCT) Abuja. Figure 1 below shows the map with the six regions and 36 states with the FCT. The country is characterised by various cultural and ethnic groups, dominated by the three largest groups, the Yorubas, Igbos, and Hausas. Other smaller groups include the Fulani, Ijaw, Kanuri, Ibibio, Tiv, and Edo. The country has three main ecological zones: Savannah, tropical forests, and coastal wetlands. These environmental zones greatly influence the cultures of the people dwelling in these zones. The savannah in the north makes cereal farming and herding occupations for the Hausa and the Fulani. The wet tropical forests in the south make farming of fruits, crops and vegetables the principal occupation of the Yorubas, Igbos, and others in this zone. The ethnic groups living along the coast, such as the Ijaw and the Kalabari, make fishing their principal occupation.

Figure 2: Map of Nigeria with regions and states

Source: Economist (2016)

1.9 Structure of the study

The study shall be structured into eight chapters including the introductory chapter. The other seven chapters of this study will be arranged in the following sequence:

Chapter two contains the narrative literature review from which themes are generated. The review focus on the economic development problems of developing nations and Nigeria. It also includes a snapshot of the Nigerian economy, agricultural developmental prospects, and a review of emerging countries agricultural sectors such as Malaysia and Thailand agricultural sectors. Model and framework development were also discussed in this chapter. The chapter also entails the systematic literature review. It was used to identify factors inhibiting the development

of agricultural companies in Nigeria and how to overcome such barriers through conducting a Systematic Literature Review (SLR) on related papers. The SLR in this paper is based on the three-stage approach which includes review planning, review exercise, and reporting of the outcomes.

Chapter three focuses on the development of the theoretical framework. This chapter was used to identify the right and appropriate framework to be adopted for this study. The chapter explain and evaluate various form of theories and considered the most suitable theory vis-a-vis the objectives, aim and the unit of analysis of the study. The adoption of the theory was also based on the method and type of data collected for the study.

Chapter four contains the research methodology adopted for this study. It explained the rationale behind the adoption of realism as ontology, critical realism as epistemology, and conjugative mixed method as a form of methodology for this study. It also explained the reason for the use of questionnaires and interviews as a means of collecting data with further analysis using narrative analysis, regression and correlation through data analysis software such as Python Anaconda or SPSS.

Chapter five entails the analysis of results and findings of the oral interview conducted on nine (9) participants across the six (6) states in the South-West region. In this chapter, the narrative analysis technique was used to analyse the result and findings of the interviews.

Chapter six deals with the empirical analysis of the result of the survey administered on 30 companies employees across the six (6) states within the South-West region. It will include the development of an empirical framework and model through the use of SPSS and artificial intelligence (Python) for agricultural companies development with expectations based on research questions. It also entails the analysis of the result of data gathered and the empirical result of the estimated model from regression with correlation for each variable in the regression model.

Chapter seven focuses on hypotheses testing using chi-square, regression, and the correlation matrix with the development of the agricultural models. Also included in

this chapter is the test of significance and coefficient of determination as well as the limitations of the models.

Chapter eight covers the conclusion on major findings and recommendations with implications of the study on various stakeholders in agricultural sectors. This chapter also entails suggestions for future related studies and the limitations of the study.

CHAPTER TWO

THE NIGERIAN ECONOMIC SNAPSHOT AND THE LITERATURE REVIEW OF AGRICULTURAL POLICY FRAMEWORK IN NIGERIA

2.1 Introduction

Despite the diversity in size, demographics and wealth, Nigeria has continued to face severe economic challenges in creating employment (ADB, 2019) and fostering more economic growth. The review of the Nigerian key economic variables will aid the trend analysis of the Nigerian economy and reveal the impact of the global economic activities on the Nigerian economy, as well as other economic challenges facing Nigeria as a developing nation.

Nigeria was traditionally an agricultural-based economy (Afolabi, 2015), providing employment and food for its citizen and exporting agricultural produce, like cocoa, palm oil, rubber, and groundnut to countries around the world. Agriculture has been a vital component of the Nigerian economy, based on its contribution to the gross domestic product (GDP), employment and foreign exchange earnings. However, the discovery of oil in 1959 (Adams, 2016) and the oil boom of the early 70s have made the agricultural sector to become, relatively small (Hazell et al., 2010) in terms of foreign exchange earnings and contribution to the GDP of the country.

Nonetheless, the oil boom has prompted the continuous dependence on oil by the nation (Adams, 2016), as the primary source of financing its economy, while other oil-producing nations, like the United Kingdom, United Arab Emirate, Indonesia and Brazil are making more headway in the diversification of their economy into other sectors (Hazell et al., 2010), such as tourism, finance and manufacturing (The Global Economy.com, 2019). The inability of the former military and successive civilian governments to diversify the Nigerian economy from being over-dependent on oil, which price in recent times has become very volatile as shown in Figure 3 below is a critical economic issue. The lack of diversification has made the Nigerian economy lag behind countries like Malaysia, Brazil, Indian and Pakistan that used to be on the same level of economic development as Nigeria in the early '60s. This challenge has made Nigeria, now ranked below most of these countries in terms of industrialisation

(Egbochuku 2001; Ogbeibu, Senadjk & Gaskin 2018), as some of them are now emerging markets and newly industrialised nations while Nigeria is classified as an economically backward nation (Haruna, 2023). Figure 3 below shows the volatility of the oil price and its impact on Nigeria's oil revenue and GDP.

Source: Statista (2020)

Apart from being over-dependent on oil revenue, Nigeria has also been facing some other severe economic challenges, some of which include poor financial management, high rate of unemployment, high standard of corruption, political inconsistency, rapid population growth, policy reversal and lack of adequate data for economic planning and research. These economic challenges prevented Nigeria from achieving the goals of vision 2020. Nigeria, therefore, need to accelerate the rate of economic development due to rapid growth in population which has further increase the level of poverty both at the rural and urban area of the country (Adeyemi et al., 2023).

2.2 The Nigeria economic snapshot

The economic variables that would be discussed in this chapter shall include unemployment, gross domestic product, agriculture, corruption, population, foreign exchange, and inflation. These variables are used to assess how the Nigerian economy has functioned between 2005 and the 2019 fiscal years.

Figure 4: Key economic variables

Source: Author

2.2.1 Demography

Nigeria is a developing nation with the largest population in Africa and seventh in the world, with a population of 201 million people as of 2019 (NBS, 2020) of which more than 50% dwell in the rural area. However, between 2005 and 2018, the population of Nigeria increased from 139 million to 201 million persons growing at an annual rate that reached a maximum of 2.71% in 2013 and then decreased to 2.68% in 2015, 2.65% in 2016 and 2.60% in 2019 (Global Economic report, 2020). It is the most densely populated country in Africa, with a very young population of which 43% are under age 0 – 14, 54% are aged 15 – 64 and 3% are aged over 65years (Statista, 2024). The percentage of these age groups has remained relatively constant between 2005 and 2018, as shown in Figure 5 below.

Figure 5: Percentage (%) of age groups in Nigeria

Source: Statista (2024)

A significant proportion of the youths are unemployed due to the poor economic situation caused by the high rate of corruption and poor financial planning (Agbibo, 2013). The increase in the rate of youth unemployment call for a primary concern as it increased from 9.04% in 2005 to 19.58% in 2019 (NBS, 2020). The rate of rural-urban migration in Nigeria is rapidly growing, as shown in Figure 6 below. The rapid growth in the rural-urban movement is a symptom of young Nigerians in search of better socio-economic benefits lacking in the rural area, such as employment and educational facilities and other social infrastructure (Ogunmakinde, Akinola, and Siyanbola, 2013). The Major problem hindering effective planning and research in the country is the lack of adequate data (Akinkunmi, 2017) and where there are data, they usually contradict data from other sources, such as contradiction in the rate of unemployment in Nigeria by the World Bank and that of National Bureau of Statistics. Figure 6 below shows the growth of both the rural and urban populations in Nigeria between 2005 and 2022. However, for effective coverage, this study shall focus on the Western Region of Nigeria.

Figure 6: Nigerian rural and urban population growth (Millions of people)

Source: Statista (2024)

South-Western Nigeria

The region is the area of study and is made up of six states (Lagos, Ogun, Ondo, Osun, Ekiti, and Oyo) which account for about 31% of the total population of Nigeria (WBI, 2018). The region is around the wet tropical forest of the country and the main crops grown in the region are cocoa, cassava, maize, yam, legumes and vegetables. The region is more industrialised than other regions in the country and the commercial centre (Lagos State) of the country is situated in this region, while Ogun and Ondo are part of the oil-producing states of the country. The GDP of the states as of 2010 are among the top 15 (Lagos-\$33.7b, Oyo-\$16.1b, Ogun-\$10.5b, Ondo-\$8.4b and Osun-\$7.3b) in the country except for Ekiti State(\$2.79) which is ranked 33rd (NBS, 2010). The population of the region is about 38.3 million people as of 2016, with Lagos having the highest number of 12.6 million persons (NBS, 2018). The region was selected because the traditional occupation of the native (the Yoruba's) of the region is agriculture and the farmers in the region have one form of education (Adeola, 2015). The region has a more effective educational system which was established immediately after the independent by the old Western Region government and that has enhanced the level of education of the people from the region including the farmers (Adeola, 2015). The region has the lowest rate of poverty compared with other regions in Nigeria, which as of 2017 was 49.8%, while

South-South, South-East, North--Central, North-East and North-West are 55.5%, 59.5%, 60.7%, 69.1% and 71.4% respectively (NBS, 2018). Table 2 below shows the total population of each state with a total population of the region and the country between 2007 and 2016. The lack of adequate data has made it impossible to secure information for 2017 to 2019.

TABLE 1.
POPULATION OF NIGERIA AND WESTERN PART OF NIGERIA

YEAR	Nigeria Population	Western Region Population	Ogun State Population	Ondo State Population	Osun State Population	Lagos State Population	Ekiti State Population	Oyo State Population
	million	million	million	million	million	million	million	million
2016	186.0	38.3	5.2	4.7	4.7	12.6	3.3	7.8
2015	181.2	37.0	5.1	4.5	4.6	12.2	3.2	7.6
2014	176.5	35.9	4.9	4.4	4.4	11.8	3.1	7.3
2013	171.8	34.7	4.7	4.3	4.3	11.4	3.0	7.1
2012	167.3	33.6	4.6	4.1	4.1	11.0	2.9	6.8
2011	162.9	32.6	4.4	4.0	4.0	10.7	2.8	6.6
2010	158.6	31.5	4.3	3.9	3.9	10.4	2.7	6.4
2009	154.4	30.5	4.1	3.8	3.8	10.0	2.6	6.2
2008	150.3	29.6	4.0	3.7	3.6	9.7	2.6	6.0
2007	146.4	28.7	3.9	3.6	3.5	9.4	2.5	5.8
2006	142.5	27.8	3.8	3.5	3.4	9.1	2.4	5.6

Source: World Development Indicators (2018).

2.2.2 The Nigerian Gross Domestic Product (GDP)

The Nigerian economy in the past has witnessed annual growth in its GDP, rising to 7.8% in 2010, when other countries around the world, including developed nations, such as the United Kingdom, recording GDP growth as low as 1.7% (Office of National Statistics, 2019), as a result of the global financial crises in which global financial market hit post-crisis low (Brett, 2017). Unlike the United Kingdom, the Nigerian economy was less affected, because its economy depends on revenue from the sale of crude oil, which price was high during the period. However, in 2016, Nigeria's GDP growth experienced negative growth, falling to -1.6% (World Bank, 2019) as a result of economic depression suffered by the country in that year.

The economic recession was caused by the decline in the oil price (Adeosun 2016 and Adams 2016) from \$96.29 per barrel in 2014, to \$40.68 per barrel in 2016, as indicated by Figure 3 above. The over-reliance on oil, which became a "Dutch disease" has resulted in the neglect of other sectors such as the agricultural sector

(Fardmanesh, 2002), which use to be the leading foreign exchange earner of the country, through the export of cash crops in the early 1960s. Agriculture was also the major contributor to the national GDP (Darek, 2015) during this period, contributing over 63% between 1962 and 1967 (Akinkunmi, 2017). However, the oil industry is now the major contributor to the Gross Domestic Products (GDP) of the country, but there is need to diversify the economy due to the volatility of the oil price in the international market which has made the GDP of the country to be cyclical as shown in Figure 3 above. It shows the cyclical movement of GDP growth caused by the volatility of oil price, and crude oil revenue. Nonetheless, the data in respect of sectorial contribution between 2007 and 2017, shows that the major contributors to Nigeria's GDP are the Agriculture, service and industrial sector of the economy. The service sector is the highest contributor, contributing over 56% of the GDP, while the agricultural sector, which is the highest employer of labour in the country, contributed about 21% of the GDP. The continuous decline in GDP contribution of agriculture which is the major employer of labour (Agbola, 2014), makes it necessary for the setting of the national economy on the path of recovery and rebirth through diversification (Adams, 2016) into other sectors of the economy, such as agriculture rather than being over-dependent on oil revenue which the price is volatile in the international market. Figure 7 below shows the trend of the gross domestic product (GDP) across the economic sectors in Nigeria from 2005 to 2018.

Source: World economic indicators (2019)

However, in 2015, with a rebased¹ GDP, the Nigeria economy was ranked 26th in the world in terms of the size of the GDP and the first in the continent, but unemployment and poverty persist in the country (Afolabi, 2015). The rebasing enable Nigeria to capture the unreported and underreported economic activities of the new sectors of the economy, which include telecommunication, movies and retail. The rebasing led to an increase of 90%, in the value of Nigeria's GDP, as it increased from USD\$270billion to USD\$510 billion (PWC, 2019) on paper. The Nigerian government plan for its economy to become one of the top 20 economies globally, by the year 2020, but with its current rate of growth in GDP, the plan is far from being achieved. "The Nigerian economy needed more than rebasing its GDP, to achieve its vision 2020" (World Bank, 2014).

2.2.3 Unemployment in Nigeria

Unemployment is the total number of the workforce who are currently not working but are readily available to work for pay and actively searching for a job (ILO, 1993). The OECD (Organisation for Economic Co-operation and Development) defines the unemployment rate as the number of unemployed persons as a percentage of the labour force (OECD, 2019). Labour force is the total number of persons employed plus unemployed, while underemployment is a condition in which workers don't use their skills in the job they are currently engaged (OECD, 2017). The total labour force participation rate in Nigeria is 54.75% in 2005, and by 2019 it has increased to 55.18% of the total population, this resulted in a marginal increase of about 0.43% over the period (NBS, 2020). Table 13 (See appendix) further shows the gender participation in the labour force of the country with 47.75% female in 2005 and 50.62% in 2019, while the male participation was 61.71% in 2005 and declined to 59.65% in 2019. The labour force participation has not shown significant growth when compared to the population growth rate over the years, as shown in Figure 8 below.

¹ 1. *Rebasing of GDP means reviewing of the method and base data used in calculating the country's GDP with the aim of replacing the old base year with a more recent base year (PWC, 2019).*

Source: NBS (2019)

Unemployment and underemployment are major economic problems, globally (Raiz and Zafar, 2018) including developed nations like the United Kingdom, Canada and the United States of America, which have low unemployment but high underemployment. In 2017, the United Kingdom's unemployment rate was 4.3%, and underemployment rate is 9.7%, in Canada, the unemployment rate is 6.3%, and underemployment is 15%, while in United States of America unemployment rate was 4.4% and the underemployment rate was 13.5% (World Economic Indicator, 2019). Widespread unemployment and underemployment of unskilled workers is a trait of the under-developed economies (Bauer and Yamey, 1965), like Nigeria. The rate of unemployment in Nigeria is ever-rising (Riaz and Zafar, 2018), as the total unemployment rate (combined unemployment and underemployment) continues to soar and in 2017 was at 38.2% from 11.9% in 2005, which indicates over 220% increase in the total unemployment rate between 2005 and 2017 (National Bureau of Statistics, 2017). In Nigeria, underemployment is considered as unemployment by the National Bureau of Statistics, because most of the income generated from the activities are insignificant and below the minimum wage of the country. Therefore, during the process of data gathering concerning unemployment, the underemployed workers are captured as unemployed (NBS, 2019). The increase in the rate of unemployment between 2005 and 2019 as shown in Figure 9 below, was majorly caused by agricultural policy reversals and somersaults (Ibietan, 2011) and neglect

of the agricultural sector which employs over forty-five (45) percent of the labour force in 2005 (World Bank, 2019). Consequently, employment in the agricultural sector has declined to 36% as of 2019 (World Bank, 2019) with no corresponding increases in other sectors of the economy. The Nigerian government over the years has not shown the zeal and capability in the implementation of aggressive agricultural policy (Hazell, Wiggins and Dorward, 2010; Adeyemi et al., 2023) that can lead to the development of the agricultural sector, which use to be the major employer of labour in the country.

Figure 9: UNEMPLOYMENT AND UNDEREMPLOYMENT RATE (%) IN NIGERIA (2005 - 2018)

SOURCE: Computed from the National Bureau of Statistics quarterly report (2005 -2018).

Figure 9 above shows that Nigeria is suffering from a high rate of unemployment and underemployment at the same time. The Nigerian rate of unemployment apart from being high is also higher than the global average, which is 4.95% in 2005 and 4.96% in 2018 (ILO, 2019). It is, however, observed that, as the population increases unemployment also increases and in turn, a rising level of poverty. The population growth was 41% between 2005 and 2018 (2005 -139m and 2018 -196m), while the total unemployment growth over the same period was about 264% (2005 - 11.9% and 2018 - 43.3%), which signifies geometric progression in the growth of unemployment when compared with the population growth rate.

2.2.4 Agricultural practices and schemes in Nigeria

Agriculture is one of the dominant sectors (Divanbeigi and Saliola 2016; Adams 2016) of the Nigerian economy, providing employment majorly for the rural dwellers that constitute the larger percentage of the Nigeria teeming population (Adeyemi et al.,

2023) The sector is responsible for direct employment of over 45% as of 2005, and by 2019, it has reduced to 36% (WDI, 2020) as a result of neglect of the agricultural sector by the government due to the oil boom. The diversity of the country's climate made it possible for the agricultural sector to be engaged in forestry, livestock and fishery. The main cash crop of the country are cocoa, rubber, cotton, yam and palm oil; others are beans, cashew nuts, gum Arabic, cassava, kola nut, maize, melon, millet, rice, sorghum, banana, groundnut and sesame (National Bureau of Statistic, 2018 quarterly report). The agricultural produce in Nigeria is classified into food crops for domestic consumption and cash crop for export. Cocoa is the number one foreign exchange earner among the cash crop, followed by rubber and palm oil, respectively (NBS, 2018). Although Nigeria is regarded as an agricultural country, the contribution of agriculture to GDP, as shown in Figure 6 above, has been on a steady decline (Dardak, 2015). The sector is also responsible for the production of food for domestic consumption, but unable to meet the demand of the populace in recent times, leading to food imports of about \$62.8 billion between 2007 and 2010 (John et al., 2012; CBN, 2011).

Policies and strategies used to promote agricultural development

The Federal Government of Nigeria had formulated various plans and strategies over the years in an attempt to promote growth in the agricultural sector. Some of these policies include Commodity Board established during the colonial period as a marketing agent; Structural Adjustment Programme (SAP) established in 1986 as a policy for deregulation of the economy; Operation Feed the Nation (OFN) of 1976 which serve as a policy to promote agricultural production and Green Revolution Programme (GRP) of 1980 initiated to foster self-sufficiency in agricultural produce (Agbola 2014; Daneji 2011; Adeyemi et al., 2023). Other strategies used by the government are directive on the minimum lending limit to Agricultural firms, in which the Central Bank will give directives to the commercial banks on the percentage of their profit to be set aside for agricultural loan and Post-Deregulation Programme, such as the establishment of Agricultural Development Programmes (ADPs); River Basin and Rural Development Authorities (RBRDAs) (Ibietan, 2011). Some of these policies have failed to realise the purpose for which they were established due to the lack of proper consultation and implementation (Ibietan, 2011), weak institutional legal and regulatory framework (Anam et al., 2024). An in-depth analysis of the

above-listed policies is similar to "broad brush policy"² (Storey 1994: Talbot and Reeves 1997) used in the United Kingdom by economic development agency in supporting new firms for economic transformation. The broad brush policy adopted by Nigerian has failed to contribute to the development of the agricultural sector in Nigeria, just as it failed in the UK to identify the new firms with high growth potentials (Storey 1994: Talbot and Reeves 1997). To support the agricultural policies in operation, the Federal Government of Nigeria also establishes some agricultural development programmes and institutions. They include The World Bank-assisted Agricultural Development Programme (ADP), National Agricultural Land Development Authority (NALDA), Federal Agricultural Coordinating Unit (FACU), New Partnership for Africa's Development (NEPAD), River Basin Development Authority (RBDA), Bank of Agriculture (BOA), Interest Drawback Programme (IDP) fund, Nigerian Agriculture and Cooperative Bank (now Nigeria Agriculture Cooperative and Rural Development Bank and Nigerian Agricultural Insurance Company (NAIC) (Adeyemi et al., 2023).

Despite the establishment of all these institutions and policies, the Nigerian agricultural companies still find it challenging to develop as a result of the high rate of corruption within the system Micah and Ruth (2014). The agricultural policies have failed to transform the sector from a conventional and passive sector to a diversified and modern sector (Dardak, 2015; Adetuyi et al., 2022), as in other developing nations such as Malaysia and India. Adeyemi et al. (2023) believe the agricultural scheme and programmes failed as a result of lack of adequate fundings of the programme; non-inclusion of critical stakeholders in the planning and implementation of the schemes; The complexities of the programme with non-compatibility with the farmers ideology and lack of effective communication between the government agencies and the agricultural stakeholders.

Table 2 below shows the growth rate of crops over agricultural policies from 1961 to 2010.

²*The broad brush policy is a mechanism where policy is formulated and implemented without considering the implication of the policy on each of the components of the sector.*

Table 2
Mean Annual Cash Crop Output (tons) and Growth rate of output in Various Agricultural Policies and Programmes Regimes in Nigeria (1961 -2010).

FOOD	PRE-OFN	OFN	GRP	SAP	POST-SAP
CROP	1961-1975	1976-1979	1980-1985	1986-1993	1994-2010
	Output -GR -CV	Output -GR -CV	Output -GR -CV	Output -GR -CV	Output -GR -CV
	000' % %	000' % %	000' % %	000' % %	000' % %
COTTON	141.97 -10.5 37.7	161.4 -17.5 39.1	60.25 -22.2 34.9	218.3 -11.4 38.7	408.7 -5.45 24.0
G/NUT	1585 -23.4 27.3	567.5 -0.05 18.9	536.2 2.35 11.9	1095.4 8.21 21.5	2749.2 4.14 22.1
COCOA	230.8 -1.86 16.5	170.5 -10.0 11.6	157.3 0.48 7.07	239.6 4.38 24.9	351.4 -2.02 19.8
RUBBER	64.68 0.18 11.6	56.31 -5.99 5.09	53.0 -0.80 13.6	111.1 7.2 35.7	126.3 -0.34 13.7
OIL PALM	5775 -1.92 11.6	5343.8 1.97 5.85	5283 1.97 5.85	6312.5 2.82 6.64	8200.1 1.01 5.13
COFFEE	2.82 -2.89 35.4	3.10 1.59 2.65	3.75 8.37 31.3	2.50 -37.8 37.8	3.69 -8.00 27.1

GR- GROWTH RATE, **CV-** COEFFICIENT OF VARIATION, **OFN-** OPERATION FEED THE NATION, **GRP-** GREEN REVOLUTION PROGRAMME AND **SAP-** STRUCTURAL ADJUSTMENT PROGRAMME

SOURCE: FAO & CENTRAL BANK OF NIGERIA (2019).

2.2.5 Inflation/Consumer Price Index (CPI)

Inflation, which can also be called the consumer price index, is a persistent rise in the general prices of goods and services in an economy (Ezeanyejji and Ugochukwu, 2015). An increase in the rate of inflation of a country will lead to a decrease in the GDP per capita and discourage investment (Barro, 1995). In 2017, the Nigerian inflation rate was ranked the 5th highest inflation globally behind other African countries; Angola, Egypt, Suriname and sierra-Leone (The Global economy, 2017). The Country's economy has continuously experiencing a high rate of inflation; it increased from 5.4% in 2007 to 16.90% in 2018 (World Bank, 2019), as shown in Table 3 below. In spite of the Central Bank interventions with the support of government policies and programmes, the inflation rate had remained in double digits (Asekunowo, 2016), except from 2013 to 2015, when it was an average of 8.5%. The high inflation rate in Nigeria has led to a significant increase in prices of commodities and services, discourages savings and investment by creating uncertainty about future prices, increased poverty level, and reduced the international competitiveness

by making the exports relatively more expensive, thus impacting negatively on the balance of payments, and reduced long-term economic growth of the nation (Ghosh and Phillips, 1998). The upward trend in the inflation rate coupled with the high rate of unemployment and underemployment has made the economic indices portray the country as one of the most impoverished nations in the world (World Bank, 2014). One of the causes of the high rate of inflation in Nigeria was due to the devaluation of Naira, the Nigerian currency in 2016, which pushed the inflation rate from 9.0% in 2015 to 15.7% in 2016 after the devaluation exercise (Samuel et al., 2018). Table 12 below shows how the Nigerian rate of inflation increases over the years from 5.4% in 2007 to 16.90% in 2018, while the exchange rate moved from 125.8/\$ in 2007 to 361.2/\$ in 2018. The exchange rate of Naira to a US Dollar in the year 2024 has however moved to 1,588.95/\$ (Oanda, 2024). The interest rate had remained constant at an average of 16.75% over the period. The increase in CPI has continuing to weaken the purchasing power of the consumer, and the zeal to invest or save has been on the decline, negatively affecting the economic growth and development (Udoh and Isaiah, 2018) of the Country.

TABLE 3

Nigeria annual inflation rate, interest rate and exchange rate/\$: 2007 - 2018

year	2005	2006	2007	2008	2009	2010	2011	2012	2013	2014	2015	2016	2017	2018
Inflation (%)	17.86	8.23	5.4	11.6	11.5	13.7	10.8	12.7	8.5	8.1	9.0	15.7	16.5	12.09
Interest (%)	17.95	16.89	16.94	15.48	18.36	17.58	16.02	16.79	16.72	16.55	16.85	16.87	17.58	16.90
Corruption perception Index	19	22	22	27	25	24	24.5	27	25	27	26	28	27	27
Exchange rate/\$	130	128.5	125.8	118.6	148.9	150.3	153.9	157.5	157.3	158.6	193.3	253.5	305.8	361.2

Source: World Bank (2019); Knoema (2020); CBN (2018)

2.2.6 The growing incidence of corruption on Nigerian economy

Corruption takes place when an official uses his position or office to derive personal benefit or gratification (Khan, 2006). Corruption is a significant challenge in most African countries, including Nigeria (Micah and Ruth,2014). According to Evans and Alenoghena (2015) corruption in Nigeria is as old as the country herself. Like most African countries Nigeria is ranked high on the corruption perception index by Transparency International (TI) which is an international organisation that rate countries on corruption perception globally. The index, rate country on the level of

corruption within the country, based on a survey carried out on the business of people in the private and public sector of the economy. The index score ranges between 100% and 0%, the 100 percent signifies highly clean, and zero per cent means highly corrupt (World Bank, 2018).

In 2005, Nigeria was ranked 147 alongside Angola and Guinea-Bissau out of 180 countries surveyed by Transparency International, making Nigeria the 33rd most corrupt nation in the world while in 2018 it further slipped to 148 (Transparent International, 2019; Anam et al., 2024). The Nigeria corruption index scores as indicated in Figure 10 below, remained very low over the years, with a maximum of 28% in 2016, similar to the position of countries such as Mauritania and Bangladesh, with a high rate of corruption. Countries such as Denmark and the United Kingdom with an index score of 88% and 82% (World Bank, 2018) respectively, are among the countries with the lowest rate of corruption in 2016.

Source: World Bank (2018)

Since after independence, political corruption has been on the increase in Nigeria, resulting in Nigeria losing over \$400billion to fraud between 1960 and 2012 (Ezekwesili, 2012). The greed, frivolous lifestyle and tribalism among Nigerian politicians were believed to have led to high rate of corruption (Akindola and Ehinome,

2017) which has become an impediment to the economic growth and development of the nation. The high rate of corruption in Nigeria has led to infrastructural decay (Akindola and Ehinome, 2017) and the collapse of many government establishments across the sector of the economy, including agricultural entities. The failure of the establishments was orchestrated by embezzlement and misappropriation of funds meant for their development by the politicians and government officials. Figure 10 above shows, there is a negative correlation between GDP per capita growth and the rate of corruption, which means, as the rate of corruption increases the GDP per capita decreases (Khan, 2006).

Corruption in Nigeria is not only prevailing among the politicians but also in other sectors such as private companies, Non-governmental organisation, educational institutions, government agencies and parastatals. The forms of corruption are; bribery, embezzlement, lack of respect for the rule of law, election rigging, kidnapping, outright looting and money laundry (Ijewereme, 2015). The Nigerian government has been making an effort to reduce the high rate of corruption in the country by setting up anti-corruption agencies, such as the Economic and Financial Crime Commission (EFCC) and Independent Corrupt Practices and other related Commission (ICPC), but these agencies seem to be occupied by corrupt official nominated by the corrupt politician (Ijewereme, 2015). The appointment of corrupt officers as the head of anti-corruption agencies has further compounded the fight against corruption in Nigeria and made the eradication of corruption more difficult.

2.2.7 Foreign exchange volatility in Nigeria

The Nigerian currency is Naira (₦ or NGN), one Naira can further be divided into 100 kobo, just as one pound sterling of Great Britain can also be broken down into 100 pence. Nigeria uses a direct quote of exchange (Omolehinwa, 2006) to interpret its foreign exchange transaction. The direct quote is a foreign exchange rate stated as the local currency per one unit of the foreign currency. Under the direct quote method, the naira rate of exchange to pounds sterling, for example, will be stated as ₦307/£. An exchange rate is an essential tool, in formulating economic policy (Ufoeze, Okuma, Nwakoby, and Alajekwu, 2018) of a nation, like Nigeria, that depends on revenue from its export to fuel its economy.

In the early 1960s, Nigeria operated a fixed exchange rate system, under this regime the exchange rate of the Nigerian naira was pegged to British pounds sterling at ₦2/£ and to US dollar at ₦0.714/\$ (Ufoeze et al., 2018). During this period the agricultural commodities were the leading foreign exchange earner, contributing significantly to the GDP of the country, but the discovery of oil in 1959, with the oil boom of the 1970s and neglect of agriculture, made oil become the Nigerian primary foreign exchange earner.

However, in 1986, with the introduction of SAP, Nigeria changed its exchange rate policy from a fixed exchange rate system to a floating exchange rate with a managed exchange rate regime (Ufoeze et al., 2017). Under this regime, the Central Bank of Nigeria (CBN) created a second-tier foreign exchange market (SFEM), in which it allows authorised and licensed foreign exchange dealers to bid for foreign exchange and sell at a margin in the SFEM. At the SFEM, the exchange rate is determined by the forces of demand and supply as a result of the non-involvement of CBN in trading of foreign exchange, but the CBN intervened whenever the need arises to stabilise the exchange rate.

The parallel market led to two exchange rates known as the official exchange rate (first tier) and the free market exchange rate and further depreciation of the naira. The volatility of oil prices in recent times has resulted in fluctuations in the exchange rate of Nigeria's naira (Adam, 2016) against international currency such as Great Britain pounds sterling (£), US dollar (\$) and euro (€) and slowing down the economic growth of the country in the short-run (Isola et al., 2016).

In 2005, the naira exchange rate was ₦131/US\$, while in 2018 it rose to ₦361/US\$, leading to an increase of over 175%. Figure 10 below, shows there is a positive relationship between the exchange rate of naira to a dollar, oil price and inflation rate except in 2015 and 2016, where the exchange rate of Naira to a dollar increases to ₦193.3 and ₦253.5 respectively as oil prices reduce to \$49.49 and \$40.76 per/barrel, for the same period. Figure 10 below also show there is an insignificant relationship between the Nigeria GDP growth rate and the exchange rate of naira, an increase in the exchange rate does not show a significant relationship with GDP (Adeniran, Yusuf, and Adeyemi, 2014) except in 2015 and 2016 when GDP growth fell from 2.7% to -1.6%, as the naira rate of exchange per dollar rises from ₦193.3/\$ to

₦253.5/\$. The trends in Figure 10 below show a contrary view to the findings of most literature such as Adam (2016), which state that oil volatility is the primary cause of foreign exchange fluctuation in Nigeria.

Source: World economic indicators (2017)

However, the impact of exchange rate fluctuations on the economy of nations varies, as it depends on whether the country is a developed or developing nation. The effect of exchange rate fluctuations depends on the level of economic development in the country, such as the state of its financial market (Mehdi and Movahed, 2014). Anucha (2017) discovered there is a significant positive relationship between exchange rate movement and the crop marketing. This signifies increase in the exchange rate will result to increase in the price of agricultural produce in Nigeria. Therefore, Nigeria's economy, being a developing economy, importing most of its goods including agricultural produce, was affected by exchange rate fluctuations, hence the upward movements in the exchange rate have led to higher cost of imported materials and finished goods and also an increase in the price of domestic products (Kandil, 2004; Noko, 2016), as a result of the depreciation of the local currency (Naira). To prevent the adverse effect of foreign exchange fluctuations on economic growth, the Nigerian government establishes various policies (Isola, Oluwafunke, Victor and Asaleye, 2016), such as the restriction on the use of foreign

currencies for the local transactions. However, most of these policies established seems not to be yielding result, because Nigeria is yet to diversify its economy (Yusuf et al., 2011) from being an import-based economy.

2.3 Narrative literature review

The purpose of this literature review is to identify the methodology and variables adopted in previous related studies. The review of the literature will also uncover gaps identified in the previous studies, methods adopted, the period covered, and conclusions on the outcome of the investigations. This will aid the adoption of a more reliable method that will lead to a quality output of the research and aid understanding of the impact of economic policy on agricultural companies' development in South-Western Nigeria.

2.3.1 Review methodology

The literature search of academic journals, articles, and textbooks will be undertaken on publications ranging from 1960 to date. The consideration of publication from 1960 was based on post-colonial era agricultural regime. The literature selection on the other hand was based on the research title-related topics from UWS Library, an online database such as UWS online database, Science Direct, ReserchGate, Wiley online resources, Emerald, Sage Journal, Taylor and Francis and Google scholar was used as the search engine.

However, it was discovered that most authors in this area of study have adopted a narrative approach because it helps to establish a theoretical framework and aid theme generation (Onwuegbuzie and Frels, 2015), but for criticality, a multistage review approach was adopted. The multistage approach is comprised of both the narrative approach and a systematic approach. Under the multistage, an initial narrative literature review was conducted in which themes were generated followed by the systematic literature review. The use systematic approach was adopted in addition to narrative because it is objective and follows a transparent and scientific process (Harrison et al., 2016) that eliminates the rule of thumb and ensures criticality which is lacking under the narrative approach (Tranfield, Denyer and Smart, 2003).

2.3.2 Regulatory framework for national economic policy

Economic development requires advancement in the provision of primary healthcare, access to education and affordable living standard for the citizen of the country on a sustainable basis. Some of these basic amenities are either lacking or not adequate in most developing nations, including Nigeria, which is "regarded as the giant of Africa" (Bray, 2018). Most developing countries find it difficult to implement sustainable economic programmes and policies due to a lack of appropriate regulatory framework (Hazell et al., 2010) which should serve as a guide for both policy-makers and beneficiaries of the policy.

A sustainable economic system requires a regulatory framework for the supervision and coordination of the commercial activities of a country (Afolabi, 2015). For sustainable economic development, the government may initiate a regulatory framework for the control of financial services, policy transmission mechanism, climate change and insurance practices for agricultural development, just as the United Kingdom developed a national planning policy framework, for sustainable development in economic, social and environmental issues. Rural development strategy that will focus on the improvement of the social life and economic benefit to the poorest in the rural community can also be adopted. The rural development strategies can include promotion of the welfare, improvement agricultural output of the rural communities and involvement of the stakeholders in the rural community in the rural development strategies (Adeyemi et al., 2023).

The review of the regulatory framework for sustainable development carried out by Luken (2006) on 18 developing nations, through data collected from their national reports/surveys, shows that the legal, economic and institutional framework for effective corporate management only exists as a document in the form of company laws, sectoral guidelines and policy documents in developing nations. The availability of SEC rule, code of corporate governance, Companies and Allied Matter Act (CAMA 2004) and Nigerian Stock Exchange guidelines which are not complied with, by the operators in the Nigerian economic sectors, further confirmed the findings of Luken (2006). Examples of non-compliance in Nigeria are the case of public listed companies, failure to holding an annual general meeting and file an annual return as required by CAMA and SEC rules. This was contrary to the view of Cervantes-Godoy

and Dewbre (2010), which state that developing countries through their system of governance and economic management were able to reduce poverty substantially, The case of Malaysia whose economy has been growing at an annual rate of 6% over 30 years and was able to reduce poverty from 52.4% to 3.8% over the period (Zin, 2014) further confirm the view of Cervantes-Godoy and Dewbre (2010).

Luken (2006), however, identifies the problems of sustainable development in developing nations, as lack of coordination and coherence among policies and programmes, lack of adequate data or database, lack of punitive measures against defaulters, lack of application of modern technologies in sectoral development, absence of involvement of all stakeholders in policy formulation and abuse of policies by the institution and government agencies. The study, however, concluded that there is a need for effective partnerships between the public and corporate sectors for the development of appropriate policies, improved control mechanism and technological progress, which will create a positive impact on business and economic development. This was corroborated by a study carried out by Ibietan (2011) which states that the causes of Nigerian government policy reversals and failure in the agricultural policy-making process from 1960 to 2011 were as a result of non-conformity with the theoretical framework of the policy-model adopted. Ayamga et al.(2021) also, believe that inclusion of stakeholders in the formulation and development of policy framework with cooperation between the regulators and the stakeholders in the implementation process will aid the effectiveness of the developed framework which has a major challenge in most African nation including Nigeria.

The case of the Green Revolution (GR) programme initiated in 1980, was evidence of non-conformity with the conceptual framework, in which the Asian countries were able to increase agricultural output through smallholders-based GR, while the African countries such as Nigeria could not make significant progress with the programme (Birner and Resnick, 2010; Adeyemi et al., 2023) due to lack of proper monitoring, evaluation and accountability of the considerable fund invested on the GR project (Iwuchukwu and Igbokwe, 2012). This programme was later jettisoned in 1986 without any meaningful achievement and replaced with the Structural Adjustment Programme (SAP). Ibietan's (2011) review, of various literature on the policy-making

process, also shows that inconsistency and lack of collaboration among the policy stakeholders has been the principal barrier of developmental programmes in Nigeria. He, therefore, concluded that the model which aid continuity of policy implementation is appropriate for the Nigerian government as policy inconsistency and failure, which is the bane of agricultural policy in Nigeria would be prevented. The study failed to point out the particular causes of failure of the national policy in Nigeria, which may be as a result of corruption, fraud, financial irregularities, lack of adequate data for planning and poor implementation of the plans.

However, Adeyemi et al. (2023) identified the causes of the failure and policy inconsistency as a result of the use of Top-Down approach in the design and formulation of policy. They believe the Top-Down approach was ineffective because of the use of professionals with exclusion of direct users of policy in the process of the formulation and development of policy. Consequently, it has resulted in direct users of the policy not adopting or taken responsibility for the failure of the planned policy. It was therefore, concluded that the lack of inclusion of the direct user of policy in the formulation and implementation of the policy has resulted in ineffective communication, lack of understanding and application of the policy, poor planning and implimentation and abandonment of the schemes and programmes.

Micah and Ruth (2014) through administered questionnaires, found that corruption, fraud and white-collar crime persists in Nigeria despite the enactments of the Economic and Financial Crime Commission (EFCC) Act of 2002, Independence Corrupt Practices and other related offenses Commission (ICPC) Act and Evidence Act of 2011. They discovered, the Acts were enacted to curb the high rate of corruption and financial crime, but the weaknesses in the regulatory framework, judicial system and supremacy and conflict among the law enforcement agencies as a result of duplication of responsibilities, such as the conflict between ICPC and EFCC on who to investigate and prosecute a corrupt public official have prevented the Acts from combating corruption effectively in Nigeria. The use of plea bargaining, where corrupt politicians, negotiate an agreement on the amount embezzled (Akpan and Eyo, 2018) to avoid prosecution is evidence of weakness in the regulatory framework of the country. The study was able to determine the causes of failure in the fight against corruption in the country but failed to identify the structural defects in

the development of the regulatory framework by the Nigerian government, such as duplications of responsibilities of the law enforcement agencies in the country. The establishment of a regulatory framework with the proper structure will effectively eliminate the weaknesses arising from political interest and duplication of responsibilities among the law enforcement agencies.

Therefore, the Nigerian government needs to define crime investigation procedures with the agencies clear line of responsibility in its regulatory framework just as it is done, in developed nations. For example, the United States of America legal system goes beyond "Black letter law" (technical legal rules to be applied in a specific issue which is most often well established and no longer subject to reasonable dispute) to prevent conflict in judgment (Micah and Ruth, 2014) with the help of a regulatory framework.

Bergh (2000) believes the framework should be restricted to the area of economic distortion, such as the area of significant negative externalities, climate change, political distortion, and where there is a comparative advantage. He, therefore, recommends an integrated step-by-step approach for decision-making by the European regulators. This approach can also be adopted by a developing country, like Nigeria, for the development of its regulatory framework, which has been inconsistent since 1960 to date (Ibietan, 2011). The step-by-step approach will integrate all the anti-corruption agencies and eliminates the area of responsibilities overlap.

Kulawczuk and Poszewiecki (2011) discover that national economic policy usually influences the tax system, government grant, financial support and incentives available for business development and the method used in disseminating information (transmission mechanism) about national economic policies to all stakeholders. This study concluded that, financial incentives are influenced by the nature of competitions within the economy and that improved economic framework will support the new entrant to the economic sector and in turn, aid business development. However, Kulawczuk and Poszewiecki (2011), failed to mention the effect of corruption and political ideology, which complicates framing in developing nations like Nigeria. For instance, Akinkunmi (2017) reveals in his paper that there is a link between political ideology and economic policy established by a political

regime, which is the reason why each government in Nigeria usually abandon the policy established by their predecessors. In the same vain Iwuchukwu and Igbokwe (2012) in their empirical study, using the time series approach, discovered that the political will of the country's leaders is very crucial in the successful implementation of national policy.

Likewise, Harrison et al. (2016) propose that the government of developing economies such as Nigeria has not given adequate attention to entrepreneurial leadership which can aid the development of the sector of the economy with great potential through the establishment of an entrepreneurial leadership framework. The establishment of a leadership framework can be used to influence the development of agricultural companies in the Western part of Nigeria. Therefore, a nation, like Nigeria, needs the political will of the leaders to develop an appropriate institutional framework for the country's agricultural companies. To overcome the challenges of a weak institutional or regulatory framework, the Nigerian government can also adopt external policies developed by international agencies, such as the climate change policy developed by UNFCCC, accounting policies developed by IASB, etc.

2.3.3 A framework for global policy adoption

Estrada, Papyrakis, Tol, and Gay Garcia (2013) found out during their study that, there is a need to integrate climate policy with the national economic policy. They believed the development of the regulatory framework in respect of climatic changes would promote government policies within the country. The absence of a framework for the climate policy will increase the risk of vulnerability from the change in climate conditions, which may lead to drought and consequently, food insufficiency in a developing country like Nigeria. Adetuyi et al.(2022) believe most developing nation such a Nigeria are having challenges in the development of and integrating of climate policy with national economic policy as a result of lack of finance and technical knowledge in climate issue. However, Nigeria being a member of many international institutions can adopt existing policies developed by the international bodies of which they are a member rather than develop a similar policy locally.

The adoption of the external or global policies developed by global agencies, such as the United Nation Organisation, World Trade Organisation and Food and Agricultural Organisation by Nigerian policy-maker will help to integrate the Nigerian economy in the area of agricultural development with other countries around the world, regulate the trade relationship between Nigeria and other countries (IMF Center, 2005) and eliminate the application of the rule of thumb in the development of policy and regulatory framework. The adoption of global policies is in line with the view of Muhammed et al. (2011), that adoption of global policies or standard such as the climate policy and international accounting standard will boost local economic activities, eliminate ethnic, cultural and political distraction in governance, attract foreign direct investment, and increase cross border transactions.

However, the study was able to give direction on how national economic policy, such as climatic policy can be used to prevent future financial crises and food shortages through the integration of climate change in the planning and budgeting strategies of the country. Likewise, Afroz and Akhtar (2017) in their paper believes the global policy adoption strategies can serve as a basis for policymakers to produce a policy that will be in line with the need of agricultural companies such as knowledge about climate change and other information that can lead to the development of agricultural companies. However, It worthy to note that climate change may render an operating framework obsolete and frustrate the economic activities of individuals, government and firm in the country (Bauer and Yamey, 1965), just as it did, to the agricultural sector in the Northern part of Nigeria, during the severe Sahel Savannah drought of 1972 to 1974 and outbreak of the disease in 1975 (Agbola, 2014) and the global pandemic of this 2020 as a result of COVID 19.

The adoption of global regulatory policy will therefore, help the stakeholders in agricultural sector in the developing nations to ameliorate the lack of effective communication and aid their competitiveness in the international market (Ayamga et al., 2021). Chelanga's et al., (2023) think the low level of adaptation of global policy by most African agriculturist is major barrier for agriculturist that intend to operate on the international market. It lack of adoption may result in the offering of agricultural produce that are below acceptable international standard and thereby leading to loss of profit and future sales of agricultural produce. To aid adoption of global policy

Chelenga's et al. (2023) believe government should organise training on the current trend in global policy and in addition, make standard for compliance less complicated and affordable for the agricultural stakeholders.

A paper produced by UNFCCC (2007) emphasizes the importance of framework in the development of climate policy and how developing countries can integrate adaptation programmes into their regulatory framework. Nigeria, a developing nation is yet to effect the recommendations of the UNFCCC of 2007 on climate change in its national policy. Climate change is a global phenomenon with diverse level of consequential effects for different part of the world such as Nigeria in Africa where global warming has negatively impact the agricultural sector of the economy (Adetuyi, Borode and Adebowale, 2021). The lack of a framework for climate policy poses a future danger to some economic sectors, such as agriculture, the health of the citizen, water resources and terrestrial ecosystem. However, the convention was able to give direction on how national economic policies through the adaptation of an appropriate framework can be used to prevent the impact of climate change on the economy. Nigeria, an agricultural-based country, will be protected from unexpected calamities of deforestation, agricultural land degradation, and hunger, through the development of agricultural policy which includes strategies for the management of climatic change impact.

2.3.4 Regulatory framework for the transformation of agricultural sector

In recent times, the agricultural sector, through transformation has been regarded as a sector that will alleviate poverty, ensure food sufficiency and security and trigger growth and development (Byerlee, de Janvry and Sadoulet, 2009) in developing nations. It is also widely accepted that a good policy framework will significantly influence the level of business development (Storey, 1994 and Satar, 2016), support the safe use of modern technologies in agricultural sector (Ayamga et al., 2021) and by extension the agricultural companies development in a developing nation like Nigeria. Most developing nations are agricultural countries with a low level of real income and low GDP per capita when compared with developed countries such as, the United Kingdom, Australia and the United State of America that are industrialised. Nigerian GDP of \$397 billion in 2018, is the highest in Africa, but low when compared to the United Kingdom with \$2.9 trillion, Australia with \$1.4 trillion and the United

States of America with \$20.5 trillion in the same year (World Economic Indicator, 2019).

In many developing countries, agriculture plays a significant role in solving the problems of food insufficiency, alleviation of poverty and source of income to rural dwellers (Bazmi 2007; Adeola and Adetunbi 2015). Unlike, the emerging economies such as Malaysia, China, and India, most African countries, including Nigeria have not been able to transform their agricultural sector from a conventional system to a mechanised system (Dardak, 2015) due to the lack of sustainable agricultural framework. The lack of an appropriate regulatory framework has resulted in the development of various agricultural policies without significant progress (Iwuchukwu and Igbokwe, 2012) on the transformation of the agricultural sector in Nigeria. Dardak, R. A. (2015) in his review, of agrarian policies and framework developed by the Malaysian government for the country's agricultural sector, discovered, how plans were used to overcome challenges and transform the agricultural sector of the economy from a passive to a mechanised sector. He further found that the transformation of the agricultural sector has increased the contribution of the agricultural sector to the economy in terms of foreign exchange earnings and the provision of employment for rural dwellers in the country. However, this is not the case, of its former contemporary, Nigeria, in which the agricultural sector contribution to GDP has been declining and unemployment increasing, despite the increase in the number of agricultural policies over the years. Dardak (2011) concluded that various agricultural policies and transformation strategies adopted had transformed the country's agricultural sector into a diversified and modern sector. Nigeria needs to learn from the agricultural transformation agenda of Malaysia that was used to transform the agricultural sector through the formulation of market-driven agricultural policies.

Adeola and Adetunbi (2015) in their investigation discovered that South Western Nigeria can transform the agricultural companies through collaboration between the government agencies and the agricultural companies in the region. The study, however, did not specify the form of collaboration that will promote the transformation of the sector in the region. Unlike Adeola and Adetunbi (2015), Morrison and Schneider (1987) in their research carried out at OECD's Development Centre, on

factors responsible for the poor performance of the agricultural sector in under-developed nations, selected Burkina Faso, Mali, Nepal, Kenya, Tanzania and Sri Lanka. They discovered that government interventions in under-developed countries had become a barrier to the development of agricultural companies, as government agencies usually use fiscal policy, such as direct tax, to regulate prices of crops as a way of controlling the economy. Ayamga et al. (2021) think the government and its agencies should just be involved in the implementation and enforcement of the developed policy rather than the use of government intervention as a means of controlling the economy. For effective development and implementation they concluded that stakeholders in the concerned economic sector should be included in the process of policy formulation and development.

However, Jayne (2019) thinks that developing nations need to transform their agricultural sector which is the heartbeat of their economy, by allowing the private sector to be the engine of the agricultural transformation, while the government concentrates on the development of the regulatory framework, just as, it is the practice in the developed nations. Morrison and Schneider (1987) also discovered, that the government agencies of the nations selected, have monopoly power to purchase the export crops from the farmers at a price, fixed by the government, export it and retain between 20% and 50% of exports value for the government. This is not the practice in developed countries such as the United States of America and Canada, where prices are determined by market forces or forces of demand and supply. They noticed that imposition of excessive income tax, export tax and levies on agricultural companies as a form of redistribution of resources for the development of the non-agricultural sector, is another major factor inhibiting the growth of agricultural companies in developing nation.

The Nigerian government, in an attempt to promote the transformation of the agricultural sector in Nigeria, decided to grant specific tax incentives to agricultural companies in for form of capital allowances and loss relief in agricultural bussiness (CITA, 2020). The tax incentives are in the form of carrying losses forward against future profit, unrestricted use of capital allowance on capital expenditure and non-imposition of the minimum tax, which is payable by other sectors. These incentives have led to the creation of fictitious agricultural companies trading in other sectors

fraudulently claiming the benefit and thereby not leading to significant development in the agricultural sector as a result of this corrupt practice.

Bauer and Yamey (1965) express their view on the policy measures affecting agricultural development in under-developed nations. The authors identified policy measures that can influence agriculture such as, necessary revision of contract terms, agricultural extension, and conservation of natural resources, appropriate regulatory framework and promotion of cooperative enterprise, compulsory cooperation and price and income stabilisation. They believed that the rapid population growth in developing nations is exerting massive pressure on little capital available for the small farm holders within the country and thereby giving rise to low agricultural output and consumption per head. In Nigeria, for example, the population is growing at an average rate of 2.7% per year, while the contribution of agriculture to GDP has fallen from 32% in 2007 to 21% in 2018 (NBS, 2019).

To overcome these challenges, Bauer and Yamey (1965) suggested the inclusion of the following in agrarian policy by the government; agricultural extensions, such as disease control, bud-grafting, veterinary support and conservation practices and mechanisation of farming as techniques of increasing output. This is contrary to the findings of Iwuchukwu and Igbokwe, (2012), who discovered that corruption, misappropriation, lack of interaction between policy-makers and stakeholders and role conflict between different programmes and projects are the major barriers facing the Nigeria agricultural sector and by extension other developing nations. Bauer and Yamey (1965) advised that developing nations can conserve resources through the use of regulatory provisions or direct control, such as the imposition of a high tax rate and preventing the use of public funds by private entities. These measures will discourage the registration of fictitious agricultural companies in Nigeria and by extension, reduce corrupt practices in the agricultural sector of the economy. However, the imposition of a high or excessive tax rate on the agricultural company may lead to an increase in the price of essential food items, cost-push inflation and discourage investors from investing in the agricultural sector.

Divanbeigi and Saliola (2016) investigate how the regulatory framework can be used to transform the traditional agricultural sector using cross-sectional data. They discovered that good regulatory practices and government policies play a crucial part

in the transformation of businesses through the elimination of hostile competition and the reduction of fraudulent practices among stakeholders in the sector. The findings show that agricultural output increase in countries where there is strict compliance with good regulatory practices, as demonstrated by Asian countries during the green revolution (Hazell et al., 2010).

Consequently, a country like Nigeria that failed to implement a useful regulatory framework in its agricultural transformation has remained trapped in economic stagnation, high rate of corruption, poverty (Dao, 2009) and hunger. Therefore, setting the Nigerian economy on the path of recovery requires an aggressive reform in the agricultural sector, which seems to be the only way out of the national conundrum (Adams, 2016). In line with the view of Divanbeigi and Saliola (2016), the interest of economic development, and the transformation of the agrarian sector through the appropriate regulatory framework should be the priority of all developing countries such as Nigeria. Therefore, as a way forward, the Nigerian government can learn from the transformation agenda of the Malaysian government that was used to transform the agricultural sector into a modern sector.

Furthermore, the Nigerian government can develop its agricultural company through the development of appropriate policy and framework rather than using the broad brush policy (Storey 1994; Talbot and Reeves 1997) approach which has not helped the sector in the past. The lack of conceptual framework and the absence of the right measuring tools (Harrison et al., 2016; Ayamga, 2021) in the implementation of agricultural policy has been the bane of agricultural companies development in South-Western Nigeria. Therefore, the conceptual framework below is for agricultural companies development in Nigeria.

Figure 12: conceptual policy framework for Agricultural companies' development

Source: Author's creation (2020)

The conceptual framework in figure 12 illustrates how the relevant research variables relate to each other and to the overall aim of the study which is agricultural

companies development in South-Western Nigeria. The conceptual framework will also inform the adoption of the appropriate theory and theoretical framework that will aid the understability of this research.

The framework above shows that individual entrepreneurs are motivated by factors such as higher return on capital employed; entrepreneurial skills; opportunities for capita creation through access to grants; low-interest loans, etc. As suggested by Chelang'a et al. (2023), that conducting research into modern strategy for agricultural development and training of the young farmers will lead to increase in agricultural produce. It was identified that there is a positive relationship between the agricultural produce and research and training. The growth of the individual start-up can be influenced by appropriate policy development and implementation in the area such as free access to education and training at a local or regional research center.

However, the establishment of a local research center will stimulate the agricultural start-up as a result of the availability of local support in the area of low-interest capital/loan and venture capital. The availability of the research center will aid the provision and availably of data which is a major barrier to effective planning for agricultural sector in Nigeria. Participation in training on modern agricultural development strategy, based on the findings of Chelang'a et al. (2023) and Ayamga et al. (2021) will improve agricultural productivity and generate employment oppurtunity. Access to training and education on farm management will also aid the development and growth of the individual entrepreneur and influence their transition (Satar, 2016) to agricultural companies. Provision of training to farmers in the rural area of the South Western part of Nigeria will serve as a rural development strategy (Adeyemi et al., 2023) which will promote development of the young farmers, equip the farmer with relevant skills and hence lead to development of agricultural companies.

Furthermore, the conceptual framework reveals how individuals that migrate to agricultural companies will further develop through effective policy implementation. The implementation of policy that promotes access to the international market, resource pooling, and support on the acquisition of modern technologies will aid the development of agricultural companies. Ayamga et al., (2021) believe Access to international market with adaptation of relevant international standard will

development and profitability of the agricultural companies. To aid access to the international market, government should support the local agricultural companies by making compliance easier and more affordable for the agricultural companies (Chelang'a et al., 2023).

The establishment of regional programmes and schemes such as public-private partnerships, the establishment of agricultural companies network by stakeholders and setting up management strategies for development by the individual agricultural companies will influence the growth of agricultural companies in the region and hence lead to national economic growth. Luken (2006) thinks the cooperation between the government and private sector such as agricultural companies in the South West Nigeria in the area infrastructural development, will lead the development of the agricultural sector in the South West Region. With public-private partnership their will be an opportunity to revolutionise the agricultura sector using the skill and the expertise of the professional in the private sector. The agricultural network on the other hand will eliminate unhealthy competition among the agricultural companies in the region.

For effective formulation, development and implementation of agricultural policy, there is need for inclusion of critical agricultural stakeholders in the process of development and implementation of agricultural policy. To maximise the benefits derivable from the above conceptual framework there is a need for both policymakers and agricultural stakeholders to develop business ethics, legal framework and appropriate policy transmission mechanisms. The development of the framework and transmission mechanisms will prevent unhealthy competition and offer effective growth of the agricultural companies within the region. In addition, offering tax benefits and incentives in form of agricultural subsidies, grant and the development of infrastructural facilities will aid the development of agricultural companies and by extension the economic growth of the nation.

However, to ascertain the significant relationship between the variables in the conceptual framework in figure 11 above the following hypothesis are tested:

Research Hypothesis 1

H₀: There is no significant relationship between the national economic policy and development of agricultural companies in South-West.

H₁: There is a significant relationship between the national economic policy and development of agricultural companies in South-West.

Research Hypothesis 2

H₀: There is no significant relationship between the agricultural models and agricultural companies development in South-West Nigeria

H₁: There is a significant relationship between the agricultural models and agricultural companies development in South-West Nigeria

Research Hypothesis 3

H₀: There is no significant relationship between the regulatory framework and agricultural companies development in South-West Nigeria.

H₁: There is a significant relationship between the regulatory framework and agricultural companies development in South-West Nigeria.

Research Hypothesis 4

H₀: There is no significant relationship between policy transmission mechanism and agricultural companies development in South-West Nigeria.

H₁: There is a significant relationship between policy transmission mechanism and agricultural companies development in South-West Nigeria

Research Hypothesis 5

H₀: There is no significant relationship between agricultural diversification and return on capital employed.

H₁: There is a significant relationship between agricultural diversification and return on capital employed.

2.3.5 Lesson from Malaysia's agricultural policies transmission mechanism

In assessing the role of agricultural policy in the development of agrarian companies, it is important to evaluate the transmission mechanism used in communicating the agricultural policies to the stakeholders in the sector. Effective communication of agricultural policy and transformation agenda through the right channel of communication will aid the implementation of established agricultural policy, agricultural sector development and the international transmission of economic policies (Omekwu, 2003), as it did in Malaysia. Malaysia is an emerging economy and plans to be a developed nation by the year 2020 (Dardak, 2015) just as intended by the Nigerian government. Nigeria, a developing country like Malaysia, can learn from the agricultural policies transformation mechanism of Malaysian policy-makers and avoid most of the negative externalities associated with the transformation strategies.

Hassan et al., (2010) in their conceptual study based on literature and document analysis on agricultural communication in Malaysia, discovered that the Malaysian government through mass media, such as television, radio, newspapers and the internet were able to disseminate vital agricultural information to the farmers. The dissemination of agricultural information through the right channel of communication led to the creation of educated and informed farmers with updated information in Malaysia.

However, the case of Nigeria agricultural sector is directly opposite of the situation in Malaysia, as farmers are disenfranchised from the implementation of agricultural policies due to lack of information flow between the Nigerian government and stakeholders in the agricultural sector (Iwuchukwu and Igbokwe, 2012; Ibietan 2011). Unlike Malaysia farmers who are knowledgeable and educated as a result of information received from Malaysian policy-makers through suitable transmission mechanism, the Nigerian farmer has remained uninformed due to lack of knowledge on how to transform from the use of peasant or traditional techniques to mechanised farming with high productivity (Cervantes-Godoy and Dewbre, 2010).

Hassan et al., (2010) further emphasised, that the use of mass media has eliminated the challenge of literacy among farmers and makes data more accessible for agricultural research. In Nigeria, the problem of literacy among farmers and non-

availability of data for agricultural research (Akinkunmi, 2017) are major problems hindering the progress of the agricultural sector. Cervantes-Godoy and Dewbre, (2010) also believed that the use of appropriate transmission mechanisms for communicating agricultural policies would improve agricultural performance and income in a rural area, influence agricultural contribution towards the growth of other sectors and stimulate the transition of agriculture towards sustainable development. Hassan et al., (2010) concluded that more funding or sponsorship on agricultural information would further improve the agricultural sector of a nation.

Figure 13 below shows the movements of food production index (FPI) of Malaysia and Nigeria between 1961 and 2016, with Malaysia overtaking Nigeria despite its versed agricultural land and massive population on FPI global ranking as a result of its improved transformation mechanism. The Malaysia FPI global ranking increase from 8.8 in 1961 to 131.3 in 2016, while Nigeria moved from 22.9 in 1961 to 124.6 in 2016. Malaysia moved by 122.5 points over the period compared to Nigeria which moves by 101.7 points over the same period. In the same vein, Osakwe (2010) states that scarcity of agricultural reliable data and information are the major precipitants of agricultural development in Nigeria which need to be addressed before there can be meaningful agricultural companies development. However, the Malaysian agricultural success story largely depends on the transformation of the oil palm sector, which accounts for more than 28% of the global palm oil export as of 2018 (Kajisa et al., 1997).

Sources: World Economic Indicators (2016)

To overcome the problem of agricultural policy transmission between the policymakers and agricultural stakeholders such as agricultural companies, the Nigerian policymakers and agricultural agencies can adopt the conceptual framework in figure 13 below developed by Osakwe for the National Agricultural Information Management System (NAIMS) in Nigeria. The adoption of the information management framework will aid the transmission, reliability, quality and value of agricultural information (Osakwe, 2010) transmitted to stakeholders in the agricultural sector. The efficient flow of information in the agricultural companies network will however improve decision making by the management of agricultural companies which will in turn lead to the growth and development of the companies in Nigeria (Afolabi, 2015).

Figure 14: A conceptual framework for the National Agricultural Information Management System in Nigeria.

Source: Osakwe (2010)

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2.3.6 The case of palm oil production in Malaysia versus Nigeria

The Malaysian oil palm sector has grown to become a very significant agricultural base (Nuyartono et al., 2016), making the country one of the leading producers and exporters of palm oil globally. Kajisa et al. (1997), examined the transformation of the palm oil plantation in Malaysia vis-a-vis stagnation of the industry in the Nigerian agricultural sector. In their study, they discovered that Malaysia agricultural transformation is aided by the application of modern technology in research and development and oil palm processing, creation of a conducive business environment and the adoption of the effective transmission mechanism in the sector.

The Nigeria government, on the other hand, has not been able to make significant progress on its transformation strategies as a result of its inability to create an enabling environment and technology frontier for the small farm holders and private sector (Iwuchukwu and Igbokwe, 2012) operating in the oil palm industry and the agricultural sector as a whole. The lack of improvement in technology application by Nigerian small farm holders in the oil palm industry has resulted in the stagnation of Nigeria oil palm production that used to be a major producer. They discovered that the transformation strategies adopted by the Malaysian government pushed the oil palm production in Malaysia from less than 10% of global palm oil production in 1965 to more than 43% as at 2005 and fell to 32% in 2018, while Nigeria that used to produce more than 40% of global production up till 1960 before independence, has fallen to 2% in 2005 and further fell to 1% of global oil palm production in 2018 (World Economic Indicator, 2018) as shown in Figure 14 below.

Iwuchukwu and Igbokwe (2012) concluded that Malaysia was able to increase its oil palm production through the transformation of its environment, transmission mechanism and taking advantage of technological innovations in oil extractions, while Nigeria remains stagnant as a result of its smallholder's farmers extracting oil through the traditional technique. The oil palm is also used to perpetuate corrupt act by companies that obtain a license to clear land for oil palm plantation, but use the area for other purposes (Fitzherbert et al., 2008) such as logging, thereby causing stagnation in the oil palm industry in Nigeria. However, the increase in oil palm production through transformation is not without cost, as it has led to deforestation as

a result of the replacement of oil palm plantation with larger forest areas in oil palm producing nations and it has also reduced the value of biodiversity in Malaysia.

Figure 15. Global oil production

Source: World Economic Indicator (2019)

Fitzherbert et al. (2008) in their review, on the impact of oil palm plantation expansion on biodiversity, they discovered that the oil palm plantation growth in the south-east of Asia has led to a rapid increase in deforestation around the continent especially in Malaysia, Thailand and Indonesia. The three countries are global leaders in palm oil production and also leading in the area of deforestation globally (Gurden, 2017).

However, the oil palm production in Nigeria has falling by 100% between 2005 and 2018 and the smallholder's farmers who are geographically spread in Nigeria keep extending the oil palm plantation into the tropical forest area without a significant increase in the oil palm production in the country due to lack of proper plantation management and use of modern mills processing method (Kajisa et al., 1997). Fitzherbert et al. (2008) further discovered that the boom in oil palm industry has reduced the value of biodiversity[3], as oil palm continues to replace the tropical forest area and brings about some negative externalities such as land disputes, pollution, greenhouse gas emissions and habitat fragmentation (Nuryartono et al., 2016).

Nonetheless, they concluded that the rapid loss of biodiversity value could only be reduced if the transformation of the oil palm industry is administered to avoid deforestation. For Nigeria to successfully transform its oil palm industry, it will need to emulate the development path of Malaysia (Kajisa et al., 1997) and avoid the negative externalities such as deforestation and loss of biodiversity (Adeola and Adetunbi, 2015; Millennium Ecosystem, 2005) associated with Malaysian oil palm transformation.

2.3.7 Agricultural development and agricultural externalities in Nigeria

From the previous literature reviewed, it was discovered that the agricultural sector has become a very complex sector of the economy as a result of factors such as externalities and the activities of the marketing board, with multiple effects on market, social, cultural, environmental and agricultural development of the most developing nation (Pretty et al., 2001) like in Nigeria. However, the activities of the peasant farmers in most of these developing nations such as Nigeria and Malaysia are leading to deforestation and causing a reduction in the biodiversity of the nation (Adeola, 2015). Likewise, the grazing of cattle on farmland by nomadic herdsmen has led to the destruction of farm produce in southern Nigeria and thereby causing a scarcity of basic food items in the region. The effect of these agricultural activities by the small farmers and nomadic herdsmen are the problems of social cost (Coase, 1960; Ruffin and Anderson, 1996) which are referred to as externalities that cause market failure (Yusuf et al., 2013) and infringement on property right. Externalities are social products in form of non-monetary benefit (good) or cost (bad) associated

with private activities of a firm (Ruffin and Anderson, 1996) in an environment which may cause social problem, market failure, infringement on property right or benefit for other participants in the environment (Coase, 1960). The externalities which arise from the activities of the peasant farmers may impact the welfare of an environment directly or indirectly, it may be positive or negative, while the activities of the cattle-raiser may lead to increase in the prices of agricultural produce, infringement on the property right of the farmers (Coase, 1960) and discourage investment in cash crop production and in turn food shortages in Nigeria.

Novikova (2014) on the evaluation of agrarian externalities through the review of economic scientific literature and logic analysis of traits of agricultural externalities, discovers that intensive and extensive agricultural activities have an effect on the environment in form of positive and negative externalities. This was corroborated by policy analysis carried out by Moss and Schmitz (2013) who identified positive externalities as benefits which include non-marketable product and services, such as the creation of recreational centres like Ikogosi recreational centre in South-Western Nigeria. However, Moss and Schmitz (2013) believes negative externalities are the cost which includes pollution, soil and water degradation, forest fire and other uncompensated damages inflicted on the property right as a result of agricultural companies activities. The control and management of these externalities depend on how it arises and whether the effect is public or private.

Coase (1960), believes government intervention may or may not be necessary for the control and management of either good or bad externalities. The impact of externalities caused by activities of a firm or sector may lead to the failure of another firm or sector in the environment in terms of market failure, deforestation, health hazard, property rights infringement and loss of profits. Unlike Coase, Pigovian theory (Pigovian tax^{[4]3}) assert that the impact of externalities such as market failure and loss of profit should be corrected through tax payment as compensation for damages suffered by other firms in the environment or compensation in form of subsidy for good externalities generated (Ruffin and Anderson, 1996; Meramveliotakis and Milonakis, 2018), just as the case in Nigeria, where government grant tax relief to agricultural companies for making loss, but has not been able to

⁴ *A pigovian tax is levy on any market activity that lead to bad externalities.*

find solution to the infringement on the property right of the agricultural companies in Southern part of the Country by cattle-raiser from the Northern part.

Nonetheless, in Nigeria, a significant portion of externalities such as deforestation and pollution is from the agricultural sector which provides social and economic benefits in form of food safety and employment to the citizenry (Yusuf et al., 2013). The effect of the externalities on the environment as a result of agricultural sector development through intensive and extensive farming cannot be ignored (Novikova, 2014) as most agricultural development activities in most developing nations like Nigeria and Malaysia are resulting to increase in negative externalities in form of market failure, infringement on property right and reduction of biodiversity (Adeola, 2015; Millennium Ecosystem, 2005).

Furthermore, Williamson (1970) in his study on the theory of externalities and compensation analysis, through the use of the case of television signal transmission of World Trade Centre construction, concluded that compensation for damages which can be regarded as demoralisation cost should be paid to the victims of the externalities for loss suffered as a result of the impact of the externalities. In line with Williamson (1970), Ruffin and Anderson (1996) in their paper, based on the review of Coase theorem and Pigovian principle on property rights, concluded that there should be payment of damages to the victims of the externalities and also reasonable tax to the government for competition. This is not the case in Nigeria, as most of the firms whose activities lead to negative externalities neither pay demoralisation cost to the victims or tax to the government for the effect of their activities, like in the case of peasant farmers activities which are leading to deforestation and reduction in biodiversity.

Also, the study carried out by Yusuf et al., (2013) on the evaluation of externalities using data from literature and multinational organisations revealed agricultural externalities exist as a form of indirect forest goods and services that arise out of the agricultural activity and influence the stakeholders in the environment where the agricultural activity is taking place (Moss and Schmitz, 2013) such as the case of deforestation in Nigeria by the peasant farmers and in Southeast Asia as a result of oil palm plantation expansion in Malaysia and Indonesia (Fitzherbert et al., 2008) without payment of demoralization cost (Williamson, 1970). The effect of negative

externalities in Nigeria is currently at a low level as the total economic value (TEV) of positive externalities outweighed the TEV of the negative externalities by (positive value - N269bn; \$747m and negative value- N4.2billion; \$11.6m) 63 times (Yusuf et al., 2013), while the cost of externalities in other countries are; UK \$3.8bn, US\$34.7bn and Germany \$2bn (Pretty et al., 2001). The total economic value is the market cost of the externalities, including the transaction cost in the form of dispute cost and damages (Ruffin and Anderson, 1996). The low level of cost or negative externalities in Nigeria may be as a result of the lack of extensive and intensive agricultural activity in Nigeria (Adams, 2016). or non-payment of transaction costs for the impact of negative externalities (McChesney, 2004).

However, McChesney (2004) in his review discovers that the view of Demsetz was contrary to the Coase theorem, Demsetz believes, certain externalities does not involve transaction cost but can negatively affect the activities of others, as in the case of cattle-raisers in Nigeria where damages or compensation are not paid to the farmers who incurred loss as a result of the activities of cattle-raiser. Also, the case of the pandemic as a result of the global outbreak of COVID-19 which led to a global economic standstill including the activities of the agricultural sector in Nigeria due to the spread of the virus to Nigeria in the early part of the year 2020 is another form of negative externalities which may not be expressly recorded by Nigeria government.

Consequently, based on Damsetz view the total effect of negative externalities may not have been fully captured in Nigeria and this has resulted in a low cost of negative externalities. Novikove (2014) further classified the positive and negative agricultural externalities on the basis of cultural, environmental, social and others (Table 4 below). He, however, concluded that policymakers should make analysis and valuation of externalities as part of agricultural policy development strategies.

Table 4. Positive and negative externalities

Positive externalities	Negative externalities
Cultural	
The landscape itself (good/goods), Sense of place Enhanced cultural landscape, tourism attraction, heritage, geographical identity, recreational and opportunity for leisure activities e.g Car race.	Impoverished landscape, destroyed heritage and destroyed geographical identity.
Environmental	
Viable ecosystems Biodiversity and its preservation Water quality and availability of water, Improved Soil quality, good air quality, resilience to flooding, Climate Stability, and Resilience to fire.	Damage populations of flora and fauna, Soil erosion, biodiversity loss, water pollution, air pollution, Pandemic Destruction of protected objects of nature, gas emissions, Polluted environment from different chemical nutrients and fertilizes
Social	
Maintenance of rural viability, employment of rural inhabitants, provision of food for citizens and Stable income and other socio-cultural factors.	Destruction of cultural objects and sculpture and other biological specimens, food insecurity and scarcity
Others	
Plants and animals welfare	Human health problems caused by agricultural activities, such as toxic wastes release to the community as a result of the flood.

Source: Author (2020)

Pretty et al., (2001) in their paper on externalities of modern agriculture, concluded that the inclusion of externalities management and valuation in the regulatory and legal framework and agricultural policies will lead to a reduction in negative externalities in Nigeria. The externalities in Nigeria can be as a result of cultural, environmental or social factors. Yusuf et al., (2013) also stated that the major limitation of research in Nigeria is as a result of the paucity of data on the agricultural sector which further justified the low cost of total transaction cost of negative externalities in Nigeria. It was believed that the low cost of negative externalities was as a result of lack of adequate data on negative externalities. They further recommend that a developing nation like Nigeria should include externalities management strategies and valuation in agricultural policy.

In line with Yusuf et al., (2013), Ruffin and Anderson (1996) in the review of Coase theorem, they discovered that theory and policy alone cannot eliminate the challenges of market failure brought about by externalities except with detailed analysis of the structure of the agricultural sector which seems not in existence in Nigeria as discovered during the initial data gathering stage of this study. During the initial data gathering it was discovered that there was no structure for agricultural

companies in Nigeria as a result of lack of relevant data on Agricultural companies in Nigeria. Afolabi (2015), argue that there is a need for a relevant structure before there can be a meaning agricultural revelation in Nigeria. In addition to the detailed analysis of the agricultural structure in Nigeria, an efficient policy framework for deciding compensation or demoralisation cost (Williamson, 1970) for both positive and negative externalities need to be developed by policymakers in Nigeria.

2.3.8 Agricultural development under marketing board and post-marketing board era in Nigeria

Evidence from previous literature reviewed shows that the marketing and distribution of agricultural produce is a significant factor inhibiting the growth and development of agricultural companies in the most developing nation like Nigeria. Like most agrarian nations, Nigeria is confronted with various kinds of market failure symptoms, like price and supply volatility, low/volatile income for agricultural companies and agricultural negative externalities (Tejvan Pettinger, 2016). To overcome the impact of the market failure in agricultural sector, many nations, both developing and developed have embarked on marketing reform with some countries scrapping the marketing board for use of private agricultural marketing channels (Barrett and Mutambatsere, 2005) while some countries like in the case of New Zealand and Canada restructure their marketing board from state-controlled board to association producer controlled board such as Dairy Farmers of Ontario in Canada and Blue Diamond Grower in the United state of America.

However, the agricultural sector in Nigeria has operated both marketing with and without board era (Williams, 1985) in an attempt to minimise the effect of market failure on agricultural companies' development in Nigeria. The marketing board era in Nigeria is the period in which the government intervened in regulating the prices of agricultural produce through government approved or controlled entities such as Western Regional Marketing Board and Cocoa Marketing Board. They were given approval for the purchase of agricultural commodities from farmers and monopoly power of exporting agricultural produce in the country (Barrett and Mutambatsere, 2005). The marketing boards in Nigeria were first established by the colonial government for the purpose of buying and exporting Nigeria agricultural commodities to the developed nation manufacturing sector (Ajayi et al., 2017).

The marketing board era in Nigeria, however, lasted from pre-independence until June 1986 when it was scrapped as a result of the implementation of the Structural Adjustment Programme (Ayinde et al., 2013). The marketing board was scrapped in Nigeria by the military regime of 1986 as a result of middlemen abuses (Williams, 1985) and exploitation of the farmers by the board (Ajayi et al., 2017) which were detrimental to the development of the agricultural sector in Nigeria. The scrapping of the marketing board in Nigeria was in consonance with the scrapping of Milk Marketing Board in the United Kingdom by the government led by Mrs. Margaret Thatcher on the basis of abuse of marketing power by the board (Bradley, 2010).

However, unlike the United Kingdom and Nigeria, the use of marketing boards is encouraged by nations such as Canada, New Zealand and Australia in the control of agricultural commodities export. Barrett and Mutambatsere (2005) discovered that marketing in developing nations such as Nigeria, are used by the government to control the price of agricultural commodities, while in a developed nation like New Zealand and Australia, marketing boards are used to control export with insignificant influence over domestic agricultural produce. Nonetheless, Barrett and Mutambatsere (2005) failed to comment on the problem and challenges faced by the two nations in using the marketing board for the control of agricultural commodities export.

The investigation carried out by Ayinde et al., (2013) using historical data from secondary sources such as data from research institutes and National Bureau of Statistics with further analysis using descriptive statistics, co-integration and trend analysis revealed that the marketing board era in Nigeria has positive impact on agricultural output, while post-marketing board regime witnessed higher output. In line with Kolawole (1974), they argue that the marketing board in a developing nation was characterised with lack of adequate incentives to farmers, discouraged farmers from increasing their productivity, stagnate export of cash crops and also promotion of smuggling of agricultural produce to the neighbouring countries.

Ajayi et al., (2017) also discovered that the Western Regional Government of Nigeria used the marketing board established in early 1960 to accumulate funds for developmental purposes, but farmers in the region did not benefit from the fund as they were misappropriated and diverted due to lack of a regulatory framework for the

developmental programme. William (1985) thinks additional burden imposed by the marketing board in terms of accumulation of surplus on trading has led to a decline in export and revenue of the agricultural firm and thereby prompting them to sell to smugglers or switch to other businesses in an attempt to avoid burden imposed by the board. The study also discovered that the free market system or private agricultural marketing channels under which prices are determined by the forces of demand and supply has not led to the development of agricultural companies as the symptoms of market failure such as poor pricing of agricultural produce, export and poor revenue to farmers (Ajayi et al., 2017) persists as a result of weak or lack of regulatory framework which should aid the implementation of agricultural programmes and policies established for agricultural development. Chikhuri (2013) also believe that policy development alone cannot lead to the development of agricultural companies in developing countries, but a replacement of government pricing policy with free trade will create access to a larger market and aid the development of agricultural companies. Ajayi et al., (2017), however, concluded that the government should not have a direct influence on the stabilisation of agricultural product prices, but should rather establish a framework that will aid the implementation of agricultural programmes and policies and allow market forces to be the price determinants.

2.4 Summary of the review findings and conclusions

The overview of key Nigerian economy variables revealed that Nigeria economic performance mostly depends on oil revenue and the price of oil in the international market. Other factors influencing the performance of Nigeria economy are foreign exchange, inflation rate, corruption, national policies and strategies, population growth and employment. The Nigeria economy has not been able to record significant economic growth due to over-dependence on revenue from the export of crude oil and neglect of agriculture, which is a major employer of labour in the country. The economic challenges facing Nigeria, are the high rate of unemployment, high level of poverty, weak agricultural policies, high import rate of consumer goods, high inflation rate and high rate of population growth.

In conclusion, since after independence, Nigeria has been unable to achieve significant economic growth and development, despite abundant human and natural resources available at the country's disposal. As suggested by most literature, Nigeria needs to diversify its economy to agriculture, which use to be its primary source of revenue and employer of labour in the pre-independence era and late 1960s. The diversification will promote food sufficiency and economic growth of the

country. However, Table 5 below shows the 2017 comparative economic indicators of Nigeria and its contemporaries in Africa.

Furthermore, to enjoy the full dividend of agricultural transformation, the Nigerian government need to fully create an environment with perfect market competition. A free market system or private agricultural marketing channels where prices of the agricultural product are determined by the forces of demand and supply and not the government agencies.

Also, in an attempt to transform and develop the agricultural sector the country needs to effectively manage the negative agricultural externalities and improve on current positive agricultural externalities. The negative agricultural externalities such as infringement on property rights, extinction of biodiversity and damages to the environment where the agricultural companies operate need to be prevented during transformation to avoid the situation of most Asian countries that has transform their agricultural sector.

However, based on the findings from the papers reviewed conceptual policy framework for agricultural companies' development (Figure 12) has been designed as a guide for effective implementation of developmental strategy for agriculture in Nigeria.

Table 5: Economic indicators of selected African countries

INDICES	NIGERIA	GHANA	ANGOLA	SOUTH AFRICA	EGYPT
Population (Million pers.)	191	29	30	57	96
Rural population (%)	50	45	36	34	57
GDP (\$billions)	456.8	50.6	101.7	426.8	271.7
GDP Growth (%)	0.81	8.14	0.15	1.37	4.18
GDP Share of agriculture (%)	20.85	19.70	10.02	2.29	11.49
Unemployment rate (%)	17.5	6.71	7.25	27	11.44
Employment in agriculture (%)	36.8	34.3	49.1	5.2	25.1
Inflation rate (%)	16.5	12.4	31.0	5.2	29.5
Crop yield per hectar	1,462	1,873	905	5,648	7311
Food production index	124.6	153.1	192.9	116.7	125
Corruption perception index 100: no corruption	27	41	19	43	35
Exchange rate : local currency/US Dollar	305.8	4.4	165.9	13.3	17.8
FDI Percentage of GDP	0.93	5.52	-6.06	0.59	3.15
Regulatory quality (Weak-2.5; Strong 2.5)	-0.89	-0.14	-1.04	0.23	-0.86

Source: World Bank and NBS (2017)

2.5 The Systematic Literature Review

2.5.1 Introduction

The literature review stages are crucial to academic investigation and serve as a blueprint for the research. The main purpose of conducting a literature review is to develop a blueprint that will assess the previous study within the area of research (Harrison, Paul, and Burnard, 2016). To ensure the development of a reliable blueprint, a systematic literature review is carried out in addition to the initial narrative literature review. The systematic literature review is an evidence-based, inclusive, and explanatory (Harrison, Paul, and Burnard, 2016) form of scientific and transparent stages of review that will further enhance the output of this study. Ahmad and Omar (2014) are of the opinion that a systematic literature review will eliminate the rule of thumb through the provision of an audit trail of the review. Therefore, reviewing literature systematically entails identification of data requirements, selection of literature, research papers classification and description, paper content analysis, referencing, and reporting of findings (Tranfield, Denyer and Smart, 2003).

2.5.2 The methodology for systematic literature review

For the effective development of the review, the systematic review methodology prescribed by Tranfield et al., (2003) and Harrison et al., (2016) was adopted. The review stages include review planning, review exercise, and reporting the outcomes were followed.

2.5.3 Stage 1: Review planning

At the commencement of the literature review and extensive discussion was undertaken with the expert panel to determine the breadth and criteria for the search. A narrative literature review was initially conducted on economic policies impact on corporate sector development in Nigeria. The initial review aided the criteria for inclusion and exclusion of literature. However, in line with the research title, the review questions were strictly adhered to determine what to include and what to exclude in the process of the systematic literature review. The exclusion and inclusion criteria will aid the identification of relevant evidence. The review questions were based on the following

- economic policies in developing economies
- impact of economic policies on corporate sector development
- agricultural policies development in Nigeria
- agricultural companies development in developing economies

2.5.4 The review questions

- Are the national economic policies used to aid the development of the agricultural sector in developing nations?
- What are the impacts of agricultural policies on agricultural companies development in developing nations?
- What are the impacts of the regulatory framework on agricultural policy implementation in Nigeria?
- Has policy transmission mechanisms been used to influence agricultural policy implementation in Nigeria?

2.5.5 Inclusion and exclusion criteria

Inclusion criteria

- The paper must be written in English
- The title of the paper must be related to economic policies in developing economy
- The study must have been published between 1960 and 2020 (both year inclusive)
- The study should focus on the review guidelines

Exclusion criteria

- Papers with the main focus on a developed economy
- Working papers
- Conference proceedings

2.5.6 Stage 2: Conducting the review

For this study, the literature search commenced by adopting the review strategy as discussed with the expert panel and using the keyword identified in the process of initial narrative review. The search string and keywords are shown in Table 6 below.

Table 6. The search string

REVIEW SEARCH STRINGS AND KEYWORDS	
Search String	keyword
Search string 1.1	<i>Economy</i>
Search string 1.2	<i>Development</i>
Search string 1.3	<i>Policies impact</i>
Search string 1.4	<i>Economic policies</i>
Search string 2.1	<i>Agric</i>
Search string 2.2	<i>Developing</i>
Search string 2.3	<i>Agricultural policies</i>
Search string 2.4	<i>Corporate or company or institution or entity</i>
Search string 3.1	<i>Africa or Nigeria</i>
Search string 3.2	<i>Agricultural companies</i>

The above search string was used in addition to Boolean such as agricultural policy and economic development in developing nations, impact agricultural policy on companies or corporate development in Nigeria etc. to search for literature in the nine databases listed in Table 7 below. The databases were considered because they are rich and suitable for social and management research.

Table 7: Sources of literature

SEARCHED DATABASES OF LITERATURE REVIEWED		
Sage Journal	Google Scholar (Academic search engine)	Emerald
Taylor & Francis	Springer link	JSTOR
Science Direct	UWS Online library	Wiley online

2.2.6.1 Analysis and quality assessment

The selection of the literature from the database was based on the title of the study as indicated under the search code in Table 15 above. The exclusion and inclusion criteria were also taken into consideration during the search. Nonetheless, 78 papers were initially sourced from the databases and later streamlined to 47 papers after the abstract screening in line with the title of the study. These papers were critically reviewed and analysed to determine the risk of bias in individual papers and the level of evidence reported. During the process of review and analysis, additional themes were generated from the papers analysed and further searches were conducted based on the theme generated and related journals included in the references. Upon scooping of the references of the initial papers sourced additional 31 papers were identified out of which 17 were identified as suitable and relevant to this study. In all 64 papers were reviewed and analysed. To ensure the quality of assessment all the papers that meet the inclusion criteria were reviewed at least twice to ensure criticality and compliance with the prescribed review processes. The reference details of the papers were also extracted and cross-checked to avoid transposition errors and it was discovered that there were no errors and duplication of paper. However, there seems to be no mention of structure or methodology adopted in some of the papers reviewed including those from the same database which makes it difficult to analyse the underlying methodology adopted by the authors.

2.5.7 Stage 3: Reporting and Dissemination

This stage involves synthesising of the studies through the descriptive analysis of the methodology, conclusion, and findings from the literature reviewed. The analysis is used to provide answers to the review questions. Furthermore, the findings from the literature review are used to justify further investigation and development of a questionnaire for primary data gathering. Other forms of quantitative analysis such as the pie chart and bar chart are also used to analyse the structures and facts extracted from the review. The quantitative analysis will entail information like geographical distributions of papers reviewed, frequency of the papers and analysis of the methodologies adopted by the authors.

2.5.8 SLR Finding and conclusion

Table 8. Summary of findings from the literature reviewed.

AUTHOR/YEARS	METHODOLOGY	FINDINGS	CONCLUSION
Hazell et al. (2010)	Review of literature on the role of agriculture.	Lack of appropriate regulatory framework in developing nations.	Development of policy package by policy-makers.
Afolabi (2015)	Narrative-Textual-Case study (NTCS) and interview.	Lack of regulatory framework for sustainable economic development.	Adoption of Schumpeter ideology of introduction of a new method.
Luken (2006)	Review of national report and use of the survey.	The economic framework exists but not functional.	Need for effective partnership between government and corporate sector.
Cervantes Godoy and Dewbre (2010)	Review of the literature.	Reduction of poverty through effective governance by developing nations.	Data from most developing are not reliable.
Ibietan (2011)	Review of literature on policy establishment and implementation.	Non-conformity with the theoretical framework of the policy-model adopted.	Adoption of a model that aid continuity of policy implementation by the Nigerian government
Micah and Ruth (2014)	Questionnaires	Persistent high level of corruption, fraud and white-collar crime in Nigeria.	Weaknesses in the regulatory framework and judicial system are a major barrier in the fight against corruption

Bergh (2000)	Review of policy documents	Restriction of the framework to area of economic distortion e.g negative externalities.	Use of a step-by-step approach in the development of the regulatory framework.
Iwuchukwu and Igbokwe (2012)	Time series approach	Nigeria needs the political will of leaders to overcome the challenges of a weak regulatory framework	Adoption of external policies developed by international agencies can help to minimise the risk associated with a weak regulatory framework
Birner and Resnick (2010)	Review of political-economic literature	Discovered that most global agricultural and economic policies such as the green revolution are having a positive impact on Asian agricultural companies, unlike their African counterpart that is struggling with the goal.	Need for the African countries to develop a framework that will guide the agricultural companies toward the achievement of an agricultural goal.
Akpan and Eyo (2018)	Descriptive analysis and ANOVA	The cash crop output was volatile over various policy programmes significantly.	There is a need for policymakers to formulate a tailor-made policy for the cash crops rather than using a broad-brush approach
Akinkunmi (2017)	Time series regression and Autoregressive Distributed Lag (ARDL)	The level of economic performance is influenced by the political will of the leaders in the country	The need for the provision of an economic growth model and necessary infrastructural facilities by the political leader.
Estrada et al. (2013)	Review of policies	The established climatic policies are weak and inconsistent and have resulted in an underestimation of the effect of future climatic change disaster	Need to improve the national policy on climatic change through adaptation strategies.
Mohammed et al. (2011)	Review of literature	Globalisation has resulted in the production of foreign products and acceptance by consumers globally	The government should adopt a global policy to increase cross-border trade.
Byelee et al. (2009)	Review of literature	The government of developing nations has neglected the Agricultural sector which has the potential to eliminate poverty and promote food security	Need to eliminate policy bias and strengthen corporate governance in agricultural companies.
Satar (2016)	Analysis of the existing	Absence of policy	The need for the

	model	framework in most developing nations.	establishment of an appropriate regulatory or policy framework for effective policy implementation.
Storey (1994)	Observation	The lack of clear policy statements and objectives is the bane of corporate development in most nations including developed countries.	Emphases should be placed on specific policies for the sector with rapid growth potential
Owombo et al. (2012)	Multi-stage sampling and regression model	There is a positive correlation between access to the machine with extension services and agricultural development in Ondo State in Nigeria	The need for the development of the right policy that will lead to easy access to agricultural technology and modern equipment at an affordable cost.
Adeola and Adetunbi (2015)	Pearson Product Moment Correlation (PPMC)	The agricultural companies in south western Nigeria are willing to adopt sustainable agriculture that will increase their income.	Government agencies should improve their collaborative effort with stakeholders in the agricultural sector through the dissemination of appropriate information on sustainable agriculture.
Daneji (2011)	Review of policies and programmes documents from 1960 to 2011.	The series of policies and programmes set up by the Nigerian government has not had a positive impact on agricultural development due to the lack of inclusion of all stakeholders in the agricultural sector.	The policymakers and other stakeholders should collectively design a framework that is based on the social and economic realities of the country.
Diao et al. (2007)	Least square regression technique	The level of poverty in a developing nation depends on the level of growth in the agricultural sector and the share of agriculture in total employment in the country.	Agriculture should be used as an engine of development in a developing nation through the development of an appropriate agricultural policy and regulatory framework
Omekwu (2003)	Review of agricultural literature published by international agricultural agencies like FAO, ATA, BA, and ISI	Developing nations are faced with the problem of data acquisition and retrieval with challenges of processing and disseminating of information to stakeholders	Development of an agricultural information framework which will integrate all agencies and agriculturists involved in the use of agricultural data and information
Morrison and Schneider (1987)	Comparative analysis of six developing nations' economic policies	The government excessive intervention in the marketing of agricultural produces in developing nations	The appropriate regulatory framework should be developed to promote and encourage the marketing of

		act as a significant barrier to agricultural development in developing nations	agricultural products without government intervention.
Jayne (2019)	Review of documents	Inadequate sustainable agricultural practice in Africa	The government of developing nation should make agriculture the engine of the economy
Zin (2014)	Review of economic policies	Economic development in developing nations can be achieved through the promotion of trade-friendly agricultural policies, infrastructural development and promotion of free trade.	Need for development of an appropriate regulatory framework that will promote structural transformation from an agricultural-based economy to an industrial economy.
UNFCCC (2007)	Convention paper	The lack of adoption of global policy poses a threat to the economic development of developing nations.	Need for the adoption of the global policy by developing nations to prevent future climatic change problem
Dardak (2015)	Review of agricultural policies	The agricultural policy transformation has led to the growth of the agricultural sector and influence economic development in Malaysia.	The need for a sustainable agricultural transformation programme in most developing nations.
Divanbeigi and Saliola (2016)	Cross-sectional data and questionnaire	Strict adherence to the regulatory framework led to lower transaction costs and increase in productivity.	Need for the development of appropriate regulations and frameworks to support agricultural performance and transformation.
Adams (2016)	Descriptive statistics and correlation analysis	Nigeria has become a mono-economy that largely depends on oil revenue as a result of continuous neglect of agriculture	Nigeria needs to diversify its economy through the development of the agricultural sector.
Hassan et al. (2010)	Literature and document analysis	Adoption of the right information transmission mechanism by agricultural agencies will lead to informed and knowledgeable agricultural companies in a country.	The government agencies and the major stakeholders in the agricultural sector should invest more funds in the agricultural transmission mechanism.
Kajisel et al. (1997)	Case study analysis	Malaysia a developing country like Nigeria was able to transform the palm oil sector through appropriate and effective agricultural research unlike	Need to create a link between the agricultural research institute activities and agricultural companies

		Nigeria with unproductive agricultural research centre with docile administrative staff	
Nuyartoro et al. (2016)	Survey	Provision of all farm input to agricultural companies will lead to the growth and development of agricultural companies as it did in Malaysia	Need to develop a framework that will facilitate the development of agricultural companies.
Fitzherber et al. (2008)	Literature review	The increase in oil palm plantations in South Asia is leading to the extinction of biodiversity in the region.	Need to adopt a strategy that will increase palm oil plantation with little impact on the environment.
Garden (2017)	Economic review	The increase in global demand for palm oil has led to widespread deforestation in most developing nations such as Malaysia, Indonesia and Nigeria which are the major producer of palm oil.	Need for government to develop a policy that will prevent the continuous damage caused by palm oil industries on biodiversity.
Millennium Ecosystem (2005)	Assessment of scientific literature, database and models.	Changes in the ecosystem have affective the physical healthy living in the environment.	Development of framework and policies which will promote a healthy environment.
Pretty et al. (2001)	Literature review	Taxes, subsidy and institutional mechanisms are the effective instruments that can be used to discourage negative externalities and promote positive externalities.	Need to develop a regulatory, legal and economic framework for effective implementation of the behavioural policy.
Harrison et al. (2016)	Systematic Review of Literature (SLR)	Discovered effective communication, innovation, creativity and appetite for risk are the traits of the corporate leader	Investigation of the attribute of corporate leaders in developing economies.
Coarse (1960)	Review of economic policies	Most social costs are cost by the factory in the environment or firm external to the victims of the social cost.	Need for the payment of adequate damages in the form of compensation to the victims and payment of Pigouvian tax.
Chikhuri (2013)	Review of Global models of agricultural trade database	Food insecurity is influenced by the extent of trade liberalization.	Free trade should be used to promote development and food security.
Ruffin and Anderson (1996)	Analysis of theory	Pigovian tax theory can only correct the market problem but cannot solve all the problems associated with externalities.	The need to develop a detailed institutional framework that will solve the problem which emanates from externalities and

			market failure
Talbot and Reeves (1997)	Postal Questionnaire.	The use of broad-brush policy does not directly aid the development of all businesses.	Need for the development of tailor-made policy for the development of companies.
Yusuf et al. (2013)	Literature review and data analysis from government agencies	The positive externalities outweigh the negative externalities in Nigeria.	Need to develop appropriate data collection strategies that will lead to efficient forest management in Nigeria.
Novikova (2014)	Economic scientific literature and logic analysis	Agricultural activities usually create both negative and positive	Need for the development of policy strategies for the effective control of externalities.
Bauer and Yamey (1965)	Review	Under-developed nations lack appropriate agrarian policy for price and income stabilisation.	The development of an inclusion policy that will aid mechanisation, price stabilisation and disease control.
Moss and Schmitz (2013)	Policy Analysis	There is an opportunity cost associated with every positive externality	Need to develop a strategy that will minimise the negative externalities associated with the public project.
Williamson (1970)	Theoretical analysis	The compensation paid to victims of externalities or demoralisation cost is usually not timely and commensurate.	Public or private entities should pay adequate compensation to the victims of negative externalities caused by the entity
McChesney (2004)	Evaluation of hypothesis and theories	Government intervention weakens the resolution to the problem of social cost and private property rights infringement.	The use of unilateral, technology is the most economical way to fix the problem of social cost.
Tejvan (2016)	Review of policy documents	Government intervention in the form of regulated prices and subsidy has failed to address the issue of price volatility in the agricultural sector.	The government of the developing nation needs to lower the tariffs imposed on agricultural products to improve the income of agricultural products exporter
Barrett and Mutambatsere (2005)	Descriptive analysis	Lack of linkage between agricultural data collection and transformational policy intervention and implementation.	Need to be engaged in micro-based research to identify the process and problem of structural transformation and informed policy development.
Agboola (2014)	Policy review	Externalities such as diseases and viruses are part of the limitation to the development of the agricultural sector in most developing nations.	Need to develop a plan that will minimise the effect of the externalities on agricultural development.
Williams (1985)	Regression analysis	The marketing board	The need to establish

	and Descriptive statistics	regime has a lower positive impact on cash crop output compared to the post-marketing board period.	the appropriate pricing policies and price stabilization mechanism
Ajayi et al. (2017)	Review of literature	The marketing board era in Nigeria was exploitative during the colonial era and characterised by fraud and misappropriation of the fund by government official's post-colonial	Need for government to establish a mechanism that will promote free trade in the agricultural sector.
Kolawole (1974)	Review of government pricing policies.	The pricing policy used by the government to control agricultural produce has resulted to decrease in cash crop production and increase smuggling of agricultural produce from Nigeria to neighbouring countries.	To prevent ambiguity in price stabilisation government should allow the forces of demand and supply to dictates the price.
Evans and Alenoghena (2015)	Vector Autoregressive (VAR) Model	Corruption has significantly hindered the development of agriculture in Nigeria.	To eliminate corruption in both public and private sectors Nigeria will need to develop an unconventional method with strong political dexterity.
Afroz and Akhtar (2017)	Logistic Regression Model	Adaptation of global policy is influenced by access to information about climatic change by the agricultural companies	Adaptation strategy can be a basis for the development of local policies that address the need of the agricultural companies.

2.5.9 Descriptive Analysis

2.5.9.1 Contribution based on the geographical distribution

The highest number of papers (20) reviewed for this study originated from Nigeria. Fifty-two (52) countries are represented with the second and third highest number of papers originating from Malaysia (12) and the United State of America (10) respectively. The other papers reviewed are spread across other developing nations with few developed countries. Thus, high number of papers have been developed on developing economies but few on agricultural development. Nonetheless, figure 13 below shows the distribution by country of the papers reviewed.

Figure 16: Distribution by countries of the papers reviewed

2.5.9.2 Period of publications

Figure 14 shows that among papers reviewed the papers between 2011 and 2020 have the highest frequency of 28 followed by 2001 to 2010 with a frequency of 14. This signifies that the review is based on a recent trend in corporate development in developing nations.

Figure 14: Frequency of paper by ten years interval.

Literature source

The 54 papers reviewed are spread across different journals, but just eight (8) of the journals can be credited with at least two (2) with World development journal having the highest with frequency of 4 (See table 9 below)

Table 9. Journals with highest frequency of publications

Journal	Number of Papers
World Development Journal	4
Journal of Business and Management	3
International Journal of Research in Agriculture & Food Science	2
Journal of Economic and Development Studies	2
International Journal of Law and Management	2
International Journal of Economic	2
IMF Staff Paper	2
British Journal of Management	2

2.5.9.3 Analysis of methodology

Analysis of findings from the literature reviewed showed 55% adopted the qualitative method, 22.5% quantitative method while 22.5% adopted a mixed method. Also, data collection instruments were 39% questionnaires, 24% interviews, 21% case studies

and others were 16%. Figure 16 and 17 shows the pictorial diagram of the methodology adopted.

Figure 16. Percentage of the method adopted

Figure 17: Data collection instruments.

2.5.10 Results

➤ *Are the national economic policies used to aid the development of the agricultural sector in developing nations?*

The review showed that national economic policies in most developing nations do not have a significant impact on the development of the agricultural sector. As indicated in the table 10 below forty-two (42) of the papers reviewed answered question one in part or as a whole. The papers revealed there was no significant development in the

agricultural sector as a result of neglect of the agricultural sector by the government (Adams, 2016; Byelee et al., 2009), lack of inclusion of all stakeholders in policy formulation and implementation (Daneji, 2011), lack of adequate and reliable data (Cervantes-Godoy and Dewbre, 2010) and incidence of corruption (Evans and Alenoghena, 2015). However, some of the papers suggested a way out of this conundrum as the development of an appropriate regulatory and legal framework that is based on the economic reality of a developing nation like Nigeria.

Table 10. Use of national economic policies to aid the development of the agricultural sector

<p>Lack of significant development and neglect of agricultural sector (Adams, 2016; Byelee et al., 2009; Birner and Resnick, 2010; Akpan and Eyo, 2018; Estrada et al., 2013; Adeola and Adetunbi, 2015; Diao et al., 2007; Jayne, 2019; Kajisel et al., 1997; Nuyartoro et al., 2016; Pretty et al., 2001; Chikhuri, 2013; Bauer and Yamey, 1965)</p>
<p>Lack of inclusion of all stakeholders in policy formulation and implementation (Daneji, 2011; Hazell et al., 2010; Afolabi, 2015; Luken, 2006; Ibietan, 2011; Satar, 2016; Owombo et al., 2012; Storey, 1994; Omekwu, 2003; Zin, 2014; Millennium Ecosystem, 2005; Ruffin and Anderson, 1996; Afroz and Akhtar, 2017)</p>
<p>Lack of adequate and reliable data (Cervantes-Godoy and Dewbre, 2010; Bergh, 2000; UNFCCC, 2007; Dardak, 2015; Talbot and Reeves, 1997; Novikova, 2014; Barrett and Mutambatsere, 2005)</p>
<p>Incidence of corruption (Evans and Alenoghena, 2015; Akinkunmi, 2017; Morrisson and Schneider, 1987; Divanbeigi and Saliola, 2016; Fitzherber et al., 2008; Garden, 2017; Yusuf et al., 2013; Ajayi et al., 2017; Kolawole, 1974)</p>

➤ *What are the impacts of agricultural policies on agricultural companies development in developing nations?*

Twenty-eight of the papers reviewed were identified to have answered review question two (See table 11). The review findings show that agricultural companies output, profitability and return on capital employed were volatile over various agricultural policies and programme in most African nation (Akpan and Eyo, 2018) and Some of the established agricultural policies are inconsistent and cannot reduce or eradicate poverty in most developing nation (Dao, 2009). Nonetheless, some of the authors such as Hazell et al. (2010) and Storey (1994) recommended the development of tailor-made policy rather than a broad-brush approach will influence the development of agricultural companies in the developing nations.

Table 11. *the impacts of agricultural policies on agricultural companies' development*

<p>Volatility of agricultural companies output, profitability and return on capital employed (Afolabi, 2015; Adams, 2016; Byelee et al., 2009; Garden, 2017; Akpan and Eyo, 2018; Omekwu, 2003; Morrisson and Schneider, 1987; Zin, 2014; Dardak, 2015 Estrada et al., 2013; Adeola and Adetunbi, 2015; Chikhuri, 2013; Kajisel et al., 1997; Nuyartoro et al., 2016; Pretty et al., 2001; Chikhuri, 2013; Tejvan and Pettinger, 2016; Williams, 1985; Bauer and Yamey, 1965; Kolawole, 1974)</p>
<p>Eradication of poverty in developing nations (Cervantes Godoy and Dewbre, 2010; Chikhuri, 2013; Daneji, 2011; Diao et al., 2007; Hazell et al., 2010; Novikova, 2014; Jayne, 2019; Ibietan, 2011; Satar, 2016; Owombo et al., 2012; Millennium Ecosystem, 2005; Agbo Kolawole, 1974 ola, 2014; Ruffin and Anderson, 1996; Afroz and Akhtar, 2017; Kolawole, 1974)</p>
<p>Effect of tailor-made policy on agricultural companies' development (Bergh, 2000; Birner and Resnick, 2010; UNFCCC, 2007; Dardak, 2015; Talbot and Reeves, 1997; Novikova, 2014; Barrett and Mutambatsere, 2005)</p>
<p>Broad brush policy versus tailor-made policy (Hazell et al., 2010; Storey, 1994; Akinkunmi, 2017; Divanbeigi and Saliola, 2016; Fitzherber et al., 2008; Yusuf et al., 2013; Ajayi et al., 2017; Kolawole, 1974)</p>

➤ *What are the impacts of the regulatory framework on agricultural policy implementation in Nigeria?*

Twenty four papers answered review question three (See table 12). The findings revealed that Nigeria agricultural sector just like any other developing nation lack an agricultural regulatory framework (Hazell et al., 2010; Afolabi), The weak regulatory framework in existence are not being complied with due to structural defect (Luken, 2006; Ibietan 2011; Morrison and Schneider, 1987) and the intervention of government in form of price regulation has further distorted the pricing mechanism in the country (Kolawole, 1974; Pettinger, 2016; McChesney 2004). However, most of the authors recommended the use of a step-by-step approach in the development of an agricultural regulatory framework (Bergh, 2000; Satar, 2016; Nuyartoro et al., 2016) and the adoption of external policy framework developed by international agencies such as FOA and World Bank which can help minimise the incidence of the weak regulatory framework (UNFCCC, 2007).

Table 12. Impacts of the regulatory framework on agricultural policy implementation in Nigeria

<p>Nigeria agricultural sector lacks an agricultural regulatory framework (Hazell et al., 2010; Afolabi, 2015; Byelee et al., 2009; Garden, 2017; Akpan and Eyo, 2018; Omekwu, 2003; Morrisson and Schneider, 1987; Zin, 2014; Estrada et al., 2013; Nuyartoro et al., 2016; Pretty et al., 2001; Chikhuri, 2013; Tejvan and Pettinger, 2016; Williams, 1985; Bauer and Yamey, 1965; Kolawole, 1974; Luken, 2006; Satar, 2016; Diao et al., 2007)</p>
<p>Structural defect due to weak regulatory framework (Luken, 2006; Ibietan 2011; Morrison and Schneider, 1987; Micah and Ruth, 2014; Storey, 1994; Zin, 2014; ; Chikhuri, 2013; Daneji, 2011; Diao et al., 2007; Hazell et al., 2010; Novikova, 2014; Ibietan, 2011; Satar, 2016; Owombo et al., 2012; Millennium Ecosystem, 2005; Agbo Kolawole, 1974 ola, 2014; Ruffin and Anderson, 1996; Afroz and Akhtar, 2017; Kolawole, 1974; Millennium Ecosystem, 2005; Pretty et al., 2001; Moss and Schmitz, 2013)</p>
<p>Distortion of price mechanism due to intervention of government in form of price regulation (Bergh, 2000; UNFCCC, 2007; Dardak, 2015; Talbot and Reeves, 1997; Novikova, 2014; Barrett and Mutambatsere, 2005; Divanbeigi and Saliola, 2016; Hassan et al., 2010; McChesney, 2004; Tejvan and Pettinger, 2016; Ajayi et al., 2017)</p>
<p>The adoption of external policy framework developed by international agencies (Bergh, 2000; Iwuchukwu and Igbokwe, 2012; Birner and Resnick, 2010; Mohammed et al., 2011; Hazell et al., 2010; Akinkunmi, 2017; Divanbeigi and Saliola, 2016; Fitzherber et al., 2008; Yusuf et al., 2013; Ajayi et al., 2017; Kolawole, 1974; UNFCCC, 2007; Millennium Ecosystem, 2005)</p>

➤ *Has policy transmission mechanisms been used to influence agricultural policy implementation in Nigeria?*

Twelve papers provided a solution to review question four (See table 13). The identified papers findings revealed there is disintegration between agricultural agencies and the agriculturist involved in the use of agricultural data and information (Omekwu, 2003), Lack of appropriate policy transmission mechanism and lack of effective communication between the policymakers and the agricultural stakeholder (Daneji, 2011; Dardak, 2016) and lack of adequate funding and provision of the appropriate policy transmission mechanism. Furthermore, the author recommends a way out of the ineffective policy transmission mechanism as the development of an effective policy transmission framework that will influence effective communication between policymakers and the agrarian in Nigeria (Omekwu, 2003; Dardak, 2016).

Table 13. Using policy *transmission mechanisms* to influence agricultural policy implementation in Nigeria

<p>Disintegration between agricultural agencies and the agriculturist (Hazell et al., 2010; Adeola and Adetunbi, 2015; Daneji, 2011; Garden, 2017; Omekwu, 2003; Ruffin and Anderson, 1996; Bauer and Yamey, 1965; Kolawole, 1974; Satar, 2016;)</p>
<p>Lack of appropriate policy transmission mechanism and lack of effective communication between the policymakers and the agricultural stakeholder (Hazell et al., 2010; Hassan et al., 2010; Storey, 1994; Daneji, 2011; Hazell et al., 2010; Novikova, 2014; Agbo Kolawole, 1974; Ruffin and Anderson, 1996; Afroz and Akhtar, 2017; Harrison et al., 2016; Kolawole, 1974; Kajisel et al., 1997)</p>
<p>Lack of adequate funding and provision of the appropriate policy transmission mechanism (UNFCCC, 2007; Dardak, 2015; Talbot and Reeves, 1997; Novikova, 2014; Barrett and Mutambatsere, 2005; Divanbeigi and Saliola, 2016; Hassan et al., 2010; Coarse, 1960; Williamson, 1970; Barrett and Mutambatsere, 2005)</p>
<p>Effective communication between policymakers and the agrarian in Nigeria (Omekwu, 2003; Dardak, 2016; Cervantes Godoy and Dewbre, 2010; Hazell et al., 2010; Harrison et al., 2016; Akinkunmi, 2017; Fitzherber et al., 2008; Yusuf et al., 2013; Ajayi et al., 2017; Kolawole, 1974; UNFCCC, 2007)</p>

2.5.11 Summary and conclusion

The literature reviewed was able to provide insightful answers to the review questions and many more. The review showed that agricultural companies in the most developing nation such as Nigeria have not been able to make significant development given the large potential of arable land and other renewable resources. From the review, it was discovered that the lack of significant development of agricultural companies in Nigeria as a result of neglect of the agricultural sector, lack of agricultural development regulatory framework, over-dependence on crude oil revenue, lack of adequate data for agricultural planning, use of broad-brush policy, lack agricultural policy transmission mechanism, the incidence of corruption in the country, poor return on agricultural investment and lack of inclusion of all stakeholders in agricultural planning. It was also discovered that Nigeria can draw a lesson from the Malaysia palm oil development experience. Malaysia is a developing oil nation with poor economic development up till the early 70s (Dardak, 2015) just as Nigeria, but Malaysia, through its agricultural development programme, has been able to reduce poverty and increase the standard of living of the citizen which has placed the country among the upper-middle-income country. Therefore, a pragmatic approach to agricultural company development in Nigeria will lead to a decrease in

the rate of unemployment, food sufficiency and an increase in foreign exchange generation.

CHAPTER THREE

The Theoretical Framework

3.1 Introduction

The quest for quality research output has led to encouraging researchers to develop theoretical framework which will aid the quality of research output. According to Varpio et al., (2020), theoretical framework is a set of assumptions, concepts, theories, and ideas that aid the understand of an investigated problem or phenomenon. It can be regarded as a prototype or blueprint that is used by researchers to investigate a specific problem or issue. It is used to by researchers or investigators develop research inquiry or methodology. Lerderman.G and Lerderman. S (2015) believe that the lack of theoretical framework is an evidence of invalid and/or non-reliable data collection processes or procedure.The theoretical framework therefore will help the researchers evaluate the appropriate research design to be adopted in a study. It also support in the choices of analysis technique and interpretation of research findings.

The theoretical framework explains the interconnectivity between dependent and independent research variables, aid the development of research questions help to identify gaps in previuos literature, current hypotheses, and the adoption of a justifiable methodologies to bridge the gap. Braidotti (2018) concluded that theoretical framework will aid theoretical grounding and pave way for the emergence of a critical theory and a sound contemporary knowledge that will stand the test of time.

The theoretical framework, serves purposes such as Provision of a guide and structure for the study; support the researcher in integrating the appropriate theory into study; help in addressing gaps in existing related literature; provision of architecture for maintenance of fucus during the research and guide in the collection of data and selection of research methods and data analysis technique (Varpio et al., 2020; Lederman and Lederman 2015).

During the literature review it was discovered that there is a difference between the theoretical framework and the conceptual framework. The literature reviewed also disclosed there are relationship or link between the theory, theoretical framework and conceptual framework (Braidotti, 2018). The relationship is shown in the figure 22 below. According to Varpio et al., (2020), A theoretical framework is a framework critically evaluated and developed based on connected set of concepts and parameters. It is based one or more theories that an investigator or researcher creates to unfold the expected output of a study. To design the architecture of a theoretical framework, the researcher involved need to define the theories or concepts that will aid the grounding of the study and link them logically (Braidotti, 2018). On the other hand, the conceptual framework is a basis for the conduct of a study (Varpio et al., 2020). It is used by researcher to explain existing knowledge through a critical literature review, use to identifies gaps in area of study and to show the methodological approach underpinning the study. The conceptual framework is use to communicate what the study will contribute to the body of knowledge (Kivunja, 2018).

Varpio et al. (2020), developed a model which shows the relationship and differences between the theory, theoretical framework and conceptual framework.

Figure 22: Relationship between theory, theoretical framework, and conceptual framework.

Source: Varpio et al. (2020, p991)

The model in figure 22 above shows the link between the theoretical framework and data collected by a researcher. The model shows how theory is developed from data collected in the process of research under a qualitative study. It further indicate how the theory can be refined based on the hypothesis generated using data collected by the researcher (Kivunja, 2018). This thesis being a mixed method daopted a theoretical framework that supports the research question, informed the analytical approach and support the development of the conceptual framework for the study.

This study however, developed a theoretical framework that identify and define the key variables, provide a structure for the study and support the development of hypotheses that can be evaluated and tested through collected data and analysis (Varpio et al., 2020).

3.2 Towards the adoption of theory and the development of theoretical framework

The aim of this section is to review and evaluate various form of management theories with the intention of adopting an appropriate and relevant theory that will aid the development of reliable theoretical framework. The theory and theoretical framework will depends on the conceptual framework in chapter 2. To meet these objectives, this study evaluated theories such as agency theory, stewardship theory, stakeholders theory and sustainable developmet theory.

3.2.1 Application of agency theory

Agency theory is an abstraction used to define the critical relationships between a company (principal) and their manager (agent). There are variuos form of interest in business acitivites, such as in agricultural companies in South-West Nigeria. Agency theory state that some of these interest, like the interest of the shareholder (Principals) and their managers (agent) are in conflict with each other (Krisnawati et al., 2014).

The conflict between the principal and their agent under agency theory is called agency problem. It is an agency problem because the principal relies heavily on the performance of their agent that have conflicting objectives in executing and implementing financial decisions and transactions that can result in desrable outcomes (Davis et al., 1997). Both the agent and principal are much interested in maximising benefits that accrue to them. The agent in agricultural companies for example want more benefits in form of bonuses, shareholding reward and other perquisites which are regarded by their principal as additional expenditure that will limit the amount of profit to be distributed to the shareholders in form of dividend.

Panda and Leepsa (2017), recommend that agency problem can be minimised by establishing strong information structure and entering into an outcome-based contract. It is however, discovered that this theory was unable to tottaly eradicate the conflict between the stakeholders in an organisation. The limitation of the agency theory therefore led the emergency of

stewardship theory (Krisnawati et al., 2014). Based on this limitation this study will seek alternative theory in the development of theoretical farmework.

3.2.2 Emergence of stewardship theory

Theory is a set of concept that are logically presented to describe the phenomenon to be investigated. Theory can be predictive, explanatory or descriptive (Varpio et al., 2020) and should be capable of supporting the theoretical framework and conceptual framework to be adopted or developed.

Davis et al.(1997) found that agency theory is the major paradigm that underlies the management, governance and business research but has become limited as a result of the complexities and flexibiliites of business environment and business entity such a the agricultural companies in the South-West Nigeria. The agency theory focuses mainly on the extrinsic reward such as bonus and dividend accruing to stakeholders in an organisation. The tangible and measurable extrinsic rewards are regarded as the main control mechanism in agency theory. The limitations of the agency theory such as managers being view as an opportunitic agent and over concentration on certainty (Panda and Leepsa, 2017) has led to the emergence of the stewardship theory. Unders stewardship theory the executives are seen as stewards motivated by the interest of their principal rather than as an agent with conflicting interest (Davis et al., 1997).

The stewardship theory is based on the premise that the executives who are the stewards have a collective behavior that are directed towards the developmet and acheivement of the their organisation goals and objectives. The benefits such as maximising the shareholders wealth, sale growth and increased profitability form the collective efforts will meet the conflicting need of the stakeholders in the business just as it is expected in the agricultural companies in the South-West Nigeria. However, the stewardship theory will not be adopted by this study as it only focuses on non-measurable intrinsic rewards such as job security, self-actualisation, growth and development. The theory. The stewardship theory is mainly in line with theory of Maslow's hierarchy of need propounded in the 40's. The theory believe executives and

manager are motivated by factors such as self-esteem, psychological need, afflictions and self-actualisation which is outside the scope of this study.

3.2.3 Evolution of stakeholders theory

In both qualitative and quantitative research the theories are set of idea or abstract description of the relationship between variables involved in an investigated phenomenon. There are so many theories that can inform the understanding of a study in management and business development (Varpio et al., 2020). One of such theory is the stakeholders theory which is based on value created for all stakeholders in corporate entity. Stakeholder theory is a management theory that focuses value created to meet the financial needs of all stakeholders such as shareholders, Government, employees, suppliers and communities objectively.

According to Freeman et al., (2010) stakeholders theory is majorly concerned about resolving the problem of trade, value creation and equity distribution of wealth generated among the stakeholders in the organisation. The theory is based on value creation for all parties that have interest in the organisation rather than focusing on maximising wealth of the shareholders. It also state that management and operation activities should be carried out in the interest of the stakeholders within and outside the company. The theory was in contrast with the stewardship theory which state that the stewards (managers) should be motivated by the interest of the shareholders who are the owners of the business (Davis et al., 1997; Panda and Leepsa, 2017).

The stakeholders theory is different from the shareholders theory which state that the main reason for the existence of business is to make profit and maximises the shareholder wealth (Krisnawati et al., 2014). Unlike the shareholders theory, the stakeholders covers the interest of all parties in the organisation. The stakeholders theory, believe the fulfillment and satisfaction of all interest parties objectively will lead to the growth and development of the company. The theory did not considers how the development of the organisation should be sustained which is the main focus of this study (Krisnawati et al., 2014; Freeman et al., 2010). This study will however adopt the stakeholders theory in addition with sustainable development theory which

is based on the long-term innovation and conservation of companies and the economy at large (Krisnawati et al., 2014).

3.2.4 The perspective of the sustainable development theory

This study is based on sustainable development of agricultural companies in a developing nation. For a quality research output there is a need for the adoption of an appropriate theory that will inform the development of an effective theoretical framework and consequently a reliable conceptual framework (Varpio et al., 2020). The sustainable development theory seems to be the relevant theory that will fill the gap identified under stakeholder theory in the development of the theoretical framework. Sustainable development is a development that meets the short-term goal of an organisation without sacrificing the future (Gwardzinska and Czyzowicz, 2021).

Sustainable development theory is an extension of the stakeholders theory. It is a theory that believes there is a relationship between the business environment and the business (Krisnawati et al., 2014). It believes the business is an open system that interacts with its environment both in the short-term and in the long-term. The theory bridges the gap uncovered by the stakeholders theory which is concerned for both long-term and short-term goals of an organisation. It is the theory adopted for this study as it is more appropriate for the area of sustainable development goals. The sustainable development goals (SDGs) agenda according to the United Nations include eradication of hunger, poverty, reduction of inequality, development of industry, innovation and infrastructure among other things (Gwardzinska and Czyzowicz, 2021). The scope of this study covers some of the agenda of the SDGs such as eradication of poverty, infrastructural development and agricultural companies development. Therefore, this study will adopt the sustainable development theory in addition to the stakeholders theory.

However, it is worthy to know that theoretical frameworks are very crucial to research output, be it qualitative, quantitative, or mixed methods research. All research either based on primary or secondary data should have a relevant,

valid and appropriate theoretical framework to justify the findings, significance and contribution of the study.

3.3 Summary and conclusion

This chapter gives insight into the theory adopted by this study for the development of the theoretical framework which was informed by the conceptual framework developed in chapter two of this study. The chapter gives theoretical background and the justification on the adoption of the stakeholders theory in conjunction with the sustainability development theory. It explains the basis and justification for the adoption of both theories in this study. It critically explained the justification which is based on both short-term and long-term sustainable development of the agricultural companies in the South-West Nigeria.

CHAPTER FOUR

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

4.1 Introduction

The literature reviewed provides a series of methodologies that deal with economic policy development and implementation in developing countries such as Malaysia and Nigeria. The literature review reveals that the most widely used methodologies are relativism and constructionism, while econometrics such as regression and correlation analysis are mostly used for analysis. However, as discovered in most of the literature reviewed, developing a research philosophy for a developing economic environment like Nigeria poses a serious challenge due to the lack of relevant data and confliction on few available data (Cervantes-Godoy and Dewbre, 2010). According to Easterby-Smith et al. (2012), methodologies are used to unravel complex real-world situations of an area of study, likewise, Dawson and Sinwell (2012) also discovered that adoption of the suitable methodology will help in reducing ethical problems such as protection of the identity of the participant and epistemological problems associated with social investigation such as identification of developmental factor in agricultural companies.

Most of the literature reviewed such as Hazell et al., (2010); Afolabi, (2015); Bergh, (2000) and Ibietan (2011) on the impact of agricultural policy on agricultural companies' development in developing nation like Nigeria has pinpointed a lack of effective framework as a major barrier to agricultural companies' development. Therefore, this section of the study entails the blueprint of the research philosophy and it will provide information on the criteria to be used to select participants from the selected companies, the research design that will be adopted for this study and the basis for the choice. The fact-finding techniques and data analysis method will also be described with a sequence that will be followed to carry out the investigation including the epistemology stance. The data collection and the analysis techniques are based on the developed theoretical framework in chapter three of this study. Stakeholders theory and sustainable development theory were adopted as the will help to identify the critical stakeholders and developmental variables in agricultural companies. The stakeholders theory will help to identify the interest of all parties

such the management; government and the relevant agencies; the shareholders and investors; agricultural workers and the affected community members. Furthermore, a discussion on validity and reliability and ethical principles as they affect this study will be included in this chapter of the study.

Figure 18 below shows the framework of the methodology which is similar to the structure of the earth with the core (Ontology) at the center and the outermost (methods and techniques) layer further from the center.

Source: Author (2020)

4.2 Research Philosophy

According to Doyle (2019) "It is a capital mistake to theorise before one has data" therefore, there is a need to take a philosophical position before embarking on research activity (Easterby-Smith et al., 2012). The philosophical positions entail the ontology which is concerned with the nature of existence and the reality which in this

study is the impact of agricultural policy and the epistemology which is about the justifiable means of inquiry into the impact of agricultural policy on agricultural companies' development in the Western part of Nigeria. The ontology that can be adopted includes realism, internal realism, relativism and nominalism while the common epistemology for social science are constructivism, positivism, critical realism, and interpretivism (Mingers et al., 2013; Easterby-Smith et al., 2012). Realism is a philosophical view that separates the experience and knowledge of the researcher from reality or the nature of the existence of the study which in this study, is the impact of agricultural policy. Realism promotes independence between the nature of the research subject and researcher (Archer et al., 1998) thereby eliminating the subjective nature of humans which may be manifested by the researcher. The relativism paradigm is based on the view that ethical truth or knowledge about the nature of reality depends on individual experience or knowledge. Unlike realism which is systematic and scientific in approach, relativism is subjective as it is based on the assumption and the experience of the researcher (Fletcher, 1996).

Furthermore, positivism is an epistemological approach that underpins the application of the scientific method in social research to arrive at a testable result (Creswell, 2009). The positivism approach uses quantitative techniques such as questionnaires, statistics, and surveys to produce an objective result. Straub (1989) believes the positivism approach gives a high level of confidence in the work of the researcher through the validation process involved in the use of the scientific methodology. Moreover, interpretivism is a pro-qualitative approach to social science research. The interprets view human beings as complex and dynamic individuals with different ways of reacting to issues and as a result, should not be analysed scientifically. Likewise, Easterby-Smith et al. (2012) believe it will be more appropriate to use a qualitative method such as interviews and participant observation to obtain results involving social research. The major limitation of interpretivism is the subjectivity and non-repeatability of the result.

However, constructivism is a philosophical approach based on the assumption of reality being constructed from the experience and idea of individuals involved (Easterby-Smith et al., 2012). The constructionist believes progress or development in the social environments is as a result of the accommodation of new experiences

through the adjustment of the mental model (Raskin, 2008). The major drawback of this approach is the lack of standard procedure in its application in social science research. Nonetheless, critical realism is an approach that lies in between positivism and interpretivism. The approach was developed for scientific research, but it has proved effective when applied in social science research (Mingers, 2004). It is a suitable approach for mixed-method research design as it combines the features of both positivism and interpretivism approach (Zachariadis et al., 2010). Critical realism is appropriate for study with diverse methodologies and different fields of study such as Knowledge based, social, and conceptual studies (Mingers, 2004).

The development of the appropriate epistemology perspective for this study will therefore aid the gathering, collection, analysis, interpretation, and understandability of data and information gathered as indicated in the various literature reviewed such as Micah and Ruth (2014) and Iwuchukwu and Igbokwe (2012). It will enable this study to overcome most of the limitations discovered in the literature reviewed such as lack of data, conflict among secondary data sources, and lack of regulatory framework. Ethical limitations in the form of company rules on confidentialities and human complexities like the state of mind of the respondents at the time of the survey (Ishola and Ishola, 2003) will also be minimised.

The literature reviewed in this area of the study shows that most authors such as Coase (1960), Dardek (2015), Talbot and Reeves (1997) and Williamson (1970) adopted relativism as ontology and constructivism as epistemology, while few authors such as Moss & Schmitz (2013), Micah and Ruth (2014), and Iwuchukwu and Igbokwe (2012) adopted Positivism. The idea of using constructivism with relativism was dropped because it does not accommodate cultural diversity and limitations in reconciling discrepancies in data generated (Easterby-Smith, et al., 2012) which are significant characteristics of the area of study.

This research shall be a mixed design as a result of it being exploratory, through the review of various related literature and causal in terms of identification of the relationship between agricultural policy and agricultural companies' development. Consequently, the mixed/triangulation method which shall comprise both the quantitative and qualitative methods (Creswell, 2009; Tashakkori and Teddlie 2003) shall be adopted. The conjugative mixed-method will be adopted because it will help

in integrating theories which will lead to greater accuracy (Jick, 1979) in the area of data collection and analysis, provide detailed reasons why things occur, through the measurement of the relationship between the agricultural policy and developmental factors and boost credibility and validity of the outcome of the study (Tashakkori and Teddlie, 2003; Crosswell, 2009). It also encourages creative thinking and allows diverse views which may not be possible where either of the methods is considered.

However, for this study, the Ontology shall be internal realism because the truth about this study exists but the fact cannot be easily accessed due to lack of data (Putnam, 1987; Easterby-Smith, et al., 2012) in Nigeria, while the epistemology approach for this study shall be the critical realism developed by Roy Bhaskar in the 70s and used in social science investigations by researchers such as Mingers (2004), Archer et al., (1998) and Sayer (2000) because it harmonises the features of different forms of ontology and epistemology (Mingers et al., 2013).

The main reason for the use of critical realism is to avoid some of the limitations discovered in most of the methodologies used in the literature reviewed such as difficulties in analysis and interpretation as expressed by Afolabi (2015), lack of accommodation of cultural differences and lack of credibility of data as stated by Cervantes Godoy and Dewbre (2010).

Moreover, the adoption of critical realism will serve as a theoretical lens for the determination of how national economic policy can use to aid agricultural companies' development in the Western part of Nigeria and the development of appropriate regulatory models which according to Micah and Ruth (2014) is lacking in Nigeria. The critical realism is also appropriate for this study as a result of the following:

- *It accepts objective reality exists and relationships about those realities exist like in positivism.*
- *It harmonises the features of different forms of ontology and epistemology (Mingers et al., 2013).*
- *critical realist position is that much of reality exists and operates independently of our awareness or knowledge of it.*
- *critical realism is critical about the justification of causation, agency, structure, etc. of reality.*

- *it is an open flexible approach that encourages creativity and flexibility in the application and rejection of methodologies (Archer et al., 2016) just as in interpretivism.*

4.3 Research design and method

The research design being a mixed method shall comprise of both quantitative and qualitative data in the area such as regulatory and theoretical framework, the effect of corruption, externalities, the return on capital employed of agricultural companies, the frequency of corporate failure in Nigeria, the level of compliance with corporate law of the country, etc. and will further be analysed and interpreted using statistical techniques such as regression (ordered logit) and correlation matrix with the aid of software such as Gretl, SPSS and (AI) Python.

The artificial intelligence is the use of machine learning or technology to display human intelligence (Wang, 2019) such as model development, data analysis, cognitive tasks and presentation of complex decision. The intelligence include development of models (Heat map), framework, structures and any other problem-solving architecture. This study will therefore, adopt Numpy which is Python library most suitable for data analysis and model development.

However, In the course of the literature review, various methods were identified as being suitable for this research, for example, Afolabi (2015) used Narrative-Textual Case Study and interview, Luken (2006) adopted a case study and survey, Hazell et al. (2010) used literature review, Micah and Ruth (2014) believed questionnaire is more appropriate, while Iwuchukwu and Igbokwe (2012) used time-series approach. Considering the complexity of this study the triangulation method refers to as the conjunctive mixed method by Mertens and Hesse-Biber (2012), which integrate both the qualitative and quantitative methods shall be adopted.

The qualitative research design is a descriptive form of measures that are based on more in-depth text or information gathered through a non-statistical instrument (Creswell, 2003). It is more suitable for the interpretivists. In contrast to quantitative, the qualitative design is a dynamic design that is systematic, demanding, and discipline approach, but can be time-consuming and lack repeatability. According to Mehrad and Zangeneh (2019), the qualitative design usually focuses on phenomena about reality and the study of phenomena like in this study where the interview will be

used to gather data about the impact of agricultural policies on agricultural companies development in South-West Nigeria. Nonetheless, the phenomenological method, ethnographic model, grounded theory method, case study, historical model, and narrative model are the common types of qualitative research while the common data collection instruments are interviews, observations, focus groups, and action research. The quantitative design, however, is a paradigm that is based on a numeric value that can be measure objectively and analysed using a statistical test (Mehrad and Zangeneh, 2019). The quantitative design though objective but mostly use statistical manipulation to reduce ideas. Furthermore, it is less in-depth but the results are repeatable. Since it underpins the deductive testing of theory It is the most effective paradigm for research carried out by a positivist. It is mostly used because it is scientific, objective focused, and acceptable for social science research (Creswell 2003; Walker 1985).

Considering the limitation of both the qualitative and quantitative methods, the adoption of the triangulation method will synthesis the benefit of both design in this study which will increase the validity of the outcome of this research (Creswell, 2003), likewise, Mertens and Hesse-Biber (2012) believe triangulation that integrates qualitative and quantitative data will enhance comprehensive framework development. In the same vein, Zachariadis et al., (2013) believe that mixed-method research in a critical realist epistemology will aid validity and causation methods such as the impact of agricultural policy on return agricultural companies through linking of theory with the method.

The qualitative method shall be used to gather a large volume of data from the perspective of participants (Walker, 1985) on the impact of agricultural policies on agricultural companies' development. The qualitative methods for this study shall be questionnaires and interviews.

4.4 Data collection activities

The data collection method is the fact-finding procedure adopted for the extraction and measuring of data that will aid the provision of answers to the research questions or testing of the hypothesis (Walker, 1985). The adoption of a suitable data collection method will aid the collection activities in a study and facilitates the outcome or result

of a study (Zachariadis et al., 2013). Creswell (2003), believes the adoption of mixed-method will underpin the data collection activities of a study. Similarly, Easterby-Smith et al. (2012), believes a combination of qualitative and quantitative method in form of compensatory design will influence the quality of research output under conjunctive mixed design adopted for this study. Likewise, Mertens and Hesse-Biber (2012) believe that under conjunctive mixed method both the qualitative and quantitative will be integrated, with qualitative methods such as interview as used by some of the authors of literature reviewed like Micah and Ruth (2014) to extract data from respondents while the quantitative methods such as questionnaire and regression analysis as used by Iwuchukwu and Igbokwe (2012) for analysis and testing of a causal relationship (Shavelon and Towne, 2002) between a dependent and independent variable like the impact of agricultural policies on return on capital employed of agricultural companies in South-Western Nigeria.

For effective primary data collection, questionnaires was distributed to respondents selected from the targeted thirty (30) firms, five (5) private agricultural companies with an average turnover of fifty (50) million naira (£25,000) from each of the six (6) states in the region of study. The questionnaire was typewritten with a 5-point Likert scale and each question requiring the respondents to state whether or not he/she strongly agree, agree, undecided, disagree, or strongly disagree with the statements, the questions are close-ended. A 5-point Likert scale was considered because the option is neither too short as in the 3-point scale nor too long as in the 7-point scale, it is also the most commonly used psychometric tool in the Business and management research, and it is basically useful for gathering data related to issues such as attitude, perceptions, traits and opinion (Joshi et al., 2015). Double barrel questions shall be avoided and the issues in the questions shall be straight to the point. The questionnaire shall be distributed to the respondent and collected back after an hour from the respondents directly.

However, the questionnaire and interview were structured to ask questions on the impact of national economic policy on agricultural companies' development and how the national economic policy has influence agricultural business in recent time based on gaps identified in the literature reviewed, data from national and international agencies such as Bureau of Statistics and World Bank. It will also be used to solve the problem of inadequate data which is a major challenge in some of the developing

nations like Nigeria as specified in most literature reviewed and also discovered during a visit to the Bureau of statistics in Nigeria at the commencement of this study.

Also, as a form of qualitative data collection, Nine (9) members of the board of directors of the selected companies were interviewed. The Nine (9) participants were selected randomly from the thirty (30) selected companies within the South-West region. The interviews were conducted on a face-to-face basis, using pre-printed questions around the impact of economic policy on agricultural companies development within the region.

Before the field collection of data, A limited pilot study was conducted using four (4) participants. The participants were selected from four agricultural companies in South West Nigeria. The participants were interviewed followed by the administration of questionnaires using initial interview questions and questionnaires. The outcome of the pilot study, however, resulted in minor amendments in both interview questions and questionnaires in areas such as policy transmission mechanism and return on capital employed by agricultural companies.

The statistical techniques was further used to analyse data gathered through the quantitative method. The statistical techniques such as regression analysis (ordered logit) and correlation as used in some of the literature reviewed like Iwuchukwu and Igbokwe (2012) in which regression analysis was used to reveal the challenge of the regulatory framework in Nigeria, correlation analysis was used by Adams (2016) to revealed lack of diversification of Nigerian economy was adopted for this study. Likewise, the augmented dickey-fuller test was used by Yusuf and Akinlade (2011) for incidence analysis of agricultural trade and exchange rate policies. Both the correlation and regression analysis was adopted based on their simplicity and reliability in the estimation and analysis of data. Luck and Rubin (1989) identify the factors to be considered in selecting the method of data analysis as what the analytical technique intends to show, the scale by which variables are measured, number of variables to be investigated, dependence versus independence, numbers of the sample involved. These factors will be considered during the analysis and interpretation of data in this study.

The data collected through the interviews on the other hand were further analysed using narrative analysis technique. This technique was adopted because is an

analysis technique that aid production of information based on social environment under study (Gilbert, 2008) and systematic analysis of data based on the expression of the respondents (Josselson, 2012). It also considered the human and social experience as well as relationship between cultural context and individual perspectives (Clandinin & Connelly, 2000).

4.4.1 Total population

Easterby-Smith et al. (2012) refer to the total population as a complete set of an entity that relates to an area of interest, which in this study, is the Western part of Nigeria. The total population of this research is, therefore, the total number of agricultural companies within the Western region of the country. However, due to the lack of data on the total number of agricultural companies within the region a random selection of companies across the six states within the region was adopted for this study. The lack of adequate data in developing nations like Nigeria was discovered during the review of the literature of authors such as Hazell et al. (2010), Owombo et al. (2012) and Cervantes Godoy and Dewbre (2010). Random selection is a sample size in which every entity (agricultural company) within the population (South-West Nigeria) has an equal probability of being selected (Easterby-Smith et al., 2012).

The potential limitation of missing out on parts of the population was prevented through the selection of agricultural companies from all states within the region. It was discovered during the literature review that authors such as Owombo et al., (2012) who have conducted related research on the region, adopted the random sampling technique in the selection of their samples due to lack of regional data on agricultural companies in Nigeria. However, through the random sampling, thirty (30) top private Agricultural firms in terms of revenue from cash crops across the six states (five from each state) was selected. The targeted firms include both private and public companies operating in the states within the region.

4.4.2 Sample size

Easterby-Smith et al. (2012) refers to Sample as a subset drawn from the population from which facts or traits about the population can be gathered and through the inferential task draw conclusion about the population or the entity which in this study

is the agricultural companies in the Western part of Nigeria. Sim et al. (2018), believe sample size can be determined through the rule of thumb, conceptual model, numerical guidelines or statistical formulae approach. They concluded that 'it is not the size of the sample that matters, it is what the researcher does with the sample that counts. For this study, the conceptual model approach shall be adopted. The approach shall be based on the complexity of the study, the aim of the study, the underlying theoretical framework and the proposed statistical technique to be adopted (Taherdoost, 2017). Based on the complexity of this study, the participants from the thirty (30) agricultural companies were selected based on status at work (junior staff, middle management level and top management level) and educational qualification (diploma certificate, degree, postgraduate qualification, and professional qualification). The respondents were selected by applying random sampling on classification based on educational qualification and status at work. The number of participants from each category was selected using the measure of central tendency (the arithmetical mean of the population in each category). On completion of the data collection process, the econometric (Regression and correlation analysis) was further be used to analyse the data gathered through the questionnaire while narrative analysis was used to analyse the data collected through the interview. However, the table below shows the framework of the research philosophy adopted.

Table 14: Summary of the methodology

Ontologies	Internal realism
Epistemology	Critical Realism
methodology	
Aims	Discovery
Starting points	Questions
Designs	Surveys and interviews

Data types	Numbers and facts
Analysis/interpretation	Correlation, Chi-square and regression and narrative analysis
Outcomes	Hypothesis testing and model generation

Source: Author (2020)

4.5 Data analysis

"One of the myths about research is that it is an ivory tower" (Easterby-Smith, et al., 2012: 76) with a sequence of activities depending on each other. Therefore, the data collection activities will precede the analysis of data gathered. Data analysis is the link between the data collection activities and the inference drawn from the sample collected (Huck, 2007). As indicated above the data collection instruments for this project is both qualitative in form of interviews and quantitative in form of questionnaires with a five point Likert scale.

The data gathered through the interview can be analysed through the use of natural language analysis such as content analysis, grounded analysis, argument analysis, discourse analysis, thematic analysis and narrative analysis (Easterby-Smith, et al., 2012). The narrative analysis will be used to analyse the qualitative data gathered through interviews. For quality analysis software called Nvivo shall be used to support the narrative analysis. The narrative analysis was adopted because it focuses on the sequence of event and the role of various parties in the event; it offers insight into the issues at hand (Sims, 2003) and aids the development of a complex picture of the situation (Easterby-Smith, et al., 2012) which is the impact of agricultural policy on agricultural development in this research.

Furthermore, the quantitative data gathered through the questionnaire will be analysed using regression and bivariate correlation. The analysis will be carried out through Gretl, SPSS and artificial intelligence such as Python Anaconda. The application of artificial intelligence in this study through the use of Python software aid the analysis of large volume of data which will be generated through questionnaire (Wang, 2019). However, features such a heath-map and algorithms model in the Python will aid the design and the development of a reliable and robust models.

The regression and bivariate correlation adopted in this study will help to determine the strength of the relationship between variables (Huck, 2007) such as the relationship between agricultural policy and return on capital employed by agricultural companies. The regression with the support of statistical software and artificial intelligence will aid the development of a complex model that will provide answers to the research questions and objectives.

4.6 Validity and Reliability

Validity is the measure of the truth or falsity of the data gathered through data collection instruments during investigation or research. Taherdoost (2016, pg.2) refers to validity as "measuring the area of investigation purported to measure" while Huck (2007: 88) describes reliability as a level of consistency in the output of a research measuring instrument. Taherdoost (2016) further classified validity into content validity, construct validity, face validity and criterion validity.

The face validity entails readability, use of unambiguous language and relevance of the content of the measuring instrument (Taherdoost 2016; Oluwatayo 2012) which in this study is the questionnaires. The face validity of the questionnaire to be used for data collection in this study shall be determined through the application of Cohen's Kappa Index (CKI). The content validity of the questionnaire of this study shall also be tested to ensure that sufficient and related facts (Straub et al., 2004; Taherdoost, 2016; Easterby-Smith, et al., 2012) about this study extracted during literature reviews such as information on the regulatory framework, transmission mechanism, etc. are included in the questionnaire and all insignificant facts are eliminated from the questionnaire of this study. The opinion of my supervisory team

being expert in the field of research was also considered before concluding the content validity of this study.

The construct validity however, test how logical the concept and ideas of this study are transformed into an operating reality which is the development of a conceptual model in this study. The construct validity also tested the expected related variables such as how crop productivity and profitability are related, while those with no correlation are regarded as not related (Oluwatayo 2012). The principal component analysis (PCA) as suggested by Taherdoost, (2016) in his paper as most appropriate for verifying construct validity, was used to measure the construct validity of this study.

The criterion validity on the other hand aimed at how well the adopted measuring instrument can effectively be used to predict the performance of variables involved in this study which is the relationship between agricultural policy and agricultural companies' development. Therefore, Validity defines how well data collected relate to the area of study, which in this study means how well the data collected through the questionnaires and interviews related to the measuring of the impact of agricultural policies on agricultural companies' development in the Western part of Nigeria.

However, Easterby-Smith et al. (2012) believes that validity of data in a study depends on the epistemological stance which in this study is critical realism due to the complexities of the area of study in terms of availability of facts and structural framework as stated in most literature review on the area of study. It is imperative to evaluate the reliability of the research instrument along with the validity of the data collected.

Reliability on the other hand is the degree of consistency or stability of instruments used in measuring the research variables (Huck and Cormier, 1996; Taherdoost, 2016). According to Huck and Cormier (1996), the reliability of research can be evaluated using test-retest reliability, alternate-forms reliability, internal consistency reliability, or interrater reliability. The coefficient of reliability, however, lies between 0.00 and +1.00. The higher the coefficient the more reliable the measuring instrument. The test-retest reliability is a technique in which a group of variables is tested twice

using the same measuring instrument but at a different interval to determine the coefficient of stability of the instrument.

The alternate-forms reliability entails the use of two forms of same instruments to measure a similar attribute of a group of variables within a short period to evaluate the coefficient of equivalence (Oluwatayo, 2012), such as the correlation between the speed and accuracy of research participants. Internal consistency reliability involves breaking down the variables into parts or subsets such as odd and even numbers, before testing each of the parts with the same measuring instrument and results further analysed with statistical technique.

The internal consistency basically measured the correlation of homogeneity. The internal can be based on the split-half reliability coefficient, K-R 20, or Cronbach's alpha technique. However, interrater reliability evaluates the reliability of the research instrument by measuring the coefficient of concordance of various objects using raters measures such as Cohen's Kappa and interclass correlation (Huck and Cormier, 1996). This study reliability test is based on internal consistency reliability with tests carried out on a pre and post-experimental basis using a mock survey for pre-experimental. The reliability of the findings is then tested through correlation or regression analysis using a statistical package such as Python or SPSS. For a high-quality output from this study, both reliability and validity tests shall be given due attention.

4.7 Ethics and Confidentiality.

Ethical dilemmas should be a focal point of any researcher involved in a study as researchers are often faced with ethical dilemmas such as informed consent, beneficence, and respect for confidentiality (Fouka and Mantzorou, 2011) in the process of investigation and data gathering, which involved the use of employees of organisations as participants in a study. Research ethics is a critical process of reflection on human activities to evaluate the values that underpin the study (Guillemin and Gillam, 2004). Ferreira and Serpa (2018) believe that ethics should be viewed as a dynamic process aimed at guiding and supporting the professional judgment of a researcher which thus aids the quality of the study.

According to Guillemin and Gillam (2004), an ethical dimension entail procedural ethics and ethics in practice. The procedural ethics involve the submission of the project in plain language to the ethics committee for approval. It also includes explaining the methodology adopted with proof of competency in such methods (Roriz and Padez, 2017).

However, Ethics in practice are those ethical challenges that arise in the field of research. They are usually not planned for but arise as a result of interaction with the participants (Guillemin and Gillam, 2004). Fouka and Mantzorou (2011), believe that one of the critical ethics in practice dilemma is where researchers may need to align their methodology to suit the norms of the selected organization before, he/she can be allowed to access or collect data from such an institution. An illustrative example is when a researcher was told he/she cannot have direct contact with the participants who are the employee of an organisation during the survey.

As a form of rules, guidelines, or precept Bell and Bryman (2007) identified ethical principle a researcher can use to minimise ethical dilemmas. The ethical principle according to Bell and Bryman (2007) dignity, informed consent, privacy, harm to participant, confidentiality, affiliation, reciprocity, honesty and transparency, deception, anonymity, and misrepresentation. The applicability of these principles in a study are briefly explained below:

Informed consent - The principle of ensuring research participants and organisations involved freely consent to participate in the research.

Harm to participant - The assurance that no physical or psychological harm will be inflicted on the research participants or their organisation during and after the research processes.

Confidentiality - The requirement of utmost care in the preservation of data collected from individuals and organisations involved in the study.

Affiliation - The need to declare any information that may influence the independence of the researcher such as personal affiliation, sponsorship, and funding.

Reciprocity - The principle of mutual benefits to all parties involved or collaboration between participants and the researcher in a study.

Honesty and transparency - *The principle of utmost good faith in communicating all facts to the parties involved in a research study.*

Anonymity - *The need for the protection of the organisation and individual participant anonymity*

Misrepresentation - *The principle which seeks the avoidance of transmitting misleading or false information or misrepresenting research findings*

Dignity - *Principle of ensuring there is mutual respect between the researcher and the participant including their organisation such as avoidance of question that may lead to anxiety or discomfort.*

Privacy - *The need to ensure the protection of privacy of the research subject where necessary.*

Deception - *The need for a mechanism that will prevent deceptive behaviour in the research processes.*

However, the ethical perspective for this study shall be built on the view of the Bell and Bryman (2007), as a result of the epistemological stance of this project, which is critical realism and the conjunctive mix-method approach. Informed consent is a major ethical issue which according to Fouka and Mantzorou (2011) means that a participant voluntarily, knowingly, and intelligently with a sound mind gives consent to participate in a survey. For this study, the informed consent shall incorporate the right of participants and prevent assaults on the integrity of the participants or their organisation through the incorporation of the purpose of the study as well as a brief explanation about the research topic as an introductory part of the questionnaire.

The ethical principle of beneficence which means to be of benefit by ensuring no harm is inflicted on participants involved in a study (Easterby-Smith et al., 2012) will also be given due attention. Fouka and Mantzorou (2011) think that beneficence also includes the protection of participants from emotional harm, physiological social, and economic harm. The imminent harm in this study which will be prevented through the protection of confidentiality and privacy of participants are social and economic harms to the employees of selected organisations in form of termination of

employment by their organisation. Easterby-Smith et al. (2012) believe that respect for confidentiality entails all steps that needed to be taken by the researcher in ensuring that the confidentiality of research data is not compromised.

Furthermore, confidentiality is based on the principle of precautionary measures which require due care in the storage and protection of confidential data (Ferreira and Serpa, 2018) generated in the course of study. For confidentiality of data and protection of the privacy of participants involved in data collection of this study an anonymity design questionnaire shall be adopted and where necessary the names shall be made optional. However, the policies of the organization such as government agencies on which research is to be carried out or its employees may hinder the success of the research.

Nonetheless, some organisations may expect the researcher to do something more practical with the data released while the researcher aims to collect and analyse to draw a theoretical conclusion about the data gathered" (Dawson and Sinwell, 2012). For example, an organization may be politically motivated to "force a researcher to report positive findings" (Easterby-Smith et al., 2012) about an individual in the entity or about the entity itself for political gain. Also, the confidentiality principles or norms of the entity may make the employee of the organization reluctant in responding to the questionnaire of the researcher.

For the avoidance of misleading research reports, due care will be exercised (Mukungu, 2017) to ensure transparency and honesty in reporting the findings of this study. However, during the study, the confidentiality of data collected will be maintained by taken cognizance of the dignity of the potentials respondent and avoid deception during the research study. The type one and type two errors which may inhibit the honesty and transparency of the outcome of the research will also be avoided as much as possible to make the report reliable for the policymakers and other stakeholders such as the agricultural companies and government agencies in the agricultural sector of the region. The political challenges that are envisaged during this research shall include lack of adequate attention from the top management of the organization; limitations that arise out of non-disclosure agreement; lack of cooperation from respondents especially the government employees.

4.8 Summary and conclusion

This chapter gives insight into the framework of the methodology adopted, the validity and reliability consideration, and ethical guidelines for the study. Based on the analysis of the various methodology of papers reviewed and in line with the complexity of the study, critical realism was adopted as the epistemology of the study while internal realism as ontology with mixed-method for data collection. The questionnaires and interviews were the most suitable data collection instrument while the statistical techniques such as regression and correlation are adopted for further analysis of data gathered through the data collection instruments. Nonetheless, the narrative method will be used to analyse the qualitative data gathered through the interview with a few top management of the selected companies. The respondents for this study are employees from thirty (30) agricultural firms (Five from each state) selected randomly across the six states in the region of study.

To ensure validity, face validity, content validity, construct validity, and criterion validity shall be given due consideration while internal consistence reliability will be adopted for this study. Furthermore, to prevent ethical dilemmas and to stimulate the output of the research ethical principles such as informed consent, beneficence, respect for confidentiality, dignity, harm to participant, affiliation, reciprocity, honesty and transparency, deception, anonymity and misrepresentation will be applied in the course of this study. The application of these principles will serve as a protective instrument for both the researcher and the respondents of this study.

Chapter Five

Qualitative Results and Findings

5.1 Introduction

This research was carried out to determine the impact of national economic policy on corporate sector development with a focus on agricultural companies' development in southwest Nigeria. The study adopted a conjugative mixed method design which comprises both qualitative and quantitative methods (Jick, 1979 and Easterby-Smith et al., 2012). The data collection and analysis was based on the perspective of stakeholders theory and the sustainable economic development theory. The theories help to identify the critical stakeholders interest and the sustainable developmental variable that aided the quality of the this study. Being a mixed method, the result and findings were therefore, splitted into two chapters, the qualitative results and findings and the quantitative results and findings. Furthermore, the data gathered was analysed using narrative analysis and inferential statistics for the interview and the survey respectively.

5.2 Process of qualitative data collection and analysis

This section aims to analyse and present the qualitative results and findings from the data gathered through the interview conducted for this research. According to Yin (2003) data for research can be extracted from different sources such as documents, observations, and interviews. As stated above, interviews and surveys were adopted as data collection instruments for this study. The qualitative data collected through the interview provide detailed and rich information that will lead to understanding and exploring of viewpoint (Arksey and Knight, 1999) of major stakeholders in the agricultural sector which is the area of this study. Under the qualitative study, interview questions can be unstructured or semi-structured (Bryman, 2004).

This study, therefore, adopted semi-structured interviews as a means of collecting qualitative primary data. The semi-structured interview was adopted as it aids the researcher to dig deep to uncover the truth and the making of choices on which question to explore further or to discard (Easterby-Smith et al., 2012; Arksey and Knight, 1999). The interview was, however, conducted on nine (9) stakeholders in

the agricultural companies within South-West Nigeria. The interviewees were randomly selected from the top management of the selected companies across the six states in the South-West region of the country. The interview was conducted through a semi-structured face-to-face interview which as a result it provides first-hand information and data that is based on the current practices and experience of the respondents (Easterby-Smith et al., 2012) as a player in the agricultural companies in the South-West region of the country.

Following the collection of the through the semi-structured interview, the narrative analysis technique was adopted as stated under the methodology chapter. According to Gilbert (2008) narrative analysis is an analysis technique that aids the understanding of the social environment and the production of information or data. Narrative analysis is also an analysis technique that synthesises human and social experience over a period and considers the relationship between cultural context and individual experience (Clandinin and Connelly, 2000; Easterby-Smith et al., 2012). Likewise, Josselson (2012) is of opinion that narrative analysis is a means through which data are systematically gathered, analysed, and narrate people’s opinions as expressed by them. Therefore, considering the nature of this study narrative analysis technique was adopted to express respondents' views the way they are expressed. The interview questions were structured to allow the respondents to discuss and express their opinion concerning their experience on agricultural practices as they relate to agricultural development in South-West Nigeria. For the purpose of confidentiality, the interviewees were coded as participants P1, P2 etc (See table 15). Nonetheless, the interview questions administered can be found in appendix 1 while the list of respondents is expressed in table 15 below.

Table 15: Interview participant’s structure

Participant ID	PARTICIPANT	POSITION	LOCATION
P1	Participant 1	Agricultural Entrepreneur/Consultant	Lagos State
P2	Participant 2	Agricultural Entrepreneur	Ogun State
P3	Participant 3	Manager	Oyo State
P4	Participant 4	Farm Manager	Osun State

P5	Participant 5	Agricultural General Manager/Entrepreneur	Ogun State
P6	Participant 6	Agricultural Entrepreneur	Lagos State
P7	Participant 7	Agricultural Entrepreneur	Ogun State
P8	Participant 8	Manager	Ogun State
P9	Participant 9	Agricultural Entrepreneur	Ogun State

However, before discussing the results and findings of the interview in detail, it is worthy to acknowledge the importance of the consent form being included within the research and the use of participant information sheets. The participant information sheet aided understanding of the participants on the reason for carrying out this study and the consent form was used as a sort of an agreement to partake in the research and to document their consent. The participant information sheet and the consent form can both be found in appendix 2 and 3.

5.2.1 Familiarization and preparation of the qualitative data

For effective analysis of the qualitative data, there is a need for the familiarisation and preparation of the result of the interview by the researcher. According to Easterby-Smith et al. (2012), it is important to understand the source of the qualitative data which is the transcript and the ideas or concept which is the code generated from the transcript before the commencement of the data analysis. The familiarization through transcription and coding will serve as the initial process of qualitative data analysis. The emergent codes, therefore, will form the independent theme or concept for the study.

Based on narrative analysis which is a form of storytelling approach (Easterby-Smith et al., 2012) adopted by this study, an open coding process was used to generate independent ideas. Open coding is a procedure through which interview transcripts or raw qualitative data are disintegrated into smaller units of meaning (Corbin and

Strauss,1990; Goulding, 2002). In this research, open codes were generated from the transcript, and they form the independent concept applied in this chapter.

However, the text below is a sample of how codes were developed from interview transcripts through the open coding process:

*“The national economic policy has not aided the agricultural development [**no influence**] due to lack proper planning [**improper planning**] and policy based on external forces due to aid received from the developed nation such as UK and US. Also putting a square peg in a round hole [**wrong allocation of staff**] is another barrier to the influence of national economic policy on agricultural development. The region also plans on what it does not have [**Improper planning**] such as planning on aid which focuses on the individual rather [**lack of framework**] than on agricultural companies. Policy focuses more on peasant farmers rather than agricultural companies” (Participant 1).*

It is worthy to know that in the process of developing the codes through the open coding process some independent concepts were developed, such as “no influence” and “lack of framework”. These concepts were categorised, reviewed, linked as suggested by Eaves (2001) and used in the discussion of the findings from the interview.

5.3 Interview Analysis and Findings

5.3.1 Influence of economic policy on agricultural companies development

Research objective 1.

To critically explore economic policy scenarios that can lead to agricultural company development through agricultural policy analysis.

Research question 1

Has the national economic policy been used to **aid the development** of agricultural companies in South-West Nigeria?

Findings:

The main theme of this question was the influence of national economic policy on agricultural companies development in South-West Nigeria. The aim and objective of the question were to critically explore how the national economic policy has been

used to aid the development of agricultural companies in Nigeria with a focus on the South-West region of the country. However, most of the participants believe that the national economic policy has not significantly aided the development of agricultural development in the region.

P1 thinks that the national economic policy has not aided the agricultural companies development due to improper planning and as a result of policies being based on external forces because of aids and grants received from the developed nations such as the United Kingdom and the United State of America. This was in consonance with the view of Haruna (2023) who believe proper planning and implementation of national economic policy with aid sustainable economic development as there seems to be a positive relationship between sustainable economic development and agricultural output. The foreing aids and the grants meant for agricultural development are, however, believed to have been fraudulently received by the non-agrarian who have diverted the fund to non-agricultural businesses. This has result to insignificant development in the agricultural sector.

"putting a square peg in a round hole is another barrier to the influence of national economic policy on agricultural companies development"
(P1, 2021).

It was also stressed that the region also plans on what it does not have such as planning on aid which focus on individual rather than on agricultural companies and also believes that the Policies seems to focus more on peasant farmers rather than agricultural companies.

P2 on the other hand thinks that the national economic policy is too centralised and the stakeholders in the agricultural sector are not aware of the policy and therefore does not aid the development of agricultural companies in South-West Nigeria. The view of P2 was in line with the opinion of Anam et al. (2024) who think the government and its agencies must work with critical stakeholder holders within and outside the country if there is going to be a sustainable development that will lead to the developemnt of agricultural companies and by extension improvement in the standard of living and alleviationof poverty. This implies that the decentralisation of establishment and implementation of policy with cooperation with critical

stakeholders on regional or state basis will influence the development of corporate organisation such as agricultural companies in South-West.

"The lack of awareness and sensitization is a major impediment to the awareness and influence of the policies as the agrarian are not involved in the development of the policy, as a result, it is being seen as an academic paper" (P2, 2021).

In line with P1 and P2, P3 is also believed the economic policy has not been used to aid agricultural companies in South-West Nigeria. P3 thinks it is because most stakeholders such as agricultural companies in the agricultural sector in the region are not even aware of the economic policy. It was however believe that the stakeholders are excluded in the process of formulation and development of policies by the policymakers.

"Some companies are not even aware there is a national policy that can aid their development. This is because the information is not well disseminated by government and its agencies" (P3, 2021).

P4 believe the benefit of the agricultural sector are usually diverted to the Northern part of the country as the government believes that the region is more into agriculture or at a disadvantage when compared to the South.

"Honestly speaking I don't think the national economic policy has been used to aid agricultural companies development in Nigeria" (P4, 2021).

Furthermore, it was stated that most of the intervention funds both local and international funds are channelled toward the region. P4 therefore, concluded that the national economic policy has not aided the agricultural companies in South-West Nigeria. Consequently, it is believed there is a regional bias in the implementation of agricultural policies in Nigeria.

However, P5 based on his working experiences in various agricultural companies within the region assert that agricultural development in Nigeria as a whole is nothing to write about after the discovery of oil. This was in line with the view of Haruna (2023) and Adeola and Adetunbi (2015) who both thinks the discovery of oil in commercial quantity has led to the manifestation of dutch disease. The dutch disease has hence resulted to neglect of agricultural sector and consequently a decline in the

agricultural output. P5 further explained that Nigeria as a nation including the South-West region was doing well in Agriculture, but the oil boom has made Nigeria neglect agriculture and the government also have been paying lip service to agriculture. We have not been having good government and governance.

"The government has not been very sincere with agriculture in South-West and other regions. The government are full of promises and where agricultural materials and input are provided, the government will give it to politicians who are not agriculturist" (P5, 2021).

P5, therefore, concluded that the national economic policy has not influenced or aided agricultural companies development in South West, unlike the Northern region. In contrast to other participants, P6 and p7 believe the stakeholders are excluded in the formulation of policy and as a result, most agricultural companies are not aware of the agricultural policies and their benefits. They responded to the question as:

"I will say yes and no. Yes, because as a component every government policy usually affects all-region including the South West region. No in the sense that the stakeholders such as agricultural companies are excluded in the formulation of the policy by the central government" (P6, 2021).

"In my opinion, not underestimating the government, the national economic policy has not been used to aid agricultural companies development. From my experience on the agricultural grant, all promises made by the government to the stakeholders in respect of agricultural development has not been fulfilled" (p7, 2021).

P6 further explained that in passing down the policy, the benefits are lost before getting to the intended beneficiaries like the agricultural companies in the South-West.

P6 and P7 therefore, concluded that the national economic policy has not aided the development of agricultural companies in the South-West because they are excluded during the process of policy formulation.

In line with other participants, P8 and P9 also agree that the national economic policy has not influenced the development of agricultural companies in any form with P8 and P9 citing the example of lack of agricultural infrastructural facilities as the bane of agricultural development in the South West Nigeria.

"Whenever we need tractors and fertilizers on the farmland the government has always failed in the provision of equipment as promised by the government and this always hinders the development of agricultural companies as a result of failure on the part of government and its agencies" (P8, 2021).

"Most of the barriers in agricultural development in South West are caused by government and those things that supposed to accrue to agricultural companies such as tractor, fertilisers etc. are given to non-farmer" (P9, 2021).

Both P8 and P9 concluded that the government in the South-West has only been paying lip service to agricultural development in South-West Nigeria. Therefore national economic policy has not been used to aid the development of agricultural companies in South- West.

The interview with the nine (9) participants suggested that the national economic policies have not been used to influence the development of agricultural companies in the South-West as a result of the non-inclusion of agricultural stakeholders in policy formulation. The findings also suggest that the government has only been paying lip service to agricultural development in South-West Nigeria. Another factor responsible is the lack of awareness of the national policy by the agricultural companies is due to lack of sensitisation by the government and its agencies. The findings from the participants were in line with some of the literature reviewed such as Adeola and Adetunbi (2015); Haruna (2023); Luken (2006) and Daneji (2011). Some of these authors believe the various policies and programmes established by the government has no meaningful positive impacts on agricultural companies development due to the lack of inclusion of all stakeholders in the planning and formulation of agricultural policies.

5.3.2 Agricultural models in South-West Nigeria

Research objective 2.

To develop a model using artificial intelligence, capable of establishing linkage between the agricultural policies and the agricultural companies development in South-West Nigeria.

Research question 2

Are there **models** on how agricultural policies can be used to influence the development of agricultural companies in South-West Nigeria?

Findings:

For agricultural companies in South-West Nigeria to experience a successful and sustainable development there must be an agricultural model that will aid the continuity of policy implementation in the region (Morrison and Schneider, 1987 and Ibietan, 2011). Therefore, this question was used to evaluate the existence of models capable of linking agricultural policies with agricultural development in South-West Nigeria.

However, in line with some of the literature reviews such as Hazell et al. (2010); Ibietan 2011; Iwuchukwu and Igbokwe (2012) and Afolabi (2015) the responses from some of the participants such as P1, P2, P3, P4, P6 and P9 indicates there used to be models in the 1960s and 1970's but those models have now been abandoned and only exist on paper. The models were abandoned as the government stop the funding of the agencies such as extension agencies and agricultural research centres responsible for the implementation and upgrading of the agricultural models. This was incoherent with the view of Ibietan (2011) that believe there are no reliable agricultural models in existence in Nigeria.

"There used to be models in the 60s such as cooperative model and aggregation model. There used to be a model for each segment of the agricultural sector such as marketing and R & D. The models are still in operation but ineffective but similar models are still effective in a country such as Ghana and India. The model aid good relation among the stakeholders in the sector in the Western Region of Nigeria up till the early 70s (P1, 2021)".

Furthermore, the interview revealed that the lack of specialisation on the part of the agricultural companies has also led to the abandoning of the existing model. It was further discovered that some of the agricultural companies are not aware of the existence of any model in the region as this was not communicated to them by the policymakers. The lack of communication was due to the liquidation of the agency implementing the model (Omekwe, 2003; Ruffin and Anderson, 1996), as they are no longer funded by the government.

"The model only exists on paper the agricultural practitioners are not aware of the model. The models are not well communicated to the stakeholders, as a result, the agricultural companies are not aware of it" (P2, 2021).

"Lack of awareness is still the major barrier to the existence of the model. Most agricultural companies are not aware of the existence of the model. Most agricultural companies operate without following any template, prototype or model" (P3, 2021).

"In my own view there are models but they are weak, not operational, poorly constructed and not available for agricultural companies" (P4, 2021).

"There used to be a model in the 60s and early 70s. As at then there used to be rural integration as a form of the model and was a policy during the administration of Chief Obafemi Awolowo as South West Region Premier" (P6, 2021).

However, few of the participants like P7 and P8 believe that there are no agricultural models in South-West Nigeria and therefore there is no basis to measure the influence of model which doesn't exist on agricultural development. The absence of agricultural models which should have guided the agricultural companies on the agricultural practices in the South-West has aided conflict between the agrarian and the herders. This conflict has led to the death of some agricultural companies employees and hence discouraging investment in the sector. P7 and P8 further express their opinion as stated below.

"No, there are models in the South-West, everyone is just doing it the way they like without plan. The government don't even have a plan and as a result, there are always clashes between the farmers and the Fulani herdsmen and government seems not to have a solution to this problem. These have led to the death of many farmers and discourage people from investing in agricultural companies" (P7, 2021).

"There are no definite models developed by the government or its agencies that can influence the development of agricultural companies in South-West Nigeria. What is common is models developed by an individual company in the region" (P8, 2021).

It is therefore imperative to note from the interview with the participants just as discovered during the literature review with authors such as Hassan et al. (2010) and Williams(1985) that there is no clear indication of the existence of the agricultural model. The lack of agricultural models will result to lack of coherence in agricultural practices, policy inconsistency, and lack of significant development in agricultural sector of the region. Consequently, the response from the participant has shown that the agricultural models is not in existence and has not either influence the agricultural companies development in South-West Nigeria.

5.3.3 Impact of regulatory framework on agricultural policy implementation

Research objective 3.

To critically evaluate and suggest a practicable agricultural regulatory framework that will serve as a policy guide towards the implementation and achievement of agricultural companies development in South-West Nigeria

Research question 3

What are the impacts of the **regulatory framework** on agricultural policy implementation in Nigeria?

Findings:

In the course of the literature review, it was discovered from most of the papers reviewed such as Satar (2016); Morrisson and Schneider (1987); Adeyemi et al. (2023); Afolabi (2015) and Hazell et al. (2010) that the agricultural regulatory framework does not exist in Nigeria and by extension none in South-West Nigeria. A policy framework gives an overarching structure and direction on how policies are to be implemented at each stage of the policy application. However, few authors like Micah and Ruth (2014) believe the regulatory framework exists but are weak and as a result, does not serve as a guide for effective implementation of agricultural policies in South-West Nigeria. According to Adeyemi et al. (2023), for effective policy implementation there is a need for a well-design policy framework that will guide the user of the policy in the application processes. Consequently, this question was designed to critically evaluate and determine the existence and impact of the

regulatory framework through an interview conducted on participants who are operating as agricultural companies within the South-West region.

However, on interviewing nine (9) interviewees that operate within the region it was discovered from some participants such as P1, P3, P5, P7 and P9 that there is no agricultural framework in South-West Nigeria. This was in line with the view of some of the literature reviewed. In response to the interview question, some participant expressed their view that:

"It's shocking!!! No regulatory body and regulatory framework for agriculture in Nigeria, as a result, no standard and no guide for agricultural practices in Nigeria. Invariably nobody to set a standard all we have is various agencies doing what they feel is right" (P1, 2021)

"There is no regulatory framework and hence no regulatory agencies for agricultural policy implementation in South West and Nigeria as a whole similar to NAFDAC for a manufactured product in manufacturing" (P5, 2021)

Furthermore, few of the participants like P8 and P2 believe there are agricultural regulatory frameworks but only exist on paper and as a result, has no significant impact on agricultural companies development in the South-West. These participants believe that the regulatory framework exists but are weak because they are an informal framework created by a body such as a cooperative society and trade association. However, the common view expressed by the participants is that the existing regulatory framework is informal. It is regarded as being informal since the framework has no statutory and legal backing and are not enforceable on agricultural companies by their association or cooperative society. The cooperative society that set up the informal framework uses more of the moral persuasions to ensure compliance by members of agricultural association or cooperative.

"There are regulatory framework but this is done through a cooperative. It is a form of an informal framework as this is done through NNACCIMA. The regulatory framework is invariably weak" (P2, 2021)

"To the best of my knowledge, there are regulatory framework and agencies who implement and regulate agricultural sectors such as Ministry of Agriculture and Ministry of science and technology, but agencies don't carry along stakeholders in the implementation of this framework" (P6, 2021).

"There are regulatory framework in South West for agricultural companies but the regulatory framework are weak and not effective. Response 9: There is no regulatory framework, so no impact on agricultural policy implementation in Nigeria" (P8, 2021).

Based on the findings from most of the participants it is evident that there is no regulatory framework in the South-West and where they exist they are weak as most stakeholders are not aware of the framework and are mostly informal. Consequently, there is no impact of the regulatory framework on agricultural companies development in the South-West. Therefore, there will be a need to suggest the development of a practical regulatory framework that will aid policy implementation to the policymakers in South-West Nigeria. The development of an effective regulatory framework with the inclusion of stakeholders in the development of the framework will aid the development of agricultural companies within the region. Stakeholders are crucial to the success of development and implementation of agricultural regulatory framework and as a result need to be included in the formulation and implementation processes (Adeyemi et al., 2023).

5.3.4 Policy transmission mechanisms in agricultural policy implementation

Research objective 4.

To identify and evaluate how policy transmission mechanisms can be used to educate stakeholders for the development of agricultural companies in South-West Nigeria.

Research question 4

Has **policy transmission mechanisms** been used to influence agricultural policy implementation in South-West Nigeria?

Findings:

As noted in chapter two transmission mechanism plays a vital role in the dissemination of information. It is the means through which the policymaker can interact with the stakeholders who are to benefit from the policy developed. Agricultural information can be transmitted through mass media and social media. According to Storey (1994), the Lack of effective communication of policy statements

is the bane of effective corporate development in a most developing nations such as Nigeria. Likewise Wang et al. (2024) in his study discovered that agricultural development depends on technological advancement with appropriate transmission mechanism. It was also discovered that application of modern technologies with appropriate transmission mechanism will aid the continuity and organisation agricultural productivity, promote efficiency in use of agricultural policy and development of agricultural companies. Therefore, For effective implementation of agricultural policy, there is a need for an efficient policy transmission mechanism that will aid communication between the agricultural stakeholders (Omekwu, 2003) and the government agencies responsible for the implementation of agricultural policy. On this premise, question four (4) through interview seeks to evaluate the influence of policy transmission mechanism on the implementation of agricultural policy in South-West Nigeria.

Unsurprisingly, it was discovered through most of the participants that there was no policy transmission mechanism in the South-West region just as revealed by some of the literature reviewed such as Omekwu (2003) and Hassan et al. (2010). In the course of the interview, some of the participants like P1, P3, P4, P5 and P7 complained bitterly about the implication of lack of transmission mechanism on agricultural companies development.

"Education in the south-west has not helped the agricultural sector in the south-west. No special transmission mechanism in whatever form in south-west like in the northern region of the country where information is transmitted through cooperative mechanism" (P1, 2021)

It was also discovered during the interview that the lack of a policy transmission mechanism in the South-West region has made some of the agricultural companies within the region to result to searching for information from any source both locally and abroad including the internet. The discussion with some of the participants shows that the information from the informal source has not helped in the development of the agricultural companies in the South-West as some of the data are based on the developed economy such as the United Kingdom and the United State of America.

"There is no special policy transmission mechanism by government and its agencies except the internet used by companies looking out for what is obtainable. There is no information available and no transmission mechanism in the south-west in any form" (P3, 2021).

"No. The transmission mechanism has not been used to influence policy implementation" (P4, 2021)

"The truth of the matter is that Nigeria is not a serious nation when it comes to agricultural development. Unfortunately, we know what to do in terms of agricultural development but we fail to do it. Not aware of any policy transmission mechanism that has been used to influence agricultural policy implementation in South West" (P5, 2021).

However, few of the participants such as P2, P6, P8 and P9 believes there are policy transmission mechanisms at the state level and not on a regional level, but the agencies responsible for the management of these mechanism have not used it to effectively communicate with the agricultural companies within the region. Hence, a lack of effective communication has resulted in a lack of awareness and existence of the policy transmission mechanism by the agricultural companies in most of the states in South-West Nigeria.

"Yes, this is done at the state level through the state agric department. The policy is not communicated effectively as most of the officers responsible are like "square pegs in round hole". The office in most cases doesn't even communicate this policy except where the stakeholders demand information. Also, the majority of the officers are not even knowledgeable on the agric policy, as a result, the channel of communication is poor" (P2, 2021)

"I think there are transmission mechanisms but all seems not to be effective as the most benefit of the policy transmitted usually accrue to those who are not stakeholders in the agricultural sector. From my experience, the information will be transmitted to the stakeholders but the benefits will go to those who are not a farmer in the region" (P8, 2021).

"There are transmission mechanisms though not in all states of the western region there is, in a place like Oyo State which is one of the states in the western region. So there are policy transmission mechanisms that are being

used to influence policy implementation in South West Nigeria but not widely spread" (P9, 2021)

In conclusion, some of the participants believe that there are no policy transmission mechanisms in South-West Nigeria just as discovered during the literature review. Though few participants think there are policy transmission mechanism but they are weak as a result of neglect of the mechanism due to lack of adequate funding from the government to the agencies reasonable for the operation of the mechanism. Therefore, the policy transmission mechanisms have not been used to influence agricultural policy implementation in South-West Nigeria. As discovered in Wang et al. (2024), a concrete effort should be made by the government to develop an effective transmission mechanism that will aid effective communication between the stakeholders in agricultural companies and the policymakers in South-West Nigeria. The development of an appropriate transmission mechanism will promote sustainable agricultural development (Omekwu, 2003), effective implementation of agricultural policy and aid development of agricultural companies (Afolabi, 2015) in the South West Nigeria.

5.3.5 The agricultural policy and agricultural companies ROCE

Research objective 5.

To critically examine the influence of agricultural diversification on the return on capital employed (ROCE) of agricultural companies towards achieving development goals in South-West Nigeria.

Research question 5

Has agricultural diversification influenced the **return on capital employed (ROCE)** of agricultural companies in South-West Nigeria?

Findings:

In the course of the literature review, it was discovered that the productivities of cash crops such as cocoa, coffee and groundnuts were volatile as a result of some of the

uncertainty in the implementation of the agricultural programmes or policies (Daneji, 2011). Sequel to the volatility of the productivities, question five (5) aim to critically evaluate the impact of agricultural policies on the return on capital employed by agricultural companies in South-West Nigeria. The return on capital employed is the reward received by agricultural investors for investing in agricultural business. The reward is measured in terms of ratio of profit to the amount capital invested in the agricultural business. The capital invested can be in form of cash, assets, biological assets and other non-tangible but valuable assets.

However, responses from most of the interviewees that are agricultural stakeholders suggested that agricultural policies have not influenced the return on capital employed by the agricultural companies in the South-West. The lack of influence was a result of poor infrastructural facilities, access to cheap funds, security challenges and pilferage within the company. Some of the participants think that the policy somersaults is the main reason for the negative correlation between the agricultural policy and agricultural companies return. Kolawole (1974) think the intervention of government in form of price stabilisation has resulted to ambiguity in the price of the agricultural product. The price stabilisation as led to the increase in smuggling of agricultural product to neighbouring countries by agricultural companies in an attempt to increase the return on capital employed as the agricultural products can be sold at higher price in the neighbouring countries.

"The agricultural policies have not positively influenced the return on capital employed by agricultural companies as many of them even struggle to break even due to lack of infrastructures. There are not adequate returns due to lack of infrastructure, lack of security, kidnapping and pilferage on the part of the workers" (P2, 2021).

"There is basically no correlation between agricultural companies return in south-west and agricultural policies using my companies as an example" (P3, 2021)

In agreement with the view of some of the authors identified during the review of literature in chapters two and three, some of the participants also believe that the inconsistency in policy formulation and eventual policy somersault is the main reason for a negative correlation between agricultural policy and agricultural companies

return. Hence the policy somersault and lack of policy transmission mechanism make it difficult for agricultural policy to positively influence the returns and productivities of agricultural companies in South-West Nigeria.

"The lack of policy transmission mechanism does not allow the benefit of agricultural policy get to the agricultural companies and as a result, the agricultural policy has not positively influenced the return on capital employed by agricultural companies in south-west Nigeria" (P6, 2021).

"Policy changes along with changes in administration. Every administration normally comes with its policy. In the last 30 years policy has changes consistently. The policy change has led to the loss by agricultural companies. The South Western Nigeria agricultural sector is driven by personality instead of ideology" (P1, 2021).

However, few of the participants such as P6, P7 and P9 thinks the agricultural policy had positively impacted the agricultural companies return during the operation of regional government but that has become a thing of the past. According to these participants, the return on capital employed by the agricultural companies cannot be measured with certainty as a result of a lack of reliable data from most agricultural companies who are mostly peasant farmers and not aware of the policy. This was in consonance with the view of Ayamga et al. (2021) that believe that the lack of appropriate regulatory framework is the bane of agricultural development in most of the developing nation. The volatility of agricultural output is another uncertainty surrounding the measurement of the impact of agricultural policy on the returns of agricultural companies in the South-West. The participant explained:

"The return used to be high in the past as there use to be a yardstick. The effect of other economic indices and lack of data on agricultural companies does not give room for measurement of return on capital employed by agricultural companies" (P6, 2021).

"We are not even aware of the agricultural policies developed by the government. However. our business is seasonal and so our income or return,

therefore I cannot certainly say agricultural policies have influenced the return on capital employed by the agricultural companies in South-West" (P7, 2021).

It is worthy to note that the insignificant return on capital employed achieved by the agricultural companies in the region was as a result of the effort of individual agricultural companies. Therefore, the agricultural policies have not influenced the return on capital employed of the agricultural companies in the South-West as there is no cooperation between the government agencies and the agricultural stakeholders (P8, 2021). Consequently, no uniformity in the rate of returns recorded by agricultural companies with the region.

"I cannot certainly say it has an impact or not. It depends on where the agricultural company is situated. Like in this our Ogun State there seems to be no influence of agricultural policies on the return of capital employed by the agricultural companies in the south-west region" (P9, 2021).

5.4 Summary of findings and conclusion

This chapter critically examined and evaluate the results and findings of the interview conducted to determine the impact of national economic policy on corporate sector development with a focus on agricultural companies development in South-West Nigeria. The result and findings of the interview provided answers to the research questions in chapter one of this thesis at the same time meet the objective of the study.

The result of the interview revealed that national economic policy has not significantly aided the development of agricultural companies in South-West Nigeria. The lack of significant development was attributed to a lack of proper planning for policy implementation; lack of agricultural infrastructures; lack of agricultural models; absence of agricultural transmission mechanisms and non-inclusion of agricultural stakeholders in policy formulation and implementation.

On the existence of models for agricultural policy implementation, the result suggests that there are no precise models on how agricultural policies can be used to influence the development of agricultural companies in the region. Hence, the lack of models

has resulted in a lack of specialisation amongst the agricultural companies in the South-West.

In line with the findings in existing literature, the results also revealed that there is no regulatory framework for agricultural policy implementation. The lack of regulatory framework for agricultural practices has resulted in the implementation of agricultural policies and a lack of standards in agricultural practices among the agricultural companies in the South-West.

It was further discovered during the interview that there is no any form of policy transmission mechanism in the region as it used to be in the early sixties (60's) up till the late seventies (70's). The lack of a policy transmission mechanism has resulted in a lack of awareness of agricultural policies and benefits available to agricultural companies in form of cheap funds, agricultural grants, reliefs and other government support.

It should also be noted that the agricultural policies have not significantly influenced the return on capital employed by the agricultural companies in the South-West region of the country. It was affirmed that the little returns recorded by the agricultural companies in the South-West were as a result of the effort made by individual companies and not the impact of agricultural policies. It was also discovered that the returns earned by the agricultural companies within the region cannot be measured with certainty due to the lack of adequate data on the activities of agricultural companies in South-West Nigeria. To this end, there is no positive correlation between the agricultural policy and the return on capital employed by agricultural companies in the South-West.

CHAPTER SIX

Quantitative Results and Findings

6.1 Introduction

This study is underpinned by a conjugative mixed-method which comprises of the qualitative and quantitative methods (Creswell, 2009). The qualitative method as discussed in chapter five involves the analysis of interviews using the narrative analysis technique. However, in this chapter, the result of quantitative data collected through the questionnaires was further analysed using statistical techniques such as chi-square, regression and correlation analysis with aid of software such as SPSS and Python Anaconda.

The aim is to examine and analyse various data and information extracted through questionnaires administered on thirty (30) companies spread across the six (6) states within South-West Nigeria which is the area of this study. It will also entail the interpretations and discussion of the result of the questionnaires.

The chapter was further sub-divided into various segments. The first section dealt with the analysis of questionnaires responses from participants from selected companies in respect of their biodata. The second section comprised of the analysis of the agricultural companies performance data which were collated from the administered questionnaires, followed by the analysis of the research models and research hypotheses.

6.2 Questionnaire responses and their analyses

This section evaluated the importance and rationale of the questions included in the questionnaires and their analysis such as questions with their percentages and so on.

The questions comprised of the bio-data of the respondents followed by questions on the main subject.

Out of 300 questionnaires administered across the six (6) states, only 202 were returned completed from 23 agricultural companies in South-West Nigeria (See table 16 below). This represents a 67% response rate of the total questionnaires administered. The bio-data questions in part one started from question 1 to question 7, while the subject-matter questions in part two are fifty (50) questions.

Table 16: Name of participants companies and location

S/N	COMPANY	LOCATION
1	AgroPark Agricultural Company Ltd	Lagos State
2	Group Farmer Limited	Oyo State
3	Agro Nigeria Ltd.	Ogun State
4	Amo Farm Ltd.	Osun State
5	Emmanuel Alayande Agricultural Farms Ltd.	Oyo State
6	Covenant University Farms Ltd	Ogun State
7	Agric Business Ltd.	Lagos State
8	BAFOT Farms Ltd.	Ogun State
9	Alabi Farms Ltd.	Osun State
10	Alade Farms Ltd.	Oyo State
11	Dele Ige Farms Ltd	Oyo State
12	BBC Professionals	Lagos State
13	ASA Botanica Ltd.	Ekiti State
14	Agric Solution Plus Concept	Ogun State
15	Oloja Farms Ltd	Ekiti State
16	Multiventures Farms Ltd.	Ondo State
17	Akinnola Cocoa Farms Ltd.	Ondo state
18	Akinbohun Farms Ltd.	Ondo State
19	Cocoa Processing Farm Ltd.	Ondo State
20	FEDAS Farms Ltd.	Ekiti State
21	Suave Africa Ltd.	Oyo State
22	DesirePlus Glabal Farm Ltd	Ogun State
23	Farm Credit Limited	Lagos State

6.3 Analysis of responses from bio-data questions

6.3.1 Gender analysis

On completion of the analysis of the responses to bio-data questions, it was discovered that out of 126 participants of the 202 participants that completed and returned the questionnaires were male employees of the selected companies. These represented about 63% of the total returned questionnaires. Consequently, the balance of 76 completed questionnaires are from the female employees, which represents 37%. It was however observed that the employment in the agricultural companies in South-West Nigeria tends to be more favourable towards the male employees than their female counterparts in the sector. There seems to be a sign of gender inequality in the recruitment process of the agricultural companies within the region. The region seems to have employed more male than female. It is therefore necessary for the agricultural companies to give equal opportunity during employment processes to both male and female.

6.3.2 Age group analysis

The analysis of the age distribution also revealed that 60 participants are between the ages of 18 and 28 and this represents about 30% of the total participants. The next on the distribution is the age bracket between 29 and 39, with 59 participants representing 29% of the total participants, while ages between 40 and 49 have a frequency of 43 participants, representing 21%. However, the two age groups with the least frequencies are ages between 50 and 60 with 29 participants and the age group of 60 and above with 11 participants representing 15% and 5% of the total respondents respectively. The age distribution analysis shows that majority of the South-West agricultural companies employees are youth with an average age of 34

years. This is in line with most of the literature reviewed such as Afolabi (2015) and Adams (2016) that regarded Nigeria as a country with a high youthful population.

6.3.3 Marital status analysis

On the bio-data section of the questionnaire, the participants were advised to state their marital status. The section aims to determine the percentages of the marital status of the employees working in the South-West agricultural companies. This will reveal if there is discrimination based on the marital status in the recruitments by South-West agricultural companies.

However, the analysis of the responses showed that most of the participants were either married or single. Of the total 202 participants that completed and returned the questionnaires, 120 participants were married representing 59%, while 79 participants are singles representing about 39% of the total participants. Nonetheless, only 3 participants, representing about 2% are widowed with none of the participants being a divorcee. The analysis, however, shows that the majority of the employees in the South-West agricultural companies are married. This seems to show that most agricultural companies workers are driven by the need to take care of their family basic needs.

6.3.4 Educational qualification analysis

The questionnaire was also used to ascertain the educational qualifications of the participants. The aim was to determine and evaluate the participants' educational qualifications. This will reveal the level of educational qualification and calibre of staff employed by the agricultural companies in the South-West. The analysis shows that Out of 202 participants, 67 had a BSc degree representing about 33% of the total questionnaire completed and returned. The HND holders were 41, representing about 20%. While 27 participants representing 13% had either MBA or MSC degrees.

Also, 26 participants either had an NCE or OND representing about 13%. The participants with GCE/WASCE are 32, representing about 16%. Furthermore, 2 participants which are 1% had PhD degrees and 7 participants are with unspecified qualifications, they represent 4% of the total questionnaires completed and returned. The analysis shows that majority of the employee are graduates with either BSc or HND. The result of the analysis further confirm the opinion of some author under literature review, which state that most of the agriculturist within the region has one form of education or the other.

6.3.5 Analysis of positions in the organisation

The analysis shows the distribution of the participants based on their positions within their various organisations. From the analysis, the highest number of participants were the junior staff with 73 in number representing 36% of total questionnaires completed and returned. This was followed by the senior staff numbering 53 and representing 26%. 21 and 27 participants were supervisors and managers representing 10% and 13% respectively. However, 4 participants were non-executive directors and 13 are executive directors while 3 are managing directors representing 3%, 6% and 2% respectively. 8 participants representing 4% did not belong to any of the groups earlier mentioned. The analysis revealed that there are high numbers of both junior and senior staff within the agricultural companies in South-West Nigeria.

6.3.6 Analysis of years of experience in the organisation

The purpose of this section was to categorise the experiences of the participant in the agricultural company into 6 groups starting from 6 months to 30 years and above. This classification revealed that the majority of the workforce in the selected agricultural companies that responded to the questions spent between 6 months to 10 years in their organisations. 35 participants spent less than 6 months, 76

participants had spent between 6 months to 5 years while 53 participants are those who have spent between 6 to 10 years representing 17%, 38% and 26% respectively. However, 22 participants have spent between 11 to 20 years, 12 participants have spent between 21 to 30 years while 4 participants have spent 30 years and above representing about 11%, 6% and 2% respectively.

Summary of respondent’s profile

Source: Researcher's field survey (2021).

6.3.7 Summary of findings on bio-data Questions

The participants' responses to the bio-data questions revealed the following about South-West agricultural companies in Nigeria:

- i. There seems to be gender disparity in the employment of the agricultural companies in the region as the percentage of males employed is almost double of their female counterparts.
- ii. The analysis of the questionnaires shows that the agricultural companies in the South-West tend to favour the employment of the youth in the sector as the average age with the highest percentage is 34 years old
- iii. The findings from the analysis of the questionnaire show that about sixty per cent of the employees in the agricultural companies in the South-West are married.
- iv. The analysis also revealed that the majority of the employees of the agricultural companies within the South-West region are Bachelors Degree or Higher National Diploma holders with experience between 6 months and 10 years.

6.4 Analysis of responses on agricultural companies performances

This section entailed the analysis of questions 1 to 50 in the questionnaire which was administered to various categories of employees in agricultural companies within the South-West States. The questions covered areas such as national economic policy; models for agricultural policies; regulatory framework on agricultural policy implementation; transmission mechanism for agricultural policies and other barriers inhibiting sustainable agricultural companies development in South-West Nigeria. However, the responses of the participants were analysed using tables 16.1 to 16.50.

6.4.1 Responses to questions on national economic policy

Questions 1 to 10 focused on the influence of national economic policies on the development of agricultural companies in South-West Nigeria. The questions were

drawn based on the objectives of the research in chapter one which is to critically explore economic policy scenarios that can lead to agricultural company development through agricultural policy analysis.

Table 16.1: The national agricultural policies have been successfully implemented by the government and its agencies in the agricultural sector.

		Frequency	Percent %	Valid Percent %	Cumulative Percent %
Valid	Strongly disagree	27	13.37	13.37	13.37
	Disagree	67	33.17	33.17	46.54
	Fairly disagree	39	19.31	19.31	65.85
	Agree	58	28.70	28.70	94.55
	Strongly agree	11	5.45	5.45	100.00
	Sub Total	202	100.0	100.0	
Missing	System	0	0.0		
Total		202	100.0	100.0	

Source: Researcher’s field survey (2021).

The question sought to evaluate how effective the government and its agencies in the agricultural sector were able to implement the agricultural policies. From the table above, 33.2% of the respondents who answered the question disagreed with the assertion that agricultural policies were successfully implemented by the government. 13.4% strongly disagreed with the question while 19.3% fairly disagreed. These three results showed that about 70% of the participants disagreed with the statement. However, 28.7% agree that the government have successfully developed and implemented the agricultural policies. The findings, therefore, revealed that national agricultural policies we not successfully implemented. This was in consonance with the opinion of author such as Luken (2006) that thinks there are regulatory in some of the developing nation but are weak due to lack of proper development and implementaion. Divanbeigi and Saliola (2016) therefore recommended that there is a Need for the government of developing nation like Nigeria to develop an appropriate

regulations national economic policy that will support sustainable agricultural performance and transformation.

Table 16.2: The broad brush policy approach used by the Nigerian government has led to the development of agricultural companies in South-West Nigeria.

		Frequency	Percent %	Valid Percent %	Cumulative Percent %
Valid	Strongly disagree	30	14.85	14.93	14.93
	Disagree	46	22.77	22.88	37.81
	Fairly disagree	63	31.19	31.34	69.15
	Agree	52	25.74	25.87	95.02
	Strongly agree	10	4.95	4.98	100.0
	Sub Total	201	99.50	100.0	
Missing System		1	0.50		
Total		202	100.0		

Source: Researcher’s field survey (2021).

Lack of clear policy statements and objectives is the bane of corporate development in most nations including developing nation like Nigeria. The broad brush policy is the use of a blanket policy for all economic sector in the nation. It also include the application of imported policy on a particular sector of a local economy (Storey, 1994). This question aimed to ascertain whether the broad brush policy approach adopted by Nigerian policymaker have influenced the development of agricultural companies in the South-West. However, 22.9% of the participants disagree that the broad brush policy approach has led to the development of agricultural companies. In addition, 31.3% fairly disagree while 14.9% strongly disagree with the statement, resulting in about 70% disagreement. Nonetheless, 25.9% agree with the assertion while about 5% strongly agree. The findings, therefore, revealed that the broad brush policy approach does not have a positive impact on the development of agricultural companies in South-West Nigeria. The outcome of this section of the survey was in agreement with the outcome of the study conducted by Storey (1994) who discovered that policy should be tailored made rather than the policy makers

adopting the broad brush policy making approach. Byelee et al. (2009) also think the elimination of policy bias and strengthen of the corporate governance will create a positive relationship between agricultural company development and agricultural policy. Likewise Talbot and Reeves (1997) believe there is a Need for development of tailor-made policy for the effective development of companies such as agricultural companies in South-West Nigeria.

Table 16.3: The exclusion of stakeholders in the formulation of agricultural policy has no effect on the successful implementation of the agricultural policy

		Frequency	Percent %	Valid Percent %	Cumulative Percent %
Valid	Strongly disagree	53	26.24	26.50	26.50
	Disagree	60	29.70	30.00	56.50
	Fairly disagree	41	20.30	20.50	77.00
	Agree	38	18.81	19.00	96.00
	Strongly agree	8	3.96	4.00	100.0
	Sub Total	200	99.01	100.0	
	Missing System	2	0.99		
	Total	202	100.0		

Source: Researcher’s field survey (2021).

Stakeholders are the related parties within and outside an organisation. They include shareholders, government, employees and other members of the business community that can have influence on the business. This question therefore intend to evaluate the impact of inclusion and exclusion of critical stakeholders in agricultural companies in the formulation and impletation of agricultural policy. From the Table above, 77% disagreed with the assertion that the non-inclusion of stakeholders in the development of policy has no impact on its successful implementation. Though, 23% believe the non-inclusion does not affect the successful implementation of the policy. It was also discovered that two participants omit the question in the process of completing the questionnaire. The analysis, therefore, showed that the non-inclusion

of the stakeholders in the formulation of the agricultural policies has served as an impediment to the successful implementation of the policies. The outcome was in agreement with some literature review such as Adeyemi et al. (2023) and Chelang'a et al. (2023) who are of the opinion that the stakeholder in the agricultural sector should be included in the development and implementation of agricultural policy. They believe the inclusion of the critical stakeholders with aid effective development of an appropriate policy framework and implementation of the policy.

Table 16.4: Government intervention through agricultural policies has influenced the increase in cash crops output in my firm.

		Frequency	Percent %	Valid Percent %	Cumulative Percent %
Valid	Strongly disagree	30	14.85	14.93	14.93
	Disagree	46	22.70	22.88	37.82
	Fairly disagree	47	23.27	23.38	61.20
	Agree	60	29.70	29.85	91.05
	Strongly agree	18	8.91	8.96	100.0
	Sub Total	201	94.10	100.0	
	Missing System	1	0.50		
	Total	202	100.0		

Source: Researcher’s field survey (2021).

According to Pretty et al. (2001) government can intervene in economy through the use of Taxes, subsidy and other institutional mechanisms. They believe the intervention of the government need to effective and capable of improving the productivity and profitability (Nwangwu et al., 2022) of the economic players within the county. This Question therefore, sought to evaluate the impact of government interventions such as grants and subsidies on the output of the agricultural firm. of workers when faced with challenging assignments in their organisations. The responses show that 61.2% believed that government interventions have not led to the increase in the cash crops of the agricultural firm in South-West Nigeria. However, 38% of the participants believed that government intervention influenced the cash

crops output of the agricultural firm. It is also important to note that a respondent did not complete this section of the questionnaire. Sequel to the responses of the majority of the respondents it is evident that the government interventions have not led to the increase in the cash crops of the agricultural companies in the South-West region. Owombo et al. (2012) believe that appropriate government intervention in form of policy which promote access to modern agricultural technology and availability of agricultural equipment at affordable cost which is lacking in Nigeria will improve agricultural output of the agricultural companies in Nigeria.

Table 16.5: The lack of an appropriate regulatory framework has led to poor implementation and failure of agricultural policy in South-West Nigeria.

		Frequency	Percent %	Valid Percent %	Cumulative Percent %
Valid	Strongly disagree	8	3.96	4.04	4.04
	Disagree	14	6.93	7.07	11.11
	Fairly disagree	20	9.90	10.10	21.21
	Agree	94	46.53	47.48	68.69
	Strongly agree	62	30.69	31.31	100.0
	Sub Total	198	98.02	100.0	
	Missing System	4	1.98		
	Total	202	100.0		

Source: Researcher’s field survey (2021).

This was one of the most fundamental questions of this study. The respondents were expected to confirm the appropriateness of the regulatory framework and its support towards the implementation of the agricultural policy. The results obtained from the respondents, however, showed that 78.8% alluded to the submission that the lack of an appropriate regulatory framework is the bane of poor implementation of agricultural policy in South-West Nigeria. Though, 21.2% did not believe the lack of appropriate regulatory framework is the cause of poor implementation of agricultural

policy. The 21.1% respondents view are in agreement with the opinion of iwuchukwu and Igbokwe (2012) who believe there are regulatory framework in Nigeria but are will due to the lack of political power in the implementation of the developed agricultural policy. Nonetheless, 4 respondents representing 1.98% of total questionnaires completed and returned did not respond to the question.

Table 16.6: Agricultural policies are recognised and motivate the workers to enhance the firm’s financial growth as a result of the application of modern technology in the agricultural processes.

		Frequency	Percent %	Valid Percent %	Cumulative Percent %
Valid	Strongly disagree	16	7.92	7.96	7.96
	Disagree	19	9.41	9.45	17.41
	Fairly disagree	41	20.30	20.40	37.81
	Agree	89	44.06	44.28	82.09
	Strongly agree	36	17.82	17.91	100.0
	Sub Total	201	99.50	100.0	
	Missing System	1	0.50		
	Total	202	100.0		

Source: Researcher’s field survey (2021).

The question was to evaluate whether the agricultural companies employees are motivated by the agricultural policies towards the application of modern technology in executing their functions and responsibilities. The analysis of the questionnaires revealed that 61.2% of the respondents agree (including 17.9% strongly agree) with the assertion that employees are motivated by the agricultural policies towards the application of modern technologies in agricultural processes for the growth of their agricultural companies. 37.8% of the participants believed the agricultural policy does not enhance the application of modern technologies by employees of agricultural companies in the agricultural processes. Furthermore, one of the participants did not respond to the question. The information gathered, therefore, revealed that the agricultural companies workers are motivated by agricultural policies to apply modern

technologies in the agricultural processes for financial growth of the agricultural companies in the South-West. In the same vein Chelang's et al. (2023) believe with relevant and adequate training the young farmer and employee of agricultural companies will be motivated to adopt good agricultural practices and modern technologies in agricultural processes.

Table 16.7: Agricultural policies are highly valued by management in my organisation because they enhance the adoption of a mechanised system that aid the company's growth and development.

		Frequency	Percent %	Valid Percent %	Cumulative Percent %
Valid	Strongly disagree	16	7.92	8.0	8.0
	Disagree	30	14.5	15.0	23
	Fairly disagree	18	8.91	9.0	32
	Agree	112	55.45	56.0	88
	Strongly agree	24	11.88	12.0	100.0
Sub Total		200	99.01	100.0	
Missing System		2	0.99		
Total		202	100.0		

Source: Researcher's field survey (2021).

Agricultural policies are developed by the government for the stakeholders in the agricultural sector. The aim of the policies developed is to promote the growth and development of agricultural firms. However, this question was designed to evaluate whether the management of agricultural companies placed a high value in agricultural policies because they influence the adoption of the mechanised system as an aid to the development of agricultural companies in South-West Nigeria. The analysis of the result showed that 68% of the respondents agreed with the assertion while 32% believed otherwise. Based on the analysis, it can be concluded that agricultural companies management placed a high value on the agricultural policies because it will aid the growth and development of agricultural companies. However, the major challenge seems to the lack of awareness of the agricultural policy due to

poor or lack of appropriate agricultural policy transmission mechanisms (Omekwu, 2003).

Table 16.8: The application of agricultural policies on our firm activities has resulted in to increase in return on capital employed by our firm.

		Frequency	Percent %	Valid Percent %	Cumulative Percent %
Valid	Strongly disagree	21	10.40	10.45	10.45
	Disagree	40	19.80	19.90	30.35
	Fairly disagree	42	20.79	20.90	51.25
	Agree	71	35.15	35.32	86.57
	Strongly agree	27	13.37	13.43	100.0
	Sub Total	201	99.05	100.0	
Missing System		1	0.5		
Total		202	100.0		

Source: Researcher’s field survey (2021).

This question sought to confirm the impact of agricultural policies on the return of capital employed (ROCE) by agricultural companies in the South-West. About 51.3% and of profitability and return on capital employed by the agricultural companies. Though 35% agree and 13.4% strongly agree that agricultural policies will influence the growth of ROCE of agricultural companies in the South-West. Based on the responses of participants, there is a weak relationship between agricultural policies and agricultural firm’s returns. This was corroborated by the findings of Morrison and Schneider (1987) that development of appropriate agricultural policy will promotes and encourages the effective marketing of agricultural products and hence positively influence the return on capital employed by the agricultural company in developing countries.

Table 16.9: The policymaker has failed to launch an agricultural revolution that will eradicate hunger, poverty and economic stagnation.

		Frequency	Percent %	Valid Percent %	Cumulative Percent %
Valid	Strongly disagree	18	8.91	8.95	8.95
	Disagree	27	13.37	13.43	22.38
	Fairly disagree	35	17.33	17.41	39.79
	Agree	74	36.63	36.83	76.61
	Strongly agree	47	23.27	23.38	100.0
	Sub Total	201	99.50	100.0	
Missing System		1	0.50		
Total		202	100.0		

Source: Researcher's field survey (2021).

This question relates to the eradication of poverty and economic stagnation through the development of appropriate agricultural policies. The analysis of the responses shows that about 60% of the participants believe the policymaker has not made an agricultural revolution that will lead to the eradication of poverty and economic stagnation. However, about 40% believe that the policymaker has revolutionised the agricultural sector intending to eradicate hunger and poverty. This reflects the view of authors such as Daneji (2011) who think the policymakers in collaboration with the critical stakeholders should develop a sustainable policy that is based on social and economic realities in the country. The development of an appropriate policy that is based on social and economic situation of the country will lead to a sustainable agricultural development and hence eradication of poverty.

Table 16.10: The adoption of global policy on climatic change by policymakers in Nigeria will reduce the risk of vulnerability from climatic change, eliminate ethnic and political distraction and influence the development of agricultural companies in South-West Nigeria.

		Frequency	Percent %	Valid Percent %	Cumulative Percent %
Valid	Strongly disagree	10	4.95	5.05	5.05
	Disagree	17	8.42	8.59	13.64
	Fairly disagree	33	16.34	16.67	30.31
	Agree	90	44.55	45.46	75.77
	Strongly agree	48	23.76	24.23	100.0
Sub Total		198	98.02	100.0	
Missing System		4	1.98		
Total		202	100.0		

Source: Researcher's field survey (2021).

Climatic change is one of the externalities affecting the growth and development of the agricultural sector around the world (Estrada et al., 2013). Global policies on climatic change are developed by organisations such as World Bank and FAO in an attempt to minimise the risk posed by climatic change on the global environment (Muhammed et al., 2011). This question, therefore, seeks to evaluate whether the adoption of global policy on climate change will minimise the risk of vulnerability as a result of climatic change. However, the responses of the participants revealed that about 70% agrees that the adoption of the global policy by Nigerian policymaker will reduce the risk of vulnerabilities posed by climate change to agricultural development in South-West Nigeria. Nonetheless, 30% of the participants believed otherwise, while four participants did not comment on the question. Government and its agencies should there give necessary support for the adaption of global policies (Adetuyi et al. 2022) that can influence development of sustainable agricultural practices, reduce the risk of vulnerability from climatic change, eliminate ethnic and political distraction in the South-West and in Nigeria as a whole.

6.4.2 Responses to questions on models for agricultural policies

Table 16.11: Development of a model for policy framework will aid the implementation of agricultural policies by agricultural companies

		Frequency	Percent %	Valid Percent %	Cumulative Percent %
Valid	Strongly disagree	6	2.97	3.06	3.06
	Disagree	10	4.95	5.10	8.16
	Fairly disagree	25	12.38	12.76	20.92
	Agree	106	52.48	54.08	75.0
	Strongly agree	49	24.26	25.00	100.0
	Sub Total	196	97.03	100.0	
Missing System	6	2.97			
Total	202	100.0			

Source: Researcher’s field survey (2021).

The lack of appropriate model, framework and other measuring tools (Storey 1994; Satar 2016; Harrison et al., 2016) are the bane of agricultural development in South-West Nigeria. This is a form of a prototype or architecture that guide the agricultural companies in the implementation of agricultural policy.

The question expected respondents to express their opinion on whether the development of a model will aid the implementation of agricultural policies in South-West Nigeria. It was, however, discovered that 79.1% agreed that the development of models will aid the implementation of agricultural policies by agricultural companies in the South-West. About 21% did not agree that the model will aid policy implementation while 6 participants did not express an opinion on the question. This was in consonance with the view of Satar (2016), who believe the absence of relevant and appropriate models in mose developing nations has resulted to policy inconsistencies and lack of development in the critical sector. As reflected in the survey, Satar (2016) therefore think there is a need for the development of an appropriate model and policy framework for effective policy implementation. The

development of such model in the South West Nigeria for agricultural sector will in turn lead to the development of the agricultural companies in the region.

Table 16.12: Policy model will aid the exchange of information and resources between government agencies and agricultural companies within the South-West region of Nigeria

		Frequency	Percent %	Valid Percent %	Cumulative Percent %
Valid	Strongly disagree	7	3.47	3.48	3.48
	Disagree	10	4.95	4.98	8.46
	Fairly disagree	33	16.34	16.42	24.88
	Agree	102	50.50	50.75	75.63
	Strongly agree	49	24.26	24.37	100.0
	Sub Total	201	98.02	100.0	
Missing System		1	0.5		
Total		202	100.0		

Source: Researcher’s field survey (2021)

Effective information flow is very important (Osakwe, 2010) among agricultural stakeholders including the exchange of information between the government agencies and the agricultural companies. The effective exchange of information between the two parties will aid the plan and decision of the agricultural companies (Afolabi, 2015) and will thus influence the growth and development of agricultural companies. It is in this line that respondents were asked to once again compare express their opinion on the impact of the policy model on the exchange of information between the government agencies and agricultural companies in South-West Nigeria.

The analysis showed that 151 (75%) respondents confirmed that the policy model will aid the exchange of information and agricultural resources between the government agencies and agricultural companies in the South-West, while 50 (25%) respondents disagree with the assertion on the importance of policy model on information exchange between the two parties. One respondent did not express opinion on the question. The view of the respondent was in agreement with Adeola and Adetunbi

(2015) who are of the opinion that Government agencies should improve their collaborative effort with stakeholders in the agricultural sector through the dissemination of appropriate information on sustainable agriculture. The development of agricultural policy model on the collaboration between the agricultural stakeholders such as agricultural companies and government agencies will aid the exchange of information within the sector and hence lead to development of the agricultural companies within the region.

Table 16.13: The policy model will show the link between the policies, agricultural companies development and economic growth

		Frequency	Percent %	Valid Percent %	Cumulative Percent %
Valid	Strongly disagree	3	1.49	1.51	1.51
	Disagree	12	5.94	6.03	7.54
	Fairly disagree	15	7.43	7.54	15.08
	Agree	120	59.41	60.30	75.38
	Strongly agree	49	24.26	24.62	100.0
Sub Total		199	98.02	100.0	
Missing System		3	1.49		
Total		202	100.0		

Source: Researcher’s field survey, 2021.

This is a follow-up to the question in Table 26.11 above. The question seeks to evaluate the fact which states that the policy model is a link between agricultural policies and agricultural development (Osakwe, 2010). The analysis of the result revealed that about 85% agrees that the policy model will show the link between policies and agricultural companies development. However, 15% did not believe the model can show the relationship between agricultural policies and agricultural development. Furthermore, 3 participants did not respond to the question. Based on the analysis it concluded that the Policy model will show a link between the agricultural policy and the agricultural companies development in South-West Nigeria.

This was in agreement with the conclusion of Kajisel et al. (1997) that the development of agricultural policy models will create a link between the agricultural research institute activities and agricultural companies. The link between the agricultural research institute activities and agricultural companies will however resulted to agricultural companies development.

Table 16.14: The value of a firm’s investment is increased by the skilful use of the model by the employees in our company.

		Frequency	Percent %	Valid Percent %	Cumulative Percent %
Valid	Strongly disagree	4	1.98	2.04	2.04
	Disagree	11	5.45	5.61	7.65
	Fairly disagree	35	17.33	17.86	25.51
	Agree	101	50.00	51.53	77.04
	Strongly agree	45	22.28	22.96	100.0
Sub Total		196	98.02	100.0	
Missing	System	6	2.97		
Total		202	100.0		

Source: Researcher’s field survey (2021).

It is important to note that If the responses obtained from respondents in the preceding table 4.00 and 4.00 above were something to go by, then this question becomes sacrosanct. This question aims to validate that the effective use of the model by the agricultural companies employees will improve the agricultural companies investment. Out of the 202 participants, 146 or 74% of valid responses believed that the skilful application of the model will lead to an increase in the value of their company. However, 50 respondents or 25.5% of valid responses do not believe there is a positive correlation between skill application of policy model and value of the agricultural firm in The South-West. sure that their present clientele will continue to do business with them. The findings of this question are noteworthy because it forms the bedrock of the agricultural companies development; the ability to revolutionalised the agricultural companies and the ability to make reasonable

returns on investment which is the hallmark of the business. The result was in agreement with the view of Afroz and Akhtar (2017) who think adaptation of the right model can be a basis for the development of local policies that address the need of the agricultural companies and hence will aid agricultural companies development and in turn the economic growth of the region.

Table 16.15: The adoption of a model will aid the development of an individual farmer in the south-West to an agricultural company

		Frequency	Percent %	Valid Percent %	Cumulative Percent %
Valid	Strongly disagree	2	0.99	0.99	0.99
	Disagree	12	5.94	5.94	6.93
	Fairly disagree	27	13.37	13.37	20.30
	Agree	115	56.93	56.93	77.23
	Strongly agree	46	22.77	22.77	100.0
	Sub Total	202	98.02	100.0	
Missing	System	0	1.98		
Total		202	100.0		

Source: Researcher’s field survey (2021).

This question sought to know if the adoption of a model will aid the transition of a peasant farmer to an agricultural company in South-West Nigeria. Following the analysis of the respondents, it was discovered that 79.7% of the respondents agreed to the fact that adoption of the model will lead to the transition of peasant farmers into an agricultural company. This further justifies the importance of the model as discovered during the review of literature, where authors such as Storey (1994) and Zin (2014) stress the importance of the model in the implementation of policy. 20.3% of the participants, however, believed otherwise. Based on the outcome of the survey it is evident that the agricultural model will aid the development of individual farmer and transform them into agricultural companies (Hazell et al., 2010).

Table 16.16: Low return on capital employed was caused by the lack of a model for agricultural policies in my company.

		Frequency	Percent %	Valid Percent %	Cumulative Percent %
Valid	Strongly disagree	16	7.92	8.0	8.0
	Disagree	26	12.87	13.0	21.0
	Fairly disagree	37	18.32	18.50	39.50
	Agree	91	45.05	45.50	85.0
	Strongly agree	30	14.85	15.0	100.0
	Sub Total	200	99.01	100.0	
Missing System		2	0.99		
Total		202	100.0		

Source: Researcher's field survey (2021).

This question intends to interpret the relevance of Return On Capital Employed (ROCE) as the investors' criteria for investing in the business and how a model can influence the maximisation of ROCE. The respondents were therefore asked to express their views on the notion that a lack of a model for effective implementation of agricultural policies can lead to low ROCE in agricultural companies. About 60% of the respondents agreed that for investors' capital contribution to be profitable, there is a need for the application of the model in the implementation of agricultural policies by agricultural companies. Majority of the respondent however, believe that an effective implementation of agricultural model will aid the return on capital employed by agricultural companies in the South West Nigeria. This was in agreement with Ibietan (2011) who opined that the Adoption of an agricultural model will aid continuity of policy implementation by the Nigerian government and can influence the profitability of the agricultural companies.

Table 16.17: The absence of a policy model has hindered the adoption of modern technology in my company

		Frequency	Percent %	Valid Percent %	Cumulative Percent %
Valid	Strongly disagree	12	5.94	6.03	6.03
	Disagree	22	10.89	11.06	17.09
	Fairly disagree	34	16.83	17.09	34.18
	Agree	96	47.52	48.24	82.42
	Strongly agree	35	17.33	17.58	100.0
Sub Total		199	98.51	100.0	
Missing System		3	1.49		
Total		202	100.0		

Source: Researcher's field survey (2021)

Modern technology is vital to the agricultural revolution. The adoption of the modern technology such as AI will positively influence the output of agricultural companies. Respondents were therefore, asked to disagree or agree with the statement that the absence of a policy implementation model will hinder the adoption of modern technology by agricultural companies in South-West Region. It was discovered that about 66% of the respondents agreed that the lack of a policy model will inhibit the adoption of modern technology by agricultural companies. The lack of adoption of modern technologies will, however, prevent hindering the growth and development of the agricultural companies in the region. On the other hand, 34.% of the respondents has a contrary view while 3 participants did not respond to the question.

Table 16.18: Investors' appraisals of companies past financial performances are used as yardsticks for the application of agricultural policies.

		Frequency	Percent %	Valid Percent %	Cumulative Percent %
Valid	Strongly disagree	10	4.95	5.18	5.18
	Disagree	23	11.39	11.92	17.1
	Fairly disagree	41	20.30	21.24	38.34
	Agree	101	50.00	52.33	90.67
	Strongly agree	18	8.91	9.33	100.0
	Sub Total	193	95.54	100.0	
	Missing System	9	4.46		
	Total	202	100.0		

Source: Researcher's field survey (2021).

The purpose of this question is to ascertain from respondents whether they believe that investor appraisals financial performances are used as a benchmark for the application of agricultural policies. From the table above, 61.7% of the respondents affirmed that investors used past financial performance as a yardstick for the application of agricultural policies. However, 38.3% did not agree with the initial opinion while 3 persons representing 4.5% of the total questionnaires and completed were indifferent and did not comment on the question.

Table 16.19: High return on capital employed is evidence of business development in my organisation.

		Frequency	Percent %	Valid Percent %	Cumulative Percent %
Valid	Strongly disagree	4	1.98	2.0	2.0
	Disagree	10	4.95	5.0	7.0
	Fairly disagree	28	13.86	14.00	21.0
	Agree	103	50.99	51.50	72.50
	Strongly agree	55	27.23	27.50	100.0
	Sub Total	200	99.01	100.0	
	Missing System	2	0.99		
	Total	202	100.0		

Source: Researcher's field survey (2021)

Further to the question in table 26.17, this question intends to evaluate whether the high return on capital employed is a symptom of growth and development in agricultural companies. Based on the answers obtained from the respondents as analysed in the table above, 79% thought that a high return on capital employed by agricultural companies is a sign of growth and development. Though 21% of the total valid responses disagreed with the statement. Based on the popular opinion it is therefore imperative to know that the higher return on investment in agricultural companies is evidence of growth and development. Apart from return on capital employed, returns to investors in agricultural businesses can be measured in terms of earning per share and dividend per share. The earning per share is the profit after tax per existing share of the company. The dividend is paid out of the profit after tax while the balance after the payment of the dividend is the retained profit. The retained profit of the business will contribute to the shareholders funds of the agricultural business and hence lead to the growth of the agricultural companies. The view of the participant is in line with the opinion of Pettinger (2016) who think the government of developing nation should lower tariff on agricultural equipments in order to increase the profitability of agricultural business. The increase in the agricultural profitability will however, aid the increase in the return of capital employed by agricultural business. The increase in the return on capital employed will in turn attract more investors towards agricultural sector and eventual agricultural companies development.

Table 16.20: Benefits arising from the assets of the firm can be associated with the ability of the management to effectively apply agricultural policies in its operation.

		Frequency	Percent %	Valid Percent %	Cumulative Percent %
Valid	Strongly disagree	4	1.98	2.01	2.01
	Disagree	12	5.94	6.03	8.04
	Fairly disagree	43	21.29	21.61	29.65
	Agree	108	53.46	54.27	83.92
	Strongly agree	32	15.84	16.08	100.0
	Sub Total	199	98.51	100.0	
	Missing System	3	1.49		
	Total	202	100.0		

Source: Researcher’s field survey (2021).

Conclusively, this question sought to affirm that a high ROCE has a direct link with business development. Therefore, this question seeks to determine the correlation between benefits arising from the agricultural company asset and the application of agricultural policies in the agricultural processes. From the results obtained, 70.3% of the respondents agreed there is a positive correlation between the benefits arising from assets and implementation of agricultural policies on the company operation by management. 29.7% however has a contrary view while 3 participants stayed neutral and did not respond to the question. The result was in agreement with the view of the view of Owombo et al. (2012) who in his study discovered that the development of the appropriate policy on the acquisition of agricultural technologies and other modern agricultural equipment will lead to the affordability of such equipment and aid the productivity of the agricultural operation.

6.4.3 Responses to question on Regulatory framework on agricultural policy implementation

Table 16.21: Regulatory framework on the agricultural policy adopted by management brings about high financial performance.

		Frequency	Percent %	Valid Percent %	Cumulative Percent %
Valid	Strongly disagree	8	3.96	4.0	4.0
	Disagree	15	7.43	7.50	11.5
	Fairly disagree	62	30.69	31.0	42.5
	Agree	92	45.54	46.0	88.5
	Strongly agree	23	11.39	11.50	100.0
	Sub Total	200	99.01	100.0	
Missing System	2	0.99			
Total	202	100.0			

Source: Researcher’s field survey (2021).

The management of an organisation are those charged with the responsibility of administration of the company (Luken, 2016). The owner of the business expect the directors or managers to maximise the wealth of the shareholders by adopting the relevant regulatory framework that will result to the high performance and return on capital employed of the company (Nwangwu et a., 2022). They are appointed by the owners of the business and in this study, they are appointed by the owner of the agricultural company. This question therefore, examines the ability of a regulatory framework in influencing the financial performance of an agricultural company and invariably lead to the growth and development of the company. The result revealed that 57.5% of the respondents believed the adoption of a regulatory framework by management will aid the implementation of agricultural policy and in turn brought about high financial performances in the agricultural companies. 31% fairly disagree, while 11.4% disagree with the statement. Two participants failed to respond to the question. The outcome of this result was in line with the conclusion of Byelee et al. (2009) who believe there is a need to develop regulatory framework which will

eliminate policy inconsistencies and strengthen corporate governance in agricultural companies.

Table 16.22: Regulatory framework on agricultural policy implementation has influenced my company’s participation in agricultural programmes.

		Frequency	Percent %	Valid Percent %	Cumulative Percent %
Valid	Strongly disagree	7	3.47	3.52	3.52
	Disagree	23	11.39	11.56	15.08
	Fairly disagree	53	26.24	26.63	41.71
	Agree	97	48.02	48.74	90.45
	Strongly agree	19	9.41	9.55	100.0
	Sub Total	199	98.51	100.0	
Missing System		3	1.49		
Total		202	100.0		

Source: Researcher’s field survey (2021).

The question aimed at corroborating the fact that the importance of a regulatory framework cannot be overemphasised as it is inevitable (Pretty et al., 2001) if an agricultural company want to benefit from the agricultural programme. The findings from the analysis of the survey revealed that about 60% of the respondents were in agreement with the assertion that the existing regulatory framework will aid the participation of agricultural companies in agricultural programmes. 26.6% fairly disagree while 15% disagree with the statement. This result implies that once there is an effective regulatory framework the management of agricultural companies will be willing to participate in agricultural programmes. The agricultural programmes will however, aid the productivity of the agricultural companies. The was in agreement with the view of Zin (2014) that believe the development of an appropriate regulatory framework twill promote structural transformation in an agricultural-based economy.

Table 16.23: National policy framework for agricultural development has been used by my company to resolve the economic, social and environmental issues.

		Frequency	Percent %	Valid Percent %	Cumulative Percent %
Valid	Strongly disagree	7	3.47	3.48	3.48
	Disagree	30	14.85	14.93	18.41
	Fairly disagree	37	18.32	18.41	36.82
	Agree	104	51.49	51.74	88.56
	Strongly agree	23	11.39	11.44	100.0
Sub Total		201	99.50	100.0	
Missing System		1	0.50		
Total		202	100.0		

Source: Researcher's field survey (2021).

The essence of this question was to further confirm the importance of the national policy framework in the agricultural revolution. Following the analysis of the responses of the participants, it was discovered that 62.2% believe that national policy for agriculture has been used by agricultural companies in the South-West to resolve economic, social and environmental issues. However, 18.4% disagree while 3.5% strongly disagree with the statement. A participant is indifferently and refused to comment on the question.

Table 16.24: Effective corporate management in agricultural companies can be achieved through strict adherence to the regulatory framework

		Frequency	Percent %	Valid Percent %	Cumulative Percent %
Valid	Strongly disagree	7	3.47	3.57	3.57
	Disagree	10	4.95	5.10	8.67
	Fairly disagree	37	18.32	18.88	27.55
	Agree	103	50.99	52.55	80.10
	Strongly agree	39	19.31	19.90	100.0
Sub Total		196	98.51	100.0	
Missing System		6	2.97		
Total		202	100.0		

Source: Researcher's field survey (2021).

The focus of this question was to ascertain whether strict compliance with the regulatory framework can translate to effective corporate management (Ruffin and Anderson, 1996) in agricultural companies in the South-West. The result of the survey showed that 72.5% of the respondents agreed that effective corporate management can be achieved through strict adherence to the regulatory framework. This is in line with the findings of some of the literature reviewed such as Bauer and Yamey (1965) and Novikova (2014). Nonetheless, 27.5% have a contrary opinion while 6 participants representing about 3% of the total questionnaire administered remained indifferent and did not comment on the question.

Table 16.25: Lack of an appropriate regulatory framework is preventing my company from implementing a developmental programme such as the application of modern technology in agricultural processes.

		Frequency	Percent %	Valid Percent %	Cumulative Percent %
Valid	Strongly disagree	18	8.91	8.96	8.96
	Disagree	47	23.27	23.38	32.34
	Fairly disagree	35	17.33	17.41	49.75
	Agree	86	42.57	42.79	92.54
	Strongly agree	15	7.43	7.46	100.0
	Sub Total	201	99.50	100.0	
Missing System		1	0.50		
Total		202	100.0		

Source: Researcher’s field survey (2021).

The application of modern technology in agricultural processes (Jayne, 2019) is an important factor in the agricultural revolution. This question, therefore, seeks to evaluate if the lack of an appropriate regulatory framework will hinder the application of modern technology in agricultural processes by agricultural companies in South-West Nigeria. The result of the analysis shows that 50.3% of the respondents agree that the lack of an appropriate regulatory framework will prevent the implementation of developmental programmes by agricultural companies in the South-West. 49.7% think otherwise.

Table 16.26: Compliance with agricultural policy and framework aid price and income stabilisation in my organisation.

		Frequency	Percent %	Valid Percent %	Cumulative Percent %
Valid	Strongly disagree	6	2.97	2.97	2.97
	Disagree	21	10.40	10.40	13.37
	Fairly disagree	58	28.71	28.71	42.08
	Agree	97	48.02	48.02	90.10
	Strongly agree	20	9.90	9.90	100.0
Sub Total		202	100.0	100.0	
Missing System		0	0.0		
Total		202	100.0		

Source: Researcher's field survey, 2021.

Respondents were asked to evaluate the contribution of agricultural policy and framework to agricultural product price stabilisation. About 58% confirmed that agricultural policy and framework will aid income and price stabilisation. This is in line with the view of Bauer and Yamey (1965) and Williams (1985) who believed an appropriate regulatory framework will catalyse a developing economy's income stabilisation. 42% of the respondents did not however agree with the statement. Perhaps, they considered price stabilisation as a form of government involvement in fixing the price of agricultural products (Kolawole, 1974).

Table 16.27: EPS as a measure of financial reward for capital investment is an important tool used by the management of my company to measure the impact of agricultural policy.

		Frequency	Percent %	Valid Percent %	Cumulative Percent %
Valid	Strongly disagree	2	0.99	1.00	1.00
	Disagree	15	7.43	7.46	8.46
	Fairly disagree	59	29.21	29.35	37.81
	Agree	103	50.99	51.24	89.05
	Strongly agree	22	10.89	10.95	100.0
Sub Total		201	99.50	100.0	
Missing System		1	0.50		
Total		202	100.0		

Source: Researcher's field survey (2021).

The question describes earnings per share as a financial reward for capital investment the agricultural investors. The earning per share is the profit after tax per share. The is estimated as total profit after tax divided by the number of shares issue by the agricultural company. It helps the investors to evaluate the return expected from the prospective company. It also reveal how management are able to use resources available in the company to maximise the wealth of the shareholders. In this regard, respondents were expected to express their opinion on the importance of EPS to management and investors. 62.2% agreed that EPS is an important tool for management in measuring the impact of agricultural policy on financial reward. 37% believed EPS is not a good deciding factor as a measure of financial reward due to the implementation of agricultural policy.

Table 16.28: The imposition of high and excessive tax rates on the agricultural company has led to cost-push inflation and discouraged investors from investing in my company.

		Frequency	Percent %	Valid Percent %	Cumulative Percent %
Valid	Strongly disagree	8	3.96	4.0	4.0
	Disagree	13	6.44	6.50	10.50
	Fairly disagree	23	11.39	11.50	22.00
	Agree	100	49.50	50.00	72.00
	Strongly agree	56	27.72	28.0	100.0
	Sub Total	200	99.01	100.0	
Missing System		2	0.99		
Total		202	100.0		

Source: Researcher’s field survey, 2021.

Tax is a compulsory levy paid by every organisation including the agricultural companies to the government. The government and its agencies are very important stakeholders in agricultural business (Afolabi, 2015). Government is are to provide basic infrasructure which will aid the smooth operation of the agricultural companies within the country. To provide these ammenities government need to charge the agricultural companies a compulsory level in form of company tax. This tax is paid

out of the profit generated by the agricultural companies after the deduction of all relevant and allowable expenses (CITA, 2020 and Agboola, 2014). This question, therefore, sought to evaluate if high and excessive tax has resulted in to increase in the price of agricultural products and discouraged investment in agricultural companies. The result showed that 78% of the respondents agreed that a high tax rate in form of multiple taxes has resulted in an increase in the price of agricultural products and discouraged investment in agricultural companies. This was contrary to the view of Pretty et al. (2001) who thinks taxes, subsidy and institutional mechanisms are effective instruments that can be used to promote sustainable development and discourage negative externalities.

Table 16.29: Regulatory practices and government policies play a crucial part in the transformation of the company’s businesses through the elimination of hostile competition and the reduction of fraudulent practices among stakeholders in the region.

		Frequency	Percent %	Valid Percent %	Cumulative Percent %
Valid	Strongly disagree	5	2.48	2.53	2.53
	Disagree	25	12.38	12.63	25.16
	Fairly disagree	39	19.31	19.70	44.86
	Agree	103	50.99	52.02	96.88
	Strongly agree	26	12.87	13.12	100.0
Sub Total		198	98.02	100.0	
Missing System		4	1.98		
Total		202	100.0		

Source: Researcher’s field survey (2021).

The regulatory practices are guidelines established by government to guide those who are charged with the responsibility of governance (Hazell et al.,2010). A sustainable economic system requires an appropriate regulatory framework for the effective supervision and coordination of the commercial activities within the country (Afolabi, 2015). The effective establishment and implementation will however prevent unhealthy competition among the market participant within a sector. This question

however, intends to find out if the regulatory practices and government policies play an important role in the elimination of unhealthy competition among the agricultural companies and other stakeholders in South-West Nigeria. 65.1% of the respondents however agreed that the government policies play a vital role in eliminating unhealthy competition among the agricultural companies operating in South-West Nigeria. 44.9% of the respondents disagree with the assertion.

The view of the participant was in consonance with conclusion of Luken (2006) who discover that the lack of proper coordination and coherence among policies and programmes in most developing nation is the bane of sustainable development. Likewise, Morrisson and Schneider (1987), believe appropriate regulatory framework should be developed to promote and encourage the marketing of agricultural products without unhealthy competition between the agricultural companies.

Table 16.30: Regulatory framework of agricultural transformation will eliminate the high rate of fraud and unhealthy competition among agricultural companies.

		Frequency	Percent %	Valid Percent %	Cumulative Percent %
Valid	Strongly disagree	6	2.97	3.08	3.08
	Disagree	11	5.45	5.64	8.72
	Fairly disagree	32	15.84	16.41	25.13
	Agree	99	49.01	50.77	75.90
	Strongly agree	47	23.27	24.10	100.0
	Sub Total	195	96.53	100.0	
	Missing System	7	3.47		
	Total	202	100.0		

Source: Researcher’s field survey (2021).

Micah and Ruth (2014), found that corruption, fraud and other white collar crime are on the increase in Nigeria despite the establishment of numerous antifraud agencies created by the Nigerian government. However, respondents’ opinions were sought on whether a regulatory framework for agricultural transmission can be used to

eliminate or reduce the rate of fraud in the agricultural companies. About 75% were of the view that regulatory framework will eliminate or reduce the incidence of fraud and corruption which is a major challenge in Nigeria (Micah and Ruth, 2014). However, 25% did not disagree with this statement. The result of the survey was in agreement with the opinino of Akpan and Eyo (2018) who opined that having an effective regulatory framework will aid the performances of the anticorruption agencies established by government to combact the menace of curruption in Nigeria including the agricultural sector in the South-West Nigeria.

6.4.4 Responses to questions on transmission mechanisms for agricultural policies

Table 16.31: The transmission mechanisms used by the government were appropriate for the agricultural sector

		Frequency	Percent %	Valid Percent %	Cumulative Percent %
Valid	Strongly disagree	18	8.91	8.96	8.96
	Disagree	22	10.89	10.95	19.91
	Fairly disagree	64	31.68	31.84	51.75
	Agree	80	39.60	39.80	91.55
	Strongly agree	17	8.42	8.45	100.0
	Sub Total	201	98.51	100.0	
	Missing System	1	0.50		
	Total	202	100.0		

Source: Researcher’s field survey (2021).

Every stakeholder in the agricultural sector is assumed to be a beneficiary of an effective agricultural transmission mechanism. This is because the transmission mechanism is the mean through which agricultural companies received information from the government and its agencies and communicate with other stakeholders (Omekwu, 2003). This question, therefore, sought to evaluate whether the government and its agencies are using appropriate transmission mechanisms to disseminate information to the agricultural companies and other stakeholders. The responses of about 52% of the respondents show that an appropriate transmission

mechanism is not in use for the dissemination of agricultural information. 48% however, believes otherwise. The view of the participants was in agreement with the interview participants who thinks government have not establish any transmission mechanisim that will aid the development of agricultural companies in the South-West. The outcome of both the survey and the interview was in consonance with Hassan et al. (2010) who concluded that the Government and its agencies should collaborative with stakeholders in the agricultural sector and develop appropriate transmission mechnism for the transmission of agricultural information that will aid sustainable agricultural development.

Table 16.32: The transmission mechanisms used by the government to communicate agricultural policies have aided agricultural policies implementation in my company.

		Frequency	Percent %	Valid Percent %	Cumulative Percent %
Valid	Strongly disagree	11	5.45	5.45	5.45
	Disagree	32	15.84	15.84	21.29
	Fairly disagree	60	29.70	29.70	50.99
	Agree	87	43.07	43.07	94.06
	Strongly agree	12	5.94	5.94	100.0
Sub Total		202	100	100.0	
Missing System		0	0		
Total		202	100.0		

Source: Researcher’s field survey (2021).

The developing nations such as Nigeria are faced with the challenges of availability of relevant data for planning a sustainable economic development and disseminating of information to the concerned stakeholders (Omekwu, 2003). Effective communication of relevant Information to agricultural stakeholders will aid sustainable development in agricultural sector. This question intends to know from the respondents, how effective the agricultural transmission mechanism has aided the implementation of agricultural policies in various agricultural companies. The

findings show that 51% (including 6% that strongly disagree) disagreed that the transmission mechanism used by the government to transmit agricultural policies has aided the implementation of agricultural policies in agricultural companies. Though 49% (including 43% that strongly agree) agree with the statement. This was in consonance with the view of Adeola and Adetunbi (2015) who think that Government and its agencies should design an agricultural transmission mechanism that will improve the flow of information to agricultural stakeholders.

An appropriate agricultural transmission mechanism such as agricultural radio station and social media will improve the collaborative effort of the government and its agencies with the agricultural stakeholders. They also believe that effective flow of appropriate information within a corporate sector such as agricultural sector will aid sustainable development. Likewise, Omekwu (2003) concluded that Development of an agricultural information architecture will integrate all agencies and agriculturist involved in the use of agricultural data and information and hence aid planning towards agricultural companies development.

Table 16.33: The information about agricultural policies was received through the mass media by my company

		Frequency	Percent %	Valid Percent %	Cumulative Percent %
Valid	Strongly disagree	3	1.49	1.52	1.52
	Disagree	18	8.91	9.10	10.62
	Fairly disagree	48	23.76	24.24	34.86
	Agree	101	50.0	51.00	85.86
	Strongly agree	28	13.6	14.14	100.0
	Sub Total	198	98.02	100.0	
	Missing System	4	1.98		
	Total	202	100.0		

Source: Researcher's field survey (2021).

Mass media such as internet, audio recording, TV and radio broadcasting that can reach large audience like agricultural practitioner in Nigeria can be used to effectively

transmit agricultural information to the agriculturist. This section further emphasis on the importance of effective means of transmitting agricultural policies to the agricultural companies by the government and its agencies in South-West Nigeria. The question, therefore, examines the relevance and impact of the agricultural transmission mechanism in South-West region. The result of the analysis revealed that 65.1% (including 13% strongly agree) of respondents agree that information about the agricultural policies was received through the mass media by agricultural companies. This is contrary to the initial view of the researcher at the initial stage of this study. However, 34.9% (including 24% fairly disagree) of the respondents disagree with the statement while 4 participants did not express their opinion on the question.

Table 16.34: Vital information was disseminated by policymakers through mass media such as television, radio and newspaper.

		Frequency	Percent %	Valid Percent %	Cumulative Percent %
Valid	Strongly disagree	8	3.96	4.0	4.0
	Disagree	14	6.93	7.0	11.0
	Fairly disagree	35	17.33	17.5	28.5
	Agree	109	53.96	54.5	83.0
	Strongly agree	34	16.83	17.0	100.0
	Sub Total	200	96.53	100.0	
	Missing System	2	0.99		
	Total	202	100.0		

Source: Researcher's field survey (2021).

For the purpose of significant impact on the sustainable development of agricultural companies, there is a need to communicate the relevant and vital information through the mass media adopted by the policymakers in the South-West Nigeria. This question was an extension of the previous question on the importance of mass media. Respondents were therefore asked to express their opinion on the transmission of vital information through the mass media. As expected, 71.5% agreed with the

question that crucial information is transmitted through mass media such as radio and television. 28.5% (including 17.5% fairly agree) have contrary opinion. This further confirm the view of author such as Omekwu (2023) and Hassan et al. (2010). They believe The government agencies and the major stakeholders in the agricultural sector should invest more funds in the agricultural transmission mechanism through which vital information should be transmitted.

Table 16.35: My company is always aware of new agricultural policies through social media and the internet.

		Frequency	Percent %	Valid Percent %	Cumulative Percent %
Valid	Strongly disagree	2	0.99	1.00	1.0
	Disagree	18	8.91	9.0	10.0
	Fairly disagree	21	10.40	10.45	20.45
	Agree	116	57.43	57.71	78.16
	Strongly agree	44	21.78	21.84	100.0
	Sub Total	201	96.53	100.0	
Missing System		1	0.50		
Total		202	100.0		

Source: Researcher’s field survey (2021).

Social media include the use of dedicated websites, and other application such as instargram, YouTube, twitter and facebook in the provision of vital information to a wider audience or target beneficiaries (Chepkirui, 2021). The social media allows businesses like agricultural companies to communicate with each other and thereby aid the excahng of ideas, create larger online business communities and promote sharing of industrial based information. The question intends to find out the impact of social media on the transmission of agricultural policies to agricultural companies and other stakeholders within the region.

Consequently, respondents were asked to express their opinion on how often they received information about agricultural policies through social media and the internet. 79.5% agreed with the assertion that they always receive information about new

agricultural policies through social media. 20.5% (including 10.5% fairly agree) think otherwise. A participant did not respond to the question and remained indifferent. This was in agreement with the view of Chepkirui (2021) who opined that transmission of agricultural information through social medial such as WhatsApp, YouTube and Facebook will aid availability of an updated data and information and hence lead to increase in the productivity and profitability of agricultural companies in developing nations like Nigeria which include the South-West Nigeria. Chepkirui (2021) However, concluded that most developing such as Nigeria lack will power to formally use social media as a means of transmitting agricultural information to agricultural stakeholders.

Table 16.36: The channel of transmitting information about agricultural policies is right for my company

		Frequency	Percent %	Valid Percent %	Cumulative Percent %
Valid	Strongly disagree	10	4.95	5.16	5.16
	Disagree	17	8.42	8.76	13.92
	Fairly disagree	40	19.80	20.62	34.54
	Agree	100	49.50	51.55	86.09
	Strongly agree	27	13.37	13.91	100.0
	Sub Total	194	96.04	100.0	
	Missing System	8	3.96		
	Total	202	100.0		

Source: Researcher’s field survey (2021).

The communication channel is the through which information is sent from the encoder to the decoder. Information such as agricultural information can be transmitted either through the verbal or non-verbal(Chepkirui, 2021). This question was an extension of the transmission of agricultural information using social and mass media. respondents were therefore asked to express their opinion on the transmission of vital information through the mass media. As expected, 71.5%

agreed with the question that crucial information is transmitted through mass media such as radio and television. 28.5% (including 17.5% fairly agree) have contrary opinion. The response of the respondents was in agreement with the view of Chepkirui (2021).

Table 16.37: The dissemination of agricultural information through the right channel of communication led to the creation of educated and informed employees with updated information in my company.

		Frequency	Percent %	Valid Percent %	Cumulative Percent %
Valid	Strongly disagree	10	4.95	5.0	5.0
	Disagree	13	6.44	6.5	11.5
	Fairly disagree	29	14.36	14.5	26.0
	Agree	101	50.0	50.5	76.5
	Strongly agree	47	23.27	23.5	100.0
	Sub Total	200	96.53	100.0	
Missing System	2	3.47			
Total		202	100.0		

Source: Researcher's field survey (2021).

Efficient and timely availability of information is crucial to the growth and development of every organisation (Osakwe, 2010) including agricultural companies. This question, therefore, intends to find out if the mode of communicating agricultural information has made the employee of agricultural companies more informed. earnings per share as a financial reward for capital investment. 74% of the responses from the participants agreed that the use of the right channel of communication has improved the knowledge of the agricultural companies employees. 26% however believed otherwise while 2 participants are indifferent and did not respond to the question. This agrees with the opinion of Chepkirui (2021) that says what ever channel adopted has to be appropriate for the information and suitable for the receiver of the information like the agriculturist.

Table 16.38: The South-West agricultural companies have remained uninformed due to a lack of knowledge on how to transform from the use of peasant or traditional techniques to a mechanised farming system with high productivity

		Frequency	Percent %	Valid Percent %	Cumulative Percent %
Valid	Strongly disagree	17	8.42	8.42	8.42
	Disagree	32	15.84	15.84	24.26
	Fairly disagree	45	22.28	22.28	46.54
	Agree	68	33.66	33.66	80.20
	Strongly agree	40	19.80	19.80	100.0
Sub Total		202	100	100.0	
Missing System		0	0.0	0.00	
Total		202	100.0		

Source: Researcher's field survey (2021).

The transformation of agricultural practice from peasant system to mechanised system required adequate and effective application of modern technology and machine in the agricultural processes (Hazell et al., 2010). Consequently, this question seeks to confirm whether the agricultural companies in the South-West has been unable to revolutionalise the farming system due to a lack of transformational knowledge and use of modern techniques in agricultural processes. The analysis of the responses of the participants showed that 54.5% agreed that the agricultural companies in the region lack transformational knowledge and are uninformed. However, 46.5% have a contrary opinion. The result of the was in consance with the view of Kajisel et al. (1997), the author concluded that Malaysia a developing nation like Nigeria was able to transform its palm oil sector through an appropriate and effective agricultural research. Similarly, Barrett and Mutambatsere (2005) believe there is a need to be engaged in micro-based research which identify the modern process of structural transformation that will aid informed policy development and in trun lead to increase in productivity.

Table 16.39: The use of mass media has eliminated the challenge of literacy among farmers and made data more accessible for agricultural research.

		Frequency	Percent %	Valid Percent %	Cumulative Percent %
Valid	Strongly disagree	12	5.94	5.97	5.97
	Disagree	17	8.42	8.46	14.43
	Fairly disagree	52	25.74	25.87	40.30
	Agree	84	41.58	41.79	82.09
	Strongly agree	36	17.82	17.91	100.0
	Sub Total	201	96.53	100.0	
	Missing System	1	0.50		
	Total	202	100.0		

Source: Researcher's field survey (2021).

The relevant skill and knowledge required for the sustainable agricultural companies development can mainly be acquired through relevant education and training. The training and education can be transmitted through the use of mass media such as YouTube and Facebook. The effectiveness of the training and education depends on the availability of a reliable data and information (Chepkirui, 2021). The question intends to evaluate how mass media has contributed to the improvement in the level of literacy of the farmers and make data more accessible in South-West Nigeria.

The result however showed that about 60% agreed that mass media has aided the level of literacy of the farmer and made agricultural data more accessible for the agricultural researcher. About 40% has a contrary view while one participant remains indifferent. This is in line with the view of Cervantes Godoy and Dewbre (2010) in which they stated that data from most developing nations are not reliable and as a result it has become difficult to plan for poverty eradication in the developing nations.

Table 16.40: The use of appropriate transmission mechanisms for communicating agricultural policies has improved the performance and income of my company.

		Frequency	Percent %	Valid Percent %	Cumulative Percent %
Valid	Strongly disagree	8	3.96	4.02	4.02
	Disagree	27	13.37	13.57	17.59
	Fairly disagree	30	14.85	15.07	32.66
	Agree	103	50.99	51.76	84.42
	Strongly agree	31	15.35	15.58	100.0
Sub Total		199	98.51	100.0	
Missing System		3	1.49		
Total		202	100.0		

Source: Researcher's field survey (2021).

Most of the literature review shows there are positive relationship between an effective and appropriate transmission of agricultural policy and the performance of the agricultural companies in area such as productivity and revenue. The respondents were asked to express their opinion on the impact of effective communication on the performances and income of the agricultural companies in the South-West. 67.3% of the participants confirmed that effective communication of agricultural policy has improved the performances and income of the agricultural companies in South-West Nigeria. 32.7% of the respondents however disagree with the statement while three participants remained neutral and did not respond to the question. The outcome of the survey was in consonance with the view of Divanbeigi and Saliola (2016) who are of the opinion that there is a need for the developing nation development of an appropriate regulatory framework and transmission mechanism that will support agricultural performance and income generation.

6.4.5 Responses to questions on barriers to effective diversification of the economy

Table 16.41: The lack of diversification of the economy has made the Nigerian economy lagged behind other emerging economies

		Frequency	Percent %	Valid Percent %	Cumulative Percent %
Valid	Strongly disagree	5	2.48	2.49	2.49
	Disagree	7	3.47	3.48	5.97
	Fairly disagree	11	5.45	5.47	11.44
	Agree	95	47.03	47.27	58.71
	Strongly agree	83	41.09	41.29	100.0
Sub Total		201	99.50	100.0	
Missing System		1	0.50		
Total		202	100.0		

Source: Researcher’s field survey (2021).

The economy of most developing nation such as Nigeria are lagging behind due to lack of effective diversification of their economic base. Nigeria being an agricultural country need to effectively diversified it agricultural system into a sustainable agricultural system (Afolabi, 2016). From the Table above, 88.5% of the respondents agreed with the assertion that Nigeria's economy has lagged behind other emerging economies as a result of lack of diversification of the economy. The result is in line with findings of some of the literature reviewed such as Birner and Resnick (2010) and Ibietan (2011) who think that developing nations like Nigeria are not making significant progress in the area of economic growth and development due to lack of appropriate transformational strategies. However, 23% believed otherwise while a participant refuse to complete that part of the questionnaire.

Table 16.42: Over-dependent on oil by the Nigerian government has resulted in the neglect of agriculture.

		Frequency	Percent %	Valid Percent %	Cumulative Percent %
Valid	Strongly disagree	7	3.47	3.52	3.52
	Disagree	3	1.49	1.51	5.03
	Fairly disagree	6	2.97	3.02	8.05
	Agree	82	40.59	41.21	49.26
	Strongly agree	101	50.0	50.74	100.0
	Sub Total	199	98.51	100.0	
	Missing System	3	1.49		
	Total	202	100.0		

Source: Researcher's field survey (2021).

From the literature reviewed it was discovered that the over dependent on oil revenue have had a significant negative impact on agricultural practices (Imo, 2012) and by extension has resulted to increase in the rate of unemployment in Nigeria. The research conducted by Adams (2016) revealed that the oil boom in the 70's has led to the manifestation of the dutch disease in Nigeria. The dutch disease is used to define the relationship between the revenue boom from exploration of crude oil and the neglect of agricultural practices in a country (Adams, 2016). This is an extension to the question in table 26.41 above on diversification of the economy. This question, however, sought to know if over-dependent on oil revenue by the Nigerian government is the major factor responsible for the neglect of agriculture as discovered during the literature review in chapter 3.

The responses from the respondents showed that 92% agreed with the assertion that being over-dependent on oil revenue is responsible for the neglect of agriculture by the Nigerian government including the Western state government. Though, 8% believe that the government did not neglect agriculture as a result of being over-dependent on oil revenue. Three participants did not respond to the question.

The result of the survey was in consonance with view of authors such as Adams (2016); Imo (2012) and Agboola (2014), they concluded that the discovery of oil in commercial quantity followed by “oil wind fall” in the 70’s has led to the neglect of agricultural sector that use to be major foreign exchange earner for Nigeria and produce job for over 70% of the population directly and indirectly. Adams (2016) further recommend that the Nigeria government in collaboration with critical stakeholders needs to diversify its economy through the sustainable development of the agricultural sector that will aid the development of agricultural companies.

Table 16.43: lack of adequate data for economic planning and research are the major impediment of agricultural companies development in South-West Nigeria

		Frequency	Percent %	Valid Percent %	Cumulative Percent %
Valid	Strongly disagree	4	1.98	2.0	2.0
	Disagree	15	7.43	7.5	9.5
	Fairly disagree	21	10.40	10.50	20.0
	Agree	86	42.57	43.00	63.0
	Strongly agree	74	36.63	37.00	100.0
	Sub Total	200	96.53	100.0	
Missing System		2	0.99		
Total		202	100.0		

Source: Researcher’s field survey (2021).

According to Cervantes Godoy and Dewbre (2010), most developing nation like Nigeria lack adequate and reliable data for planning of sustainable economic development. From the Table above, 80% of the respondents agreed with the assertion that lack of adequate data is the bane of agricultural companies development in South-West Nigeria. The responses are in line with some of the literature reviewed such as Cervantes Godoy and Dewbre (2010). However, 20% of the respondents believed there are adequate data for planning and research in South-West Nigeria. In addition, two participants did not respond to the question and that make them indifferent. The outcome of the survey is line with the opinion of

author such as Hazell et al. (2010), Afolabi (2015) and Omekwu (2003) who believed that the non availability of a reliable data is the bane of sustainable agricultural development in most developing nation like Nigeria and other African countries.

Table 16.44: high standard of corruption is a major barrier to the development of agricultural companies in South-West Nigeria.

		Frequency	Percent %	Valid Percent %	Cumulative Percent %
Valid	Strongly disagree	5	2.48	2.5	2.5
	Disagree	3	1.49	1.5	4.0
	Fairly disagree	18	8.91	9.0	13.0
	Agree	83	41.01	41.5	54.5
	Strongly agree	91	45.05	45.50	100.0
	Sub Total	200	99.01	100.0	
	Missing System	2	0.99		
	Total	202	100.0		

Source: Researcher’s field survey (2021).

Corruption is a serious menace inhibiting sustainable economic development in most developing nation including Nigeria (Ibietan, 2011). During the literature review, it was discovered that a persistently high level of corruption, fraud and white-collar crime in Nigeria is part of the factors responsible for the lack of economic growth and development (Micah and Ruth, 2014). Consequently, this question seeks to determine whether a high level of corruption is a major barrier to the growth and development of agricultural companies in South-West Nigeria.

The result of the analysis revealed that 87% of the responses of the participants agreed with the assertion while 13% believed the high level of corruption is not a major impediment to agricultural companies development in South-West Nigeria. Furthermore, two participants did not comment on the question. The outcome of the survey is similar to the conclusion of Micah and Ruth (2013) they opined that Persistence high level of corruption, fraud and white-collar crime have hindered

sustainable economic. They development in Nigeria. They therefore, recommend that Nigeria government should eliminate the weaknesses in the regulatory framework and judicial system which are major barrier in fights against corruption.

Table 16.45: The rapid growth in rural-urban movement is responsible for the lack of agricultural companies development in South-West Nigeria.

		Frequency	Percent %	Valid Percent %	Cumulative Percent %
Valid	Strongly disagree	5	2.48	2.5	2.5
	Disagree	17	8.42	8.5	11.0
	Fairly disagree	38	18.81	19.0	30.0
	Agree	86	42.57	43.0	73.0
	Strongly agree	54	26.73	27.0	100.0
Sub Total		200	99.01	100.0	
Missing System		2	0.99		
Total		202	100.0		

Source: Researcher’s field survey (2021).

The findings during the literature review show that there is a rapid increase in rural-urban movement as many youths in the rural are migrating to the cities in search of a better condition of living thereby abandoning their agricultural occupation (Okhankhuele and Opafunso, 2013). This question, therefore, seeks to confirm the effect of the rapid rural-urban movement on agriculture companies development in South-West Nigeria. Findings revealed that 70% of the respondent agree with the assertion that an increase in the rate of rural-urban movement is of the factors responsible for the lack of development of agricultural companies in South-West Nigeria. Though, 30% have a contrary opinion while 2 participants remain indifferent. This was in consonance with the view of Okhankhuele and Opafunso (2013), the findings of their research revealed that the mass movement of youth from rural area to urban center in Nigeria has resulted to lack of youthful manpower in required in the rural area for agricultural sector development. Consequently, the lack adequate work force has however resulted in the continuous decline in the agricultural companies

productivity and profitability. The authors therefore recommend that government should develop a policy that will narrow the gap between the wage and other socio-economic infrastructure in the rural and urban center in Nigeria including South-West region.

Table 16.46: The lack of educational facilities and other social infrastructure facilities are responsible for the lack of agricultural development in South-West Nigeria.

		Frequency	Percent %	Valid Percent %	Cumulative Percent %
Valid	Strongly disagree	5	2.48	2.49	2.49
	Disagree	21	10.40	10.45	12.94
	Fairly disagree	28	13.86	13.93	26.87
	Agree	79	39.11	39.30	66.17
	Strongly agree	68	33.66	33.83	100.0
	Sub Total	201	99.50	100.0	
Missing System		1	0.50		
Total		202	100.0		

Source: Researcher’s field survey (2021).

People migrate for reasons such as search for qualitative education, availability of basic infrastructures and other social amenities. In most developing nation like Nigeria, qualitative education are very scarce in rural area where the agricultural companies and their farms are domiciled. The quest for the for a quality education has resulted to mass movement of youth form rural area to the urban center. The search for quality education has therefore inhibit the development of the agricultural companies that are mostly situated in the rural area (Okhankhuele and Opafunso, 2013).

From the Table above, 74.1% agreed with the assertion that the lack of educational and social facilities are responsible for the lack of agricultural development in South-West Nigeria. The result is a further confirmation of rapid rural-urban migration in search of a better condition of living. However, 26.9% did not agree with this statement while a participant did not respond to the question. Okhankhuele and

Opafunso (2013) recommended that government should create necessary educational facilities and other social amenities that will discourage mass migration of people from rural area to the urban center. This will aid the availability of man power development and quality of living standard in rural area and hence act as catalyst for the sustainable agricultural companies development.

Table 16.47: The neglect of agriculture by the Nigerian government is responsible for the decline in the contribution of agriculture toward the national Gross Domestic Product

		Frequency	Percent %	Valid Percent %	Cumulative Percent %
Valid	Strongly disagree	5	2.48	2.5	2.5
	Disagree	2	0.99	1.0	3.5
	Fairly disagree	7	3.47	3.5	7.0
	Agree	97	48.02	48.5	55.5
	Strongly agree	89	44.06	44.50	100.0
	Sub Total	200	96.53	100.0	
Missing System	2	0.99			
Total		202	100.0		

Source: Researcher’s field survey (2021).

According to Imo (2012) the manifestation of the dutch disease as a discovery of oil in commercial quantity in the 60’s couples with the oil boom of the 70’s has led to the neglected the agricultural sector which is a mojour employer of labour in Nigeria. This question therefore sought to evaluate whether the neglect of agriculture sector is responsible for the decline of contribution from agriculture toward the GDP. From the Table above, the analysis of the responses showed that 93% of the participants believed the neglect of agriculture is responsible for the decline of share agriculture toward the GDP. This was 7% of the participants (including 7% fairly disagree) who thinks otherwise while two participants are indifferent. The outcome of the survey corroborate the findings of Adams (2016) and Imo (2012), that concluded that dutch disease has led to the neglect of agricultural sector and this has consequentially

reduce the contribution of agricultural sector toward the nation's Gross Domestic Products.

Table 16.48: The neglect of agriculture has increased the level of hunger and poverty level of the South-West Region.

		Frequency	Percent %	Valid Percent %	Cumulative Percent %
Valid	Strongly disagree	7	3.47	3.5	3.5
	Disagree	2	0.99	1.0	4.5
	Fairly disagree	7	3.47	3.5	8.0
	Agree	82	40.59	41.0	49.0
	Strongly agree	102	50.50	51.0	100.0
	Sub Total	200	99.01	100.0	
Missing	System	2	0.99		
Total		202	100		

Source: Researcher's field survey (2021).

Most developing nation including Nigeria that is traditionally an agricultural country are faced with high level of poverty and hunger. Byelee et al. (2009) discover that some of the government of developing nation has neglected or failed to mechanise the Agricultural sector which has the potentials to eliminate the poverty and promote food security. Also, from the findings of the literature reviewed, it was discovered that there is a positive correlation between neglect of agriculture and hunger and poverty in Nigeria. This question, therefore, seeks to further confirm if neglect of agriculture has led to a widespread of hunger and poverty in South-West Nigeria.

The Table above however showed that 92% agreed with the assertion that there has been an increase in the level of hunger as a result of neglect of agriculture in the region. Though, 8% believed the neglect is not responsible for the hunger and poverty in the region while two participants did not comment on the question. The non-inclusion does not affect the successful implementation of the policy. It was also discovered that two participants omit the question in the process of completing the

questionnaire. The analysis, therefore, showed that the non-inclusion of the stakeholders in the formulation of the agricultural policies has served as an impediment to a successful implementation of the policies. Byelee et al. (2009) therefore recommend that the government of developing nation should establish and implement an appropriate policy that will lead to sustainable agricultural practices and development and hence reduce the level of poverty and hunger.

Table 16.49: The low level of cost or negative externalities in Nigeria has resulted to the lack of extensive and intensive agricultural activities in Nigeria

		Frequency	Percent %	Valid Percent %	Cumulative Percent %
Valid	Strongly disagree	8	3.96	3.98	3.98
	Disagree	9	4.46	4.48	8.46
	Fairly disagree	19	9.41	9.45	17.91
	Agree	122	60.40	60.70	78.61
	Strongly agree	43	21.29	21.39	100.0
	Sub Total	201	96.53	100.0	
Missing System		1	0.50		
Total		202	100.0		

Source: Researcher’s field survey (2021).

Agricultural externalities can be negative or positive. The negative externalities include impact of pesticides poisoning on human health, water pollution, deforestation and extinction of biodiversity. The positive externalities on the other hand include provision of foods, employment and community cohesion. The literature reviewed showed that Nigeria has a low level of negative externalities when compared with other nations such as Malaysia and Indonesia where the expansion of agricultural activities has resulted in a high cost of Negative externalities (Williamson, 1970 and Fitzherbert et al., 2008). This question, therefore, seeks to evaluate the rationale behind the low cost of negative externalities from Nigeria's agricultural activities.

The result of the responses revealed that 82.1% agreed with the assertion that the lack of intensive and extensive level of agricultural activities is responsible for the low cost of negative externalities. The lack of intensive and extensive agricultural activities (Bergh, 2000) has resulted in the lack of development of agricultural companies and thereby leading to poverty and food insufficiency (Diao et al., 2007) in the South-West and Nigeria as a whole. Though 17.9% of the participant has a contrary opinion and a participant is indifferent to the assertion.

Table 16.50: There is a need for the development of a policy framework for the management of agricultural externalities in South-Western Nigeria.

		Frequency	Percent %	Valid Percent %	Cumulative Percent %
Valid	Strongly disagree	4	1.98	2.0	2.0
	Disagree	5	2.48	2.5	4.5
	Fairly disagree	9	4.46	4.5	9.0
	Agree	83	41.09	41.5	50.5
	Strongly agree	99	49.01	49.5	100.0
Sub Total		200	96.53	100.0	
Missing System		2	0.99		
Total		202	100.0		

Source: Researcher’s field survey (2021).

Some of the literature reviewed concluded that most developing nation lack a clear policy statement and framework (Storey, 1994) and where available they are usually weak. Consequently, this question seeks to further confirm the assertion. The analysis in the table above showed that 91% of the respondents agreed that there is a need for the development of an effective policy framework for the management of the agricultural externalities in Nigeria. However, 9% of the respondent believed there is no need for the development policy framework for the management of agricultural externalities in the South-West. Two participants remain indifferent as they did not comment on the question. Ruffin and Anderson (1996) therefore advise that the developing nation like Nigeria should develop a detailed institutional

framework that will solve the problem which emanates from negative externalities as they strive towards the development of a sustainable agricultural practices and development.

6.4.6 Summary of findings and conclusion

Source: Researcher’s field survey (2021).

The dearth of data in the area (Cervantes Godoy and Dewbre, 2010) of agricultural company development in Nigeria prompted the study to adopt the use of primary data as a means of achieving the aims and objective of the study. To effectively achieve these aims and objectives a conjugative mixed method was adopted with the use of both interview and survey as a data collection instrument. The semi-structured interview was used to collect the qualitative data while the survey on the other hand was used to collect the quantitative data. Chapter five discussed the analysis of the qualitative data while this chapter entails the analysis of the quantitive data.

However, of the 300 questionnaires administered, the analysis shows that only 202 questionnaires were completed and returned. As revealed in most of the literature reviewed and the result of the interview in chapter five, the analysis of the result revealed that the majority of the participants believed that the national economic policy formulation, implementation and intervention does not have a significant impact on the agricultural development in South-West Nigeria. Larger percentage of the respondents (See figure 20 above) believed that effective implementation of the regulatory framework and agricultural models will influence the development of the agricultural companies in the South-West region of the country. As revealed in figure 20 above some of the respondents thinks the use of reliable and effective agricultural transmission mechanism will improve the performance and income of agricultural companies in South-West Nigeria.

Furthermore, most of the participants believed neglect of agriculture as a result of being over-dependent on oil revenue is the bane of agricultural companies development in South-West Nigeria. The respondents, however, believed that these factors have significantly contributed to the widespread poverty, hunger and economic degradation in South-West Nigeria. The was in agreement with the findings of the result of the interview in chapter five of this study.

CHAPTER SEVEN

HYPOTHESES TESTING AND PRESENTATION OF THE AGRICULTURAL MODELS

7.1 Introduction

In chapters five and six the results and findings of both qualitative and quantitative data collected were discussed and analysed respectively. This chapter, however, entails the testing of the hypothesis expressed in chapter two using chi-square, correlation, and regression analysis. It also includes the development of the agricultural model's correlation and multiple regression analysis. The hypothesis was tested from the perspective of the stakeholders theory and the sustainable economic development theory. Both theory take into consideration, the interest of all the stakeholders such as the agricultural investors, the management of agricultural companies and the member of the public into consideration. The short-term and long-term agricultural companies development were taken into consideration from the perspective of sustainable development theory while the interest of the stakeholders was based on the stakeholders theory (Krisnawati et al., 2014; Freeman et al., 2010).

The Pearson's chi-square test of association was used to test the significance of association between the factors that can influence the agricultural development in South-West Nigeria. The result of the test described the statistical relationship between one or more independent (predictor) variables and a dependent (response) variable (Huck and Cormier, 1996). The result and data from the survey in chapter six were used to test the significant of the association between agricultural development variables.

However, Chi-squared tests of association may provide insufficient answer to all the research questions but may indicate the level of significant association that exists between variables under consideration (Odetunmibi, Adejumo and Anake, 2021). Consequently, the correlation and multiple regression were further used to test the hypothesis and develop the agricultural models with the aid of Python Anaconda and SPSS. Regression analysis is an analysis technique that can be used to predict the outcome of a categorical or non-numerical dependent variable. Therefore, the multiple regression was further used to predict the level of relationship between the

independent variables and the dependent variable such as the relationship between transmission mechanism and agricultural companies' development. The hypothesis was tested using the samples of quantitative data collected which were analysed in chapter six.

7.2 Test of hypothesis using chi-square

The test of significance through the use of chi-square was used to determine the individual significance of the estimated parameters. This was achieved by using the p-values of each of the variables. The p-value showed the direction in which the acceptance or the rejection of the hypothesis would go. A low p-value (<0.05) indicated that the null hypothesis (H_0) could be accepted and the alternative hypothesis (H_1) rejected. On the other hand, a high p-value (>0.05) indicated that the null hypothesis (H_0) was to be rejected and the alternative hypothesis (H_1) accepted. A low p-value is said to be statistically insignificant. This meant that the changes in the independent variables were related to the changes in the dependent variable. Also, a high p-value is said to be statistically significant. This suggested that the changes in the independent variables were not associated with the changes in the dependent variable.

The hypothesis 1 to 5 in line with the research objectives was tested using the chi-square model stated below.

Chi-square formular

$$\chi^2 = \sum \frac{(O - E)^2}{E}$$

Where: **O** – represents observed frequency from table 26.2 above.

E- represents expected frequently

$$E = \frac{\text{Total respondents}}{\text{Total number of row}}$$

Degree of freedom (df) is $(r-1)(c-1)$

Where level of significance = $\alpha = 5\%$ error i.e. $p < .05$

Decision rule

Reject the null hypothesis (H_0) if the x^2 calculated is greater than the p value in the chi-square distribution table. Otherwise, do not reject the null hypothesis (H_0).

7.2.1 Restatement and Testing of Hypothesis 1

Restatement of Research Objective 1, Question 1 and Hypothesis1

Research Objective 1

To critically explore economic policy scenarios that can lead to agricultural company development through agricultural policy analysis.

Research Question 1

Has the national economic policy been used to **aid the development** of agricultural companies in South-West Nigeria?

Research Hypothesis 1

H_0 : There is no significant relationship between the national economic policy and development of agricultural companies in South-West.

H_1 : There is a significant relationship between the national economic policy and development of agricultural companies in South-West.

Test of Hypothesis 1

Hypothesis 1 was tested in line with the research objective to find out the relationship between agricultural companies development and national economic policy.

TABLE 17.1 Data computation used for testing of hypothesis 1

Expectations	Observed Frequency (O)	Expected Frequency (E)	O-E	(O-E)²	$\frac{(O-E)^2}{E}$
Strongly Agree	10	40.2	-30.2	912.04	22.69
Agree	52	40.2	11.8	139.24	3.46
Fairly Disagree	63	40.2	22.8	519.84	12.93
Disagree	46	40.2	5.8	33.64	0.84
Strongly Disagree	30	40.2	-10.2	104.04	2.59
Total	201	201	0	1708.8	42.51

Source: Field survey (2021) from table 26.2

$$\therefore fe = \frac{201}{5} = 40.2$$

Where calculated value of chi-square = $x^2 = 42.51$

Degree of freedom (*df*) is (r-1) (c-1)

$$= (5-1) (2-1)$$

$$df = 4$$

x^2 calculated	x^2 tabulated (P< .05)	Degree of freedom (<i>df</i>)	Level of confidence
42.51	9.49	4	0.95

Inference

Since the calculated value of x^2 is 42.51 and it is greater than the p-value in the chi-square distribution table (as 9.49), we, therefore, reject the null hypothesis (H_0) and accept the alternate hypothesis (H_1).

Conclusion on hypothesis 1

Reject the null hypothesis and accept the alternate hypothesis that there is a relationship between national economic policy and agricultural companies development.

The result of the hypothesis tested, however, showed that national economic policy can be used to influence the development of agricultural companies in South-West Nigeria. The result further confirm the view expressed by most of the participant interviewed, in which some of the participants opined that the national economic policy can be used as an economic developmental tool. The view of both the interviewee and the outcome of this hypothesis were also in agreement with the conclusion of author such as Dardak (2015) who think the development of an appropriate and reliable economic policy will aid sustainable agricultural transformation programme in developing nation like Nigeria.

7.2.2 Restatement of Research Objective 2, Question 2 and Hypothesis2

Research Objective 2

To develop a model using artificial intelligence, capable of establishing linkage between the agricultural policies and the agricultural companies development in South-West Nigeria.

Research Question 2

Are there **models** on how agricultural policies can be used to influence the development of agricultural companies in South-West Nigeria?

Research Hypothesis 2

H₀: There is no significant relationship between the agricultural models and agricultural companies development in South-West Nigeria.

H₁: There is a significant relationship between the agricultural models and agricultural companies development in South-West Nigeria.

TABLE 17.2 Data computation used for testing of hypothesis 2

Expectations	Observed Frequency (O)	Expected Frequency (E)	O-E	(O-E) ²	$\frac{(O-E)^2}{E}$
Strongly Agree	49	39.2	9.8	96.04	2.45
Agree	106	39.2	66.8	4462.24	113.83
Fairly Disagree	25	39.2	-14.2	201.64	5.14
Disagree	10	39.2	-29.2	852.64	21.75
Strongly Disagree	6	39.2	-33.2	1102.24	28.12
Total	196	196	0	6714.8	171.29

Source: Field survey (2021) from table 26.10

$$\therefore fe = \frac{196}{5} = 39.2$$

Where calculated value of chi-square = $x^2 = 171.29$

Degree of freedom (*df*) is (r-1) (c-1)

$$= (5-1) (2-1)$$

$$df = 4$$

x^2 calculated	x^2 tabulated (P< .05)	Degree of freedom (<i>df</i>)	Level of confidence
171.29	9.49	4	0.95

Inference

Since the calculated value of x^2 is 171.29 and it is greater than the p-value in the chi-square distribution table (as 9.49), we therefore reject the null hypothesis (H_0) and accept the alternate hypothesis (H_1).

Conclusion on hypothesis 2

Reject the null hypothesis and accept the alternate hypothesis that there is a relationship between agricultural models and agricultural companies development in South-West Nigeria.

The outcome of the hypothesis tested revealed that agricultural models can influence the development of agricultural companies in South-West Nigeria. This was in line with the findings of the interview in chapter five of this study. The result is in consonance with the view of the interview participants. Though few of the participants believed are of the opinion that there is no relationship between the agricultural model and agricultural companies development. However, most literature review such as Kajisel et al. (1997) confirms that the existence agricultural models will aid the agricultural companies development as it did in some developing nations like Malaysia and Indonesia.

7.2.3 Restatement of Research Objective 3, Question 3 and Hypothesis 3

Research Objective 3

To critically evaluate and suggest a practicable agricultural regulatory framework that will serve as a policy guide towards the implementation and achievement of agricultural companies development in South-West Nigeria

Research Question 3

What are the impacts of the **regulatory framework** on agricultural policy implementation in Nigeria?

Hypothesis 3

H₀: There is no significant relationship between the regulatory framework and agricultural companies development in South-West Nigeria.

H₁: There is a significant relationship between the regulatory framework and agricultural companies development in South-West Nigeria.

TABLE 17.3 Data computation used for testing of hypothesis 3

Expectations	Observed Frequency (O)	Expected Frequency (E)	O-E	(O-E) ²	$\frac{(O-E)^2}{E}$
Strongly Agree	23	40	-17	289	7.23
Agree	92	40	52	2704	67.6
Fairly Disagree	62	40	22	484	12.1
Disagree	15	40	-25	625	15.63
Strongly Disagree	8	40	-32	1024	25.6
Total	200	200	0	5126	128.16

Source: Field survey (2021) from table 26.20

$$\therefore fe = \frac{200}{5} = 40$$

Where calculated value of chi-square = $\chi^2 = 128.16$

Degree of freedom (*df*) is (r-1) (c-1)

$$= (5-1) (2-1)$$

$$df = 4$$

χ^2 calculated	χ^2 tabulated (P< .05)	Degree of freedom (<i>df</i>)	Level of confidence
128.16	9.49	4	0.95

Inference

Since the calculated value of χ^2 is 128.16 and it is greater than the p-value in the chi-square distribution table (as 9.49), we therefore reject the null hypothesis (H_0) and accept the alternate hypothesis (H_1).

Conclusion on hypothesis 3

Reject the null hypothesis and accept the alternate hypothesis that there is a relationship between regulatory framework and agricultural companies development in South-West Nigeria. This result was in line with the view of the majority of participants interviewed. They opined that the development of an appropriate regulatory framework in consultation with critical stakeholders will aid the development of agricultural companies in the South-West Nigeria. Likewise, some authors of literature review such as Iwuchukwu and Igbokwe (2012) concluded that the regulatory framework, if effectively implemented will aid the development of agricultural companies in Nigeria including the South-West region.

7.2.4 Restatement of Research Objective 4, Question 4 and Hypothesis 4

Research Objective 4

To identify and evaluate how policy transmission mechanisms can be used to educate stakeholders for the development of agricultural companies in South-West Nigeria.

Research Question 4

Has **policy transmission mechanisms** been used to influence agricultural policy implementation in South-West Nigeria?

Research Hypothesis 4

H₀: There is no significant relationship between policy transmission mechanism and agricultural companies development in South-West Nigeria.

H₁: There is a significant relationship between policy transmission mechanism and agricultural companies development in South-West Nigeria.

TABLE 17.4 Data computation used for testing of hypothesis 4

Expectations	Observed Frequency (O)	Expected Frequency (E)	O-E	(O-E) ²	$\frac{(O-E)^2}{E}$
Strongly Agree	12	40.4	-28.4	806.56	19.96
Agree	87	40.4	46.6	2171.56	53.75
Fairly Disagree	60	40.4	19.6	384.16	9.51
Disagree	32	40.4	-8.4	70.56	1.75
Strongly Disagree	11	40.4	-29.4	864.36	21.40
Total	202	202	0	4297.2	106.37

Source: Field survey (2021) from table 26.2

$$\therefore fe = \frac{202}{5} = 40.4$$

Where calculated value of chi-square = $x^2 = 106.37$

Degree of freedom (*df*) is (r-1) (c-1)

$$= (5-1) (2-1)$$

$$df = 4$$

x^2 calculated	x^2 tabulated (P< .05)	Degree of freedom (<i>df</i>)	Level of confidence
106.37	9.49	4	0.95

Inference

Since the calculated value of x^2 is 106.37 and it is greater than the p-value in the chi-square distribution table (as 9.49), we therefore reject the null hypothesis (H_0) and accept the alternate hypothesis (H_1).

Conclusion on hypothesis 4

Reject the null hypothesis and accept the alternate hypothesis that there is a relationship between policy transmission mechanism and agricultural companies development in South-West Nigeria. The result shows that availability of appropriate policy transmission mechanism will aid the development of agricultural companies in the South-West Nigeria. Most interview participants express their view on the non-existence of agricultural transmission mechanism and as a result unable to give opinion on whether there is a relationship between the agricultural companies development and transmission mechanism. Nonetheless, the author such as Hassan et al. (2010) believe that the development and effective implementation of the right information transmission mechanism by government and agricultural agencies will lead to informed and knowledgeable agricultural companies management and hence aid sustainable agricultural companies development in a country like Nigeria.

7.2.5 Restatement of Research Objective 5, Question 5 and Hypothesis 5

Research Objective 5

To critically examine the various barriers faced by agricultural companies in South-West Nigeria towards achieving desired ROCE through diversification.

Research Question 5

Has agricultural policies influenced the **return on capital employed (ROCE)** of agricultural companies in South-West Nigeria through diversification?

Research Hypothesis 5

H₀: There is no significant relationship between agricultural policy and return on capital employed of agricultural companies in South-West Nigeria.

H₁: There is a significant relationship between agricultural policy and return on capital employed of agricultural companies in the South-West Nigeria.

TABLE 17.5 Data computation used for testing of hypothesis 5

Expectations	Observed Frequency (O)	Expected Frequency (E)	O-E	(O-E) ²	$\frac{(O-E)^2}{E}$
Strongly Agree	43	40.2	2.8	7.84	0.20
Agree	122	40.2	81.8	6691.24	166.45
Fairly Disagree	19	40.2	-21.2	449.44	11.18
Disagree	9	40.2	-31.2	973.44	24.22
Strongly Disagree	8	40.2	-32.2	1036.84	25.79
Total	201	201	0	9158.8	227.84

Source: Field survey (2021) from table 26.2

$$\therefore fe = \frac{201}{5} = 40.2$$

Where calculated value of chi-square = $x^2 = 227.84$

Degree of freedom (*df*) is (r-1) (c-1)

$$= (5-1) (2-1)$$

$$df = 4$$

x^2 calculated	x^2 tabulated (P< .05)	Degree of freedom (<i>df</i>)	Level of confidence
227.4	9.49	4	0.95

Inference

Since the calculated value of x^2 is 227.40 and it is greater than the p-value in the chi-square distribution table (as 9.49), we, therefore, reject the null hypothesis (H_0) and accept the alternate hypothesis (H_1).

Conclusion on hypothesis 5

Reject the null hypothesis and accept the alternative hypothesis that there is a relationship between agricultural policy and ROCE of agricultural companies in South-West Nigeria. The result, however, showed that the agricultural policy can influence the return on capital employed by the agricultural companies in South-West Nigeria and hence attract more investment towards the agricultural companies within the region. The outcome of the hypothesis was in consonance with the view of Nwangwu et al. (2022) who discover that there is a significant positive relationship between the return on capital employed by agricultural companies and their market share price which is an evidence of growth in a company.

7.3 Summary of findings from the hypothesis using chi-square

The hypothesis test using chi-square analysis was used to explore the relationship between the agricultural companies development and the developmental variables. The variable tested include national economic policy, agricultural models, regulatory framework, agricultural transmission mechanism and return on capital employed by agricultural companies. The chi-square test perform on each of the variables revealed the relationship between the agricultural companies development and the developmental variables.

The result of hypothesis 1 led to the rejection of the null hypothesis as the calculated value is higher than the specified level of significance of 0.05. However, the alternative hypothesis was accepted. This signifies there is a relationship between the national economic policy and agricultural companies development. It, therefore, means an effective development of national economic policy will lead to agricultural companies development in the region.

The result of hypothesis 2 also lead to the rejection of the null hypothesis as a result of the chi-square value exceeding the 5% level of significance specified. The alternative hypothesis, which state there is a relationship between agricultural models and agricultural development was accepted. This means that the development of agricultural models for the implementation of agricultural policies will influence the development of agricultural companies. This was in line with the findings of some of the literature reviewed such as Satar (2016) and Chikhuri (2013).

In exploring hypothesis 3, the chi-square test result led to the rejection of the null hypothesis as the calculated values seems to be higher than the specified level of

significant leading to acceptance of the alternative hypothesis. The alternative hypothesis stated that there is a relationship between the agricultural companies development and regulatory framework. It invariable means, the availability of a strong agricultural regulatory framework will lead to the development of agricultural companies in the South-West of Nigeria.

However, the null hypothesis was rejected under hypothesis 4 because the chi-square value was higher than the suggested level of significant. The alternative that states there is a relationship between agricultural transmission mechanisms and agricultural development was accepted. This shows that there is a dedicated transmission mechanism through which agricultural information is transmitted to agricultural companies and other agricultural stakeholders, which will lead to the development of agricultural companies in South-West Nigeria.

Likewise, hypothesis 5 was tested using the chi-square test. The null hypothesis was however rejected based on the chi-square value being higher than the set level of significant which is 0.05. The alternative hypotheses of the existence of a significant relationship between agricultural policy and return on capital employed by agricultural companies in South-West Nigeria were accepted. It shows that agricultural policy is capable of influencing the rate of return on capital employed by the agricultural companies in the South-West.

The findings from the test of hypotheses conducted, therefore, means, there is a significant relationship between the agricultural companies and developmental variables which include national economic policy, agricultural models, regulatory framework, and agricultural transmission mechanism.

7.4 Testing of hypotheses based on Correlation Coefficient (r)

Correlation matrix which can also be referred to as a heatmap was used as a further test of a mutual relationship between independents and dependent variables in the developed models. Correlation is used to determine the connection or relationship between (Huck and Cormier, 1996) the independent agricultural variable such as technology impact, return on capital employed and the dependent variable such as agricultural transmission mechanism and regulatory framework. The correlation coefficient is denoted by “r”, and it ranges between +1 and -1 with +1 signifying a

strong positive correlation and -1 signifying a negative strong correlation between the agricultural variables in the model.

The correlation matrix was generated using Python Anaconda software (See Appendix 5 for the sample of the Jupiter Notebook). However, the hypotheses with the result of the analysis on the connection between the variables in the models are as detailed below.

7.4.1 National agricultural policy implementation

This section was used to evaluate the relationship between national economic policy and the developmental variables such as the inclusion of stakeholders, policy approach, influence of government interventions and application of technology in agricultural processes. The relationship was evaluated based on hypotheses one using a correlation matrix.

Research Hypotheses 1

H₀: There is no significant relationship between the national economic policy and development of agricultural companies in the South-West.

H₁: There is a significant relationship between the national economic policy and development of agricultural companies in South-West.

Equation one (1)

$$NatPol = \alpha + \beta_1 Dev + \beta_2 AgSth + \beta_3 GovInfl + \beta_4 RegFrm + \beta_5 MTech + \beta_6 HiVal + \beta_7 Roc + \beta_8 AgRev + \beta_9 Clim + \mu$$

Where:

NatPol = National economic policy

α	= constant
<i>Dev</i>	= Development
<i>AgSth</i>	= coefficient of stakeholders
<i>GovInfl</i>	= Government influence
<i>RegFrm</i>	= Regulatory framework
<i>MTech</i>	= Modern technology
<i>HiVal</i>	= high value
<i>Roc</i>	= High/low return on capital employed
<i>AgRev</i>	= Agricultural revolution
<i>Clim</i>	= Climate change
μ	= error level incorporating omitted variables

$\beta_1, \beta_2, \beta_3, \beta_4, \beta_5, \beta_6, \beta_7, \beta_8,$ and β_9 = coefficients

Note: Roc, signifies high or low impact on corporate development

Figure 21: Correlation matrix:

Source: Researcher’s correlation output (2022)

The figure 21 above shows from participants responses there is a positive correlation between all the variable in the agricultural model developed under objective 1 and hypothesis 1. The heatmap revealed there is a strong positive correlation between successful implementation of agricultural policies by government and agricultural companies’ development (0.69), positive influence on cash crops output (0.72), adoption of modern technology in the agricultural processes (0.6) and increase in return on capital employed by agricultural companies. However, from the analysis of the respondents it was discovered that there is a weak relationship between the successful implementation of agricultural policies in South-West Nigeria and stakeholders participation in policies formulation (0.5), appropriate regulatory framework (0.46) risk of vulnerability from climate change (0.37) and agricultural revolution that will eradicate hunger and poverty (Byelee et al., 2009). The matrix also shows that there is a positive correlation among all the variables with the least being 0.30 (development and revolution; climate and influence).

Furthermore, the correlation matrix shows that the successful implementation of the national agricultural policies is aided by factors such as the adoption of the right policy developmental approach; inclusion of stakeholders in the formulation of agricultural policy; development of appropriate agricultural regulatory framework; the motivation towards the application of modern technology in agricultural processes; the evidence of the policies influencing an increase in the return of capital employed by the agricultural companies and revolutionising of agricultural sector which will eradicate hunger, poverty and economic stagnation.

The successful implementation of the national agricultural policies (Hazell et al., 2010) based on the above identified factor will therefore lead to agricultural companies' development (Satar, 2016) in the South-West Nigeria. The result was in line with the view of most the literature reviewed such as Storey (1994); Talbot and Revees (1997); Bergh (2000) and most of the respondents interviewed of which analysis is in chapter five of this study.

7.4.2 Models for agricultural policies

Research Hypotheses 2

H₀: There is no significant relationship between the agricultural models and agricultural companies development in South-West Nigeria.

H₁: There is a significant relationship between the agricultural models and agricultural companies' development in South-West Nigeria.

Equation two (2)

$$AgMod = \alpha + \beta_1 ExgInf + \beta_2 EcoGrot + \beta_3 SkilApp + \beta_4 Dev + \beta_5 Roc + \beta_6 ModTech + \beta_7 FinPerf + \beta_8 BusDev + \beta_9 BenAss + \mu$$

Where:

AgMod = Agricultural models

α = constant

ExgInf = Exchange of information

EcoGrot = Economic growth

SkilApp = Skill Application

Dev = Development

Roc = High/low return on capital employed

ModTech = Modern technology

FinPerf = Financial performance
BusDev = Business development
BenAss = Benefit from the assets
 μ = error level incorporating omitted variables
 $\beta_1, \beta_2, \beta_3, \beta_4, \beta_5, \beta_6, \beta_7, \beta_8,$ and β_9 = coefficients

Figure 22: Correlation matrix:

Source: Researcher’s correlation output (2022)

Figure 22 above shows that the correlation between agricultural model and the developmental variables are positive. These results imply that effective exchange of information; link between agricultural policies and agricultural companies growth; the increase in value of a firm as a result of skilful use of agricultural models and development of individual farmers as a result of adoption of agricultural models have positive relationship with availability of model for agricultural policy framework. However, The correlation matrix also revealed there is weak positive correlation between agricultural models and the return on capital employed of agricultural companies; adoption of modern technology by agricultural companies and deriving of benefits from the asset of the firm by agricultural companies. This was in line with the view of most participant interviewed stated in chapter five of the study.

However, there are also positive correlation among the variables with the highest positive correlation, for example the relationship between agricultural companies

growth and effective exchange of information between agricultural companies and government agencies (Adeola and Adetunbi, 2015). Which implies effective exchange of information will aid the growth (Omekwu, 2003 and Harrison et al., 2016) of agricultural companies in the South-West Nigeria. The least positive correlation from the heatmap was between the benefits arising from use of the agricultural assets and the development of an effective model for agricultural policy regulatory framework. Though this was contrary to the view of Akinkunmi (2017) who believe there is a strong positive correlation between the development of policy regulatory framework model and benefit arising from the use of assets. Nonetheless, the results from the correlation matrix invariably support the alternative hypothesis (H_1) which state that there is a significant relationship between the agricultural models and agricultural companies development in the South-West Nigeria.

7.4.3 Regulatory framework for agricultural policy implementation

Hypotheses 3

H_0 : There is no significant relationship between the regulatory framework and agricultural companies development in South-West Nigeria.

H_1 : There is a significant relationship between the regulatory framework and agricultural companies' development in South-West Nigeria.

Equation three (3)

$$RegFrm = \alpha + \beta_1 Infl + \beta_2 EcoSoc + \beta_3 StrAdh + \beta_4 DevProg + \beta_5 PrzStab + \beta_6 EPS + \beta_7 ExcTax + \beta_8 BusTrans + \beta_9 Compt + \mu$$

Where:

<i>RegFrm</i>	= Regulatory framework
α	= constant
<i>Infl</i>	= Influence
<i>EcoSoc</i>	= Economic and social issues
<i>StrAdh</i>	= Strict adherence
<i>DevProg</i>	= Developmental programmes
<i>PrzStab</i>	= Price stabilization
<i>EPS</i>	= High/low earnings per share
<i>ExcTax</i>	= Excessive tax
<i>BusTrans</i>	= Business transformation
<i>Compt</i>	= Competition
μ	= error level incorporating omitted variables

$\beta_1, \beta_2, \beta_3, \beta_4, \beta_5, \beta_6, \beta_7, \beta_8$ and β_9 , = coefficients

Figure 23: Correlation matrix:

Source: Researcher’s correlation output (2022)

The coefficients of the correlation on figure 23 above shows there is positive relationship between adopting agricultural regulatory framework by agricultural companies and financial performances in the agricultural companies in the South-West Nigeria. The correlation matrix therefore, revealed that there is are strong positive correlation coefficients between adoption of agricultural regulatory framework and influence on participation in agricultural programme (0.66); use of regulatory framework by agricultural companies in resolving economic, social and environmental issues(0.68); stabilisation of price and income of the agricultural companies through compliance with the regulatory framework(0.65); the adoption regulatory framework has aided the EPS of the agricultural companies in South-West Nigeria(0.63); transformation of agricultural companies is aided by regulatory practices(0.62). These results were in line with the outcome of the hypothesis test under the chi-square test above. This result implies that the adoption of the regulatory framework by management of agricultural companies in the South-West

Nigeria will bring about high financial performance (Birner and Resnick, 2010; Adams, 2016; Ajayi et al., 2017) and hence will lead to the development of agricultural companies (Afolabi, 2015 and Storey, 1994) in the region.

However, results of the correlation matrix further indicate that effective corporate management in agricultural companies; implementation of developmental and innovative programmes; Imposition of high and excessive tax on agricultural companies; elimination of fraud and unhealthy competition has weak positive relationship with adoption of agricultural regulatory framework. The result confirms the opinions of the respondents who answered relevant questions on their perception of the effect of adoption of agricultural regulatory framework as a tool for measuring financial performance innovation and creativity (Harrison et al., 2016) in agricultural companies in the South-West Nigeria. The priori view regarding this analysis was contradicted. The priori expectation base on literature review such as Birner and Resnick (2010); Morrison and Schneider (1987) was that agricultural regulatory framework will strongly contribute positively to high financial performances in agricultural company.

Non-the-less, from the correlation matrix there is weak positive relationship between all financial performance variable with the weakest relationship between effective corporate management (Harrison et al., 2016; Pretty et al., 2001) through strict adherence to regulatory framework and implementation of appropriate developmental programme (Talbot and Reeves, 1997) through compliance with agricultural regulatory framework (Satar, 2016). This signifies that effective corporate management lack significant impact in the development of agricultural programme in agricultural companies in the South-West Nigeria

However, Given the result displayed in figure 23 above, there is a significant relationship between the regulatory framework and agricultural companies' development in South-West Nigeria.

7.4.4 Transmission mechanism for agricultural policies

Research Hypotheses 4

H₀: There is no significant relationship between policy transmission mechanism and agricultural companies' development in South-West Nigeria.

H₁: There is a significant relationship between policy transmission mechanism and agricultural companies development in South-West Nigeria.

Equation Four (4)

$$TransMech = \alpha + \beta_1 AidCom + \beta_2 MasMed + \beta_3 VitInf + \beta_4 SocImp + \beta_5 RitChan + \beta_6 EduEmp + \beta_7 Knwg + \beta_8 DatAcc + \beta_9 ImpPerf + \mu$$

Where,

TransMech = Transmission mechanism

α	= constant
<i>AidCom</i>	= Aided communication
<i>MasMed</i>	= Information through mass media
<i>VitInf</i>	= Vital information
<i>SocImp</i>	= Social media impact
<i>RitChan</i>	= Right channel
<i>EduEmp</i>	= Educated employees
<i>Knwg</i>	= Knowledge availability
<i>DatAcc</i>	= Data accessibility
<i>ImpPerf</i>	= Improved performance
μ	= error level incorporating omitted variables

$\beta_1, \beta_2, \beta_3, \beta_4, \beta_5, \beta_6, \beta_7, \beta_8,$ and β_9 , = coefficients

Figure 24: Correlation matrix:

Source: Researcher’s correlation output (2022)

The result of the correlation matrix above confirms the opinions of the respondents who answered relevant questions on their perception of the relationship between policy agricultural transmission mechanism and the agricultural developmental variables as coefficients of the agricultural companies’ development in South-West Nigeria. The correlation matrix shows there is a strong positive correlation between appropriate agricultural transmission mechanisms and variables such as effective communication of agricultural policies (0.78); dissemination of vital information by policymakers through mass media(0.68); Agricultural companies in the South-West becoming aware of new policies through social media like Facebook and LinkedIn (0.62); creation of educated and informed employees among the agricultural companies(0.60); improved performance and income of agricultural companies in the South-West Nigeria (0.75). These agreed with the findings of the interview in chapter five.

However, there seems to weak correlation between the agricultural transmission mechanism and variables such as access to information through mass media by the agricultural companies; use of the right channel in transmitting agricultural policies to

the agricultural companies; application of technical knowledge on how to transform from traditional techniques to a mechanised farming system; availability of data for agricultural research. This was contrary to the findings on some of the literature reviewed Omekwu (2003) and Adeola and Adetunbi (2015). Some of the literature reviewed believed most developing nation like Nigeria have not used mass media in transmitting agricultural policies (Dardak, 2015) and has failed to use the right channel in communicating agricultural information (Hassan et al., 2010) and also believe there were no reliable data for agricultural research (Kajisel et al., 1997). Nonetheless, the findings from the correlation matrix in line with the result of interview in chapter five suggest that the development and implementation of an appropriate transmission mechanism (Omekwu, 2003) for agricultural policies by the government will aid the development of agricultural companies in the South-West Nigeria.

7.4.5 Barriers to agricultural companies returns

Research Hypotheses 5

H₀: There is no significant relationship between agricultural diversification and return on capital employed of agricultural companies in South-West Nigeria.

H₁: There is a significant relationship between agricultural diversification and return on capital employed of agricultural companies in South-West Nigeria.

Equation five (5)

$$DiverRtn = \alpha + \beta_1 OilDep + \beta_2 AdeData + \beta_3 Curp + \beta_4 RurMov + \beta_5 Infra + \beta_6 GDP + \beta_7 Povt + \beta_8 Exter + \beta_9 PolFrw + \mu$$

Where:

DivRtn = Diversification returns

α = constant

OilDep = Oil-dependent

AdeData = Adequate data

Curp = Corruption

RurMov = Rural-Urban movement

Infra = Infrastructures

GDP = Increase/decrease in gross Domestic Product

Povt = poverty

Exter = Externalities
PolFrw = Policy framework
 μ = error level incorporating omitted variables

$\beta_1, \beta_2, \beta_3, \beta_4, \beta_5, \beta_6, \beta_7, \beta_8,$ and β_9 = coefficients

Figure 24: Correlation matrix:

Source: Researcher’s correlation output (2022)

Figure 24 above explains that effective diversification of South-West Nigeria’s agricultural sectors is hindered by the following measurable input factors: over-dependent on oil (0.70); high-level corruption (0.68); high rate of rural-urban migration (0.73); lack of infrastructural facilities (0.77); decline in the agricultural contribution to GDP (0.80); High level of poverty as a result of neglect of agriculture (0.76); lack of extensive and intensive agricultural practices; lack of policy framework for the management of agricultural externalities (0.73).

The correlation matrix in figure 24 further revealed that over-dependent on oil revenue (Adams, 2016), the incidence of corruption (Micah and Ruth, 2014; Evans and Alenoghena, 2015)), lack of infrastructure with lack of intensive and extensive agricultural activities are major barriers to effective diversification (Divanbeigi and

Saliola, 2016; Dardak, 2015; Zin 2014). The outcome of this analysis is in line with some of the findings of the literature reviewed in chapter four of the study.

Consequently, the positive coefficients in the correlation matrix in figure 24 above means the aforementioned factors are the major barriers to effective diversification of agricultural practices in the South-West Nigeria. These factors, in the opinion of the respondents, have hindered the growth return on capital employed by the agricultural companies in South-West Nigeria and by extension has resulted in the Nigerian economy lagging behind other emerging economies (Afolabi, 2015 and Byeleeet al., 2009).

Furthermore, it was discovered that there is a positive relationship between the lack of adequate data for economic planning (0.57) and ineffective diversification of agricultural activities in South-West Nigeria. This signifies that lack of adequate data for economic planning is one of the barriers inhibiting effective diversification (Kajisel et al., 1997; Yusuf et al., 2013) in the region, hence it has made the development of the agricultural companies in the region to lagged.

7.5 Test of Hypotheses and model development using regression analysis

At this section the regression analysis (ordered logit) was used to evaluate, develop, and test the significance of the research models and the research hypotheses. The regression analysis was used to generate coefficient and equation which described the statistical relationship between one or more independent (predictor) variables and a dependent (response) variable. The statistical tools used in addition to regression coefficient included the odd ratios, the correlation matrix, likelihood ratio test, and the coefficient of determination (R^2).

The regression was used to assess the relationship between agricultural development and the developmental variables. Furthermore, the regression through SPSS and gretl software was used to build, test and developed agricultural models. According to Hunter and Schmidt (2004) a regression is an analytical technique that attach weight to all predictors. Consequently, it can be used to test hypothesis about direct and indirect relationship among the predictors. However, the value generated through regression connoted a measurement that determined the quality of the prediction in relation to the dependent variables.

7.5.1 Test of Significance

The test of significance was used to determine the individual significance of the estimated parameters. This was achieved by using the p-values of each of the variables. The p-value showed the direction in which the acceptance or the rejection of the hypothesis would go. A low p-value (>0.05) indicated that the null hypothesis (H_0) could be rejected, and the alternative hypothesis (H_1) accepted. On the other hand, a high p-value (<0.05) indicated that the null hypothesis (H_0) was to be accepted and the alternative hypothesis (H_1) rejected.

A low p-value is said to be statistically significant. This meant that the changes in the independent (predictor) variable were related to the changes in the dependent (response) variable. Also, a high p-value is said to be statistically insignificant. This suggested that the changes in the independent (predictor) variable were not associated with the changes in the dependent (response) variable.

7.5.2 Correlation Coefficient (R)

The R-value signifies a measurement that determined the strength of the prediction in relation to the dependent variables. Where R stood between -1 and +1, the prediction was said to be of a good level. In that wise, a measurement of good fit was therefore attributed to the relationship between one variable and another variable. In other words, R was interpreted to be the correlation of the dependent variables with the predicted values.

For a simple regression, this association could be given as: $R = \frac{1-6\sum d}{n(n^2-1)}$

Where:

d = the difference between the ranked values

n = number of ranked values

7.5.3 Coefficient of Determination (R^2)

This was a further measure of the goodness of fit of the regression estimate. The R^2 was a statistical measure that showed how close the data was to the fitted regression line. It was the percentage of the dependent variable that was explained by a linear model. For instance, a 0% indicated that the model explained none of the variability of the dependent data around its mean, whilst a 100% indicated that the model explained all the variability of the dependent data around its mean. Where additional variables were added, the coefficient of the multiple determination R^2 was said to be fitted more appropriately.

A general formula may be given as:

$$R^2 = \frac{\text{Explained Variation}}{\text{Total Variation}}$$

However, it should be noted that a high or low R^2 does not necessarily indicate whether the model has a good fit or not.

7.5.4 Restatement of Research Objective 1, Question 1 and Hypothesis 1

Research Objective 1

To critically explore economic policy scenarios that can lead to agricultural company development through agricultural policy analysis.

Research Question 1

Has the national economic policy been used to **aid the development** of agricultural companies in South-West Nigeria?

7.5.4.1 Test of Hypothesis 1

Hypothesis 1 was tested in line with the research objective to find out the relationship between agricultural companies' development and national economic policy.

The regression coefficient was given as:

Equation one (1)

$$\text{NatPol} = \alpha + \beta_1 \text{Dev} + \beta_2 \text{AgSth} + \beta_3 \text{GovInfl} + \beta_4 \text{RegFrm} + \beta_5 \text{MTech} + \beta_6 \text{HiVal} + \beta_7 \text{Roc} + \beta_8 \text{AgRev} + \beta_9 \text{Clim} + \mu$$

Where:

NatPol = National economic policy

- α = constant
- Dev* = Development
- AgSth* = Agricultura of stakeholders
- GovInfl* = Government influence
- RegFrm* = Regulatory framework
- MTech* = Modern technology
- HiVal* = high value
- Roc* = High/low return on capital employed
- AgRev* = Agricultural revolution
- Clim* = Climate change
- μ = error level incorporating omitted variables

$\beta_1, \beta_2, \beta_3, \beta_4, \beta_5, \beta_6, \beta_7, \beta_8,$ and β_9 = coefficients

Table 7.5.4.1: Hypothesis 1 model

Variable	Coefficient (β)	Std. Error (μ)	t-statistic	P value (Sig.)
Constant	.030	.194	.156	.876
<i>Dev</i>	.411	.053	7.810	.000
<i>AgSth</i>	.100	.050	1.980	.049
<i>GovInfl</i>	.438	.054	8.103	.000
<i>RegFrm</i>	.101	.063	1.610	.109
<i>MTech</i>	-.018	.076	-.242	.809
<i>HiVal</i>	-.167	.066	-2.528	.012
<i>Roc</i>	.123	.068	1.793	.075
<i>AgRev</i>	-.112	.048	-2.346	.020
<i>Clim</i>	.090	.060	1.489	.138

Significant at $\alpha = 0.05$

Source: Researcher's regression output (2022)

This model measured the relationship between the national economic policy and the agricultural companies developmental variable in South-West Nigeria using multiple regression. Table 7.5.4.1 indicated the coefficient of the nine (9) independent variables in the model. The output of the model based on hypothesis one on the

policy development approach revealed a coefficient of 0.411, with $P(\text{Dev}=x_1=0.000 < 0.05)$ which is less than 0.05 and shows there is a significant influence. The result indicated that the broad-brush policy approach (Hazell et al., 2010; Storey, 1994) used by the Nigerian government has a significant impact on the successful implementation of the national agricultural policies (Ibietan, 2011) in South-West Nigeria. This was contrary to the view of authors such as Akpan and Eyo (2018) who believe that the development of tailor-made policy rather than a broad-brush approach will lead to agricultural development in South-West Nigeria. From the model, the result on agricultural stakeholder participation shows a coefficient of 0.100 with a P-value of 0.049 which is less than 0.05 ($\text{AgSth} = x_2 = 0.049 < 0.05$). This shows that exclusion of the stakeholders in the formulation of agricultural policies will have a significant effect on the successful implementation of the agricultural policy. Authors such as Daneji (2011); Adeola and Adetunbi (2015) as revealed by the model think the policymakers and all the stakeholders in the agricultural sector should collectively design the agricultural policies as it will lead to successful implementation (Satar, 2016) and development of the agricultural companies in all regions in Nigeria.

However, Table 7.5.4.1 shows coefficient of 0.438 for government influence with P values of 0.00 which is less than 0.05 ($\text{AgSth} = x_3 = 0.049 < 0.05$). The result indicates that government intervention through agricultural policies can influence the output and productivity (Byelee et al., 2009) of agricultural companies in South-West Nigeria. The result of the model invalidates the view of Morrison and Schneider (1987) who think the government intervention in the agricultural sector in a developing nation like Nigeria will act as a barrier to agricultural business development. The result also suggests that a regulatory framework with a beta of 0.101 and a P-value of .109 ($\text{RegFrm} = x_4 = 0.109 > 0.05$) is greater than 0.05, hypothesis one is therefore supported. This signifies that lack of an appropriate regulatory framework has led to poor implementation and failure of agricultural policy in South-West Nigeria. This was in line with the view of author such as Talbot and Reeves (1997) and Diao et al. (2007) that believe there is need for development of an appropriate regulatory framework that will aid implementation of agricultural policy that will in turn aid agricultural companies' development.

Furthermore, the model revealed coefficient of -0.018 and P value of .809 ($MTech = x_5 = 0.809 > 0.05$) is greater than 0.05. This shows that government must formulate the right agricultural policies that will motivate the agricultural companies toward the adoption and application of modern technology (Zin, 2014) in the agricultural processes. It is evident from the result that there is a relationship between agricultural policies and the adoption of modern technologies in agricultural processes in South-West Nigeria. This was in line with the findings of the result of interview in chapter five and the opinion of most author such as Owombo et al. (2012) that thinks the development of the right agricultural policy will lead easy access and adoption of modern technology (McChesney, 2004) in agricultural processes and thus result to the development of agricultural companies in South-West Nigeria. Likewise, the result shows a coefficient of -.162 and a P-value of .012 ($HiVal = x_6 = 0.012 < 0.05$) is less than 0.05. This signifies that the management of agricultural companies highly valued the right agriculture because they enhanced the adoption of the mechanised system of agriculture because they aid agricultural company's growth and development (Nuyartoro et al., 2016; Owombo et al., 2012). This result was in consonance with a priori Literature reviewed such as Ibietan (2011) and findings of the interview conducted for this study where the participants believe that the right agricultural policies will influence the value placed on agricultural policies and enhance the mechanised system of agriculture. The coefficient of return on capital employed is .123 while the P-value is .075 ($Roc = x_7 = 0.075 > 0.05$) which is greater than 0.05. This implies that the government has not established the right agricultural policies that can significantly influence the return on capital employed hence it has not aided the development of agricultural companies in South-West Nigeria.

In the same vein the coefficient of agricultural revolution was -.112 with P value of 0.020 ($AgRev = x_8 = 0.020 < 0.05$) which is less than 0.05. This suggests that the policymaker had failed to launch an agricultural revolution which should have eradicated hunger, poverty, and economic stagnation (Cervantes-Godoy and Dewbre, 2010; Byelee et al., 2009). This implies that the national economic policy through the agricultural revolution can be used to aid the development of agricultural companies in South-West Nigeria. The outcome of the model was in consonance with the opinion of the interview participants who believe the government have not made an

adequate effort to revolutionise the agricultural practices in Nigeria as a whole. Table 7.5.4.1 shows that the coefficient of climate change is .090 with a P value of .138 ($Clim = x_9 = 0.138 > 0.05$) which is greater than 0.05. These results imply that the adaptation of global policy on climate change (Estrada et al., 2013) will not have a statistically significant impact successful implementation of policy (UNFCCC, 2007) in South-West Nigeria. This result was in consonance with the views of most participants interviewed for this study (See chapter five). However, this was contrary to the findings of the literature reviewed where author such as Iwuchukwu and Igbokwe (2012); Estradal et al. (2013) thinks adaptation of global developed my international agencies will aid the successful implementation of national policy.

The result displayed in the model 1 above, shows that P value connected with predictors x_1, x_2, x_3, x_6 and x_8 are lower than the specified levels of significance, that is, ($P < 0.05$). Therefore, hypothesis 1 is rejected for models x_1, x_2, x_3, x_6 and x_8 . While the related P value for predictors $x_4, x_5, x_7,$ and x_9 are greater than ($P > 0.05$) the stipulated level of significance, thus, hypothesis 1 is accepted for these models. Nonetheless, the table 7.5.4.2 below is the summary of the model

Table 7.5.4.2

Model Summary ^b										
Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate	R Square Change	Change Statistics			Sig. F Change	Durbin-Watson
						F Change	df1	df2		
1	.836 ^a	.700	.685	.648	.700	49.429	9	191	.000	1.064

a. Predictors: (Constant), Effects of climate change, Government intervention, Exclusion of stakeholders, Impact of broad-brush policy on development, Eradication of poverty, Agricultural policy value, Regulatory framework implementation, increase in return on capital employed due to agricultural revolution, Application of modern technology

b. Dependent Variable: Successful implementation of national policy

Table 7.5.4.2 above revealed, the combined effect of all the predictors (independent variables) on the successful implementation of national policy (Dependent variable). These values represent the combined effect of how the 9 independent variables

influence the successful implementation of the national policy and in turn aid the development of agricultural companies in South-West Nigeria.

The R^2 shows the strength of the relationship (Huck and Cormier, 1996) between the predictors such as the exclusion of stakeholders and the successful implementation of agricultural policy which will lead to the development of agricultural companies in the region. The result from table 7.5.4.2 indicated that a change in the successful implementation of national policy (Hazell et al., 2010) will lead to 70% ($R^2 = .700$ and Adjusted $R^2 = .685$) of the change in the development of agricultural companies in South-West Nigeria. The result also shows that there is a strong positive correlation of .836 ($R = .836$) between the predictors and the successful implementation of national policy.

However, the Durbin Watson coefficient which is a test of autocorrelation is 1.064. Since this is a small P-value it cast doubt on the null hypothesis which signifies that the alternative should be accepted. While the joint or aggregate F-value is significant at $P = 0.000$ ($P=0.000 < 0.05$). Consequently, the combined effect of all the predictors is significant for the successful implementation of the national policy. Therefore, the coefficient in the table 7.5.4.1 can be substituted for the original equation one models of α , β_1 , β_2 , β_3 , β_4 , β_5 , β_6 , β_7 , β_8 and β_9 thus:

$$\mathbf{NatPol} = 0.03 + (0.411)Dev + (0.100)AgSth + (0.438)GovInfl + (0.101)RegFrm + (0.018)MTech + (0.167)HiVal + (0.123)Roc + (0.112)AgRev + (0.090)Clim + \mu.$$

The model implies that research question 1 and its objective have therefore been achieved. In consonance with the findings of the interview the model averred that the successful implementation of national economic policy by the government can be used to aid the development of agricultural companies in South-West Nigeria.

7.5.5 Restatement of Research Objective 2, Question 2 and Hypothesis 2

Research Objective 2

To develop a model using artificial intelligence, capable of establishing linkage between the agricultural policies and the agricultural companies development in South-West Nigeria.

Research Question 2

Are there **models** on how agricultural policies can be used to influence the development of agricultural companies in South-West Nigeria?

7.5.5.1 Test of Research Hypothesis 2

H₀: There is no significant relationship between the agricultural models and agricultural companies development in South-West Nigeria.

H₁: There is significant relationship between the agricultural models and agricultural companies development in South-West Nigeria.

The regression coefficient was given as:

Equation two (2)

$$AgMod = \alpha + \beta_1 ExgInf + \beta_2 EcoGrot + \beta_3 SkilApp + \beta_4 Dev + \beta_5 Roc + \beta_6 ModTech + \beta_7 FinPerf + \beta_8 BusDev + \beta_9 BenAss + \mu$$

Where:

AgMod = Agricultural models

α	= constant
<i>ExgInf</i>	= Exchange of information
<i>EcoGrot</i>	= Economic growth
<i>SkilApp</i>	= Skill Application
<i>Dev</i>	= Development
<i>Roc</i>	= High/low return on capital employed
<i>ModTech</i>	= Modern technology
<i>FinPerf</i>	= Financial performance
<i>BusDev</i>	= Business development
<i>BenAss</i>	= Benefit from the assets
μ	= error level incorporating omitted variables
$\beta_1, \beta_2, \beta_3, \beta_4, \beta_5, \beta_6, \beta_7, \beta_8, \text{and } \beta_9$	= coefficients

Table 7.5.5.1: Hypothesis 2 model

Variable	Coefficient (β)	Std. Error (μ)	t-statistic	P value (Sig.)
Constant	.476	.261	1.821	.070
<i>ExgInf</i>	.430	.077	5.548	.000
<i>EcoGrot</i>	.180	.089	2.006	.046
<i>SkilApp</i>	.073	.087	.845	.399
<i>Dev</i>	.181	.095	1.893	.060
<i>Roc</i>	-.136	.061	-2.214	.028
<i>ModTech</i>	.150	.066	2.285	.023
<i>FinPerf</i>	.018	.069	.254	.800
<i>BusDev</i>	.027	.083	.323	.747
<i>BenAss</i>	-.040	.078	.517	.006

Significant at $\alpha = 0.05$

Source: Researcher's regression output (2022)

This model measured the relationship between the agricultural models and agricultural companies development in South-West Nigeria using multiple regression analysis. Table 7.5.5.1 shows the coefficient of the nine (9) independent variables (predictors) in the model. The result of the model based on hypothesis one on the exchange of information between government agencies and agricultural companies shows a coefficient of 0.430, with a P-value of 0.000 ($ExgInf = x_1 = 0.000 < 0.05$) which is less than 0.05 and shows there is a significant relationship. The result indicated that there is a significant relationship between the effective exchange of information amongst agricultural stakeholders (Daneji, 2011) and agricultural models. This was in consonance with the view of authors such as Omekwu (2003) that stated the exchange of agricultural information will integrate all agricultural agencies and the agricultural companies. The integration will in turn aid the development of agricultural companies. From the model, the result of the economic growth shows a coefficient of 0.180 with a P-value of 0.046 which is less than 0.05 ($EcoGrot = x_2 = 0.046 < 0.05$). This indicates that economic growth is a sign of a link between the agricultural model and agricultural development (Zin, 2014) in South-West Nigeria. The result is in consonance with the findings from interviews conducted and the view of authors such

as Afolabi (2016); Akinkunmi (2017). These authors believe that the provision of an appropriate agricultural model will aid the development of agricultural companies.

However, Table 7.5.5.1 revealed a coefficient of 0.073 for skill application with P values of 0.399 which is greater than 0.05 ($SkilApp = x_3 = 0.399 > 0.05$). The result shows that the government has failed to establish a model that will aid the application of skill (Kajisel et al., 1997) in the development of agricultural companies in South-West Nigeria. The output of the model is in line with the findings of the interview in chapter 5. The result also suggests that the development of an individual farmer into an agricultural company is associated with a beta of 0.181 and a P-value of .060 ($Dev = x_4 = 0.060 > 0.05$) which is greater than 0.05, the null hypothesis is therefore supported. This signifies the lack of adoption of the agricultural model by individual farmers due to the nonexistence of an appropriate (Luken, 2006) agricultural model (Ibietan, 2011) in South-West Nigeria. The result of the model was in line with the response of the interview participants that stated that there is no established agricultural model in the South-West. The participants also think that the individual agricultural company are operating without a specific or uniform model, and this has been one of the main impediments to the development of agricultural companies (Birner and Resnick, 2010) in South-West Nigeria.

Furthermore, the model revealed a coefficient of -0.136 and a P-value of .028 ($Roc = x_5 = 0.028 < 0.05$) which is less than 0.05. The result affirms that the low return on capital employed by the agricultural companies in South-West Nigeria is due to a lack of an appropriate agricultural model for the implementation (Barrett and Mutambatsere, 2005) of agricultural policies in the region. The result aligns with the opinion of authors such as Bauer and Yamey (1965) and Novikova (2014) that believe the developing like Nigeria should develop an appropriate agrarian model that will aid the implementation and stabilisation of agricultural policies. The result of the model was also in consonance with the view of the participants interviewed for this research. On the other hand, the result shows a coefficient of .150 and a P-value of .023 ($ModTech = x_6 = 0.023 < 0.05$) which is less than 0.05. The model signifies that there is a positive relationship between the availability of appropriate agricultural models and adoption of the modern technology in the agricultural process (Zin, 2014). This was in line with the findings from the result of the interviews which shows that

the absence of an agricultural model has hindered the adoption of modern technology in the region. The lack of application of modern technology in agricultural processes has negatively affected the development of agricultural companies (Ibietan, 2011) in South-West Nigeria.

The model on table 7.5.5.1 also, shows that the coefficient of financial performance as a yardstick for application agricultural is 0.18 while the P-value is .800 ($FinPerf = x_7 = 0.800 > 0.05$) which is greater than 0.05. This implies that the government has not established the right agricultural models that can aid the financial performance of agricultural companies in South-West Nigeria. The result agreed with the view of authors such as Agboola (2014) and Hazell et al. (2010). In the same vein the coefficient of business development is 0.27 with P value of 0.747 ($BusDev = x_8 = 0.747 > 0.05$) which is greater than 0.05. This suggests that the policymaker has not established an agricultural model which can aid business development in agricultural companies despite the direct relationship between the agricultural model and the business development. The result of the model is in consonance with the findings of the interview. Most of the participants believe the lack of an agricultural model is the missing link between business development and the adequate return on capital employed by agricultural companies (Byelee et al., 2009). However, the coefficient of benefits arising from the business asset as a result of the application of agricultural models is -0.040 with P value of .606 ($BenAss = x_9 = 0.006 < 0.05$) which is less than 0.05. These results imply that the government have not established agricultural models that will maximise the benefits derived (Mohammed et al., 2011) from agricultural assets. This result was in consonance with the views of most participants interviewed for this study.

The result displayed in Table 7.5.5.1 above, shows that P-values connected with predictors x_1 , x_2 , x_5 , x_6 and x_9 are lower than the specified levels of significance, that is, ($P < 0.05$). Therefore, hypothesis 1 is rejected for models x_1 , x_2 , x_5 , x_6 and x_9 . While the related P-value for predictors x_3 , x_4 , x_7 , and x_8 are greater than ($P > 0.05$) the stipulated level of significance, thus, hypothesis 1 is accepted for these models. Nonetheless, skill table 7.6.2 below shows the summary of the models.

Table 7.5.5.2

Model Summary										
Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate	R Square Change	Change Statistics			Sig. F Change	Durbin-Watson
						F Change	df1	df2		
2	.751 ^a	.563	.542	.639	.563	26.515	9	185	.000	1.008
a. Predictors: (Constant), Benefits arising from assets, Skilful application of models, return on capital employed, Exchange of information and resources, Evidence of business development, Application of modern technologies, Economic growth, Financial performance as a yardstick, Development of individual farmer b. Dependent Variable: Successful implementation of agricultural models										

The table 7.5.5.2 above revealed, the combined effect of all the predictors (independent variables) on successful implementation of agricultural models (Dependent variable). These values represent the combined effect of how the 9 independent variables can aid the establishment and successful implementation of the agricultural models that will lead to the development of agricultural companies in South-West Nigeria.

The R^2 However indicates the strength of the relationship (Huck and Cormier, 1996) between the independent variable such as the return on capital employed and exchange of information and resources and the successful implementation of agricultural models that will aid the development of agricultural companies in the region. The result from table 7.5.5.2 indicated that a positive change in the successful implementation of agricultural models (Ibietan, 2011) will lead to 56.3% ($R^2 = .563$ and Adjusted $R^2 = .542$) of the change in the development of agricultural companies in South-West Nigeria. The result also shows that there is a strong positive correlation of .751 ($R = .751$) between the predictors and the successful implementation of agricultural models.

However, the Durbin Watson coefficient which is a test of auto correlation is 1.008. Since this is a small P-value it cast doubt on the null hypothesis which signifies that the alternative should be accepted. While the joint or aggregate F-value is significant at $P = 0.000$ ($P = 0.000 < 0.05$). Consequently, the combined effect of all the predictors is significant on the development and successful implementation of agricultural models. Therefore, the coefficient in the table 7.6.1 can be substituted for the original equation two models of α , β_1 , β_2 , β_3 , β_4 , β_5 , β_6 , β_7 , β_8 and β_9 thus:

$$AgMod = .476 + (.430)ExgInf + (.180)EcoGrot + (.073)SkilApp + (.181)Dev + (.136)Roc + (.150)ModTech + (.018)FinPerf + (.027)BusDev + (.040)BenAss + \mu$$

The model implies that research question 1 and its objective has therefore been achieved. The model confirmed that the development and successful implementation of agricultural models by the government and its agencies can be used to aid the development of agricultural companies in South-West Nigeria.

7.5.6 Restatement of Research Objective 3, Question 3 and Hypothesis 3

Research Objective 3

To critically evaluate and suggest a practicable agricultural regulatory framework that will serve as a policy guide towards the implementation and achievement of agricultural companies development in South-West Nigeria

Research Question 3

What are the impacts of the **regulatory framework** on agricultural policy implementation in Nigeria?

7.5.6.1 Test of Research Hypothesis 3

H₀: There is no significant relationship between the regulatory framework and agricultural companies development in South-West Nigeria.

H₁: There is a significant relationship between the regulatory framework and agricultural companies' development in South-West Nigeria.

The regression coefficient was given as:

Equation three (3)

$$RegFrm = \alpha + \beta_1 Infl + \beta_2 EcoSoc + \beta_3 StrAdh + \beta_4 DevProg + \beta_5 PrzStab + \beta_6 EPS + \beta_7 ExcTax + \beta_8 BusTrans + \beta_9 Compt + \mu$$

Where:

<i>RegFrm</i>	= Regulatory framework
α	= constant
<i>Infl</i>	= Influence
<i>EcoSoc</i>	= Economic and social issues
<i>StrAdh</i>	= Strict adherence
<i>DevProg</i>	= Developmental programmes

PrzStab = Price stabilization
EPS = High/low earnings per share
ExcTax = Excessive tax
BusTrans = Business transformation
Compt = Competition
 μ = error level incorporating omitted variables

$\beta_1, \beta_2, \beta_3, \beta_4, \beta_5, \beta_6, \beta_7, \beta_8$ and β_9 , = coefficients

Table 7.5.6.1: Hypothesis 3

Variable	Coefficient	Std. Error	t-statistic	P-value (Sig.)
Constant	.344	.194	1.773	.078
<i>Infl</i>	.126	.069	1.810	.072
<i>EcoSoc</i>	.139	.064	2.189	.030
<i>StrAdh</i>	.178	.060	2.972	.003
<i>DevProg</i>	-.082	.047	-1.754	.810
<i>PrzStab</i>	.022	.066	.338	.736
<i>EPS</i>	.193	.070	2.770	.006
<i>ExcTax</i>	.127	.052	2.443	.016
<i>BusTrans</i>	.193	.059	3.295	.001
<i>Compt</i>	.147	.064	2.306	.022

Significant at $\alpha = 0.05$

Source: Researcher's regression output (2022)

The output of the multiple regression models with nine (9) independent variables investigated the relationship between the regulatory framework and agricultural companies development in South-West Nigeria. The output of the multiple regression led to 0.126 at a P-value of 0.072 ($Infl = x_1 = 0.072 > 0.05$). Which is greater than 0.05 indicating there is a significant relationship. These results imply that the regulatory framework on agricultural policy implementation established by the government had insignificant influence in motivating agricultural companies to participate in agricultural programmes. The non-participation of agricultural companies in the

agricultural programme has been one of the impediments to agricultural companies development in South-West Nigeria. This was in consonance with the view of most of the interview participants and authors of the literature reviewed such as Hazell et al. (2010); Afolabi (2015) and Micah and Ruth (2014). From the model, the result of the economic, social and environmental issues shows a coefficient of 0.139 with a P-value of 0.030 which is less than 0.05 ($EcoSoc = x_2 = 0.030 < 0.05$). This signifies there is a relationship between the agricultural regulatory framework and economic, social and environmental issues. This implies the establishment and implementation of an appropriate regulatory framework that can be used by agricultural companies to resolve the economic and environmental issues in South-West Nigeria. This was the view of the interview participants and is also in consonance with the view of authors such as Byelee et al. (2009) and Cervantes Godoy and Dewbre (2010). These authors believe that the establishment of an appropriate regulatory framework will promote food security and eliminate poverty.

The model in table 7.5.6.1 revealed a coefficient of 0.178 for strict adherence to the regulatory framework with a P-value of 0.003 which is less than 0.05 ($StrAdh = x_3 = 0.003 < 0.05$). The result implies that effective corporate management (Harrison et al., 2016) can be achieved through strict adherence to the regulatory framework (Storey, 1994) established by the government. The strict adherence will in turn aid the development of all the businesses (Talbot and Reeves, 1997) of the agricultural companies in South-West Nigeria. The output of the model is in line with the opinion of the interviewee in chapter 5. The result also indicated that the developmental programme is associated with a beta of -0.082 with a P value of .81 ($DevProg = x_4 = 0.81 > 0.05$) which is greater than 0.05. This suggests that the lack of an appropriate regulatory framework in South-West Nigeria has inhibited the agricultural companies from implementing the agricultural developmental programmes. This agrees with the view of most interview participants who believe the regulatory framework only exists on paper and is not functional (Luken, 2006). Hence, the regulatory framework has not significantly aided the development of agricultural companies in South-West Nigeria.

Furthermore, the model revealed a coefficient of 0.022 and a P-value of .736 ($PrzStab = x_5 = 0.736 > 0.05$) which greater than 0.05. The result affirms that the

government has failed to establish an appropriate regulatory framework that will aid the stabilization of the price of agricultural products and the income of agricultural companies (Bauer and Yamey, 1965; Williams, 1985; Adeola and Adetunbi, 2015; Tejvan, 2016) in South-West Nigeria. This was in consonance with the findings of the interview results in which the participants think the government are not committed to the development of an appropriate and reliable agricultural regulatory framework. On the other hand, the result shows a coefficient of .193 and a P-value of .006 ($EPS = x_6 = 0.006 < 0.05$) which is less than 0.05 in respect of EPS as a measure of the impact of the regulatory framework and agricultural policy (Diao et al., 2007). The model signifies that there is a relationship between the EPS of agricultural companies and the regulatory framework. There is therefore needed to implement a reliable and appropriate regulatory framework that aid (Nuyartoro et al., 2016) the EPS as a form of the financial reward of agricultural companies in South-West Nigeria. Most participants interviewed believe the agricultural companies are not earning adequate returns due to weakness or nonexistence of agricultural regulatory framework (Micah and Ruth, 2014).

However, the model in table 7.5.6.1 also, shows the coefficient of the excessive tax rate on agricultural companies as 0.127 while the P-value is .016 ($ExcTax = x_7 = 0.016 < 0.05$) which is less than the 0.05 level of significance. This implies that the government's excessive tax rate imposed on the agricultural companies has been a major barrier discouraging investment in agricultural companies. Government should therefore establish a framework that will lead to granting agricultural companies adequate tax relief (Zin, 2014) that will attract investors to the agricultural companies in South-West Nigeria. The result was in line with the view of Pretty et al. (2001) who thinks taxes and relief can be used as a mechanism to promote development in agricultural businesses. In the same vein the coefficient of business transformation is 0.193 with P value of 0.001 ($BusTrans = x_8 = 0.001 < 0.05$) which is less than 0.05. This suggests that there is a relationship between regulatory framework and business transformation. Therefore, the government should establish a regulatory framework that will aid agricultural business transformation (Dardak, 2015) and eliminate hostile competition and reduce fraudulent practices among agricultural stakeholders within the region.

However, the coefficient of healthy competition among agricultural companies is 0.147 with a P value of .022 ($Compt = x_9 = 0.022 < 0.05$) which is less than 0.05. These results imply that the establishment of an appropriate regulatory framework for agricultural transformation can eliminate high fraud (Micah and Ruth, 2014; Evans and Alenoghena, 2015 Ajayi et al., 2017) and unhealthy competition among agricultural companies in South-West Nigeria. Therefore, the government being the regulator need to establish and successfully implement an agricultural framework that minimises the high rate of corruption among agricultural companies in the South-West. The elimination of healthy competition will influence the development of agricultural companies in the region.

The result displayed in Table 7.5.6.1 above, shows that P-values connected with predictors x_2, x_3, x_6, x_7, x_8 and x_9 are lower than the specified levels of significance, that is, ($P < 0.05$). Therefore, the null hypothesis is rejected for models x_2, x_3, x_6, x_7, x_8 and x_9 . While the related P-value for predictors x_1, x_4 and x_5 are greater than ($P > 0.05$) the stipulated level of significance (0.05), thus, hypothesis 1 is accepted for these models. Nonetheless, the table 7.5.6.2 below shows the summary of models:

Table 7.5.6.2

Model Summary ^b										
Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate	R Square Change	Change Statistics			Sig. F Change	Durbin-Watson
						F Change	df1	df2		
1	.847 ^a	.718	.704	.503	.718	51.733	9	183	.000	1.192
a. Predictors: (Constant), Regulatory framework eliminate unhealthy competition, EPS as a measure of financial reward for capital investment, Regulatory practices play a crucial part in the transformation of agricultural company, Excessive tax imposition discourage investor in the agricultural sector, Lack of appropriate framework is preventing development, Strict adherence will lead to effective corporate management, Compliance with the framework will aid price stabilisation, Framework used to resolve economic, social and environmental issue, Framework influence companies participation b. Dependent Variable: Regulatory framework aids financial performance										

Table 7.5.6.2 above revealed, the combined effect of all the predictors (independent variables) on the successful establishment and implementation of agricultural regulatory framework for agricultural policy implementation in South-West Nigeria (Dependent variable). These values represent the combined effect of how the 9 independent variables can aid the establishment and successful implementation of

the agricultural models that will influence the development of agricultural companies in South-West Nigeria.

According to Huck and Cormier (1996), the R^2 indicates the strength of the relationship between the predictors (x) and the dependent variable (Regulatory framework). The result from table 7.6.2 indicated that a change in the successful implementation of the agricultural regulatory framework (Hazell et al., 2010) will result in 71.8% ($R^2 = .718$ and Adjusted $R^2 = .704$) of the change in the development of agricultural companies in South-West Nigeria. The result, however, shows that there is a strong positive correlation of .847 ($R = .847$) between the predictors and the agricultural regulatory framework.

Consequently, the Dubin Watson coefficient which is a test of autocorrelation is 1.192. Since this is a small P-value it cast doubt on the null hypothesis which signifies that the alternative should be accepted. While the joint or aggregate F-value is significant at $P = 0.000$ ($P=0.000 < 0.05$). Consequently, the combined effect of all the predictors is significant for the establishment and successful implementation of agricultural regulatory framework. Therefore, the coefficient in the table 7.7.1 can be substituted for the original equation three models of α , β_1 , β_2 , β_3 , β_4 , β_5 , β_6 , β_7 , β_8 and β_9 thus:

$$RegFrm = \alpha + (.126)Infl + (.139)EcoSoc + (.178)StrAdh + (.082)DevProg + (.022)PrzStab + (.193)EPS + (.127)ExcTax + (.193)BusTrans + (.147)Compt + \mu$$

The model implies that research question 1 and its objective have therefore been achieved. The model confirmed that the establishment and successful implementation of a regulatory framework by the government and its agencies can be used to influence the development of agricultural companies in South-West Nigeria.

7.5.7 Restatement of Research Objective 4, Question 4 and Hypothesis 4

Research Objective 4

To identify and evaluate how policy transmission mechanisms can be used to educate stakeholders for the development of agricultural companies in South-West Nigeria.

Research Question 4

Have **policy transmission mechanisms** been used to influence agricultural policy implementation in South-West Nigeria?

7.5.7.1 Test of Research Hypothesis 4

H₀: There is no significant relationship between policy transmission mechanism and agricultural companies' development in South-West Nigeria.

H₁: There is a significant relationship between policy transmission mechanism and agricultural companies development in South-West Nigeria.

The regression coefficient was given as:

Equation four (4)

$$TransMech = \alpha + \beta_1 AidCom + \beta_2 MasMed + \beta_3 VitInf + \beta_4 SocImp + \beta_5 RitChan + \beta_6 EduEmp + \beta_7 Knwg + \beta_8 DatAcc + \beta_9 ImpPerf + \mu$$

Where,

TransMech = Transmission mechanism

α	= constant
<i>AidCom</i>	= Aided communication
<i>MasMed</i>	= Information through mass media
<i>VitInf</i>	= Vital information
<i>SocImp</i>	= Social media impact
<i>RitChan</i>	= Right channel
<i>EduEmp</i>	= Educated employees
<i>Knwg</i>	= Knowledge availability
<i>DatAcc</i>	= Data accessibility
<i>ImpPerf</i>	= Improved performance
μ	= error level incorporating omitted variables

$\beta_1, \beta_2, \beta_3, \beta_4, \beta_5, \beta_6, \beta_7, \beta_8,$ and β_9 , = coefficients

Table 7.5.7.1: Hypothesis 4

Variable	Coefficient	Std. Error	t-statistic	P-value (Sig.)
Constant	-.089	.209	-.428	.669
<i>AidCom</i>	.574	.079	7.288	.000
<i>MasMed</i>	-.145	.081	-1.781	.077
<i>VitInf</i>	.247	.073	3.380	.001
<i>SocImp</i>	-.047	.077	-.606	.545
<i>RitChan</i>	-.023	.071	-.322	.747
<i>EduEmp</i>	-.038	.071	-.534	.594
<i>Knwg</i>	.144	.047	3.065	.003
<i>DatAcc</i>	.189	.068	-2.778	.006
<i>ImpPerf</i>	.453	.068	6.610	.000

Significant at $\alpha = 0.05$

Source: Researcher's regression output (2022)

The model in table 7.5.7.1 above showed the relationship between the agricultural policy transmission mechanism and the Nine (9) independent variables of agricultural companies development. The output of the model revealed a coefficient of 0.574 and a P-value of 0.000 ($AidCom = x_1 = 0.000 > 0.05$) which is less than 0.05 indicating there is a significant relationship. The results show that the agricultural policy transmission mechanism is capable of influencing communication between the government agencies and the stakeholders in the agricultural sector in South-West Nigeria. Therefore, the government need to establish an appropriate transmission mechanism that will aid communication (Omekwu, 2003) and implementation of agricultural policies between the agricultural companies and government agencies regulating agricultural businesses in South-West Nigeria. This is in consonance with the responses of most of the participants in the interview conducted for this study. This is also in line with the view of authors such as Hassan et al. (2010); Adeola and Adetunbi (2015) who believe the government agencies should improve their collaborative effort through the transmission of the agricultural information using the right channel.

The findings on information through mass media show a coefficient of -0.145 with a P-value of 0.077 which is greater than 0.05 ($MasMed = x_2 = 0.077 > 0.05$). This signifies that the government has not fully utilised the mass media as a means of communicating (Dardak, 2015) the agricultural policies to the agricultural companies. To aid the effective implementation of agricultural policy the government should therefore improve on the use of mass media as a means of transmitting information about agricultural policies to the agricultural companies in the South-Nigeria. This was the view of the interview participants in this study. Table 7.5.7.1 also revealed a coefficient of 0.247 for the dissemination of vital information with a P-value of 0.001 which is less than 0.05 ($VitInf = x_3 = 0.001 < 0.05$). The result implies that policymaker can effectively utilise mass media to transmit vital information (Omekwu, 2003) to the agricultural companies in South-West Nigeria. The output of the model is in line with the opinion of the interviewee in chapter 5. The result also indicated that the social media impact has a beta coefficient of -0.047 with a P value of .545 ($SocImp = x_4 = 0.545 > 0.05$) which is greater than 0.05. This suggests that the social media has not impacted the awareness of agricultural policy and as a result has not influenced the development of agricultural companies (Owombo et al., 2012) in South-West Nigeria. Likewise, the interview participants believe government agencies have not taken the advantage of using social media to transmit information about agricultural policy adoption and implementation (Diao et al., 2007).

Furthermore, the model revealed a coefficient of -0.023 and P value of .747 ($RitChan = x_5 = 0.747 > 0.05$) which is greater than 0.05 for use of an appropriate channel. The result affirms that the government has failed to use the right channel to transmit agricultural policy information (Omekwu, 2003) to agricultural companies in South-West Nigeria. This was in consonance with the findings of some of the literature review such as Barrett and Mutambatsere (2005); Afroz and Akhtar (2007). The authors believe using the right channel of communication to disseminate the agricultural policies information to the stakeholders in the agricultural companies will aid the effective implementation of agricultural policies and hence the development of the agricultural companies in South-West Nigeria. Similarly, the result shows a coefficient of -0.038 and P value of .594 ($EduEmp = x_6 = 0.594 > 0.05$) that is greater than 0.05 for the creation of educated and informed employees. The result of the model shows where agricultural information is disseminated through the right channel

of communication it will lead to informed and educated employees within the agricultural companies in South-West Nigeria. Most participants of the interviewed have the same view as the outcome of the model and believe this will aid the development of agricultural companies in South-West Nigeria.

However, from the model on table 7.5.7.1, the coefficient of the availability of knowledge for transformation is 0.144 while the P-value is .003 ($Knwg = x_7 = 0.003 < 0.05$) which is less than 0.05 level of significance. This implies that the South-West agricultural companies have remained uninformed due to a lack of knowledge on how to transform the traditional agricultural system to a mechanise agricultural system that will lead to high productivity. The transformation from the traditional system to the mechanised system of agriculture will influence the development of agricultural companies in South-West Nigeria. Government, therefore, need to establish the right policy (Akpan and Eyo, 2018) that will support capacity building in the area of educating the agricultural company on the adoption of mechanising system of agriculture (Birner and Resnick, 2010; Owombo et al., 2012). On the other hand, the coefficient of data accessibility is -0.189 with a P-value of 0.006 ($DatAcc = x_8 = 0.006 < 0.05$) which is less than 0.05. This suggests that the use of mass media can use to overcome the dearth of data for agricultural research (Kajisel et al., 1997) in South-West Nigeria. Consequently, overcoming the barrier of accessibility and availability of data (Yusuf et al., 2013) using mass media will aid the development of agricultural companies in the region. The findings of the interview revealed that accessibility of data is a major issue for the agricultural companies in the South-West. It was further stated that the non-availability of data has prevented the agricultural company from effective and efficient planning.

Nonetheless, the model revealed the coefficient of improved performance as a result of appropriate transmission to be 0.453 with a P-value of .000 ($ImpPerf = x_9 = 0.000 < 0.05$) which is less than 0.05. These results imply that the use of an appropriate transmission mechanism (Williams, 1985) can improve the agricultural companies performances and income. This was in line with the view of authors such as Bauer and Yamey (1965); Yusuf et al. (2013) Who believe the development of the right transmission strategies will stabilise the price of agricultural products and aid the development of the agricultural companies.

The result displayed in Table 7.5.7.1 above, shows that P-values connected with predictors x_1 , x_3 , x_7 , x_8 and x_9 are lower than the specified levels of significance, that is, ($P < 0.05$). Therefore, the null hypothesis is rejected for models x_1 , x_3 , x_7 , x_8 and x_9 . While the related P-value for predictors x_2 , x_4 , x_5 and x_6 are greater than ($P > 0.05$) the stipulated level of significance (0.05), thus, hypothesis 1 is accepted for these models. Nonetheless, the table 7.8.2 below shows the summary of models:

Table 7.5.7.2

Model Summary ^b										
Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate	R Square Change	Change Statistics			Sig. F Change	Durbin-Watson
						F Change	df1	df2		
1	.851 ^a	.724	.710	.569	.724	53.308	9	183	.000	1.029

a. Predictors: (Constant), Appropriate transmission mechanism leading to improve performance and income, Good knowledge of the application of mechanise system, Use of right channel for transmission leading to informed employee, Awareness of agricultural policies through social media, Use of mass media to transmit agricultural information, Transmission of vital information through mass media, Appropriate transmission mechanism leading to the accessibility of data, Use of right channel for transmitting agricultural policies, Use of transmission mechanism to aid communication of policies

b. Dependent Variable: Policy transmission mechanism

The table 7.5.7.2 above revealed, the combined effect of all the predictors such as the application of mechanise system and use of social media in transmitting information on policy transmission mechanism in South-West Nigeria (Dependent variable). These values represent the cumulative effect of how the 9 independent variables can influence the establishment and application of the agricultural policy transmission mechanism that will influence the development of agricultural companies in South-West Nigeria.

However, the result from the table 7.5.7.2 indicated that a change in the application of agricultural policy transmission mechanism will result to 72.4% ($R^2 = .724$ and Adjusted $R^2 = .710$) of the change in the development of agricultural companies in the South-West Nigeria. The result, however, shows that there is strong positive correlation of .851 ($R = .847$) between the predictors and agricultural regulatory framework.

Consequently, Dubin Watson coefficient is 1.029. Since this is a relatively small P value it cast doubt on the null hypothesis which signifies that the alternative should be accepted. Hence, there is a significant relationship between policy transmission mechanism and agricultural companies development in South-West Nigeria. However, the aggregate F-value is significant at $P = 0.000$ ($P=0.000 < 0.05$). Therefore, the combined effect of all the predictors is significant in the application of the policy transmission mechanism. The coefficient in the table 7.8.1 can be substituted for the original equation four models of α , β_1 , β_2 , β_3 , β_4 , β_5 , β_6 , β_7 , β_8 and β_9 thus:

$$TransMech = \alpha + (.574)AidCom + (.145)MasMed + (.247)VitInf + (.047)SocImp + (.023)RitChan + (.038)EduEmp + (.144)Knwg + (.189)DatAcc + (.453)ImpPerf + \mu$$

The model implies that research question 4 and its objective have therefore been achieved. The model confirmed that the use of transmission mechanism in transmitting agricultural policy information to agricultural stakeholders can be used to aid the development of agricultural companies in South-West Nigeria.

7.5.8 Restatement of Research Objective 5, Question 5 and Hypothesis 5

Research Objective 5

To critically examine the various diversification barriers faced by agricultural companies in South-West Nigeria towards achieving desired ROCE.

Research Question 5

Has agricultural policies on diversification influenced the **return on capital employed (ROCE)** of agricultural companies in South-West Nigeria?

7.5.8.1 Test of Research Hypothesis 5

H_0 : There is no significant relationship between agricultural diversification and return on capital employed of agricultural companies in South-West Nigeria.

H_1 : There is a significant relationship between agricultural diversification and return on capital employed of agricultural companies in the South-West Nigeria.

The regression coefficient was given as:

Equation four (5)

$$DiverRtn = \alpha + \beta_1 OilDep + \beta_2 AdeData + \beta_3 Corp + \beta_4 RurMov + \beta_5 Infra + \beta_6 GDP + \beta_7 Povt + \beta_8 Exter + \beta_9 PolFrw + \mu$$

Where:

DivRtn = Diversification returns

- α = constant
- OilDep* = Oil-dependent
- AdeData* = Adequate data
- Corp* = Corruption
- RurMov* = Rural-Urban movement
- Infra* = Infrastructures
- GDP* = Increase/decrease gross Domestic Product
- Povt* = poverty
- Exter* = Externalities
- PolFrw* = Policy framework
- μ = error level incorporating omitted variables

$\beta_1, \beta_2, \beta_3, \beta_4, \beta_5, \beta_6, \beta_7, \beta_8,$ and β_9 , = coefficients

Table 7.5.8.1: Hypothesis 5

Variable	Coefficient	Std. Error	t-statistic	P value (Sig.)
Constant	-.012	.177	-.068	.946
<i>OilDep</i>	.285	.064	4.455	.000
<i>AdeData</i>	-.013	.045	-.263	.793
<i>Corp</i>	.130	.057	2.258	.025
<i>RurMov</i>	.080	.055	1.440	.151
<i>Infra</i>	.124	.055	2.269	.024
<i>GDP</i>	.198	.066	2.993	.003
<i>Povt</i>	.127	.058	2.211	.028
<i>Exter</i>	.114	.048	2.352	.020
<i>PolFrw</i>	-.037	.066	-.565	.573

Significant at $\alpha = 0.05$

Source: Researcher's regression output (2022)

The output of the multiple regression models with nine (9) independent variables investigated the relationship between agricultural diversification and return on capital employed by agricultural companies in South-West Nigeria. The result of the model for oil-dependency showed a coefficient of 0.285 and a P-value of 0.000 ($OilDep = x_1 = 0.000 < 0.05$) which is less than 0.05 indicating there is a significant relationship. The results show that being over-dependent on oil can influence the agricultural companies to return on capital employed by the agricultural companies in South-West Nigeria. Consequently, the government need to diversify the revenue base (Adam, 2016) of the country through an agricultural revolution (Birner and Resnick, 2010) and the implementation of agricultural transformational policies that will aid agricultural businesses in South-West Nigeria. This agrees with the response of most of the participants of the interview conducted for this study. The outcome of the model also aligned with the view of authors such as Byelee et al. (2009); Akpan and Eyo (2018).

The findings on adequate data shows a coefficient of -0.013 with a P-value of 0.793 which is greater than 0.05 ($AdeData = x_2 = 0.794 > 0.05$). This signifies that the government and its agencies have not been able to provide adequate data for agricultural planning that will aid the return on capital employed by the agricultural companies in South-West Nigeria. This was the view of the participants interviewed for this study. To aid effective diversification and returns of the agricultural companies in South-West Nigeria the government should therefore establish a mechanism that will lead to the availability of reliable and sufficient data for planning (Omekwu, 2003) and agricultural research (Kajisel et al., 1997) South-West Nigeria.

Table 7.5.8.1 further revealed a coefficient of 0.130 for the effect of corruption with a P-value of 0.025 which is less than 0.05 ($Corp = x_3 = 0.025 < 0.05$). The output of the model indicates that corruption has an influence (Micah and Ruth, 2014) on the return of the agricultural company in South-West Nigeria. The output of the model is in consonance with the opinion of authors such as Evans and Alenoghena (2015); Ajayi et al. (2017); Micah and Ruth (2014). These authors believe that the high level of corruption in the country has significantly hindered the development of agriculture

in Nigeria including the South-West region of the country. Therefore, Government needs to establish a policy framework that will reduce the frequency and incidence of corruption in agricultural activities. The result also indicated that the rural-urban movement has a beta coefficient of 0.080 with a P value of .151 ($RurMov = x_4 = 0.151 > 0.05$) which is greater than 0.05. This suggests that the rural-urban movement has not significantly impacted the return of agricultural companies (Owombo et al., 2012) ie South-West Nigeria. Likewise, the interview participants believe that the rural-urban movement does not correlate with the return of the agricultural companies in the South-West. They believed the movement was as a result of a lack of agricultural activities (Zin, 2014) in the rural area and that has made most of the youth migrate to the city in search of greener pasture.

Furthermore, the model revealed a coefficient of 0.124 and P-value of .024 ($RitChan = x_5 = 0.024 < 0.05$) which is less than 0.05 for the availability of infrastructure. The result affirms that there is a relationship between the availability of social infrastructure and return of agricultural companies in South-West Nigeria. The lack of infrastructure was confirmed by the participants during the interview for this study. Government should therefore create social and educational infrastructure (Zin, 2014) that will influence the agricultural companies returns within the region. Likewise, the result shows the coefficient of 0.198 and p-value of .003 ($GDP = x_6 = 0.003 < 0.05$) that is less than 0.05 for the contribution of agriculture toward national GDP. The result of the model shows there is a significant relationship between the contribution of agricultural companies toward national GDP and return of the agricultural companies in South-West Nigeria. The result suggests that neglect of the agricultural (Afolabi, 2015) sector by the government will lead to a decline in the national GDP and turn a decrease in the return of agricultural companies in South-West Nigeria.

However, findings from the model shows that the coefficient of the increase in the level of poverty is 0.127 while the p-value is .028 ($Povt = x_7 = 0.003 < 0.05$) which is less than 0.05 level of significance. This implies that the neglect of agriculture and agricultural companies in the South-West by the government has led to an increase in the level of poverty and hunger within the region. The results of the interview further confirmed that the neglect of the agricultural sector by the government has resulted to increase in the level of poverty and hunger. The government should

therefore establish a framework and policy that will aid the transformation (Hazell et al., 2010) and commitment to the development of the agricultural companies in the region and hence eliminate poverty and hunger (Byelee et al., 2009). On the other hand, the coefficient of negative externalities is 0.114 with a p-value of 0.020 ($Exter = x_8 = 0.020 < 0.05$) which is less than 0.05. This suggests that the low level of cost or negative externalities (Williamson, 1970; Coarse, 1960) in Nigeria was as a result of the lack of extensive and intensive agricultural activities in South-West Nigeria. The outcome of the model is in line with the view of authors such Yusuf et al., (2013) and Novikova (2014). They believed that agricultural activities usually created both positive and negative externalities, but Nigeria negative externalities outweigh the positive externalities as a result of subsistence system of agriculture. Consequently, government and its agencies should establish a regulatory, economic, and legal framework that will minimise the effect of negative externalities (Pretty et al., 2001; Agboola, 2014) that can accompany the extensive and intensive agricultural activities in South-West Nigeria.

Nonetheless, the output of the model shows that the coefficient of development of a policy framework for externalities management is -0.037 with a P value of .573 ($PolFrw = x_9 = 0.573 > 0.05$) which is greater than 0.05. These results imply that there is a need for the development of a policy framework for the management of agricultural externalities in South-West Nigeria. The findings are in agreement with the view of the authors such as Ruffin and Anderson (1996); Barrett and Mutambatsere (2005); Yusuf et al., (2013). They believe developing nation like Nigeria needs an appropriate data collection strategy on agricultural externalities that will aid the management of agricultural externalities. Therefore, the government should develop policy strategies that are appropriate for the management and control of agricultural externalities in South-West Nigeria.

The result displayed in table 7.5.8.1 above, shows that p-values connected with predictors x_1 , x_3 , x_5 , x_6 , x_7 and x_8 are lower than the specified levels of significance, that is, ($P < 0.05$). Therefore, the null hypothesis is rejected for models x_1 , x_3 , x_5 , x_6 , x_7 and x_8 . While the related P-value for predictors x_4 and x_9 are greater than ($P > 0.05$) the stipulated level of significance (0.05), thus, hypothesis 1 is accepted for these models.

However, the table 7.8.2 below shows the summary of models:

Table 7.5.8.2

Model Summary ^b										
Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate	R Square Change	Change Statistics			Sig. F Change	Durbin-Watson
						F Change	df1	df2		
1	.897 ^a	.805	.795	.402	.805	85.678	9	187	.000	1.427
a. Predictors: (Constant), Need for framework, Cost and consequences of externalities, Lack of adequate data for economic planning, Rural-Urban migration, Level of poverty, High level of corruption as a major impediment to agricultural development, Low agricultural contribution towards GDP, Lack of infrastructural facilities, Neglect of agriculture due to over-dependent on oil b. Dependent Variable: Lack of diversification resulting in poor economy and ROCE										

The model summary in table 7.5.8.2 shows the combined effect of all the predictors such as the need for a framework, rural-urban migration, and the effect of the high level of corruption on the return of capital employed by agricultural companies in South-West Nigeria (Dependent variable). These values represent the cumulative effect of how the 9 independent variables can influence the transformation of agricultural practices which will aid the return on capital employed (ROCE) by the agricultural companies and in turn lead to agricultural companies development in South-West Nigeria.

However, the model summary shows that a change in the ROCE of the agricultural companies will result to 80.5% ($R^2 = .805$ and Adjusted $R^2 = .795$) of the change in the return of agricultural companies in South-West Nigeria. The result, therefore, indicates that there is a strong positive correlation of .897 ($R = .897$) between the predictors and the returns of the agricultural companies.

Consequently, the Durbin Watson coefficient is 1.427. Since this is a relatively small P value it cast doubt on the null hypothesis which signifies that the alternative should be accepted. Hence, there is a significant relationship between agricultural diversification and return on capital employed by agricultural companies in South-West Nigeria. Furthermore, the aggregate F-value is significant at $P = 0.000$ ($P = 0.000 < 0.05$). Therefore, the combined effect of all the predictors is significant for diversification returns. The coefficient in the table 7.9.1 can be substituted for the original equation five models of α , β_1 , β_2 , β_3 , β_4 , β_5 , β_6 , β_7 , β_8 and β_9 thus:

$$DiverRtn = \alpha + (.285)OilDep + (.013)AdeData + (.130)Corp + (.080) RurMov + (.124)Infra + (.198)GDP + (.127)Povt + (.114)Exter + (.037)PolFrw + \mu$$

The model implies that research question 5 and its objective have consequently been achieved. The model confirmed that effective diversification towards agriculture from being dependent on crude oil will aid the return on capital employed by agricultural companies and lead to the development of agricultural companies in South-West Nigeria.

Analysis of hypothesis using Gretl

To further aid the criticality of the output of this research gretl was used in addition to the SPSS to analyse the five (5) hypothesis. The result of the analysis are further confirm the relationship between the independent variables and the dependent variable as stated below.

7.5.9 Test of Hypothesis 1

Hypothesis 1 was tested in line with the research objective to find out the relationship between agricultural companies' development and national economic policy.

The regression coefficient was given as:

Equation one (1)

$$NatPol = \alpha + \beta_1 Dev + \beta_2 AgSth + \beta_3 GovInfl + \beta_4 RegFrm + \beta_5 MTech + \beta_6 HiVal + \beta_7 Roc + \beta_8 AgRev + \beta_9 Clim + \mu$$

Table 7.5.9: Hypothesis 1

Variable	Coefficient	Std. Error	Odd ratio	p-value
Development	1.51409***	0.382977	4.545305	<0.0001
Stakeholders	0.294825*	0.170586	1.342891	0.0839
Influence	1.31772***	0.177390	3.73489	<0.0001
Framework	0.451888**	0.196369	1.571276	0.0214
Technology	-0.178202	0.243438	0.8367736	0.4642
Value	-0.470905**	0.212039	0.6244369	0.0264
Returns	0.290368	0.202661	1.33692	0.1519
Revolution	-0.388228***	0.150313	0.6782577	0.0098
Climate	0.270459	0.199934	1.310566	0.1761
Pseudo R-squared	0.420069			
Log likelihood	-177.1560			
LR statistic	287.681			
Number of cases 'correctly predicted' (131)	65.2%			
Prob(LR statistic)	0.0000			
Obs	201			
p-value	***=1%	**=5%	*=10%	
cut1	4.87771	0.706181	6.907	<0.0001
cut2	8.61656	0.907041	9.500	<0.0001
cut3	10.5376	1.00737	10.46	<0.0001
cut4	14.6924	1.23143	11.93	<0.0001

Where:

Dependent variable

NatPol = National economic policy

α = constant

Independent variable (x)

Dev = Development

AgSth = Agricultura of stakeholders

GovInfl = Government influence

RegFrm = Regulatory framework

MTech = Modern technology

HiVal = high value

Roc = High/low eturn on capital employed

AgRev = Agricultural revolution

Clim = Climate change

μ = error level incorporating omitted variables

The theme for this section is “has the national economic policy been used to **aid the development** of agricultural companies in South-West Nigeria”. The dependent variable is proxy as national policy and regressed on the listed independent variables in the table above.

A. The model, Likelihood ratio test (chi-square)⁴ is 287.681 with 9 d.f. statistically it is highly significant, and it means that the independent variables such as developemnt, government influence and agricultural revolution have effect on national economic policy (as a catalyst to agricultural company development)

B. The McFadden R² (aka pseudo R²) is

$$\text{Pseudo } R^2 = 0.420069$$

C. The table 7.5.9 presents the statistical significance of individual regression coefficients (β s) making use of chi-square; the coefficients of variables such as development, agricultural stakeholders, and government influence are positive. This signifies that the quest for agricultural development will lead to the establishment of various economic policies that will aid agricultural company development in South-West Nigeria. This aligns with the view of

authors such as Adeyemi et al. (2023); Akpan and Eyo (2018), who believe that the development of a tailor-made policy rather than a broad-brush approach will lead to agricultural development in Nigeria. The table revealed that the development was a statistically significant predictor for the event where $p < 0.05$. The coefficient 1.51409 with a p-value of 0.0001 ($Dev < 0.05$) represents the log odds for an increase in the quest for agricultural development will result in increases in the establishment of policy. Likewise, Table 7.5.9 shows a coefficient of 1.31772 for government influence with p-values of 0.0001 ($AgSth < 0.05$). The result indicates that government intervention will lead to the creation of agricultural policies that can influence the output and productivity of agricultural companies in South-West Nigeria. The result of the model invalidates the view of Tejvan (2016); Morrison and Schneider (1987), who think that government intervention in the agricultural sector in a developing nation like Nigeria will act as a barrier to agricultural business development.

The result also suggests that a regulatory framework with a coefficient of 0.451888 and a p-value of 0.0214 ($RegFrm < 0.05$). This signifies an appropriate regulatory framework will lead to an effective implementation of agricultural policy in South-West Nigeria. This was in line with the view of Hazell et al. (2010) and Diao et al. (2007), who believe there is a need for the development of an appropriate regulatory framework that will aid the implementation of agricultural policy that will, in turn, aid agricultural companies' development. The result of the model on agricultural stakeholder participation shows a coefficient of 0.294825 with a p-value of 0.0839 ($AgSth < 0.05$). This shows that the inclusion of the stakeholders in the formulation of agricultural policies will have a significant effect on the successful implementation of the agricultural policy. The result is in line with authors such as Daneji (2011) and Adeola and Adetunbi (2015), who think the policymakers and all the stakeholders in the agricultural sector should collectively design the agricultural policies as it will lead to successful implementation and development of the agricultural companies in all regions in Nigeria.

However, the following variables have negative coefficients: Technology (-0.178202), Value (-0.470905) and Revolution (-0.388228). The negative coefficient shows that the more modern technologies are adopted, the fewer policies are needed. It is evident from the result that there is a negative relationship between agricultural policies and the adoption of modern technologies in agricultural processes in South-West Nigeria. This was in line with the findings of Owombo et al. (2012), who think the development of the right and appropriate agricultural policy will lead to easy access and adoption of modern technology in agricultural processes in South-West Nigeria. In the same vein, the coefficient of the agricultural revolution is (-0.388228) with a p-value of 0.0098 ($AgRev < 0.05$). This suggests that the policymaker had failed to launch an agricultural revolution that should have eradicated hunger, poverty, and economic stagnation.

The result of the model shows a coefficient of -0.470905 and a p-value of 0.0264 ($HiVal < 0.05$). This signifies that the management of agricultural companies does not value agricultural policies because the management feels they did not enhance the adoption of the mechanised system of agriculture and hence can not aid agricultural companies' growth and development. This result agreed with the view of Ibietan (2011) that inconsistencies in the establishment and implementation of policies are the bane of agricultural development in Nigeria. Therefore, the government needs to adopt an implementation strategy that will aid the continuity and application of agricultural policies by the management of agricultural companies in Nigeria.

However, the following variables have a positive slope coefficient: Returns with a coefficient of 0.290368 (p-value - 0.1519) and climate with a coefficient of 0.270459 (p-value - 0.1761). This signifies the return on capital employed and climate change does not have a significant impact on the development of national policy. Therefore, an increase in return and frequency of climate change will not influence national policy.

*D. Based on the outcome of the model, the null hypothesis (H_0) is rejected, while the related p-value for predictors *Dev*, *AgSth*, *GovInfl*, *RegFrm*, *MTech*, *HiVal*,*

and *AgRev*, are greater than ($p > 0.05$) the stipulated level of significance, thus, hypothesis 1 is accepted for these models.

The equation one models of α , β_1 , β_2 , β_3 , β_4 , β_5 , β_6 , β_7 , β_8 and β_9 thus:

$$\mathbf{NatPol} = \alpha + (1.51409)Dev + (0.294825)AgSth + (1.31772)GovInfl + (0.451888)RegFrm + (-0.178202)MTech + (-0.470905)HiVal + (0.290368)Roc + (-0.388228)AgRev + (0.270459)Clim + \mu.$$

- E. The number of cases correctly predicted is 131 which means that degree of outcomes was predicted correctly 65.2.3%, See the table above for further information, which also shows the predicted probability values of each of the four possible outcomes
- F. The Proportional odds were similar to the model output of Edward and Bryan (2018), which suggests that the magnitude of the odd ratios of a dependent variable depends on the independent variable changes (the conditioning set). Therefore, the odd ratio of 4.545305 for development indicates that the odds for an increase of 4.55 times will result in an increase in the number of policies that will aid agricultural companies' development. This has the effect of reducing the frequency of agricultural companies' failure by 1 unit. These proportional odds are the same as other variables in the model that are statistically significant, such as Influence (3.73489), Framework (1.571276), Value (0.6244369), Revolution (0.6782577) and Stakeholders (1.342891). These proportional odds suggest that the odds for an increase by the values in brackets (based on a number of occurrences) when the values of each of the independent variables are increased by 1 unit will influence the dependent variable.

7.6.0 Test of Research Hypothesis 2

H_0 : There is no significant relationship between the agricultural models and agricultural companies development in South-West Nigeria.

H_1 : There is significant relationship between the agricultural models and agricultural companies development in South-West Nigeria.

Due to the high correlation among the variables two models were set up. The model 2a and 2b. The regression coefficient for the model 2a was given as:

Equation two (2a)

$$AgMod = \alpha + \beta_1 SkilApp + \beta_2 Dev + \beta_3 ModTech + \beta_4 FinPerf + \beta_5 BusDev + \mu$$

Table 7.6.0.1: Hypothesis 2a

Variable	Coefficient	Std. Error	Odd ratio	p-value
Development	0.656912**	0.261958	1.242938	0.0122
Technology	0.149144	0.194558	1.592330	0.4433
Performance	-0.0149127	0.207045	0.911971	0.9426
Business	-0.426133*	0.236583	1.097258	0.0717
Skill	0.746035**	0.315076	1.511849	0.0179
Pseudo R-squared	0.223602			
Log likelihood	-213.8685			
LR statistic	136.068			
Number of cases 'correctly predicted' 116)	57.7%			
Prob(LR statistic)	0.0000			
Obs	201			
p-value	***=1%	**=5%	*=10%	
cut1	2.34205	0.720534	3.250	0.0012
cut2	3.54732	0.889096	3.990	<0.0001
cut3	4.54409	1.06761	4.256	<0.0001
cut4	5.93626	1.23495	4.807	<0.0001
cut5	9.19153	1.41949	6.475	<0.0001

Where:

Dependent variable

AgMod = Agricultural models

α = constant

Independent variable (x)

SkilApp = Skill Application

Dev = Development

ModTech = Modern technology

FinPerf = Financial performance

BusDev = Business development

μ = error level incorporating omitted variables

$\beta_1, \beta_2, \beta_3, \beta_4, \beta_5$ = coefficients

The theme for this section is “the effects of **agricultural models** on agricultural policies implementation in South-West Nigeria”. The dependent variable is proxy as agricultural model and regressed on the listed independent variables in the table above.

A. The model, Likelihood ratio test (chi-square)⁵ is 136.068 with 9 d.f. statistically it is highly significant, and it means that the independent variables such as skill application, development, modern technology, financial performance and business development have influence on agricultural model (as a catalyst to agricultural company development)

B. The McFadden R² (aka pseudo R²) is

$$\text{Pseudo } R^2 = 0.241338$$

C. The table 7.6.0.1 presents the statistical significance of individual regression coefficients (β s) making use of chi-square; the coefficients of variables such as development, technology, performance, business and skill are positive. This shows that the agricultural model aided by the regressors will lead to the effective implementation of agricultural policies in South-West Nigeria. The effective implementation of agricultural policies will, in turn, aid agricultural company development in South-West Nigeria. The output of the model shows a coefficient of 0.656912 for development and economic growth

with a p-value of 0.0122 (*Dev* <0.05). This result implies that the agricultural model established by the government is significantly influenced by the development of agricultural companies and economic growth. It, therefore, means that the quest for development and growth of the agricultural company in Nigeria will influence the establishment of agricultural models, which will, in turn, aid effective implementation of agricultural policy in South-West Nigeria. This was in consonance with the view of most of the authors of the literature reviewed such as Hazell et al. (2010); Afolabi (2015) and Micah and Ruth (2014). They think that the quest for agricultural company development will lead to the adoption of an established agricultural model in the implementation of agricultural policy. The coefficient of business development is -0.426133 with a p-value of 0.0717 (*BusDev* <0.05). This suggests that there is a relationship between business development and the agricultural model. This means that if the policymaker established a less appropriate agricultural business model, there would be an increase in the return of capital employed by the agricultural companies. Consequently, it will lead to the development of agricultural companies in South-West Nigeria. The result of the model is in consonance with the findings of the interview, in which the participants believed every agricultural company has its own model. Most of the participants believe the lack of a unified agricultural model is the missing link between agricultural business development and the adequate return on capital employed by agricultural companies. Furthermore, the model revealed a coefficient of 0.746035 for skill application with p-values of 0.0179 (*SkilApp* <0.05). The result shows there is a significant relationship between skill application and the use of agricultural models. This means the value of agricultural companies will increase as a result of the use of the agricultural model by the employees of agricultural companies in the South-West. The output of the model is in consonance with the view of Akinkunmi (2017), who thinks there is a need for the provision of an economic growth model that will aid the economic development of a country. There is, therefore, a need for the development of an agricultural model that will aid the development of agricultural companies in South-West Nigeria.

However, modern technology, with a positive coefficient of 0.149144 and p-value of 0.4433, has an insignificant relationship with the agricultural model. Likewise, the financial performance with a negative coefficient of -0.0149127 with a p-value of 0.9426 has a weak relationship with the agricultural model. This shows that these variables have no significant influence on the application of agricultural models in agricultural practices by agricultural companies in South-West Nigeria. Therefore, changes in these variables will not impact the development of a model for policy framework.

D. *Based on the outcome of the model, the null hypothesis (H0) is rejected, while the related p-value for predictors development, business and skill application, are greater than ($p > 0.05$) the stipulated level of significance, thus, hypothesis 1 is accepted for these models.*

The equation two (2a) models of α , β_1 , β_2 , β_3 , β_4 , and β_5 , thus:

$$AgMod = \alpha + (0.746035)SkilApp + (0.656912)Dev + (0.149144)ModTech + (-0.014913)FinPerf + (0.426133)BusDev + \mu$$

E. The number of cases correctly predicted is 136.068, which means that the degree of outcomes was predicted correctly at 57.7%. See the table above for further information, which also shows the predicted probability values of each of the four possible outcomes.

F. Proportional odds were consonance with the model's output of Edward and Bryan (2018), which implies that the rate of change of the odd ratios of a dependent variable depends on the independent variable changes. Therefore, the odd ratio of 1.242938 for development indicates that the odds for an increase of 1.24 times will lead to an increase in the number of agricultural models that will aid the implementation of agricultural policy. This has the effect of reducing the frequency of policy failure by 1 unit. These proportional odds are similar to other statistically significant independent variables in the model output, such as Skill (1.511849) and Business (1.097258). These proportional odds mean that the odds for an increase by the values in brackets (multiplied by a number of occurrences) when the values of each of these

variables change by 1 unit will influence the development of agricultural models.

The regression coefficient for model 2b was given as:

Equation two (2b)

$$AgMod = \alpha + \beta_1 ExgInf + \beta_2 EcoGrot + \beta_3 SkilApp + \beta_4 Roc + \mu$$

Table 7.6.0.2: Hypothesis 2b

Variable	Coefficient	Std. Error	Odd ratio	p-value
Information	1.19517***	0.325352	3.394199	0.0002
Growth	0.192738	0.297495	1.137453	0.5171
Skill	0.645804**	0.289241	1.511849	0.0256
ROCE	-0.00682506	0.175932	0.7917683	0.9691
Pseudo R-squared	0.261482			
Log likelihood	-204.1901			
LR statistic	155.425			
Number of cases 'correctly predicted' (128)	63.7%			
Prob(LR statistic)	0.0000			
Obs	201			
p-value	***=1%	**=5%	*=10%	
cut1	2.28949	0.713554	3.209	0.0013
cut2	3.49559	0.893896	3.911	<0.0001
cut3	4.53396	1.02193	4.437	<0.0001
cut4	6.03877	1.20504	5.011	<0.0001
cut5	9.51854	1.42241	6.692	<0.0001

Where:

Dependent variable

AgMod = Agricultural models

α = constant

Independent variable

ExgInf = Exchange of information

EcoGrot = Economic growth

SkilApp = Skill Application

Roc = Return on capital employed

μ = error level incorporating omitted variables

$\beta_1, \beta_2, \beta_3,$ and β_4 = coefficients

The theme for this section is “the effects of **agricultural models** on agricultural policies implementation in South-West Nigeria”. The dependent variable is proxy as agricultural model and regressed on the listed independent variables in the table above.

G. The model, Likelihood ratio test (chi-square)⁶ is 155.425 with 9 d.f. statistically it is highly significant, and it means that the independent variables such as exchange of information, economic growth, skill application, and return on capital employed have influence on agricultural model (as a catalyst to agricultural company development)

H. The McFadden R^2 (aka pseudo R^2) is

$$\text{Pseudo } R^2 = 0.275671$$

I. The table 7.6.0.2 presents the statistical significance of individual regression coefficients (β s) making use of chi-square; the coefficients of variables such as development, technology, performance, business, and business and skill are positive. This shows that the agricultural model aided by the regressors will lead to effective implementation of agricultural policies in South-West Nigeria. The effective implementation of agricultural policies will in turn aid agricultural company development in South-West Nigeria.

The result of the model on the exchange of information between government agencies and agricultural companies shows a coefficient of 1.19517 with a p-value of 0.0002 (*ExgInf* <0.05). This means there is a significant relationship between the effective exchange of information amongst agricultural stakeholders and agricultural models. It implies that the exchange of information between agricultural stakeholders will aid the establishment and application of agricultural models in agricultural processes. This is in consonance with the view of authors such as Omekwu (2003), who thinks the exchange of agricultural information will integrate all agricultural agencies and agricultural companies. The integration will, in turn, aid the development of agricultural companies. The output of the model further revealed a coefficient of 0.645804 for skill application with a p-value of 0.0256 (*SkilApp* <0.05). It shows that the application of skill will aid the establishment and use of agricultural models in the agricultural processes. This means that the more agricultural companies' employees are willing to apply their skills in the agricultural processes, the more agricultural models are needed as a guide. This aligns with the view of Kajisel et al. (1997), who opined that the government should establish a framework that will aid the application of skills in the development of agricultural companies.

However, economic growth with a positive coefficient of 0.192738 and p-value of 0.5171 has an insignificant relationship with the agricultural model. Likewise, the return on capital employed with a negative coefficient of -0.00682506 with a p-value of 0.9691 has no influence on the application of the agricultural model in agricultural processes. This suggest that these variables have no significant impact on the use of agricultural model by agricultural comapnies in South-West Nigeria. Therefore, the growth or decline in these variables will not impact the development and application of the agricultural model.

J. Based on the outcome of the model, the nul hypothesis (H_0) is rejected, while the related p-value for predictors development, business and skill application, are greater than ($p > 0.05$) the stipulated level of significance, thus, hypothesis 1 is accepted for these models.

The equation two (2b) models of α , β_1 , β_2 , β_3 , β_4 , and β_5 , thus:

$$AgMod = \alpha + (1.19517)ExgInf + (0.192738)EcoGrot + (0.645804)SkilApp + (-0.00682506)Roc + \mu$$

- K. The number of cases correctly predicted is 136.068 which means that degree of outcomes was predicted correctly 57.7%. See the table above for further information, which also shows the predicted probability values of each of the four possible outcomes
- L. Furthermore, the odd ratio of 3.394199 for development signifies that the odds for an increase of 3.4 times will result in an increase in the number of agricultural models that policymakers will establish as a guide for the effective implementation of the agricultural policy. This has the effect of increasing the success rate of agricultural companies' development by 1 unit. These proportional odds are the same for other independent variables in the model that are statistically significant, such as skill with (1.511849). The proportional odds, therefore, suggest that the odds for an increase in these values (based on a number of occurrences) will lead to a proportional change dependent variable (Agricultural model) and hence influence the implementation of agricultural policy.

7.6.1 Test of Hypothesis 3

Hypothesis 1 was tested in line with the research objective to find out the relationship between agricultural companies' development and national economic policy.

The regression coefficient was given as:

Equation three (3)

$$RegFrm = \alpha + \beta_1Infl + \beta_2EcoSoc + \beta_3StrAdh + \beta_4DevProg + \beta_5PrzStab + \beta_6EPS + \beta_7ExcTax + \beta_8BusTrans + \beta_9Compt + \mu$$

Table 7.6.1: Hypothesis 3

Variable	Coefficient	Std. Error	Odd ratio	<i>p</i> -value
<i>Infl</i>	0.566019***	0.183619	1.761243	0.0021
<i>EcoSoc</i>	0.706728**	0.276095	2.027340	0.0105
<i>StrAdh</i>	0.305887	0.199262	1.357827	0.1248
<i>DevProg</i>	-0.238205	0.209882	0.788041	0.2564
<i>PrzStab</i>	0.375286	0.297587	1.455411	0.2073
<i>EPS</i>	0.758804**	0.301739	2.135721	0.0119
<i>ExcTax</i>	0.590260**	0.237349	1.804453	0.0129
<i>BusTrans</i>	0.642416*	0.361711	1.901070	0.0757
<i>Compt</i>	0.348544	0.356788	1.417007	0.3286
Pseudo R-squared	0.433606			
Log likelihood	-157.7770			
LR statistic	273.354			
Number of cases 'correctly predicted' (138)	68.7%			
Prob(LR statistic)	0.0000			
Obs	201			
<i>p</i> -value	***=1%	**=5%	*=10%	
cut1	4.97908	0.912031	5.459	<0.0001
cut2	7.88328	1.20995	6.515	<0.0001
cut3	10.2127	1.40758	7.255	<0.0001
cut4	14.6070	1.86558	7.830	<0.0001
cut5	18.7154	2.13337	8.773	<0.0001

Where:

Dependent variable

RegFrm = Regulatory framework

α = constant

Independent variable (x)

Infl = Influence of agricultural programme

EcoSoc = Economic and social issues

StrAdh = Strict adherence

DevProg = Developmental programmes

PrzStab = Price stabilization

EPS = High/low earnings per share

ExcTax = Excessive tax

BusTrans = Business transformation

Compt = Competition

μ = error level incorporating omitted variables

$\beta_1, \beta_2, \beta_3, \beta_4, \beta_5, \beta_6, \beta_7, \beta_8$ and β_9 , = coefficients

The theme for this section is “the impacts of the **regulatory framework** on agricultural policy implementation in Nigeria”. The dependent variable is proxy as Regulatory framework and regressed on the listed independent variables in the table above.

A. The model, Likelihood ratio test (chi-square)⁷ is 273.354 with 9 d.f. statistically it is highly significant, and it means that the independent variables

such as influence, economic & social issues, Strict adherence, developmental programmes, price stabilization, High/low earnings per share, excessive tax, business transformation and competition have effect on national economic policy (as a catalyst to agricultural company development)

B. The McFadden R^2 (aka pseudo R^2) is

$$\text{Pseudo } R^2 = 0.464171$$

C. The table above presents the statistical significance of individual regression coefficients (β s) making use of chi-square; the coefficients of variables such as influence, economic & social issues, earnings per share, excessive tax, and business transformation are positive. This shows that the development of a right and an appropriate regulatory framework aid by the regressors will lead to effective implementation of agricultural policies in Nigeria. The effective implementation of agricultural policies will in turn aid agricultural company development in South-West Nigeria.

The output of the model shows a coefficient of 0.566019 for influence for participation in agricultural programmes with a p-value of 0.0021 ($Infl > 0.05$). This result implies that the regulatory framework on agricultural policy implementation established by the government is significantly influenced by agricultural companies participating in agricultural programmes. It, therefore, means that the non-participation of agricultural companies in the agricultural programme may serve as an impediment to agricultural policy implementation in South-West Nigeria. This was in consonance with the view of most of the interview participants and authors of the literature reviewed, such as Hazell et al. (2010), Afolabi (2015), and Micah and Ruth (2014). The output of the model on the economic, social and environmental issues shows a coefficient of 0.706728 with a p-value ($EcoSoc > 0.05$). This signifies there is a relationship between the agricultural regulatory framework and economic, social and environmental issues. This implies that the economic, social, and environmental issues in the business community should be considered as factors in the establishment and implementation of an appropriate regulatory framework in South-West Nigeria. This was the view of the interview participants and is also in consonance with the view of authors such as Byelee

et al. (2009) and Cervantes Godoy and Dewbre (2010). These authors believe that the establishment of an appropriate regulatory framework will aid agricultural company development and food security and eliminate poverty in the rural areas in South-West Nigeria.

Furthermore, the result shows a coefficient of 0.758804 and a p-value of 0.0119 with respect to EPS ($EPS > 0.05$). The model signifies that there is a relationship between the EPS of agricultural companies and the regulatory framework. It, therefore, means that the more EPS agricultural companies earn as a result of policy implementation, the more motivated they are to implement the agricultural regulatory framework and policy in South-West Nigeria. Most participants interviewed believe the agricultural companies are not earning adequate returns due to the weakness or nonexistence of the agricultural regulatory framework. The table above also shows the coefficient of the excessive tax rate on agricultural companies as 0.590260 and a p-value of .0129 ($ExcTax > 0.05$). This implies that the government's excessive tax rate imposed on agricultural companies has been a significant barrier discouraging investment in agricultural companies and a major impediment in the implementation of agricultural policy. This aligns with the view of Zin (2014), who thinks the government should establish a framework that will lead to granting agricultural companies adequate tax relief that will attract investors to agricultural companies in developing nations. The result was in line with the view of Pretty et al. (2001), who think taxes and relief can be used as a mechanism to promote development in agricultural businesses and implementation of policy. In the same vein, the coefficient of business transformation is 0.642416 with a p-value of 0.0757 ($BusTrans > 0.05$). This suggests that there is a relationship between regulatory framework and business transformation. The quest for business transformation with the aim of eliminating hostile competition among agricultural companies will aid the adoption and implementation of agricultural regulatory framework and policy. This reflects the view of Dardak (2015), who is of the opinion that the government should establish a regulatory framework that will aid agricultural business transformation and eliminate fraudulent practices among agricultural stakeholders.

However, the following variables have a positive slope coefficient: Strict adherence with a coefficient of 0.305887 (p-value - 0.1248), Price stabilization with a coefficient of 0.375286 (p-value - 0.2073) and competition with a coefficient of 0.348544 (p-value - 0.3286). On the other hand, the development programme shows a negative coefficient of -0.238205 and a p-value of 0.2564. This shows that these variables have no significant impact on the adoption and effective implementation of the agricultural policy. Therefore, changes in these variables will not influence the implementation of the agricultural regulatory framework and policy.

*D. Based on the outcome of the model, the nul hypothesis (H₀) is rejected, while the related p-value for predictors *Infl, EcoSoc, EPS, ExcTax and BusTrans*, are greater than (p > 0.05) the stipulated level of significance, thus, hypothesis 1 is accepted for these models.*

The equation models of α , β_1 , β_2 , β_3 , β_4 , β_5 , β_6 , β_7 , β_8 and β_9 thus:

$$\text{RegFrm} = \alpha + (0.566019)\text{Infl} + (0.706728)\text{EcoSoc} + (0.305887)\text{StrAdh} + (-0.238205)\text{DevProg} + (0.375286)\text{PrzStab} + (0.758804)\text{EPS} + (0.590260)\text{ExcTax} + (0.642416)\text{BusTrans} + (0.348544)\text{Compt} + \mu$$

E. The number of cases correctly predicted is 138 which means that degree of outcomes was predicted correctly 68.7%, See the table above for further information, which also shows the predicted probability values of each of the four possible outcomes

F. Proportional odds were similar to the model output of Edward and Bryan (2018), which suggests that the rate of change of a dependent variable depends on the independent variable changes (based on the set conditions). Therefore, the odd ratio of 1.761243 for influence indicates that the odds of an increase of 1.8 times will result in an increase in the frequency of impact of regulatory framework on agricultural policy implementation by agricultural companies. This has the effect of reducing the frequency of

abandonment of the agricultural policy by 1 unit. The proportional odds of other independent variables with significant relationships have similar effects. The independent with similar effects include EcoSoc (2.027340), EPS (2.135721), ExcTax (1.804453), and BusTrans (1.901070). These proportional odds suggest that the odds for an increase by these values will lead to an increase by 1 unit in the effect of the regulatory framework on the agricultural policy implementation.

7.6.2 Test of Research Hypothesis 4

H₀: There is no significant relationship between policy transmission mechanism and agricultural companies' development in South-West Nigeria.

H₁: There is a significant relationship between policy transmission mechanism and agricultural companies development in South-West Nigeria.

The regression coefficient was given as:

Equation four (4)

$$TransMech = \alpha + \beta_1 AidCom + \beta_2 MasMed + \beta_3 VitInf + \beta_4 SocImp + \beta_5 RitChan + \beta_6 EduEmp + \beta_7 Knwg + \beta_8 DatAcc + \beta_9 ImpPerf + \mu$$

Table 7.6.2: Hypothesis 4

Variable	Coefficient	Std. Error	Odd ratio	<i>p-value</i>
Communication	2.20739***	0.348932	9.091969	<0.0001
MassMedia	-0.707854**	0.288780	0.492701	0.0142
VitalInformati~	0.945771***	0.310493	2.574798	0.0023
SocialMedia	-0.0987981	0.301847	0.905926	0.7434
RightChannel	-0.101468	0.197236	0.903511	0.6069
Education	-0.130347	0.230954	0.877791	0.5725
MechanisedSyst~	0.535163***	0.165207	1.707727	0.0012
DataAccessibil~	-0.630839***	0.239002	0.532145	0.0083
ImprovedPerfor~	1.66127***	0.401999	5.266020	<0.0001
Pseudo R-squared	0.469645			
Log likelihood	-156.0364			
LR statistic	310.289			
Number of cases 'correctly predicted' (133)	66.2%			
Prob(LR statistic)	0.0000			
Obs	201			
p-value	***=1%	**=5%	*=10%	
cut1	7.04564	1.10118	6.398	<0.0001
cut2	9.41937	1.21847	7.730	<0.0001
cut3	13.2101	1.45509	9.079	<0.0001
cut4	17.7461	1.72051	10.31	<0.0001

Where:

Dependent variable

TransMech = Transmission mechanism

α = constant

Independent variable (x)

AidCom = Aided communication

MasMed = Information through mass media

VitInf = Vital information

SocImp = Social media impact

RitChan = Right channel

EduEmp = Educated employees

MechSys = Mechanise System

DatAcc = Data accessibility

ImpPerf = Improved performance

μ = error level incorporating omitted variables

$\beta_1, \beta_2, \beta_3, \beta_4, \beta_5, \beta_6, \beta_7, \beta_8,$ and β_9 , = coefficients

The theme for this section is “How **policy transmission mechanisms** can be used to influence agricultural policy implementation in South-West Nigeria”. The dependent variable is proxy as Policy transmission mechanism and regressed on the listed independent variables in the table above.

A. The model, Likelihood ratio test (chi-square)⁸ is 310.289 with 5 d.f. statistically it is highly significant, and it means that the independent variables such as aided communication, information through mass media, vital

information, social media impact, use of right channel, educating employees, availability of knowledge, data accesibility and performance improvement have effect on policy transmission mechanism (as a catalyst to agricultural company development)

B. The McFadden R^2 (aka pseudo R^2) is

$$\text{Pseudo } R^2 = 0.49856$$

C. The table above presents the statistical significance of individual regression coefficients (β s) making use of chi-square; the coefficients of variables such as Communication, VitalInformation, MechanisedSyst, DataAccessibil and ImprovedPerfor are positive while Massmedia showed a negative coefficient. This signifies that the regressors has influence on the agricultural policy transmission mechnism which is capable of aiding an effective development and implementation of agricultural policy in the South-West Nigeria.

The output of the model in the table above revealed a coefficient of 2.20739 and a p-value of 0.001 for aided communication (*AidCom* <0.05). The results show that an aided communication system has a significant relationship with agricultural policy transmission mechanism and is capable of influencing an effective agricultural policy transmission mechanism. An effective agricultural policy transmission mechanism will aid communication between government agencies and the stakeholders in the agricultural sector in South-West Nigeria. Therefore, the government need to establish an appropriate transmission mechanism that will aid communication and implementation of agricultural policies between the agricultural companies and government agencies regulating agricultural businesses in South-West Nigeria. This is in consonance with the responses of most of the participants in the interview conducted for this study. This is also in line with the view of authors such as Omekwu, (2003); Hassan et al. (2010); Adeola and Adetunbi (2015), who believe the government agencies should improve their collaborative efforts through the transmission of agricultural information using the right channel. The output on transmitting policy implementation through mass media show a coefficient of -0.707854 with a p-value of 0.0142 (*MasMed* >0.05). This

signifies there is an inverse relationship between the use of mass media and effective agricultural policy transmission mechanisms. It shows that the use of mass media as an agricultural policy transmission mechanism will negatively impact the effective implementation of agricultural policy. Therefore, the government should avoid the use of mass media as a means of transmitting agricultural policy implementation to agricultural stakeholders in South-West Nigeria. This was contrary to the view of Omekwu (2003), who thought that policymakers could effectively utilise mass media to transmit policy to critical stakeholders like agricultural companies in South-West Nigeria.

The table also revealed a coefficient of 0.945771 with a p-value of 0.0023 for the dissemination of vital information ($VitInf < 0.05$). The output of the model shows that effective dissemination of vital information has a relationship with the agricultural policy transmission mechanism. An effective dissemination of vital information will aid the policy transmission mechanism, which will, in turn, influence the implementation of agricultural policy. The effective implementation of agricultural policy will, therefore, aid agricultural companies' development in South-West Nigeria. The output of the model on the table above shows a coefficient of 0.535163 in respect of knowledge for transformation to Mechanised System, while its p-value is 0.0012 ($MechSys < 0.05$). This implies that the availability of knowledge on how to transform the agricultural system from a traditional system to a mechanised system will aid the development of agricultural transmission mechanisms and agricultural companies development in South-West Nigeria. This was in agreement with the view of Owombo et al. (2012), who think the agricultural stakeholders have remained uninformed due to a lack of knowledge on how to transform the traditional agricultural system to a mechanised agricultural system that will lead to high productivity. The transformation from the traditional system to the mechanised system of agriculture will influence the development of agricultural companies in South-West Nigeria. The government, therefore, need to establish the right policy that will support capacity building in the area of educating the agricultural companies on the adoption of a mechanising system of agriculture.

From the model, the coefficient of data accessibility is -0.630839 with a p-value of 0.0083 ($DatAcc < 0.05$). This suggests that there is a negative relationship between the lack of accessible data and agricultural policy transmission mechanisms. It means the availability of a reliable data will eliminate the challenge of literacy among the farmers in the South-West Nigeria through the use of appropriate agricultural policy transmission mechanism. This is in consonance with the view of (Yusuf et al. (2013) who believe that overcoming the barrier of accessibility and availability of data using mass media will aid the development of agricultural companies in Nigeria. The findings of the interview revealed that data accessibility is a major issue for agricultural companies in the southwest. It was further stated that the non-availability of data has prevented the agricultural company from effective and efficient planning. Nonetheless, the model revealed the coefficient of improved performance as a catalyst to the agricultural policy transmission mechanism to be 1.66127 with a p-value of 0.0001 ($ImpPerf < 0.05$). These results imply that improved agricultural companies' performances and income can influence the development of an appropriate agricultural policy transmission mechanism in South-West Nigeria. This was in line with the view of authors such as Bauer and Yamey (1965); Yusuf et al. (2013), Who believe the development of the right transmission strategies will stabilise the price of agricultural products and aid the development of the agricultural companies.

The result also indicated that the social media impact has a beta coefficient of -0.047 with a P value of $.545$ ($SocImp = x4 = 0.545 > 0.05$), which is greater than 0.05 . This suggests that the social media has not impacted the awareness of agricultural policy and, as a result, has not influenced the development of agricultural companies (Owombo et al., 2012) in South-West Nigeria. Likewise, the interview participants believe government agencies have not taken advantage of using social media to transmit information about agricultural policy adoption and implementation (Diao et al., 2007).

On the other hand, the following variables have a negative slope coefficient: Social media with a coefficient of -0.0987981 (p-value - 0.7434), Right Channel with a coefficient of -0.101468 (p-value - 0.6069) and Education with a coefficient of -0.130347 (p-value - 0.5725). This signifies that social media, using the right channel and educating employees does not have a significant influence on agricultural policy transmission mechanisms.

Therefore, an increase or decrease in the use of this variables by the agricultural companies in the South-West will not impact the agricultural policy transmission mechanism.

D. Based on the outcome of the model, the nul hypothesis (H_0) is rejected, while the related p-value for predictors AidCom, MasMed , VitInf , MechSys, DatAcc, DatAcc , and ImpPerf, are greater than ($p > 0.05$) the stipulated level of significance, thus, hypothesis 1 is accepted for these models.

The equation four models of α , β_1 , β_2 , β_3 , β_4 , β_5 , β_6 β_7 , β_8 and β_9 thus:

$$\begin{aligned} TransMech = & \alpha + (2.20739)AidCom + (-0.707854)MasMed + (0.945771)VitInf \\ & + (-0.0987981)SocImp + (-0.101468)RitChan + (-0.130347)EduEmp + \\ & (0.535163)MechSys + (-0.630839)DatAcc + (1.66127)ImpPerf + \mu. \end{aligned}$$

E. The number of cases correctly predicted is 131 which means that degree of outcomes was predicted correctly 65.2.3%, See the table above for further information, which also shows the predicted probability values of each of the four possible outcomes.

F. Based on the research conducted by Edward and Bryan (2018), proportional odds suggest that the magnitude of the odd ratios of a dependent variable depends on the independent variable changes. However, the odd ratio of 9.091969 for communication signifies that the odds for an increase of 9.1 times will lead to an increase in the agricultural transmission mechanism that will aid agricultural policy implementation. The 9.1 have the effect of reducing the frequency of agricultural policy failure by 1 unit. These proportional odds are the same for other independent variables which are statistically significant such as MassMedia (0.492701), Vital information (2.574798), MechanisedSyst (1.707727), DataAccessibility (0.532145) and ImprovedPerformance

(5.266020). These proportional odds suggest that the odds for an increase by the values in brackets will lead to a proportional change in the dependent variable (Agricultural transmission mechanism).

7.6.3 Test of Research Hypothesis 5

H₀: There is no significant relationship between agricultural diversification and return on capital employed of agricultural companies in South-West Nigeria.

H₁: There is a significant relationship between agricultural diversification and return on capital employed of agricultural companies in the South-West Nigeria.

The regression coefficient was given as:

Equation five (5)

$$DiverRtn = \alpha + \beta_1 OilDep + \beta_2 AdeData + \beta_3 Corp + \beta_4 RurMov + \beta_5 Infra + \beta_6 GDP + \beta_7 Povt + \beta_8 Exter + \beta_9 PolFrw + \mu$$

Table 7.6.3: Hypothesis 5

Variable	Coefficient	Std. Error	Odd ratio	<i>p-value</i>
OilDependent	0.580337*	0.319987	1.786641	0.0697
Data	0.276364	0.252707	1.318328	0.2741
Corruption	0.320180	0.530144	1.377375	0.5459
RuralUrban	0.828148**	0.385107	2.289074	0.0315
Infrastructure	1.00250***	0.348228	2.725094	0.0040
GDP	1.17503**	0.474855	3.238247	0.0133
Poverty	0.644593	0.463313	1.905211	0.1641
Externalities	0.425624	0.360132	1.530546	0.2373
Framework	0.115312	0.453221	1.122224	0.7992
Pseudo R-squared	0.569366			
Log likelihood	-93.10278			
LR statistic	287.992			
Number of cases 'correctly predicted' (161)	80.1%			
Prob(LR statistic)	0.0000			
Obs	201			
p-value	***=1%	**=5%	*=10%	
cut1	9.64256	1.78802	5.393	<0.0001
cut2	14.7462	2.49598	5.908	<0.0001
cut3	17.0949	2.24192	7.625	<0.0001
cut4	23.6960	2.68110	8.838	<0.0001

Where:

Dependent variable

DivRtn = Diversification returns

α = constant

Independent variable (x)

OilDep = Oil-dependent

AdeData = Adequate data

Corp = Corruption

RurMov = Rural-Urban movement

Infra = Infrastructures

GDP = Increase/decrease Gross Domestic Product

Povt = poverty

Exter = Externalities

PolFrw = Policy framework

μ = error level incorporating omitted variables

$\beta_1, \beta_2, \beta_3, \beta_4, \beta_5, \beta_6, \beta_7, \beta_8,$ and β_9 = coefficients

The theme for this section is “Effect of diversification on the **return on capital employed (ROCE)** of agricultural companies in South-West Nigeria”. The dependent variable is proxy as diversification returns and regressed on the listed independent variables in the table above.

A. The model, Likelihood ratio test (chi-square) is 287.992 with 5 d.f. statistically it is highly significant, and it means that the independent variables such as oil dependent, adequate data, corruption, rural-urban movement, Infrastructures, Gross Domestic Product, Poverty, externalities and policy framework (as a catalyst to agricultural company development)

B. The McFadden R^2 (aka pseudo R^2) is

$$\text{Pseudo } R^2 = 0.607325$$

C. Table 7.6.3 above presents the statistical significance of individual regression coefficients (β s) making use of chi-square; the coefficients of variables such as oil dependent, rural-urban, infrastructures and Gross Domestic Product are positive. This shows that an effective agricultural diversification aided by the regressor will lead to agricultural company development in South-West Nigeria. This is in consonance with the view of Adams (2016), who think there is a need for government to establish agricultural policies that will discourage over dependence on oil and aid an effective diversification into mechanised agriculture.

The result of the model for oil-dependency showed a coefficient of 0.580337 and a p-value of 0.0697 (*OilDep* <0.05) , indicating there is a relationship between being over-dependent oil and agricultural diversification. This implies that the more the nation becomes over-dependent on the revenue from crude oil and oil industries for employment, the more it will be difficult to attain effective agricultural diversification that will aid the ROCE of agricultural companies in South-West Nigeria. The table 7.6.3 further revealed that the rural-urban movement has a coefficient of 0.828148 with a p-value of 0.0315 (*RurMov* <0.05). This suggests that the rural-urban movement has significantly impacted agricultural diversification and, hence, the return of capital employed by agricultural companies in South-West Nigeria. This means that the more people migrate to the urban area, the more difficult it will be to achieve effective agricultural diversification and the more it will impact the returns of the agricultural companies. Likewise, the interview participants believe that the rural-urban movement has an impact on the return of the agricultural companies in the South-West. They believed the movement was a result of a lack of agricultural activities in the rural area, and that has made most of the youth migrate to the city in search of greener pastures.

The output of the model also affirms that there is a relationship between the availability of social infrastructure and agricultural diversification and, consequently, the return of agricultural companies in South-West Nigeria. This

means that the availability of adequate social infrastructures will lead to effective agricultural diversification, which will, in turn, aid the ROCE of the agricultural companies in South-West Nigeria. This was in consonance with the view of Zin (2014), who opined that the government should adequately create a social and educational infrastructure that will influence the economic development of the country. Likewise, the result shows a coefficient of 1.17503 and P-value of 0.0133 for GDP ($GDP < 0.05$). The result of the model signifies there is a significant relationship between GDP and the return of the agricultural companies in South-West Nigeria. The result suggests that neglect of the agricultural sector by the government will lead to a decline in the national GDP and, in turn, a decrease in the return of agricultural companies in South-West Nigeria. This was in agreement with the view of Afolabi (2015) who thinks the neglect of agriculture by Nigeria government as result to the decrease in the contribution of agriculture towards the GDP of the country.

Non-the-less, the following variables have a positive slope coefficient: adequate data with a coefficient of 0.276364 (p-value - 0.2741), corruption with a coefficient of 0.320180 (p-value - 0.5459), poverty with a coefficient of 0.644593 (p-value - 0.1641), externalities with a coefficient of 0.425624 (p-value - 0.2373) and policy framework with a coefficient of 0.115312 (p-value - 0.7992). This signifies that the return on capital employed as a result of agricultural diversification is not significantly influenced by variables such as availability of data, corruption, agricultural externalities and level of poverty. This was contrary to the view of authors such as Evans and Alenoghena (2015), Ajayi et al. (2017), Micah and Ruth (2014). These authors believe that the high level of corruption in the country has significantly hindered the development of agriculture in Nigeria including the South-West region of the country.

D. Based on the outcome of the model, the nul hypothesis (H_0) is rejected, while the related p-value for predictors OilDependent, RuralUrban, Infrastructure, and GDP are greater than ($p > 0.05$) the stipulated level of significance, thus, hypothesis 1 is accepted for these models.

The equation five models of α , β_1 , β_2 , β_3 , β_4 , β_5 , β_6 , β_7 , β_8 and β_9 thus:

$$DiverRtn = \alpha + (0.580337)OilDep + (0.276364)AdeData + (0.320180)Corp + (0.828148)RurMov + (1.00250)Infra + (1.17503)GDP + (0.644593)Povt + (0.425624)Exter + (0.115312)PolFrw + \mu.$$

E. The number of cases correctly predicted is 161 which means that degree of outcomes was predicted correctly 80.1%, See the table above for further information, which also shows the predicted probability values of each of the four possible outcomes.

F. Proportional odds from this model output were similar to the model output of Edward and Bryan (2018), which suggests that the rate of change of a dependent variable depends on the independent variable changes (based on the set conditions). Therefore, the odd ratio of 1.786641 for OilDependent diversification indicates that the odds of an increase of 1.8 times will result to increase in the return of agricultural companies. This means that the more the economy diversified away from depending on the oil revenue, the more the return of the agricultural companies. The proportional odds of other independent variables with significant relationships have similar effects, such as RuralUrban (2.289074), Infrastructure (2.725094), and GDP (3.238247). These proportional odds suggest that the odds for an increase by these values will lead to an increase by 1 unit in the impact of diversification on the agricultural companies' return.

7.7 Summary and conclusion

Five equations expressed in the form of agricultural models for the agricultural companies development in South-West Nigeria were estimated individually using correlation matrix and regression (ordered logit) analysis. Each of the five agricultural models is specified for national economic policy; agricultural model development; agricultural regulatory framework; agricultural policy transmission mechanism and return on capital employed by agricultural companies respectively.

The result of the models shows that the agricultural companies development in South-West Nigeria is positively related to the establishment and effective implementation of national economic policy; successful implementation of agricultural

models; establishment and application of agricultural regulatory framework; use of relevant agricultural policy transmission mechanism and adequate return on capital employed by agricultural companies. The result of the model is in consonance with the findings of the interviews conducted for this study and the opinion of authors such as Bergh (2000); Luken (2006); Byelee et al. (2009); Hazell et al. (2010) and Ibietan (2011). The result of the model, however, confirms that effective implementation of the national economic policy will lead to an increase in productivity of the agricultural companies and help in reducing poverty and hunger within the region. In the same vein also agrees that the successful establishment and implementation of the agricultural model will aid the implementation of the agricultural policy by agricultural companies in South-West Nigeria.

The outcome of the model shows that the establishment of an appropriate regulatory framework will influence the implementation of the agricultural policy by the agricultural companies and lead to Strict adherence that will promote effective corporate management (Harrison et al., 2016). The outcome of the model also suggests that the development of an appropriate agricultural transmission mechanism will lead to improved performance and income of agricultural companies through knowledge gained (Hassan et al., 2010) on the application of a mechanised system. The models further revealed how diversification toward agriculture from being over-dependent on oil revenue (Adams, 2016; Divanbeigi and Saliola, 2016) will lead to an increase in the returns of agricultural companies and hence the development of agricultural companies in South-West Nigeria.

Summary of the hypotheses tested

Hypotheses tested	OUTCOME
<p>Research Hypothesis 1</p> <p>H₀: There is no significant relationship between the national economic policy and development of agricultural companies in South-West.</p> <p>H₁: There is a significant relationship between the national economic policy and development of agricultural companies in South-West.</p>	<p>H₀ Rejected</p> <p>H₁ Accepted</p>
<p>Research Hypothesis 2</p> <p>H₀: There is no significant relationship between the agricultural models and agricultural companies development in South-West Nigeria</p> <p>H₁: There is a significant relationship between the agricultural models and agricultural companies development in South-West Nigeria</p>	<p>H₀ Rejected</p> <p>H₁ Accepted</p>
<p>Research Hypothesis 3</p> <p>H₀: There is no significant relationship between the regulatory framework and agricultural companies development in South-West Nigeria.</p> <p>H₁: There is a significant relationship between the regulatory</p>	<p>H₀ Rejected</p> <p>H₁ Accepted</p>

<p>framework and agricultural companies development in South-West Nigeria.</p>	
<p>Research Hypothesis 4</p> <p>H₀: There is no significant relationship between policy transmission mechanism and agricultural companies development in South-West Nigeria.</p> <p>H₁: There is a significant relationship between policy transmission mechanism and agricultural companies development in South-West Nigeria</p>	<p>H₀ Rejected</p> <p>H₁ Accepted</p>
<p>Research Hypothesis 5</p> <p>H₀: There is no significant relationship between agricultural diversification and return on capital employed of agricultural companies in South-West Nigeria.</p> <p>H₁: There is a significant relationship between agricultural diversification and return on capital employed of agricultural companies in the South-West Nigeria.</p>	<p>H₀ Rejected</p> <p>H₁ Accepted</p>

CHAPTER EIGHT

SUMMARY, CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATIONS

8.0 Introduction

This chapter entails discussions around the conclusion, summary and recommendations on the study of how the national economic policies can be used to aid the development of agricultural companies in South-West Nigeria. The section also includes implications of agricultural models developed, limitations of the study and areas of further study. The study explored the use of a conjugative mixed method with semi-structured interviews and surveys as a data collection instrument. The data collected were further analysed using narrative analysis and inferential statistics. The study is, however, structured into eight (8) chapters.

8.1 Summary of the study

Chapter one covers the introduction, objectives and background of agricultural practices, policies and schemes including the demography of Nigeria. The neglect of agriculture (Byelee et al., 2009), lack of appropriate regulatory framework (Hazell et al., 2010; Luken 2006) and over-dependent on oil revenue was identified as the major barrier to agricultural companies development in Nigeria (Adams, 2016). Consequently, five research hypothetical questions were developed with the aim to proffer solutions to the problems. The area of the study was limited to the development of agricultural companies in South-West Nigeria.

Chapter two entails the review of relevant and appropriate literature on agricultural development in developing countries. The narrative literature review approach was adopted for this section. From the literature reviewed themes such as agricultural

regulatory framework (Hazell et al., 2010; Nuyartoro et al., 2016; Afolabi, 2015), global policy adoption (Iwuchukwu and Igbokwe, 2012; Afroz and Akhtar, 2017)), agricultural transmission mechanism (Hassan et al., 2010), agricultural externalities (Williamson, 1970; Novikova, 2014) and agricultural marketing board era in Nigeria (Kolawole, 1974; Ajayi et al., 2017) were generated. The conceptual framework for agricultural companies development was also developed. Consequently, gaps in the literature reviewed resulted in the development of the five research hypotheses. The Chapter two also contains the systematic literature review (SLR). The systematic literature review was conducted in addition to the narrative review in chapter two. The SLR is a scientific method (Harrison, Paul, and Burnard, 2016) that eliminates the rule of thumb in the review process and provides an audit trail of the review (Ahmad and Omar, 2014). This section explains the methodology adopted for the SLR, the search strings and keywords used to search for the papers reviewed and the sources of the literature (Tranfield, Denyer and Smart, 2003). The section explained the analysis and quality of the assessment of the papers including the exclusion and inclusion rules that guide the selection of the papers reviewed. Furthermore, the summary of findings and results of the review questions including the methodology, findings and conclusions of the papers reviewed were discussed in this chapter.

Chapter three explains the theoretical framework that underpins this study. It discusses the basis for adapting the stakeholders' theory and sustainable development theory, including the emergence, evolution, and perspective of stewardship, stakeholders, and sustainable development theory. The basis for developing the theoretical framework is also discussed in this section.

Chapter four gives a detailed explanation of the methodology design adopted for the research. Based on the complexity of the study a mixed-method approach was adopted. A target sample of 300 participants from 30 companies across the six (6) states in the region was identified and discussed in the section. Five Likert scale questionnaires were distributed to 300 employees of 30 agricultural companies located within the six states in South-West Nigeria. Of the 300 questionnaires, only 202 were completed and returned. In addition to the survey conducted 9 members of the board of directors of companies selected were interviewed using a semi-structured interview. The data collected through the interview was analysed using narrative analysis while the result of the survey was analysed using chi-square, correlation and regression (ordered logit). Models were developed and tested using Gretl, SPSS and Python anaconda. The ethical principle such as informed consent, harm to participants, confidentiality, anonymity and dignity which guide the conduct and development of the study were also discussed in this chapter.

Chapter five is designed to provide the results and findings of the qualitative data collected through the semi-structured interview. It entails the process of qualitative data collection and analysis and the participant's structure, which comprises the position and location of the interviewee in the region. The chapter also includes familiarization and preparation of the qualitative data collected through open coding which disintegrates the raw qualitative data into a smaller, reasonable, and appropriate unit of meaning that form independent concepts (Corbin and Strauss,1990). The research objectives and questions were recalled in this section of the study for critical linkages of the interview findings with the research objectives.

Chapter six of this study presents the quantitative data results, analysis and findings with interpretation and data presentation. Firstly, the analysis of responses on bio-data was conducted. The analysis of bio-data responses covers gender analysis; analysis of age distribution; educational qualification analysis; marital status analysis; analysis of the position in the organisation; The job experience of the participants, professional qualifications and a summary of respondents' profiles. These were followed by the analysis of responses on agricultural companies' performances. Frequency distribution tables were used in the presentation of the results of the 50 questions in the survey. A chart showing the trend of participants was also included in this chapter.

Chapter seven is concerned with the hypotheses testing and presentation of the agricultural models. In this chapter, the five hypotheses were evaluated and tested to determine whether the relationship among the agricultural developmental variables is significantly positive or negative using chi-square and heatmap (correlation matrix). However, regression (ordered logit) and coefficient of determination with the aid of Gretl and SPSS were used to develop and test the agricultural models which are built upon the five hypotheses and research objectives. In addition to the p-value and beta coefficient the value of Odd ratios, Log-likelihood, Durbin Watson and F-Value were also reported in this chapter.

Furthermore, this chapter entails the contribution to the body of knowledge. The implication of the study to agricultural stakeholders such as shareholders/owners,

employees, government, management, government, and its agencies. To end this chapter some suggestions for further related studies were discussed.

8.2 Conclusion on the major findings of the study

This section explains the major findings of the interviews conducted and the result of the data collected through the survey. The result of the interviews and the survey were further analysed using narrative analysis and statistical techniques respectively. Five hypotheses based on the research objectives were evaluated and tested with the study modelled into five equations. The hypotheses were tested using chi-square, correlation matrix and regression analysis (Logit). From these five equations models were developed. The dependent variables include national economic policy; agricultural models; regulatory framework; agricultural policies transmission mechanisms and diversification returns. The relationship between these dependent variables and the independent variables was tested and resulted in the following:

8.2.1 Evaluating the impacts of national economic policy on the development of agricultural companies.

The result of the analysis and testing of hypothesis 1 indicated a strong positive relationship between the impacts of national economic policy and the agricultural companies development in South-West Nigeria. This was evidenced by the correlation coefficient of 0.45 and the F value of .000 ($F=.000<.05$). Hence the null hypothesis was rejected, and the alternative was accepted. This means proper transmission and implementation of national economic policy will lead to the development of agricultural companies (Zin, 2014) in South-West Nigeria. Similarly, the outcome of the interviews conducted also shows that the lack of proper transmission and implementation of the national economic policy has been the bane

of the agricultural companies development in the region. As a result, the respondents believe the proper implementation of national economic policy can influence the development of agricultural companies in South-West Nigeria.

8.2.2 Assessing the effect of agricultural models on agricultural companies development

The analysis of data on the effects of agricultural models on agricultural companies development with testing of the model equation based on hypothesis 2 shows a positive relationship at 0.28 ($R = .28$) and the F value of .000 ($F = .000 < .05$). This means that the combined effect variables such as skilful application of models, ROCE, effective exchange of resources and information (Omekwu, 2003) and application of modern technologies have a significant influence on the successful implementation (Owombo et al., 2012) of agricultural models in South-West Nigeria. The responses of the interview participants also show that effective implementation and operation of agricultural models will aid good relationships among agricultural stakeholders in the region. Consequently, the null hypothesis was rejected and the alternative which states that there is a significant relationship between the agricultural models and agricultural companies development in South-West Nigeria was accepted.

8.2.3 Assessing the impacts of regulatory framework on agricultural policy implementation

The results of the interviews and the statistical analysis of the quantitative data on the impact of the regulatory framework on agricultural policy implementation revealed there is a significant relationship between the establishment of an appropriate regulatory framework (Diao et al., 2007) and the development of agricultural

companies in South-West Nigeria. The outcome of the model equation that is based on hypothesis 3 shows a positive relationship of 0.46 ($R = .46$) with an F-value of .000 which is less than .05 ($F = .000 < .05$). This means that the combined effect of variables such as elimination of unhealthy competition, increase in ROCE, agricultural transformation and effective corporate management have a significant influence on the establishment (Harrison et al., 2016) and successful implementation of an agricultural regulatory framework. Based on this evidence the null hypothesis which states “there is no significant relationship between the regulatory framework and agricultural companies development in South-West Nigeria” is therefore rejected and the alternative accepted. Likewise, the findings from the responses of the interview show that the lack of an appropriate regulatory framework has resulted in insignificant development in agricultural companies.

8.2.4 Evaluating the effect of policy transmission mechanism on agricultural policy implementation

The results of both the qualitative and quantitative data analysis with testing of the model equation showed that the effect of the agricultural policy transmission mechanism on agricultural policy implementation is statistically significant. The evidence from the model summary showed there is a strong positive correlation ($R = .851$) between the agricultural policy transmission mechanism and the combined effect of variables such as improved performance and income; use of the right channel in transmitting agricultural information; use of mass media and social media in communicating vital agricultural information (Adeola and Adetunbi, 2015). Hence this resulted in the rejection of the null hypothesis (H_0) and acceptance of the alternative (H_1) that expressly stated, “there is a significant relationship between

policy transmission mechanism and agricultural companies development in South-West Nigeria". Similarly, the responses of the interview participants show that there is no policy transmission mechanism, and this has resulted in a lack of effective transmission of vital agricultural information to the relevant stakeholders (Daneji, 2011) in the region.

8.2.5 Evaluating the Influence of diversification on the return on capital employed by agricultural companies

The analysis of interview responses and quantitative data collected through the survey was carried out to evaluate and determine whether there is a significant relationship between agricultural diversification and return on capital employed by agricultural companies in South-West Nigeria. The qualitative and quantitative data were analysed while the model developed based on hypothesis 5 was tested using statistical techniques. The output of the model tested shows there is a significant relationship between diversification and return on capital employed by the agricultural companies in the South-West. This suggests the combined effect of variables such as over-dependent on oil revenue (Adams, 2016); rural-urban migration, high level of corruption (Micah and Ruth, 2014) and lack of infrastructure are the major barriers to effective diversification that will lead to an increase in the return (Dardak, 2015) of agricultural companies in South-West Nigeria. Hence, the null hypothesis (H_0) was rejected while the alternative hypothesis (H_1) was therefore accepted. In the same vein, the analysis of the interview responses shows that the agricultural companies return has not been influenced by agricultural policies due to lack of infrastructural facilities, lack of data on agricultural companies and inconsistencies in the policy implementation. Based on this evidence the study, therefore, affirmed that there is a

significant relationship between barriers to effective diversification and return on capital employed by agricultural companies in South-West Nigeria.

From this study five important conclusions can be drawn:

- (1) The study shows that there is a significant relationship between national economic policy and agricultural development. However, the poor implementation of the policy has led to insignificant development of agricultural companies in South-West Nigeria.
- (2) The establishment and skilful application of agricultural models will aid the development of agricultural companies in South-West Nigeria.
- (3) The establishment and successful implementation of an appropriate agricultural regulatory framework will influence the effective application of agricultural policies by agricultural companies in South-West Nigeria.
- (4) The use of appropriate agricultural transmission mechanisms as a means of communicating vital agricultural information to agricultural stakeholders will aid the implementation of agricultural policies in the South-West.
- (5) The barriers to effective diversification will negatively influence the return on capital employed by agricultural companies in South-West Nigeria.
- (6)

8.3 Recommendations

Given the outcome of this study, the recommendations are suggested as a way forward for the development of agricultural companies in South-West Nigeria:

- The government agencies responsible for the formulation of economic policies should ensure that the policies formulated are based on economic realities and not on the rule of thumb. In addition, the stakeholders in the industry should be engaged in the development of the policy. However, the approved policy should be effectively communicated to the end-user such as agricultural companies using an appropriate transmission mechanism.

- The finding from this research revealed that there are no agricultural models that can support the implementation of the agricultural policy by the agricultural company. This study, therefore, recommends the adoption of five models developed in the course of this study. The adoption of these five models will aid the successful implementation of the established policies and standardisation of agricultural practices in South-West Nigeria.
- To promote healthy competition among agricultural stakeholders, effective agricultural transformation, and good corporate management an effective and appropriate regulatory framework should be used to replace the current obsolete and weak agricultural regulatory framework. The establishment of the agricultural regulatory framework based on the recommended conceptual framework in figure 12 will aid the implementation of the agricultural policy by agricultural companies. This will hence lead to the development of the agricultural companies in South-West Nigeria.
- Evidence from this study shows there are no agricultural transmission mechanisms through which agricultural policy and other vital agricultural information are transmitted to the agricultural stakeholders in South-West Nigeria. Therefore, standard agricultural transmission mechanisms that will aid the transmission of agricultural policy using mass media and social media should be developed. The adoption of the agricultural policy transmission mechanism in table 7.5.7.2 is however recommended.
- For effective diversification towards agriculture, the government should avoid being over-dependent on revenue, build more infrastructure and reduce the level of corruption in the agricultural sector. The government should build more infrastructure in the rural area to discourage the high rate of rural-urban migration

which is one of the main factors responsible for the lack of development agricultural companies in South-West Nigeria.

8.4 Contribution to the body of knowledge

This study has made some valuable contributions to the body of knowledge:

- 1) Determination and evaluation of the impact of national economic policy on the development of agricultural companies in South-West Nigeria.
- 2) Evaluation and development of agricultural models for agricultural companies in South-West Nigeria.
- 3) Assessment and establishment of the link between agricultural regulatory framework and agricultural policy implementation.
- 4) Identification of effective channel of transmitting agricultural information to agricultural stakeholders in South-West Nigeria.
- 5) From this study two articles were published in the area of climate change and agricultural companies development. The paper on climate change that was titled “*Climate change: Policy support for national adaptation plans in Sub Saharan Africa*” was published in WSEAS Transactions on Environmental and Development on 14 October, 2022 with DOI: 10. 37394/232015. 2022. 18. 69. However, the paper titled “Study of agricultural companies development in Nigeria: A systematic literature review was published in International Journal of Agricultural Science on 30 December, 2022. The paper can be located at <http://iaras.org/iaras/journals/ijas>. This paper was co-authored with my supervisors.

8.5 Implications of the Study

This study has shown that the development of agricultural companies has impacts on the interests of various groups of stakeholders in the agricultural sector in South-West Nigeria. The findings from the study revealed that agricultural companies

development is important to the shareholders, management, government, government agencies and other stakeholders. The finding further revealed that the development of the agricultural companies will lead to economic growth and development in the region (Hassan et al., 2010). However, below are the implications of the research findings on various agricultural stakeholders in the region.

8.5.1 The implication of findings to owners/shareholders of agricultural companies

The shareholders are one of the key stakeholders in the corporate venture. The shareholder's or owner's main objective in a business is usually to the maximization of earnings or values of the company. Consequently, the shareholders regularly evaluate the state of their stake in a business through earnings from the business in form of financial outcomes such as dividend, return on capital employed, share price, earnings per share and return on assets. The findings of this study, however, established there is a significant positive relationship between agricultural companies development and maximization of shareholders and returns. The outcome of the model further shows that implementation of appropriate agricultural transmission mechanism, agricultural models, regulatory framework and effective diversification will aid agricultural companies ROCE, EPS, benefit from assets and value of the company.

8.5.2 The Implication of findings to the employees of agricultural companies

Employees are vital stakeholders in agricultural companies development. According to Agboola (2014), It is the aggregate productive efforts of employees in a company that will aid the productivity of the organisation and lead to the overall development

and growth of the business. However, this study also shows there is a positive relationship between agricultural companies development and increase in productivity through the skilful application of modern technology, education of employees and strict adherence to agricultural models. Furthermore, the findings suggest that the use of the right channel of transmission for vital agricultural information with effective implementation of agricultural models will lead to educated and knowledgeable employees in agricultural companies. Thus, the availability of educated, skilful and knowledgeable employees in the agricultural companies will aid the productivity and development of the agricultural companies in South-West Nigeria.

8.5.3 The Implications of findings to the management of the agricultural companies

Management is generally 'judged' by the returns they make or the value-added to the business. Corporate management scholars such as Akinkunmi (2017); Harrison et al. (2016); Byelee et al. (2009); Cervantes Godoy and Dewbre (2010) have postulated that effective corporate management through innovation and creativity maximises a firm's value. The study of corporate development is therefore very important to the management of organisations including agricultural companies. This study however revealed that there is a positive link between corporate development and variables such as the adoption of the right channel of communication, compliance with the regulatory framework and effective application of models.

8.5.4 The Implications of findings to the government and regulators

Several government agencies such as the Ministry of Agriculture, research institute and Bank of Agric who make use of data for the appraisal and regulation of the

activities of the agricultural companies depend on data and information from this kind of report. Such reports may also be used for regional and national planning purposes. The significance of this study is that government agencies including the Revenue boards can make use of this research report which contains reasonable, accurate and reliable data, model and framework that can be used for government budgets and planning.

However, the findings from this study include agricultural companies development components such as agricultural models, and agricultural policy transmission mechanisms that are required in the present-day economic planning. One of the gains from accurate and reliable data and information by the government is the increase in productivity and ROCE of the agricultural companies. From the model tested in table 7.6.3, it was revealed that the availability of adequate data for economic planning will result in an increase in the ROCE of the agricultural companies. This clearly shows the implication of the findings of this report to the government and other regulatory agencies.

8.5.5 The Implications of the findings to the general public

The public includes several other users such as consumers, the local business community, potential investors, and the international community who need reliable data for business decisions on agricultural companies. However, findings from this study provide a wide variety of information such as the level of poverty, the effect of corruption, cost of externalities and ROCE which can serve as a guide in decision making.

8.6 Limitations of the Study

Some constraints have been identified that limit the coverage of this study. Some of these limitations include:

- a. This study initially intends to cover the whole of Nigeria as the area of study. However, in the course of the study, it was discovered that it will be impossible to cover the entire country due to factors such as security challenges caused by the activities of the insurgent in the Northern of the country. The Eastern part of the country was also excluded due to social unrest caused by the agitation for secession by the people in the region. Other limitations include a lack of access to the agricultural companies due to the poor state of the road network.
- b. The study initially intends to adopt ethnography in addition to other forms of methodology. However, the idea of using ethnography was dropped due to budget constraints and lack of time to effectively applied the technique in collecting data from agricultural companies. Using ethnography could have offered the opportunity of natural experience to explore how the agricultural companies implement the agricultural policies in the agricultural practices. Furthermore, the sampling issues of responses not up to 90% of the survey administered due to difficulty in gaining access to the employee of a few agricultural companies selected. The challenge of access to the agricultural companies was a result of the Covid-19 pandemic which was at its peak during the data collection stage of this study.
- c. The lack of adequate data on the agricultural companies in terms of size and number of agricultural companies in the country or the region is another constraint which has limited the scope of the research. The absence of this data has

prevented this research from drawing conclusions based on the size and number of the agricultural companies within the country or the region being studied.

8.7 Suggestions for future related studies

It is therefore suggested that the study of agricultural companies development in the future should include:

- (a) A study on the agricultural development in the Northern and Eastern regions of Nigeria.
- (b) An ethnography research of agricultural companies development in developing nations.
- (c) A comparative study of agricultural companies development in a developed and developing countries.

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2. The broad brush policy is a mechanism where policy is formulated and implemented without considering the implication of the policy on each of the component of the sector.

APPENDICES

APPENDIX 1: ETHICAL APPROVAL LETTER

APPENDIX II: RESEARCH QUESTIONNAIRE SAMPLE

APPENDIX III: SAMPLE OF QUESTIONNAIRE PARTICIPANT CONSENT FORM

APPENDIX IV: SAMPLE OF INTERVIEW QUESTIONS

APPENDIX V: NAME OF PARTICIPANT COMPANIES AND LOCATION

APPENDIX VI: ANALYSIS OF QUESTIONS ON AGRICULTURAL POLICY

APPENDIX VII: ANALYSIS OF THE 23 COMPANIES RESPONSES

APPENDIX I

09/02/2021

Dear Ayodele Adetuyi,

Your application 13916: NATIONAL ECONOMIC POLICY AND CORPORATE SECTOR DEVELOPMENT IN A DEVELOPING ECONOMY: A STUDY OF AGRICULTURAL COMPANIES DEVELOPMENT IN SOUTH-WEST NIGERIA, submission 13305, has been approved by the Business and Creative Industries SEC . You may now proceed with your study. If you wish to make any significant changes to the study you must seek the committee's approval before actioning them.

Good luck with your research.

Dr D Turner

APPENDIX II

RESEARCH QUESTIONNAIRE

SCHOOL: UNIVERSITY OF THE WEST OF SCOTLAND, SCOTLAND, UK.

TOPIC: National economic policy and corporate sector development in a developing economy: A study of agricultural companies development in South-West Nigeria.

Dear Respondent,

The under-signed is a PhD, student at School Business and Creative Industries of University of the West of Scotland, Scotland, United Kingdom.

He is carrying out research on the above subject matter. This instrument is to be used in assessing economic policies and its impacts on agricultural companies development in South-West Nigeria. To aid the completion of the study, your frank responses to these questions would go a long way in providing valid and reliable data for appropriate recommendations at the end of his study.

Your sincere responses would be kept strictly confidential and used only for the purpose of this research. You may, therefore, avoid names or any element that could lead to your identification.

Thank you for your co-operation.

Ayodele Adetuyi
Student/Researcher

SECTION A: BIODATA INFORMATION OF THE RESPONDENT

Instructions: Please tick the appropriate answer and specify where necessary.

1. Gender

- (a) Male (b) Female

2. Age group (in years).

- (a) 18-28 (b) 29-39 (c) 40-49 (d) 50- 60 (e) 60 and above.

3. Marital Status

- (a) Married (b) Single (c) Divorced (d) Widowed

4. Highest Educational Qualification

- (a) GCE/WASCE/SSCE (b) OND/NCE (c) HND
(d) BSc (e) MSc/MBA (f) PhD (g) Others (Please specify)

5. Position in the organization.

- (a) Junior staff (b) Senior staff (c) Supervisor (d) Manager
(e) Non-executive Director (f) Executive Director (g) MD/CEO
(h) Others (Please specify).

6. How many years have you worked with this organization?

- (a) Less than 6 months (b) More than 6 months to 5 years
(c) 6 years to 10 years (d) 11 years to 20 years (e) 21 years to 30 years (f)
30 years and above

7. Number of Employees in your organisation

*Please specify.

Key: 1=Strongly Disagree, 2=Disagree, 3=Fairly Disagree, 4=Agree, 5=Strongly Agree

No.	Questions for your consideration	1	2	3	4	5
	❖ National economic policy					
1	The national agricultural policies have been successfully implemented by government and its agencies in the agricultural sector.					
2	The broad brush policy approach used by the Nigeria government has led to the development of agricultural companies in South-West Nigeria.					
3	The exclusion of stakeholders in the formulation of agricultural policy has no effect on the successful implementation of the agricultural policy					
4	Government intervention through agricultural policies has influence increase in cash crop output in my firm.					
5	The lack of an appropriate regulatory framework has led to poor implementation and failure of agricultural policy in South-West Nigeria.					
6	Agricultural policies are recognised and motivate the workers to enhance the firm's financial growth as a result of the application of modern technology in the agricultural processes.					
7	Agricultural policies are highly valued by management in my organisation because they enhance the adoption of a mechanised system which aid the company's growth and development.					
8	The application of agricultural policies on our firm activities has resulted to increase in return on capital employed by our firm.					
9	The policymaker has failed to lunch agricultural revolution which will eradicate hunger, poverty and economic stagnation.					
10	The adoption of global policy on climatic change by policymaker in Nigeria will reduce the risk of vulnerability from climatic change, eliminate ethnic and political distraction and influence development of agricultural companies in South-West Nigeria.					
	❖ Models for agricultural policies					

11	Development of a model for policy framework will aid the implementation of agricultural policies by agricultural companies					
12	Policy model will aid the exchange of information and resources between government agencies and agricultural companies within the South-West region of Nigeria					
13	The policy model will show the link between the policies, agricultural companies development and economic growth					
14	The value of a firm's investment is increased by the skilful use of the model by the employees in our company.					
15	The adoption of a model will aid the development of an individual farmer in the south-West to an agricultural company					
16	Low return on capital employed was caused by the lack of a model for agricultural policies in my company.					
17	The absence of a policy model has hindered the adoption of modern technology in my company					
18	Investors' appraisals of companies past financial performances are used as yardsticks for the application of agricultural policies.					
19	High return on capital employed is evidence of business development in my organisation.					
20	Benefits arising from the assets of the firm can be associated with the ability of the management to effectively applied agricultural policies in its operation.					
	❖ Regulatory framework on agricultural policy implementation					
21	Regulatory framework on the agricultural policy adopted by management brings about high financial performance.					
22	Regulatory framework on agricultural policy implementation has influenced my company's participation in agricultural programmes.					
23	National policy framework for agricultural development has been used by my company to resolve the economic, social and environmental issue.					

24	Effective corporate management in agricultural companies can be achieved through strict adherence to the regulatory framework					
25	Lack of an appropriate regulatory framework is preventing my company from implementing a developmental programme such as application modern technology in agricultural processes.					
26	Compliance with agricultural policy and framework aid price and income stabilisation in my organisation.					
27	EPS as a measure of financial reward for capital investment is an important tool used by the management of my company to measure the impact of agricultural policy.					
28	The imposition of High and excessive tax rate on the agricultural company has led to cost-push inflation and discourage investors from investing in my company.					
29	Regulatory practices and government policies play a crucial part in the transformation of the company's businesses through the elimination of hostile competition and reduction of fraudulent practices among stakeholders in the region.					
30	Regulatory framework for agricultural transformation will eliminate the high rate of fraud and unhealthy competition among agricultural companies.					
	❖ Transmission mechanisms for agricultural policies					
31	The transmission mechanisms used by the government were appropriate for the agricultural sector					
32	The transmission mechanisms used by the government to communicate agricultural policies have aided agricultural policies implementation in my company.					
33	The information about agricultural policies was received through the mass by my company					
34	Vital information was disseminated by policymaker through mass media such as television radio and newspaper.					
35	My company always become aware of new agricultural policies through social media and the internet.					

36	The channel of transmitting information about agricultural policies is right for my company					
37	The dissemination of agricultural information through the right channel of communication led to the creation of educated and informed employees with updated information in my company.					
38	The South-West agricultural companies have remained uninformed due to lack of knowledge on how to transform from the use of peasant or traditional techniques to a mechanised farming system with high productivity					
39	The use of mass media has eliminated the challenge of literacy among farmer and make data more accessible for agricultural research.					
40	The use of appropriate transmission mechanism for communicating agricultural policies has improved performances and income of my company.					
	❖ Barriers of agricultural companies development					
41	The lack of diversification of the economy has made the Nigerian economy lagged behind other emerging economies					
42	Over-dependent on oil by Nigeria government has resulted in the neglect of agriculture.					
43	lack of adequate data for economic planning and research are the major impediment of agricultural companies development in South-West Nigeria					
44	high standard of corruption is a major barrier to the development of agricultural companies in south-west Nigeria.					
45	The rapid growth in rural-urban movement is responsible for the lack of agricultural companies development in South-West Nigeria.					
46	The lack of educational facilities and other social infrastructure facilities are responsible for the lack of agricultural development in South-West Nigeria.					

47	The neglect of agriculture by the government is responsible for the decline in the contribution of agriculture toward the national Gross Domestic Product					
48	The neglect of agriculture has increased the level of hunger and poverty level of the South-West Region.					
49	The low level of cost or negative externalities in Nigeria was as a result of the lack of extensive and intensive agricultural activity in Nigeria					
50	There is a need for the development of a policy framework for the management of agricultural externalities in South-Western Nigeria.					

APPENDIX III

PARTICIPANT CONSENT FORM

Name of the participant:-

Title of the research project: **National economic policy and corporate sector development in a developing economy: A study of agricultural companies development in South-West Nigeria.**

Main investigator and contact details: **Ayodele Morounkeji Adetuyi School** of Business and Creative Industries of the University of the West of Scotland, [REDACTED]

Research supervisory team: **Professor Heather Tarbert and Doctor Christian Harrison.**

I confirm that I agree to take part in the above research. I have read the participant information sheet which is attached to this consent form. I understand what my role will be in this research work, and all my questions/clarifications have been answered to my satisfaction.

I understand that I am free to withdraw from participating in this research at any time I want, for any reason and without prejudice

I have been adequately informed that the confidentiality of the information I provide will be safeguarded.

I am free to ask any questions at any time before and during the study.

I have been provided with a copy of this form and the participant information sheet

Data protection, I agree to the University of the West of Scotland processing personal data which I have supplied. I agree to the processing of such data for any purposes connected with the Research project as an outline to me.

Name of Participant.....

Signed

Date

YOU WILL BE GIVEN A COPY OF THIS FORM TO KEEP

If you would like to withdraw from the research, please complete the form below and return to the main investigator named above

I WISH TO WITHDRAW FROM THIS STUDY

Singed Date

**NATIONAL ECONOMIC POLICY AND CORPORATE SECTOR
DEVELOPMENT IN DEVELOPING A ECONOMY: A STUDY OF
AGRICULTURAL COMPANIES DEVELOPMENT IN SOUTH-WEST NIGERIA**

The interview questions

The pertinent research questions that will underpin the aim of this study are as follows:

- i. Has the national economic policy been used to **aid the development** of agricultural companies in South-West Nigeria?
 - a) What are the factors that has led to the development or under-development of agricultural companies in South-West Nigeria?
 - b) What are the impediment to effective implementation of national economic policy in South-West Nigeria?

- ii. Are there **models** on how agricultural policies can be used to influence the development of agricultural companies in South-West Nigeria?
 - a) Does agricultural companies in South-West Nigeria operate using agricultural models?
 - b) If any who develop the models used by agricultural companies in South-West Nigeria?

- iii. What are the impacts of the **regulatory framework** on agricultural policy implementation in Nigeria?

-
- a) Is there relationship between the agricultural regulatory framework and agricultural companies development in the South-West Nigeria?

 - iv. Has **policy transmission mechanisms** been used to influence agricultural policy implementation in South-West Nigeria?

 - V. Has agricultural policies influenced the **return on capital employed (ROCE)** of agricultural companies in South-West Nigeria?

APPENDIX V**Name of participants company and location**

S/N	COMPANY	LOCATION
1	AgroPark Agricultural Company Ltd	Lagos State
2	Group Farmer Limited	Oyo State
3	Agro Nigeria Ltd.	Ogun State
4	Amo Farm Ltd.	Osun State
5	Emmanuel Alayande Agricultural Farms Ltd.	Oyo State
6	Covenant University Farms Ltd	Ogun State
7	Agric Business Ltd.	Lagos State
8	BAFOT Farms Ltd.	Ogun State
9	Alabi Farms Ltd.	Osun State
10	Alade Farms Ltd.	Oyo State
11	Dele Ige Farms Ltd	Oyo State
12	BBC Professionals	Lagos State
13	ASA Botanica Ltd.	Ekiti State
14	Agric Solution Plus Concept	Ogun State
15	Oloja Farms Ltd	Ekiti State
16	Multiventures Farms Ltd.	Ondo State
17	Akinnola Cocoa Farms Ltd.	Ondo state
18	Akinbohun Farms Ltd.	Ondo State
19	Cocoa Processing Farm Ltd.	Ondo State
20	FEDAS Farms Ltd.	Ekiti State
21	Suave Africa Ltd.	Oyo State
22	DesirePlus Glabal Farm Ltd	Ogun State
23	Farm Credit Limited	Lagos State

APPENDIX VI

ANALYSIS OF QUESTIONNAIRES ON AGRIC POLICY														
Question	Strongly	% SD	Disagree = 2	% D	Fairly	% FD	Agree = 4	% A	Strogly	% SA	Missin g	% M	TOTAL	TOTAL
ID	Diagree= 1				Disagree = 3				Agree = 5					
1	27	13.37	67	33.17	39	19.31	58	28.71	11	5.45	0	0	202	100
2	30	14.85	46	22.77	63	31.19	52	25.74	10	4.95	1	0.50	202	100
3	53	26.24	60	29.70	41	20.30	38	18.81	8	3.96	2	0.99	202	100
4	30	14.85	46	22.77	47	23.27	60	29.70	18	8.91	1	0.50	202	100
5	8	3.96	14	6.93	20	9.90	94	46.53	62	30.69	4	1.98	202	100
6	16	7.92	19	9.41	41	20.30	89	44.06	36	17.82	1	0.50	202	100
7	16	7.92	30	14.85	18	8.91	112	55.45	24	11.88	2	0.99	202	100
8	21	10.40	40	19.80	42	20.79	71	35.15	27	13.37	1	0.50	202	100
9	18	8.91	27	13.37	35	17.33	74	36.63	47	23.27	1	0.50	202	100
10	10	4.95	17	8.42	33	16.34	90	44.55	48	23.76	4	1.98	202	100
11	6	2.97	10	4.95	25	12.38	106	52.48	49	24.26	6	2.97	202	100
12	7	3.47	10	4.95	33	16.34	102	50.50	49	24.26	1	0.50	202	100
13	3	1.49	12	5.94	15	7.43	120	59.41	49	24.26	3	1.49	202	100

14	4	1.9 8	11	5.4 5	3 5	17. 33	10 1	50. 00	45	22. 28	6	2.97	202	100
15	2	0.9 9	12	5.9 4	2 7	13. 37	11 5	56. 93	46	22. 77	0	0.00	202	100
16	1 6	7.9 2	26	12. 87	3 7	18. 32	9 1	45. 05	30	14. 85	2	0.99	202	100
17	1 2	5.9 4	22	10. 89	3 4	16. 83	9 6	47. 52	35	17. 33	3	1.49	202	100
18	1 0	4.9 5	23	11. 39	4 1	20. 30	10 1	50. 00	18	8.9 1	9	4.46	202	100
19	4	1.9 8	10	4.9 5	2 8	13. 86	10 3	50. 99	55	27. 23	2	0.99	202	100
20	4	1.9 8	12	5.9 4	4 3	21. 29	10 8	53. 47	32	15. 84	3	1.49	202	100
21	8	3.9 6	15	7.4 3	6 2	30. 69	9 2	45. 54	23	11. 39	2	0.99	202	100
22	7	3.4 7	23	11. 39	5 3	26. 24	9 7	48. 02	19	9.4 1	3	1.49	202	100
23	7	3.4 7	30	14. 85	3 7	18. 32	10 4	51. 49	23	11. 39	1	0.50	202	100
24	7	3.4 7	10	4.9 5	3 7	18. 32	10 3	50. 99	39	19. 31	6	2.97	202	100
25	1 8	8.9 1	47	23. 27	3 5	17. 33	8 6	42. 57	15	7.4 3	1	0.50	202	100
26	6	2.9 7	21	10. 40	5 8	28. 71	9 7	48. 02	20	9.9 0	0	0.00	202	100
27	2	0.9 9	15	7.4 3	5 9	29. 21	10 3	50. 99	22	10. 89	1	0.50	202	100

APPENDIX VII

ANALYSIS OF THE 23 COMPANIES RESPONSES

Question ID	Strongly Disagree = 1	Disagree = 2	Fairly Disagree = 3	Agree = 4	Strogly Agree = 5
1	5	5	5	5	0
2	4	6	6	3	1
3	3	2	3	2	0
4	6	0	5	1	0
5	6	4	3	3	4
6	5	5	2	4	2
7	2	5	7	0	0
8	6	2	3	3	0
9	3	7	3	3	3
10	8	1	0	1	2
11	5	3	1	3	3
12	5	2	0	2	2
13	4	4	3	2	2
14	6	4	1	6	2
15	2	8	5	2	3
16	4	6	2	3	3
17	8	2	5	2	2
18	5	2	2	4	0
19	7	0	0	2	1
20	9	1	0	0	2
21	10	0	0	0	7
22	6	4	4	4	0
23	7	3	0	4	4
Total	126	76	60	59	43